

Proceedings
**1st Symposium and Workshop
for Analytical Youth
on Applied Mechanics
(SWAYAM 2018)**

July 04 - 06, 2018

Editors

Sandeep Singh, Bishweshwar Babu, Swathika M.
Tushar Sharma, Ranjit S Patil

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1st Symposium and Workshop for Analytical Youth on Applied Mechanics (SWAYAM 2018)

Sandeep Singh, Bishweshwar Babu, Swathika M., Tushar Sharma, Ranjit S Patil

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PREFACE

Symposium and Workshop for Analytical Youth on Applied Mechanics (SWAYAM) is the yield of the collective efforts of the Departments of Applied Mechanics in the country, to provide the technical platform for the young researchers in the area of Applied Mechanics, and a parallel series of Indian Conference on Applied Mechanics (INCAM). Department of Mechanical Engineering, BITS Pilani, K. K. Birla Goa Campus, in association with the Indian Society for Applied Mechanics (ISAM), feels proud and privileged to organize the 1st Symposium and Workshop for Analytical Youth on Applied Mechanics (SWAYAM 2018). It is indeed an honour and privilege to organize the SWAYAM 2018 at BITS Pilani, K. K. Birla Goa Campus and we are indebted to ISAM for entrusting us this responsibility.

SWAYAM 2018 explores the challenges and advances in Applied Mechanics and Design Engineering and offers great opportunities to research scholars, young students, faculty members and scientists to share the recent advancements and future trends in the different aspects of Solid Mechanics, Fluid Mechanics, Material Science, Biomedical Engineering and Design Engineering.

Around 120 research papers from all over the country were received, reviewed and 106 extended abstracts have been published in the proceedings. The organizing committee is very much grateful to all the authors who have shown interest and trust in this workshop and symposium. We hope the contributions contained in the proceedings will be fruitful and refreshing source of reference to all the researchers working in these areas.

The editors would like to acknowledge the efforts of all the authors for their research participation and choosing SWAYAM 2018 to present and share their research findings. It is their interest that has made SWAYAM 2018 a great event. We are thankful to our patron Prof. Raghurama G, Director, BITS Pilani, K. K. Birla Goa Campus, Goa for providing institute facility to organize this event successfully. The editors would like to express their gratitude to the advisory committee, organizing committee, reviewers, plenary and keynote speakers, sponsors and volunteers for their support and valuable contributions. We are also grateful to all those who have contributed, directly or indirectly, to the success of this workshop and symposium.

Sandeep Singh
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Augmented Thermophysical and Electromagnetic Transport Properties of Graphene Nanosuspensions

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Abstract

The lecture deals with the thermophysical and electromagnetic transport characteristics of graphene based nanofluids and nanogels and their augmentation vis-à-vis the base fluid in an externally applied electromagnetic fields. The first part deals with the thermophysical transport characteristics of graphene based nanofluids and nanogels, which includes the thermal conduction caliber and the viscous behavior of the fluids and gels as well as the viscoelastic nature of the gels. The graphene gels exhibit highly augmented thermal conductivities compared to the base polymer. The rheological and viscoelastic response of the pastes show promise as '*smart fluids*' and can be tuned towards targeted applications. The second part deals with the augmented charge transport capabilities of graphene based nanofluids, both in polar and non-polar medium. The dominant modes of charge transport in polar liquid based dilute nanofluids have been theorized. Nano-oils comprising stable and dilute dispersions of synthesized graphene nanoflakes have been experimentally observed to exhibit augmented dielectric breakdown strengths for the first time compared to the base transformer oils. Variant nano-oils comprising different graphene samples suspended in two different grades of transformer oils have yielded consistent and high degrees of enhancement in the breakdown strength. The last part deals with the electro and magnetorheological response of the graphene nanogels. The contents provide a clear and comprehensive picture of the physics and mechanisms behind the augmented thermophysical and electromagnetic transport in graphene nanofluids and nanogels and mathematically predicts the same for design and utility.

Nonlinear Vibrations of Cylindrical Shells

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Abstract

The nonlinear vibrations of thin walled circular/noncircular cylindrical shells is investigated computationally and experimentally. Some interesting results depicting circumferentially travelling wave response of different types (waves travelling in one direction over full circumference, waves travelling in opposite directions over halves of the circumference with variable/constant amplitudes), participation of sub-/super-harmonics including multiples of 1/2, 1/3 and side bands corresponding beating phenomena, presence of external resonance (1:1, 1:2, 1:3) and internal resonance (1:1, 1:2, 2:3) among different modes are brought out.

1. Introduction

Circular and noncircular thin walled cylindrical shells subjected to dynamic loading may undergo vibrations with amplitude of the order of their thickness or greater resulting in a significant effect of geometric nonlinearity. The nonlinear effect leads to amplitude dependence of the resonant frequencies, multi-valued region in the nonlinear frequency response curve, traveling wave response, internal and parametric resonance, participation of sub-or super-harmonics, quasi periodic response, chaotic response, etc. The experimental investigations of nonlinear vibration of structures are important to validate their numerical prediction and to explore new phenomena/modal interactions. Some of the recent reviews on the nonlinear vibrations of shells are due to Kubenko and Kovalchuk [1], Amabili and Paidoussis [2], Alijani and Amabili [3]. Circumferentially closed shells may depict hardening or softening depending on the mode of vibration/loading/boundary conditions/geometrical parameters due to the mid-surface stretching in radially outward motion and compression in the inward motion. In this work, steady state response of circular/noncircular cylindrical shells is investigated through finite element model, shooting technique, arc length continuation and experimental study.

2. Solution Methodology

The circular/noncircular cylindrical shells are modelled using first-order shear deformation theory and semi-analytical finite element method. The resulting governing equation of motion is given by:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\delta} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}\dot{\delta} + [\mathbf{K} + (1/2)\mathbf{K}_1(\delta) + (1/3)\mathbf{K}_2(\delta)]\delta = \mathbf{F} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{M} is mass matrix; \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{K}_1 , \mathbf{K}_2 are linear and nonlinear (linearly and quadratically dependent on displacement) stiffness matrices, damping matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \alpha\mathbf{M} + \beta\mathbf{K}$ (α , β : Rayleigh proportional damping parameters); $\ddot{\delta}$, $\dot{\delta}$ and δ are acceleration, velocity and displacement vectors. The steady state solution is obtained efficiently using shooting technique wherein the solution for state vector starts from an initial guess $\boldsymbol{\eta}_0$ and correction $\{\Delta\boldsymbol{\eta}\}$ is applied to this such that the periodicity condition is satisfied as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta(T, \boldsymbol{\eta}_0 + \Delta\boldsymbol{\eta}, \omega_F) \\ \dot{\delta}(T, \boldsymbol{\eta}_0 + \Delta\boldsymbol{\eta}, \omega_F) \end{Bmatrix} - \{\boldsymbol{\eta}_0 + \Delta\boldsymbol{\eta}\} \approx \{\mathbf{0}\} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is solved by first-order approximation (Taylor series) wherein the coefficients in the resulting equation are obtained using

$$\mathbf{M} \left. \frac{\partial \ddot{\delta}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}} \right|_{t+\Delta t} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \left. \frac{\partial \dot{\delta}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}} \right|_{t+\Delta t} + \mathbf{K}_T \Big|_{t+\Delta t} \left. \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}} \right|_{t+\Delta t} = [\mathbf{0}] \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_T \Big|_{t+\Delta t} = [\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_1(\delta) + \mathbf{K}_2(\delta)]_{t+\Delta t}$ is the tangent stiffness matrix.

The frequency response determination starts from forcing frequency slightly away from resonance region and whenever a bifurcation point is encountered, the solution is continued with the arc length continuation method. To increase the computational efficiency, asymptotic numerical method is used wherein the state variables vector is expanded in a polynomial series in path length, substituted in Eq. (1) and the resulting set of equations are solved using shooting technique. The typical experimental set-up is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Experimental setup.

Figure 2. Travelling wave response.

3. Results

The typical travelling wave response of a cylindrical shell is depicted in Figures 2 (computational) and 3 (experimental). In Figure 3, the circumferential variation of experimentally measured radial acceleration at different time instances is shown. The shifting peak acceleration location represents travelling wave response. The response spectra of an elliptical cylindrical shell depicting participation of sub-harmonics and side bands is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Radial acceleration variation along circumference at different time.

4. References

- [1] Kubenko V.D., Kovalchuk P.S., 1998, Nonlinear problems of the vibration of thin shells (review), *International Applied Mechanics*, 34, 703–728.
- [2] Amabili M., Paidoussis M.P., 2003, Review of studies on geometrically nonlinear vibrations and dynamics of circular cylindrical shells and panels, with and without fluid–structure interaction, *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, 56, 105–125.
- [3] Aljani F., Amabili M., 2014, Nonlinear vibrations of shells: a literature review from 2003 to 2013, *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, 58, 233–257.

Alternate Materials for Cement and Reinforcements for Application in Concrete

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Abstract

Concrete has undergone significant transformations in recent years. These include use of mineral admixtures as partial replacements for cement or fine aggregate and geopolymer concretes as a no cement concrete. Manufactured sand and aggregates and recycled wastes are becoming essential alternatives for aggregates. Fibers mixed into a concrete, bars made from glass, carbon or hybrid (glass and steel) fiber reinforcement with polyester or epoxy binders as rebars and fabrics made from glass and carbon together with an epoxy binder form a class of reinforcement. Experimental results and analytical procedures to predict the capacity of structural elements will be presented.

1. Overview

Self-compacting concrete (SCC) is a highly flow-able concrete that can spread easily under its own weight without segregation and blockage. Such a concrete is used to ensure the filling of spaces between heavily congested reinforced sections and in areas with restricted access to vibration. The proportioning of SCC is considered complex because it depends on various factors such as grain size distribution, quantity and quality of aggregates, distribution of sizes of aggregates, dosage and quality of superplasticizer, cement content, etc. A highly flow-able SCC should have a good flow-ability but an adequate resistance to segregation and bleeding, until the onset of hardening. High flow-ability of the mix can be achieved by increasing the water to powder ratio but this reduces cohesiveness of the mix. Due to this reason segregation of aggregate takes place which results in the blockage of the flow. Because of this inter-particle friction, the flow-ability will be restricted when SCC flows through the congested space between densely reinforced zones. Blockages can be eliminated by carefully reducing the inter-particle friction among coarse aggregate, sand and fines through proper proportioning and with the proper dosage of superplasticizers and viscosity enhancing admixtures. From the various proposed models, it is understood that the fluidity and viscosity of the paste is adjusted by careful selection of materials and proper proportioning of the cement and additives. Self-compact-ability can also be obtained by limiting the water/powder ratio and by adding a superplasticizer and a viscosity modifying admixture. The friction between particles can be reduced by using larger amounts of paste so that the coarse aggregate particles are fully coated with a layer of paste. This decreases the friction and increases the fluidity thus improving the homogeneity. The increased fluidity improves the passing ability of SCC through the narrow openings and gaps between reinforcement. However, these mix design methods require large number of trials to refine and obtain the target strength and flow-ability for the mix. The presentation will trace the developments leading up to a mix design basis for self-compacting concrete (SCC) that makes use of mineral admixtures like fly ash and micro silica.

Use of conventional rebar reinforcements and prestressing reinforcements in structural concrete applications to mitigate the weakness of concrete in tension have been in vogue for a very long time. Use of short fibers in the concrete mixing process to mitigate crack initiation and propagation at a micro-crack level is relatively newer and has been studied over the last few decades. The mechanical strength properties of steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) are closely related to the fiber parameters, matrix strength and their interaction. However, the matrix strength fiber interaction too contributes to the overall performance and needs to be accounted for its contributions in strength and durability of structural concrete. The fiber matrix interaction is an important factor that represents the strength enhancement due to the fiber bridging action across the micro-cracks in the concrete matrix. The presentation will highlight the significant enhancement in strength and durability of concrete through the use of fibers in a concrete matrix.

In recent years repair and retrofit of existing structures such as buildings, bridges, etc., has been amongst the most important challenges in Civil Engineering. The primary reason for strengthening of structures includes upgrading of its resistance to withstand underestimated loads, increase the load carrying capacity for higher permit loads, eliminating premature failure due to inadequate detailing, restoration of lost load carrying capacity due to corrosion or other types of degradation caused by aging, etc.

Different procedures have been developed to retrofit a variety of structural deficiencies. Strengthening of concrete members is accomplished by construction of external reinforced concrete or shotcrete jackets, by epoxy bonding of steel plates to the tension face of the member or by external post tensioning. A relatively new technique involves replacement of the steel plates by fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP) in the form of laminates or wraps. These studies have examined the performance of FRP repair / retrofit in both flexural load induced cracking and steel corrosion damage conditions and in the case of shear induced cracking type of damage. FRP offers the engineer an outstanding combination of properties such as low weight, easier site handling, immunity from corrosion, excellent mechanical strength and stiffness, and the ability of formation in long lengths, thus eliminating the need for lap joints. Concrete having a high early gain in strength; normal strength concretes exhibiting high levels of durability, and self-compacting concrete containing fiber cocktails exhibiting high levels of straining capacity have been developed. Use of such concretes meeting high requirements of durability and strength has also opened up the possibility for the use of this new concrete material in the process of repair. The present study evaluates the performance of three repair materials (GFRP, CFRP and SCC with fibers-2 mixes) in repair of flexure/shear induced damage in flanged reinforced concrete beams under monotonic four-point loading.

Although steel is most commonly used as a reinforcing material in concrete due to its competitive cost and favorable mechanical properties, the problem of corrosion of steel rebars leads to a reduction in life span of the structure and adds to maintenance costs. Many techniques have been developed in recent past to reduce corrosion (galvanizing, epoxy coating, etc.) but none of the solutions seem to be viable as an adequate solution to the corrosion problem. Apart from the use of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) rebars, hybrid rebars consisting of both FRP and steel are also being tried to overcome the problem of steel corrosion. This paper evaluates the performance of hybrid rebars as longitudinal reinforcement in normal strength concrete beams.

2. Closing Remarks

The presentation will highlight the current developments in mix proportioning of self-compacting concrete making use of mineral and chemical admixtures to meet mechanical strength requirements together with ease in placement techniques. Use of short fibers in conjunction with conventional rebar and prestressing is also examined in the context of superior strength and durability in structural concrete applications. Finally, developments in rehabilitation and retrofit through the use of FRP polymer sheets/wraps as an external reinforcement and pultruded rebars as a replacement to conventional reinforcements is discussed to show its potential in diverse range of applications covering both short and long term durability aspects.

Umbilical Release Mechanisms for a Releasable Vehicle

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Abstract

Umbilical connection extends between a canister and a releasable flight vehicle. This is to be retracted i.e. physically separated just after the initiation or launch of the releasable vehicle using a special mechanism or an arrangement. Often, this separation needs to be at an inclination to the longitudinal axis of the vehicle which poses many challenges in conceptualization and design. A new mechanism was designed, realized, and functional tested successfully in a flight trial. This paper presents this mechanism for an inclined retraction of an electrical umbilical connection and details the requirement specifications, principle, configuration design and functionality. Further, it briefly discusses few other release mechanisms for axial and radial retractions of umbilical connection.

1. Introduction

An electrical umbilical extends between a releasable flight vehicle (RV) and a canister (or a host / mother vehicle). This umbilical connection between RV and canister allows the communication of information in both directions and operational commands and power from the canister to the RV before the RV is mechanically separated. The electrical umbilical connection is featured with an electrical cord terminated with an umbilical connector plug which is attached or engaged firmly with the umbilical receptacle. This umbilical cord and the connector plug are a part of the canister whereas the umbilical receptacle is a part of the RV. This electrical umbilical cord with the connector plug needs to be retracted or detached (mechanically separated) from the RV after the RV travels a predetermined distance just after the launch of the RV. This release in most cases is perpendicular (i.e. radial) or inclined to the longitudinal axis of the vehicle. In few other cases, this release can be axial to the vehicle. Design for physical separation of the umbilical in inclined direction poses many challenges. Particularly, it needs a special mechanism that meets all requirements for retraction.

There are a few special mechanisms and arrangements adopted in practice and are available in open literature [1-5] but are associated with many limitations for their suitability for an inclined umbilical retraction. This paper presents a new mechanism for an inclined retraction of an electrical umbilical connection extending between a canister and a RV that overcomes many limitations and readily adaptable for such requirements. The requirement specifications, principle, configuration design, and functional tests of this mechanism will be presented. Few other mechanisms for axial and radial umbilical retractions will be discussed for a comprehensive understanding of these retraction mechanisms.

2. Requirement Specifications

There are few essential requirements that the design of an umbilical retraction mechanism for an inclined retraction must comply. These requirements are specifications derived based on the actual requirement of umbilical retraction in RV's launch condition. They are:

- a) Retraction distance must be minimum 30 mm from the projected RV's fairing and it should not interfere with any parts of the RV viz. wings and control surfaces during powered movement of RV;
- b) Minimum force required to retract umbilical connectors must be of 20 kgf;
- c) Retraction force must be applied along axis of the connectors;
- d) Feasibility to tolerate probable misalignments arising from practical integration;
- e) Easy assembly and disassembly of mechanism with the RV as well as with the Canister;
- f) The mechanism shall not offer any kind of pulling force onto the connectors before launch of RV;
- g) Total height of mechanism (in assembled condition) should not exceed 175 mm which is the maximum available gap between canister and RV in loaded condition; and
- h) It should be simple, compact without any loose parts and reliable.

3. Principle of Mechanism

The umbilical retraction mechanism (URM) designed to meet the requirement specifications is based on the principle of a four bar mechanism as shown in Figure 1. This consists of a short link and a long link attached over a rigid base link of the canister wherein a connecting link links the short and long links and also carries the umbilical connector plug for engagement with the umbilical receptacle located within the RV. This mechanism is driven by a spring actuator which is connected between the rigid stationary link and the short link.

Figure 1. Principle of an umbilical retraction mechanism.

The principle of this URM is a simple four bar kinematic linkage mechanism and is conceived with additional features to offer special advantages. This mechanism operates between two extreme positions (initial and final) and one intermittent or retraction position. In the *initial position*, the umbilical connector plug attached to the connecting link of URM is engaged with the umbilical receptacle in the RV. In *retraction position*, the umbilical connector plug experiences a maximum retraction force due to the powered movement of the RV on one side and a resistance offered to the connector plug by the mechanism on the other side due to which the umbilical retraction occurs. The *final position* is achieved after the umbilical connector plug is retracted from the umbilical receptacle of RV.

4. Summary

An umbilical retraction mechanism for an inclined umbilical retraction is presented in this paper. This mechanism retracts the umbilical connector plug from the umbilical receptacle residing within the RV just after the initiation of the RV from the canister. This is designed based on the principle of a four bar kinematic linkage mechanism and featured with provisions to meet the requirement specifications of this mechanism. This was designed, realized, functionally tested at laboratory and it performed well in actual flight test of a RV. More details on few other special mechanisms for axial and radial umbilical retractions will be elaborated in extended presentations.

5. References

- [1] Reed RE, 1973, Retractable electrical connector for missiles, *United States Patent-3,724,322*.
- [2] Griffin D, Field, CA, 1987, Missile launcher, *United States Patent-4,711,151 A*.
- [3] Hutchinson DA, Nunn J, 1998, Umbilical cord for projectile launching device, *United States Patent-5,710,388 A*.
- [4] Hardo PJ, 2007, Umbilical retractable assembly and method, *United States Patent-7,182,013 B1*.
- [5] Gopinath K, Narayanamurthy V, Umakanth M, Gopinath, S, 2012, Umbilical retraction mechanism, Indian patent: 2670/DEL/2012.
- [6] Gopinath K, Narayanamurthy V, Umakanth M, Gopinath, S, 2014, A detachment mechanism, Indian patent: 1893/DEL/2014.

A Novel Error Indicator and an Adaptive Refinement Technique Over Polygons

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a novel error indicator based on the scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM) for arbitrary polygons in two dimensions. The SBFEM is a semi-analytical approach that combines the best features of the boundary element method and the conventional finite element method. The salient feature of the proposed approach is that the local error is estimated directly from the solution of the scaled boundary governing equations without requiring any stress recovery techniques. The accuracy and the robustness of the proposed error indicator and refinement technique are demonstrated with a few numerical examples.

1. Introduction

The accuracy and the convergence properties of the finite element method (FEM) depend on the shape of the element and the nodal spacing. Typical refinements involve h -, p - and hp - refinement technique that either reduce the size of the element or increase the order of approximation or a combination of the both. An important requirement in an adaptive analysis is the error indicator. The error indicator identifies the location within the mesh topology that needs to be refined. When exact and/or analytical solutions are not available, post-processing techniques are used to estimate the error, which is normally done by recovery methods. Another approach would be use a complementary energy formulation, however, it is not popular as it involves global computations. In this paper, we propose a novel error indicator based on the scaled boundary finite element solutions. We employ arbitrary polygons with linear elements on the boundary and h -adaptive mesh refinement. A novel mesh refinement strategy for the polygons is also proposed. Recently with the introduction of the polygonal element method, the aforementioned restriction on the element topology is relaxed. Of the different approaches available in the literature to employ the polygonal elements within the Galerkin framework, the scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM) is getting popular. This is because, the SBFEM can handle arbitrary polygons and can model singularities of any type [1,2,4]. Moreover, the method transforms the governing PDE into set of ODEs.

2. Overview of the Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method

The SBFEM is a semi-analytical method, developed by Wolf and Song [1] and finds applications in both bounded and unbounded domain problems. The salient feature of the method is the flexibility of its formulation. Unlike the conventional FEM, which limits the type of discretization to simplex elements, the SBFEM can handle elements with arbitrary shapes and sizes. The only restriction is that the arbitrary sided polygons should satisfy the star convexity condition, i.e., the boundary of the polygon is visible from the geometric center. The first step is to transform the coordinates to the scaled boundary coordinate system, given by:

$$\{x(\xi, \eta)\} = \xi \{N(\eta)\} \{x_b\} \quad (1)$$

The corresponding displacement field and the strain field within an element is expressed in terms of the scaled boundary coordinates. Upon following the approach given in [1,2,4], we end up with the following scaled boundary equation:

$$\{E_o\} \xi^2 \left\{ u(\xi) \right\}_{,\xi\xi} + (\{E_o\} + \{E_1^T\} - \{E_1\}) \xi u(\xi)_{,\xi} - \{E_2\} u(\xi) = 0 \quad (2)$$

The above equation is an Euler-Cauchy differential equation whose general solution is given by $u(\xi) = \xi^{-\lambda} \{\phi\} \{c\}$, where c are the integrations constants that depend on the boundary conditions. With this, the total potential energy can be written as an additive sum of energy contributed by the displacement modes that are exactly reproduced and the energy contributed by the higher order displacement modes that are reproduced

only approximately by an element. This approximate component is used as the error indicator in this study. For more details, interested readers are referred to [1, 2, 4] and references therein.

3. Numerical Example

To show the adaptability of the proposed error indicator for problems with corner singularity, an L-shaped domain, which is a portion of an infinite domain, is considered. The geometry and boundary conditions of the domain are shown in Figure 2. Traction corresponding to the first symmetric term of the asymptotic expansion that describes the exact solution under mode I loading conditions around the singular vertex is applied (along the dashed red lines in Figure 2). The domain is discretized with arbitrary polygons. Based on the error indicator obtained from the scaled boundary equations, the elements are ordered in terms of increasing error and refined employing a hierarchical data structure. This is based on the principle of recursive spatial decomposition of a parent element with n ($n > 3$) nodes into $(n+1)$ arbitrary children. The domain in the polytree substructure is arbitrary with an initial polygonal mesh and a representative polytree mesh as shown in Figure 1. During refinement, hanging nodes are generated if new elements and their neighbors are at different levels of refinement. The presence of hanging nodes is not a problem for the current formulation, as the SBFEM treats the elements with hanging nodes as another polygonal element. Interested readers are referred to [3] for the details of the implementation and the pseudo code. The exact displacement and the stress fields are given in [4]. The material properties are Young's modulus $E=1000$ N/m² and Poisson's ratio = 0.3. A state of plane stress condition is assumed. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the mesh with adaptive refinement using linear elements. It can be inferred that the refinement is restricted to the vicinity of the re-entrant corner.

Figure 1. Schematic of discretization of the domain with arbitrary polygons and a representative tree.

Figure 2. L-shaped domain: geometry and boundary conditions and sequence of meshes.

4. Summary

A novel error indicator and an adaptive refinement technique over arbitrary polygon were presented. The error indicator can be computed directly computed from the scaled boundary equations without requiring additional stress recovery techniques. From the numerical example presented, it can be inferred that the proposed technique is robust and accurate.

5. References

- [1] C. Song, J. P. Wolf, 1997, The scaled boundary finite-element method-alias consistent infinitesimal finite-element cell method-elastodynamics., *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.*, vol. 147, no. 3-4, pp. 329-355.
- [2] E. T. Ooi, C. Song, F. Tin-Loi, 2012, Polygon scaled boundary finite element for crack propagation modeling, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering.*, vol. 91, pp. 319-342.
- [3] H. Nguyen-Xuan, 2017, A polytree-based adaptive polygonal finite element method for topology optimization, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering.*, vol. 110, pp. 972-1000.
- [4] C. Song, E. T. Ooi, A. L. N. Pramod, S. Natarajan, 2018, A novel error indicator and an adaptive refinement technique using the scaled boundary finite element method, *Engineering Analysis with Boundary Elements.*

Challenges in Computation of Turbulent Slot Jet Impinging on a Heated Wall

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Abstract

Computations of impinging slot jet for high and low nozzle-to-plate spacings have been performed and discussed. Computations using the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations based turbulence models and large eddy simulations (LES) have been performed in order to obtain detailed flow and thermal characteristics. For the case of low spacing the standard $k-\omega$ and SST $k-\omega$ models and for high spacing the standard $k-\epsilon$ model showed good agreement with the reported experimental results. LES computations of mean and instantaneous flow and thermal characteristics were observed to be close to the reported experimental results.

1. Introduction

Jet impingement heat transfer is widely used in industrial applications as an effective way of heat transfer between a fluid and a solid surface. Jet impingement heat transfer techniques are used wherever high performance cooling, heating or drying of a surface is required. Some important industrial applications [1] are cooling/heating of electrical equipment, drying requirement associated with textile industries, cooling of turbine blades, cooling of outer combustor wall, etc. Apart from its industrial significance it is widely used to test computational models, such as, RANS based turbulence models, LES models and hybrid models [1-3]. A jet impingement involves several complex flow and heat transfer phenomena, such as, free jet, potential core region, stagnation zone, wall jet region and existence of secondary peak in Nusselt number profiles for low nozzle-to-plate spacing [4-5]. Computations with all these complexities is a challenging task [1-3, 5]. Different RANS based turbulence models considered in the literature for impinging jet were not able to predict flow and heat transfer characteristics accurately excluding a few [1-3]. Some researchers have reported that LES is capable of predicting flow field and heat transfer data within the accuracy limits [1, 5]. Direct numerical simulation (DNS) can be useful but is limited to simple geometry with low Reynolds number. The application of DNS is computationally more expensive than that for LES [1].

The present work deals with a numerical investigation of heat transfer and flow structures arising due to a planar slot jet impinging on a heated plane surface. The computations were performed using the packages ANSYS Fluent 15 and OpenFOAM 4.1. Several RANS turbulence models were tested on a planar jet impinging on a smooth surface. LES computations were also carried out and obtained results showed better accuracy with the reported experimental data compared to those using RANS models.

2. General Specifications

Figure 1. (a, b) Computational domain and important boundary conditions; (c, d, e) typical flow characteristics of iso-surface of low pressure, mean and instantaneous velocity contours.

Figure 1 shows details of the computational domain considered in the present study and typical flow pattern. Figure 1a shows 2D computational domain for RANS computations and Figure 1b 3D computational domain for LES computations of jet impingement on flat surface. The no slip boundary condition was applied at all the walls (confined and impingement walls). A constant temperature was considered at the impingement plate. A fully

developed velocity profile observed in experiments was applied at the nozzle exit with the specification of the nozzle exit velocity U based on Re with turbulence intensity (I) and turbulent length scale. The outflow boundary conditions were applied at sufficiently large distance to avoid a reversed flow. Periodic boundary conditions were applied at $z = 0$, $W[1]$.

3. Equations

In the RANS approach, the time-averaged governing equations are solved. The instantaneous velocity field can be decomposed into its mean (time-averaged) $\bar{u}_i(x)$ and fluctuating components $u'_i(x, t)$, such that, $\bar{u}'_i = 0$. The time-averaged governing equations for the conservations of mass, momentum and energy can be written as (here all symbols have their standard meanings):

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \rho \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (2\mu \bar{\delta}_{ij} - \rho \overline{u'_i u'_j}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\kappa}{c_p} \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial x_j} - \rho \overline{u'_i T'} \right) \quad (3)$$

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 2. Nu Profiles for (a, d) $H/B = 4$ and 9.2 (RANS computations); (c) $H/B = 4$ (LES computations).

Figure 2 shows Nusselt number profiles obtained using different RANS based turbulence models and LES computations with Smagorinsky's SGS model. From Figure 2a one can observe that the standard and SST $k-\omega$ models perform better than other turbulence models. Both the models show a secondary peak in Nu as in reported experimental data. For high spacing the standard $k-\epsilon$ model performed better than other models, which showed a false secondary peak in Nu . A secondary peak in Nu can also be seen in LES computations for low spacing in accordance with the experimental data [4] (Figure 2c). Other flow quantities, such as, instantaneous, mean and turbulence profiles of velocity, temperature, etc., were also studied from the computations of RANS and LES. LES computations of turbulent slot jet impingement were observed to be quite accurate.

5. Summary

We have observed that the standard $k-\omega$ and SST $k-\omega$ models were able to predict a secondary peak in Nusselt number for low H/B value. The standard $k-\epsilon$ model was found to be appropriate for high H/B value. Turbulence quantities predicted by LES were more accurate than those by RANS computations.

6. References

- [1] Shukla AK, Dewan A, 2017, Flow and thermal characteristics of jet impingement: comprehensive review, Int. J. of Heat and Tech., 35, 153-166.
- [2] Shukla AK, Dewan A, 2017, Convective heat transfer enhancement using slot jet impingement on a detached rib surface, J. of Applied Fluid Mechanics, 10 (6), 117-126.
- [3] Dutta R, Dewan A, Srinivasan B, 2013, Comparison of various integration to wall (ITW) RANS models for predicting turbulent slot jet impingement heat transfer, Int. J. of Heat and Mass Transf., 65, 750-764.
- [4] Ashforth-Frost S, Jambunathan K, Whitney CF, 1997, Velocity and turbulence characteristics of a semiconfined orthogonally impinging slot jet, Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science, 14, 60–67.
- [5] Dutta R, Dewan A, Srinivasan B, 2016, Large eddy simulation of Turbulent slot jet impingement heat transfer at small nozzle-to-plate spacing, Heat Transfer Engineering, 37, 142-1251.

Damage Detection of Beam Using EMI Technique

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Abstract

Researchers from the globe are trying to replace Conventional Non-Destructive technique using smart material i.e. Piezo-ceramics. The electro-mechanical impedance technique is the most powerful technique due to its simplicity and online monitoring application of aircraft, ship etc is the principle behind the electro-mechanical impedance technique is to excite the PZT (lead Zirconate Titanate) transducer bonded to the monitored structure by means of impedance analyzer and to measure the electrical Impedance of receiving signal. A change in the electrical impedance values indicates a change in the properties & dimensions of the structure. There are many kinds of damage whose intensity is very difficult to calculate by other methods but using electro-mechanical impedance it is possible to calculate the intensity of such damages by using damage indexes such as Root mean square deviation, and cross-correlation co-efficient such damages are corrosion, non-linear crack, change in the room temperature or dis-connectivity to the system. The aim of the electro-mechanical impedance is to introduce the voltage (transmission) signal in to the structure by the means of PZT and Impedance analyzer if there is any change in the structure properties and dimensions there will be a change in the impedance Vs frequency graph which records by the help of impedance analyze.

Keywords: Electrical Impedance, Impedance analyzer, Root mean square deviation, Damage, Piezo-ceramics.

1. Introduction

Structural health monitoring (SHM) is a real world application that tells the status of the structures like aircraft, buildings, bridges etc or it is the early damage detection warning technique. Due to the environmental factors like excessive heat, rain etc. Material will suffer from mechanical properties like strength, stiffness. The objective of SHM is to provide high level of safety and security. There are several methods under SHM like ultrasonic testing, eddy current testing but our main attention is on electro-mechanical impedance technique. In this technique, PZT (piezo-ceramics) transducer bonded to the structure to be monitored. PZT has a piezoelectric effect due to this property there is an interaction between electric impedance of PZT and Mechanical impedance of the structure any change in the mechanical properties or dimensions of structure there is a corresponding change in the electric impedance of the PZT.

Figure 1. PZT patch bonded to the structure is connected to the Impedance Analyzer.

2. Principle

A PZT (Piezo-ceramics) Patch is surface bonded to the monitored structure as shown in Figure 1. PZT patch is

dynamically excited by a transmitting voltage signal sourced by an impedance analyzer. PZT has a piezoelectric effect that converts electrical in to a mechanical energy (vibration, stress) by the property of PZT vibration/stress is introduced in to the monitored structure. The structural response at different excitation frequency will results in the receiving electric signal across the PZT patch. The complex electrical admittance (conductance and susceptance signatures)/electrical impedance are measured by the impedance analyzer at required frequency range. Any subsequent damage on the structure causes a change in structural response can be reflected to the electrical impedance/admittance values which is recorded by the Impedance Analyzer [1, 2].

3. Result

Figure 2. Rmsd, Ccmd and Mapd values of small, medium and large damage.

Rmsd: Root mean square deviation, Ccmd: cross-correlation mean deviation, Mapd: Mean amplitude percentage deviation.

As we increase the size of the screw nut the Damage signature Rmsd, Ccmd, Mapd will increase. The damage signature is low for small Screw nut and high for large screw nut. In our case Mapd is more dominating than Rmsd and Ccmd.

4. References

- [1] F. G. Baptista and J. Vieira Filho, A new impedance measurement system for PZT based structural health monitoring, *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 58, no. 10, pp. 3602–3608, Oct. 2009.
- [2] V. Giurgiutiu and C. A. Rogers, Electro-mechanical (E/M) impedance method for structural health monitoring and nondestructive evaluation, in *Proc. Int. Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring*, Stanford, CA, 1997, pp. 433–444.

Methodology for Vibration Isolation of Snorkel Duct

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Abstract

The current work presents a methodology for the design of snorkel duct mounting system used in construction vehicles to address the issue of vibration isolation. The methodology is formulated in analytical and numerical form to develop the concepts of the snorkel rigid body modes for existing mountings. Impact testing is conducted for in-use rubber mounts to characterize them and use the data in numerical model. The numerical approach is extended further to formulate the optimization of mount parameters. The proposed methodology is validated by comparing the numerical results of the isolated snorkel response with the experimental vibration measurements.

1. Introduction

The Chassis and Vehicle Dynamics Engineering team at Volvo Group India, is in need of a methodology to improve the dynamic response of the snorkel air inlet duct assembly of construction vehicles. This is to ensure reliable functioning of snorkel without undue failures due to different source of vibration excitations. The typical source of excitations is originated due to the use of vehicle on different road profiles and at different engine operating conditions. Permanent deformation and cracks at the snorkel mounting regions are considered as the major issues due to prolonged direct interaction of forces. This necessitates isolation of snorkel duct from such excitations by flexible mounting using isolation mounts over the cabin rear surface.

2. General Specifications

The analytical and numerical models of the snorkel is built to predict the rigid body natural frequencies [1]. The validated numerical model is updated to include mount optimization capability [2]. The dynamic vibration response is predicted for a given set of input excitation profiles. These excitation profiles are the actual field measurements on a truck during its testing over the *torture track*. The outcome of the numerical model gives the isolation mount characteristics i.e., stiffness and damping of mounts that would minimize the vibrations.

3. Equations

The snorkel duct is treated as a rigid part having its mass and inertia properties defined at its center of gravity location. The governing equation of motion for undamped in-plane (Lateral, Vertical, Roll) and out-of-plane (Longitudinal, Pitch, Yaw) motions is presented below.

$$\begin{bmatrix} m & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & I_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \\ \ddot{\theta} \\ \ddot{\phi} \\ \ddot{\psi} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{15} & K_{16} \\ 0 & K_{22} & 0 & K_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{33} & K_{34} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_{42} & K_{43} & K_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ K_{51} & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{55} & K_{56} \\ K_{61} & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{65} & K_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ \theta \\ \phi \\ \psi \end{Bmatrix} = \{0\} \quad (1)$$

The natural frequencies of snorkel rigid body modes are obtained for a nominal mount stiffness value input. The numerical model is formulated using commercial FEA software and the model is validated with the analytical results (Table 1).

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the rigid body mode natural frequencies of snorkel with an assumed mount stiffness value of 100 N/mm in three orthogonal directions.

The numerical model is further validated with experimental vibration measurements on a truck fitted with in-use mounts. The experiments are conducted at idle engine operating speed of 600 rpm and the vibration spectrum is

measured at different mounted locations of the snorkel duct. A good correlation is obtained in the frequency content of the numerical and experimental results (Figure 1).

Table 1. Natural frequencies for snorkel rigid body motions in Hz.

Mode No.	Analytical	Numerical		Mode shape pattern (from FEA)
		*	\$	
1.	33.53	32.06	32.91	Longitudinal x' translation
2.	35.21	34.48	34.38	Lateral y' translation
3.	40.46	40.44	40.44	Vertical z' translation
4.	47.03	51.09	49.20	Rotation about z'
5.	65.76	66.13	64.87	Rotation about y'
6.	67.39	70.10	74.95	Rotation about x'

Without (*) and with (\$) off-diagonal inertia tensor terms.

Figure 1. Comparison of vibration spectrum for experimental and numerical results at snorkel top mount location.

5. Summary

The present work ensures that the numerical model can be used to optimize the mount parameters and predict the response of the snorkel with the optimized mount parameters.

6. References

- [1] Shangguan, W.B., Liu, X.A., Lv, Z.P. and Rakheja, S., 2016. Design method of automotive powertrain mounting system based on vibration and noise limitations of vehicle level. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 76, pp.677-695.
- [2] Suresh, N., Shankar, S. and Bokil, V., 1994. Development of idealistic hydromount characteristics to minimize engine induced vibrations using unconstrained minimization (No. 941741). SAE Technical Paper.

Nonlinear Static Analysis of Shallow Panels On Rectangular Plan-Form

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Abstract

Nonlinear static response of singly and doubly curved shallow panels on rectangular plan-form is investigated analytically in the present analysis. Mathematical formulation is based on higher order shear deformation theory and Von Karman non-linearity. The governing equations of equilibrium are obtained using principle of virtual work. Fast converging finite double Chebyshev series is used for special discretization. The nonlinear equations are linearized using quadratic extrapolation technique. The accuracy of the present solution methodology is checked by the convergence study of the central displacement and bending moment. The effect of different parameters on central displacement and bending moment of laminated composite shallow curved panels are investigated.

Keywords: Nonlinear analysis, analytical solution, higher order shear deformation theory, doubly curved panels, Chebyshev polynomial.

1. Introduction

In the last few decades, fiber reinforced laminated composites panels have gained considerable attention of the researchers due to their tailoring properties according to the requirements. Curved panels of different materials are used as structural members in many industries such as automobile, aerospace, chemical, naval, civil structures and many others. The tremendous increase in the use of laminated composite material is due to their attractive properties like, enhanced corrosion resistance and the possibility to get the optimal design by changing the stacking sequence and fiber orientation. Plates/panels have been analyzed by many researchers using different numerical and analytical methods. Utilizing extended Sanders' shell theory, Reddy and Chandrashekhara [1] obtained geometrically nonlinear response of laminated composite shells. Sabir and Djoudi [2] presented geometrically nonlinear behaviour of shallow shells using finite element method with linearized incrementation and Newton Raphson technique. Mahapatra et al. [3] obtained results for large deformation of singly and doubly curved panels on rectangular plan-form, using HSDT with Green Lagrange nonlinearity. Sahoo et al. [4] used finite element method to investigate the nonlinear static behavior of composite curved panels.

In the present study, the nonlinear flexural response of singly and doubly curved panels on rectangular plan-form, subjected to uniformly distributed transverse loading is presented. Mathematical formulation is based on the higher order shear deformation theory and principle of virtual work is used to obtain the governing partial differential equations. Quadratic extrapolation technique is used to linearize the nonlinear terms. Fast converging finite double Chebyshev series is used for spatial discretization of governing partial differential equations.

2. Mathematical Formulation

In the present work, governing differential equations are obtained using higher order shear deformation theory with third order variation of in-plane displacement and constant transverse displacement. At a point in the panel, the displacement field is given as:

$$\begin{aligned}u(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + z\psi_x(x, y) + z^2u_1(x, y) + z^3\phi_x(x, y) \\v(x, y, z) &= v_0(x, y) + z\psi_y(x, y) + z^2v_1(x, y) + z^3\phi_y(x, y) \\w(x, y, z) &= w_0(x, y)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where, u_0, v_0 are the in-plane displacements and w_0 is the transverse displacement of a point (x, y) on the middle plane of the panel, respectively. The functions ψ_x, ψ_y are the rotations of the normal to the middle plane about y and x -axes, respectively. u_1, v_1 and ϕ_x, ϕ_y are the higher order terms in the Taylor's series expansion, representing higher order transverse cross-sectional deformation modes.

3. Strain-Displacement Relations

Assuming thickness of the panel very much less than the radii of curvatures ($h \ll R_x, R_y$), the general strain-displacement relations are given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{w}{R_x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2, \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{w}{R_y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2, \quad \gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}, \\ \gamma_{yz} &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \frac{v}{R_y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \quad \gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \frac{u}{R_x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

4. Results and Discussion

The following material properties are considered for the analysis:

$$E_1=175.78 \text{ GPa}, E_2=7.0312 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}/E_2= G_{13}/E_2=0.5, G_{23}/E_2=0.2, \nu_{12}=0.25.$$

Figures 1 and 2 show the convergence of non-dimensional transverse central displacement (w_0^*) and bending moments (\bar{M}_x) of a moderately thick ($a/h=20$), symmetric (0/90/90/0) cross-ply doubly curved panel ($R/a=10$) on the square plan-form. Displacement and moments show good convergence at 9-10 terms expansion of the variables. In further analysis, 9 terms expansion of the displacement variables in Chebyshev series is taken.

Figure 1. Convergence of nonlinear central displacement.

Figure 2. Convergence of nonlinear bending moment (M_x).

where M, N are the number of terms in the Chebyshev series expansion.

5. Summary

Only convergence of central displacement and bending moments is shown in results and discussion due to sake of brevity. Results with discussion and concluding remarks will be included in the full length paper.

6. References

- [1] Reddy JN, Chandrashekhara K. 1985. Nonlinear analysis of laminated shells including transverse shear strains, *AIAA Journal* 23(3), 441-443.
- [2] Sabir AB, Djoudi MS. 1995. Shallow shell finite element for the large deflection geometrically nonlinear analysis of shells and plates, *Thin-Walled Structures* 21, 253-267.
- [3] Mahapatra TR, Kar VR, Panda SK. 2016. Large amplitude bending behaviour of laminated composite curved panels, *International Journal for Computer-Aided Engineering and Software* 33(1), 116-138.
- [4] Sahoo SS, Singh VK, Panda SK. 2016. Nonlinear flexural analysis of shallow carbon/epoxy laminated composite curved panels: experimental and numerical investigation, *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, 142(4), 04016008.

A Numerical Investigation into The Collapse Behavior of Thin Walled Grooved Tubes Under Axial Impact

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Abstract

In this paper, a numerical simulation has been performed on thin-walled circular mild steel tubes to investigate the transition between dynamic progressive buckling and dynamic plastic buckling mechanism. The mild steel tube has a moderate diameter-to-thickness ratio and was examined over a range of axial length, impact velocity and impactor mass. Standard collapse modes developed in the tubes and the associated energy absorbing characteristics have been examined and compared with thin walled 'V' shape groove with different groove depth, width, and groove angle.

1. Introduction

In the axial impact of thin-walled tubes, two buckling mechanisms are active in the initial stages of impact loading; these are dynamic progressive buckling and dynamic plastic buckling mechanisms. The dominance of deformation mechanism depends on impactor mass and velocity besides the geometric and material properties of the structure. In general, the high-speed impact causes dynamic plastic buckling under some special conditions whilst low-speed impact leads to dynamic progressive buckling. In low-velocity impact, since the strain distribution is uniform, it is taken as quasi-static and the influence of inertia forces is ignored. The wrinkles develop progressively and the phenomenon is known as dynamic progressive buckling. During the dynamic plastic buckling, a uniform axial deformation along the length of the structure occurs, and half-wave buckling lobes arise [1]. Depending on these collapse mechanisms, the crash parameters such as maximum crash force and absorbed energy amount varies. Karagiozova and Jones [1] explored the influence of approximation of strain hardening modulus on the type of buckling shape (plastic or progressive buckling) and also the effect of axial inertia on initiation and development of buckling shape of tubes under axial impact. The effect of different parameters such as material properties, geometry and impact velocity on the peak load of the tube subjected to axial impact is investigated by Chen and Ushijima [2] and an approximate equation for estimation of peak load at a relatively low velocity was proposed. The effect of grooves on the crashworthiness characteristics and the energy absorption behavior of thin walled tubes was examined experimentally and analytically under quasi-static loading condition in [3]. In the present study, the transition between dynamic progressive buckling and dynamic plastic buckling mechanism are investigated by numerical simulation by considering the geometrical intensity. All simulations were explicitly run in ABAQUS software.

2. Numerical Model and Validation

The geometric dimensions and material properties of thin-walled mild steel tube are taken as Table 1, the D , t , L , ρ , E , σ_y , σ_u show the tube diameter, tube thickness, tube length, density, elastic modulus, yield strength and ultimate strength respectively.

Table 1. The dimensions and mechanical properties of steel tube.

D (mm)	t (mm)	L (mm)	ρ (kg/m ³)	E (GPa)	σ_y (MPa)	σ_u (MPa)
91	2	350	7800	210	292	488

Impact simulation was performed via ABAQUS software. In the impact models, the nodes on one end of the tube were fixed whereas the other subjected to an impact by means of a rigid block modeled as axisymmetric.

3. Results and Discussion

The numerical simulation results were analyzed based on the load-displacement curves, the results show that the initial peak load becomes higher with increases of the impact velocity; however, tubes with grooves shape show a

remarkable reduction in initial peak load. Formation of wrinkles at higher velocities in the grooved tubes is better and can be observed from smooth force-displacement curve.

Figure 1. Numerical simulation of a thin-walled tube.

Figure 2. Force vs Displacement graph with groove.

Figure 3. Force vs Displacement graph of simple tube.

The detailed discussion on the transition between dynamic progressive buckling and dynamic plastic buckling mechanism will be presented in the full-length paper.

4. References

[1] Karagiozova D, Jones N, 2001, Influence of stress waves on the dynamic progressive and dynamic plastic buckling of cylindrical shells, International journals of solid and structure, 38, 6723-6749.
 [2] Chen DH, Ushijima K, 2011, Estimation of the initial peak load for circular tubes subjected to axial impact, Thin-walled structures, 49, 889-898.
 [3] Darvizeh M, Ansari A, Meshkinzar M, 2014, Analytical and experimental investigations into the controlled energy absorption characteristics of thick-walled tubes with circumferential grooves, J. Mech. Sci. Technol. 28 (10), 4199-4122.

Simulation and Analysis of Light Weight Bullet Proof Patka

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Abstract

This numerical study presents the effect of the shape of bullet and impact angle on ballistic impact response of bulletproof patka. A numerical model of bulletproof patka subjected to high-velocity impact is simulated with the help of commercial finite element tool ABAQUS. The FE analysis depicts that the ballistic impact response in terms of back face deformation largely depends on the angle of impact and shape of the bullet. Presently used patka is made of the metallic annular band which is quite heavy. The main objective of present study is to model the bulletproof patka with the three composite annular band. It is also observed that the extent of transverse deformation also depends on obliquity of the impact.

1. Introduction

Bulletproof patka has been used as an individual protection gear by armed forces. It offers protection around the forehead and sides of the head from fragmentation high-velocity bullets. Presently used patka is made of the metallic annular band and it is quite heavy. In view of above, a study is carried out to develop lightweight bulletproof patka to facilitate effective use by individuals. Many authors developed protective structure model of the helmet and widely used aramid composite Kevlar because of excellent mechanical properties, mainly high strength, high modulus, and high strength to weight ratio [1, 2]. Protective capabilities of patka are commonly evaluated in terms of two parameters like impact velocity and backface deformation (BFD).

2. Modeling of Bulletproof Patka and Projectile

a. Material and Geometrical Modeling of the Bulletproof Patka and Projectile

For the study, three composite annular band of different material is used. Each annular band consists six layers of thickness 0.25mm each. The outer composite annular band is made of Boron carbide epoxy for which elastic, plastic and failure properties are taken from Aare and Kleiven [3]. For plastic and failure model, Johnson-Cook model, neglecting the effect of high strain rate and thermal softening on material ductility is used. The ballistic dummy head form is constructed in cylindrical shape according to dimensions specified. The dummy head form material was aluminium and the clay which is taken from Aare and Kleiven [3]. The inner foam is also modeled using low-density foam material made available in ABAQUS which is intended for low density, highly compressible elastomeric foam. The projectile is supposed to be made-up of deformed material consisting of a penetrator head and filler cylindrical body and carriage jacket of pure metal.

b. Description of the FE Model

ABAQUS v6.16 is used for simulating the transverse impact with the constrained environment. An appropriate element size of patka is 2 mm and 1 mm for a projectile is used. For meshing, elements of brick type (C3D8R) are used. The element type of each layer of patka is solid. The friction coefficient of 0.2 is also introduced for sliding contact by using a hard contact-penalty algorithm. Edge of bulletproof patka is constrained at eight points. The projectile is given an initial velocity of 425 m/s and back face deformation is measured for each impact test. From the data, energy absorbed by fabric (ΔE) is calculated based on the change in the K.E. of the projectile.

3. Results and Discussion

In this section the numerical results obtained with the model of the bulletproof patka impact from different shape of the bullet. The analysis of BFD was carried out with different shape of the bullet on the bullet proof patka were conducted with 9 mm full metal jacket bullet. Figure 1 shows the maximum values for the cases of impact considered. The maximum BFD value was 5.935 mm for hemispherical shape of the bullet and 5.292 mm for cylindrical shape of bullet. The relationship of the BFD with time was presented in Figure 2 for three different shape of bullet.

Figure 1. Back face deformation of patka under 9 mm hemispherical bullet at the end impacts at 700 m/s.

Figure 2. Backface deformation comparison for different shapes of the bullet.

4. Summary

A bulletproof patka has a minimum back face deformation for conical shape of the bullet and has a maximum for cylindrical shape of the bullet which is shown in Figure 2. On increasing the obliquity backface deformation of patka is increased due to increasing of the surface contact region. Due to increase of curvature of patka back face deformation is decreased.

5. References

- [1] J. Van Hoof, D. S. Cronin, M. J. Worswick, K. V Williams, and D. Nandlall, Numerical head and composite helmet models to predict blunt trauma, in 19th International Symposium on Ballistics, Interlaken, Switzerland, pp. 7–11, May 2001.
- [2] C. Y. Tham, V. B. C. Tan, and H. P. Lee, Ballistic impact of a KEVLAR® helmet: Experiment and simulations, *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 304–318, 2008.
- [3] M. Aare and S. Kleiven, Evaluation of head response to ballistic helmet impacts using the finite element method, *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 596–608, 2007.

Mechanical Behavior of Polyurethane Foam Under Quasi-Static and Repeated Impact Loading

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Abstract

Polymeric foam materials are used as energy absorbing materials for protection in impact and the mechanical properties of these materials vary over a range of deformation rates. In view of this, an experimental evaluation of the the properties and impact response of open cell rigid Polyurethane foam under quasi-static and impact loading has been conducted. Uniaxial tensile test and shear test have been also performed to collect material properties. The result shows a significant change in mechanical property of foam under compression at different strain rates. It exhibits increasing stress with increasing deformation rate. Up to densification polyurethane foam is capable of high energy absorption in quasi-static compression.

1. Introduction

Cellular materials such as polyurethane foam (PU) are used in protective application, safety of packaging e.g. electronic component, aeronautical structure and for personal safety e.g. helmets, knee-pad and military applications [1]. They are also used as a core material for sandwich composite structures in aircraft, naval and automobile industry (e.g. seat cushions, bumper system, side impact protection system) because of their low density, relatively cheap, allow great design flexibility and high specific energy absorption capacity, where absorbed energy per unit volume is equal to area under stress – strain curve [2]. An efficient energy-absorbing materials have to dissipate the kinetic energy of the impact while keeping force below some limit, which is obtain by the use of polymeric foam as cushioning. The design of cushioning is affected by factors, like shape of structure which influence load transfer during impact and the ability to absorbed elastic energy, which controls rebound.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1. Material and Specimen

Investigation has been done on a high density open cell, rigid polyurethane foam of density 130 kg.m^{-3} . Specimen used for experiment is of dimension $25 \text{ mm} * 25 \text{ mm} * 25 \text{ mm}$ for quasi-static compression and direction of loading is in foam rise direction in all the cases.

2.2. Quasi-Static and Dynamic Experiment

Quasi-static tests were performed as per ASTM D1621 [3] on an electronically controlled universal testing machine (TINIUS OLSEN) with maximum load capacity 10 kN. In order to evaluate the quasi static mechanical behavior of PU foam, three compression tests at strain rate 5 min^{-1} , 7.5 min^{-1} and 10 min^{-1} have been performed Shear and uniaxial tensile tests have been also carried out to know the mechanical behavior of PU foam in shear and tension.

3. Results

During compression, PU foam compressed uniformly it can be seen in Figure 1a. The stress-strain curve exhibit three regions – a linear elastic phase (up to 5%) and slope gives the young modulus of foam, second is plateau where the foam is subjected to high strain without much increase in stress and in the third region, further increase in load leads to densification of collapsed cell wall (in the plateau region) causing stress to increases with little increases in strain. Figure 1b shows the quasi-static stress strain curve of PU foam subjected at strain rate 5 min^{-1} , 7.5 min^{-1} and 10 min^{-1} . The mechanical behavior result of rigid PU foam of density 288 kg/m^3 under quasi-static (0.0033 s^{-1}) compressive loading compared with result at strain 5 min^{-1} , 7.5 min^{-1} and 10 min^{-1} curve come similar in both the cases with yield strain (%) 2.00, plateau stress (MPa) 7.50 and densification strain (%) 26.0. The result of polyurethane foam obtained under quasi-static compressive loading at strain rate 5 min^{-1} , 7.5 min^{-1} and 10 min^{-1} is summarized in the Table 1. Clearly, it can be seen that foam subjected to high strain rate is capable to dissipate

more energy up to lockup strain in comparison to lower strain rate. The mechanical behavior of foam is affected by strain rate as it can be seen in Figure 1b.

Figure 1. (a) Specimen during compression; (b) Stress-strain curves for open cell rigid PU foam at strain rate 5 min⁻¹, 7.5 min⁻¹ and 10 min⁻¹.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of PU foam ($\rho=130 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

Property	5 min ⁻¹	7.5 min ⁻¹	10 min ⁻¹
Yield Stress (KPa)	17.28	19.20	20.00
Yield Strain (%)	3.20	2.70	1.40
Plateau Stress (KPa)	107.52	145.20	176
Densification Strain (%)	48	42	40

4. Conclusion

Although character of curve is similar in all strain rate, the plateau stress and densification stress increases as strain rate increases. It is clear from the graph that high strain rate is capable to high energy dissipation up to lockup strain. The range of foam i.e. strain at lockup occur reduced with increase in strain rate. Yield strength increases with increase in strain rate

5. References

- [1] Ouellet, S., Cronin, D. and Worswick, M., 2006. Compressive response of polymeric foams under quasi-static, medium and high strain rate conditions. *Polymer testing*, 25(6), 731-743.
- [2] L.J. Gibson, M.F. Ashby, *Cellular Solids, Structure and Properties*, second ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- [3] ASTM- D1621 10: Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Rigid Cellular Plastics.
- [4] Mane, J.V., Chandra, S., Sharma, S., Ali, H., Chavan, V.M., Manjunath, B.S. and Patel, R.J., 2017. Mechanical property evaluation of polyurethane foam under quasi-static and dynamic strain rates-an experimental study. *Procedia Engineering*, 173, 726-731.

Static Response of CNT Reinforced Composite Plates: Isogeometric Analysis

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Abstract

This paper presents an investigation on static response of *carbon nanotube reinforced composite (CNTRC)* plates using *isogeometric analysis (IGA)*, based on *first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT)*. Material properties of CNTRC are considered in four different types of volume fraction distribution varying across the thickness direction. *Non uniform rational B-spline (NURBS)* basis functions are used for interpolation of geometry as well as relevant field variables, for the formulation for isogeometric analysis. The formulation developed, is incorporated into a computer program developed in-house. Effect of different boundary conditions, volume fraction of CNT and aspect ratio with other parameters, on non-dimensional central deflection are evaluated, after due validation of the developed computer program.

1. Introduction

After the advent of *Carbon nanotubes (CNTs)*, relevant research was initially focused on finding their thermal, mechanical, electrical and other properties through experimental and computational means. Once their basic properties became evident, including properties like light weight, high elastic modulus, strength and resilience, their potential for use as reinforcing element on polymer / metal matrix based composites was recognized. Subsequently, evaluations of effective material properties of such *CNT reinforced composites (CNTRCs)* caught the attention of some researchers, e.g., Liu and Chen [1]. Once the excellent mechanical properties of such CNTRCs became evident, they started to be researched for application as primary load bearing structural components like plates. In this direction, Phung-Van et al. [2] investigated the static and dynamic behaviour of square CNTRC plates using the *isogeometric analysis (IGA)* based on a *higher order shear deformation theory (HSDT)*. Some investigations on stresses and natural frequencies of CNTRC plates were presented very recently by Thanh et al. [3].

In this work, non-dimensional central deflection of CNTRC plates are investigated further using IGA based on Reissner-Mindlin FSDT, for non-unit plate aspect ratios as well. CNTs are considered to be dispersed into matrix in four different types of volume fraction distribution varying across the thickness, as per Van et al [2]. The formulation developed, is incorporated into a computer program developed in-house. NURBS basis functions in place of conventional polynomial shape functions are used for interpolation of geometry and the relevant field variables, for the isogeometric finite element analysis.

2. Methodology and Problem Description

The volume fraction of CNT, considered for the four types of volume fraction distribution varying across the thickness coordinate z of the plate, are taken following Phung-Van et al. [2] as below.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} v_{CNT} = v_{CNT}^* & (UD \text{ CNTRC}) \\ v_{CNT}(z) = \left(1 + \frac{2z}{h}\right) v_{CNT}^* & (FG-V \text{ CNTRC}) \\ v_{CNT}(z) = 2 \left(1 - \frac{2|z|}{h}\right) v_{CNT}^* & (FG-O \text{ CNTRC}) \\ v_{CNT}(z) = 2 \left(\frac{2|z|}{h}\right) v_{CNT}^* & (FG-X \text{ CNTRC}) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Detail on theoretical formulation for the IGA based on Reissner-Mindlin FSDT is omitted here to keep brevity.

3. Numerical Results

The developed computer program based on present formulation is first validated for computing non dimensional central deflection for CNTRC plates, through comparison with results from Table 2 of Van et al. [2], as presented in Table 1 herein. Upon satisfactory validation, new problems of CNTRC plates are considered, as in Table 2.

Table 1. The non-dimensional ($w=w/h$) central deflection for clamped CNTRC plate under uniform load for square (CCCC) plate (Validation).

V^*_{CNT}	h/a	Distribution Type	Van et al. [2]	Present (IGA) P=2	Van et al. [2]	Present (IGA) P=3
0.11	0.02	UD	0.253	0.261	0.254	0.252
		FG-V	0.359	0.358	0.359	0.348
		FG-O	0.468	0.459	0.468	0.445
		FG-X	0.180	0.188	0.181	0.183
	0.05	UD	1.187×10^{-2}	1.293×10^{-2}	1.197×10^{-2}	1.29×10^{-2}
		FG-V	1.452×10^{-2}	1.536×10^{-2}	1.463×10^{-2}	1.54×10^{-2}
		FG-O	1.726×10^{-2}	1.789×10^{-2}	1.736×10^{-2}	1.81×10^{-2}
		FG-X	9.971×10^{-3}	1.109×10^{-2}	1.008×10^{-2}	1.11×10^{-2}
0.14	0.02	UD	0.204	0.215	0.205	0.205
		FG-V	0.288	0.289	0.288	0.283
		FG-O	0.375	0.362	0.375	0.360
		FG-X	0.147	0.159	0.147	0.150
	0.05	UD	1.038×10^{-2}	1.146×10^{-2}	1.048×10^{-2}	1.14×10^{-2}
		FG-V	1.250×10^{-2}	1.340×10^{-2}	1.260×10^{-2}	1.34×10^{-2}
		FG-O	1.470×10^{-2}	1.546×10^{-2}	1.480×10^{-2}	1.55×10^{-2}
		FG-X	8.900×10^{-3}	9.965×10^{-3}	9.000×10^{-3}	9.98×10^{-3}

Table 2. The non-dimensional ($w=w/h$) central deflection of simply supported CNTRC plate under uniform load; Non-unit plate aspect ratio ($a/h=1$) (Parametric Study).

b/a	V^*_{CNT}	UD (10^{-3})	FG-V (10^{-3})	FG-O (10^{-3})	FG-X (10^{-3})
10	0.11	3.446	3.596	5.077	2.873
	0.14	3.006	3.119	4.293	2.548
5	0.11	3.484	3.631	5.060	2.921
	0.14	3.050	3.160	4.300	2.597
3.333	0.11	3.401	3.541	4.925	2.859
	0.14	2.981	3.086	4.186	2.545
2.5	0.11	3.352	3.494	4.899	2.811
	0.14	2.933	3.038	4.147	2.500

4. Conclusion

As evident from Table 1, the present results in terms of non-dimensional central deflection are found to be in close conformity with those from published literature, for CNTRC plates. From Table 2, it can be seen that the non-dimensional central deflection increases when the plate aspect ratio (b/a) is decreased and increases with increase of volume fraction of CNT. Further results related to the effects of other parameters and boundary conditions on non-dimensional central deflection of such CNTRC plates would be presented in full paper and skipped here due to space constraints.

5. References

- [1] Liu YJ, Chen XL, 2003, Evaluations of the effective material properties of carbon nanotube based composites using a nanoscale representative volume element, *Mechanics of Materials*, 35, 69–81.
- [2] P. Phung-Van, M. Abdel-Wahab, K.M. Liew, S.P.A. Bordas, H. Nguyen-Xuan, 2015, Isogeometric analysis of functionally graded carbon nanotube-reinforced composite plates using higher-order shear deformation theory, *Composite Structures*, 123, 137–149.
- [3] Cuong-Le Thanh, P.Phung-Van, Chien H.Thai, H.Nguyen-Xuan, M.Abdel Wahab, 2018, Isogeometric analysis of functionally graded carbon nanotube reinforced composite nanoplates using modified couple stress theory, *Composite Structures*, 184, 633-649.

Dynamics of Piezoelectric Cantilevered Beam at Higher Bending Mode for Wind Energy Harvesting

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Abstract

In the present work, a numerical study of dynamics of a piezoelectric embedded cantilevered beam vibrating at higher bending mode is carried out. Electric power output from the vibrating structure is also investigated. The investigation is primarily focused for higher mode vibration response as during the natural wind/flow induced vibration (flutter instability), the structure vibrates in combination of higher bending modes. A mathematical model of a cantilever beam with single/multiple piezoelectric patches is developed and solved by model super position approach. It is observed that during higher bending mode vibration, role of frequency of vibration has become more dominant than the amplitude of vibration.

1. Introduction

Technologies to harvest electrical energy from wind have vast potentials because wind is one of the cleanest and most sustainable energy sources that nature provides. The objective of the work is to understand the effect of oscillation frequency, location of piezo-patch on the beam, level of vibration, etc. on the electric output of layered structure.

2. Mathematical Formulation

In present study a cantilever beam with piezoelectric material has been considered as test model. Figure 1 shows the schematic image of the test model.

Figure 1. Test model.

Different types of test models in terms of variation in the position of the piezo-patches along the length have been studied [1, 2]. For the solution of the problem, Euler Bernoulli beam theory has been employed for flexible structure to calculate the strain in the problem.

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4}(x, t) + pA \frac{d^2 w}{dt^2}(x, t) = f(x, t) \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), E is Young's modulus, I is the moment of inertia of the beam cross section about the y -axis, p is the mass density and $A(x)$ is the cross-sectional area of the beam. For calculating the charge produced by flexible structure along with piezoelectric patches the following Eq. (2) is used.

$$Q = -b \int_{l_0}^{l_1} e_{31} \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} dx + b \int_{l_0}^{l_1} \epsilon_{33} E_z dz = \frac{b h e_{31}}{2} [\varphi(l_0) - \varphi(l_1)] - b L \epsilon_{33} \frac{v}{\Delta} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), h , L and b are corresponding length, height and width of cantilevered beam. Δ is thickness of piezo-layer. ϵ_{33} and e_{31} are dielectric and piezoelectric constant. $\varphi(l_0)$ and $\varphi(l_1)$ lengths of piezo patch, v is potential difference and E_z is electric field.

The prime objective of the work is to calculate the response at higher bending mode and for that model super-position method employed.

3. Numerical Results and Discussion

The developed solution method has been validated with the standard results available in the literature. A cantilevered beam is excited for a harmonic point force of different amplitude and frequency at specific node of beam. Figures 2a-2d show the response of the beam obtained from the analytical solution [3] and by the present

approach. The results obtained from both formulations depict a good matching in terms of both amplitude and frequency.

Figure 2. Deflection shape of the beam for different excitations (a) 7 Hz; (b) 58 Hz; (c) mixed frequency 7 Hz, 58 Hz and 185 Hz; (d) time history; (e) frequency spectrum.

The validated model is employed for calculation of electric charge from a piezoelectric cantilevered patches. Different harmonic excitation such as single/multiple frequency excitation has been employed as shown in Figure 2e.

4. Acknowledgement

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5. References

[1] Lu, F., H. P. Lee, and S. P. Lim. Modelling and analysis of micro piezoelectric power generators for micro-electromechanical-systems applications. *Smart Materials and Structures* 13.1 (2003): 57.
 [2] Erturk, Alper, et al. A distributed parameter electromechanical model for cantilevered piezoelectric energy harvesters. *Journal of vibration and acoustics* 130.4 (2008): 041002.
 [3] Rao, S. S., and Fook Fah. Yap. *Mechanical Vibrations*. Prentice Hall, 2011.

Towards an Interaction Based FE for Large Deformation Adhesive Contacts

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Abstract

Adhesive forces, arising from van der Waals' interactions, are predominant in mediating the contact response at the few micron and submicron length scales. The accurate simulation of adhesion is important in micromechanical and biological systems. Traditional adhesive contact mechanics (JKR) is inadequate for soft bodies and large deformations. The present work attempts to build a physically accurate, interaction-based continuum contact model and simulate micro-scale contacts. Present techniques of this kind are computationally limited to nano-scale contacts. An overview of our algorithm, and the numerical and computational challenges encountered during its implementation are presented.

1. Introduction

Analytical adhesive contact models, such as the Johnson et al. [1], Derjaguin et al. [2] and Maugis [3] models, have been studied extensively by many researchers over the years. However, these pioneering analytical models are concerned with regular geometries (circle, half space, cylinder, toroid etc.) and small deformation. Attempts to extend these models to large deformations semi-analytically have only been partially successful, with considerable restrictions on the geometry. An interaction-based FE framework for adhesion with large deformation was first introduced by Sauer and Li [4] to remove these restrictions. This so-called Coarse Grained Contact Model (CGCM) is efficient in simulating nano-scale adhesion, but demands modification of the underlying continuum. In addition, it is computationally infeasible to simulate micro-scale adhesion with CGCM. Similarly, a purely atomistic (all-atom) adhesion simulation at the 10-micron scale is infeasible even with supercomputers. The first interaction-based FE using a classical continuum was set up by Fan et al. [5] and Fan and Li [6], based on an efficient adhesion model proposed by Argento et al. [7] and Jagota and Argento [8]. This model is computationally superior to all volume-volume interaction-based adhesion models, as it only involves surface interactions. A few examples of adhesive contacts were used by Fan et al. [5] and Fan and Li [6] to illustrate the model. However, these examples were restricted to nano-sized contacting bodies. Moreover, the interaction potentials used are often not representative of real adhesion pairs. In fact, it is not clear that this model can scale to micro-scale contacts.

The present work aims to overcome some of these limitations: A micro scale interaction-based continuum FE algorithm (MIBCFE), based on the Fan-Li framework, is under development. MIBCFE attempts to overcome numerical issues in the contact stiffness matrix, uses an adaptive refinement strategy to capture near surface stress gradients, and is intended to scale to the micrometer scale. After completion, an MIBCFE-based solver will be validated against the model numerical examples used by Fan et al. [5] and Fan and Li [6].

2. Formulation

The principle of stationary potential energy is used to obtain the equation of motion of the adhesive contact problem. If two bodies interact with each other (conservative system), then the total potential energy can be written as,

$$E_{\text{TOTAL}} = E_{\text{CONTACT}} + E_{\text{INTERNAL}} + E_{\text{EXTERNAL}} \quad (1)$$

The equation of motion can be expressed symbolically as

$$F_{\text{INERTIA}} + F_{\text{INTERNAL}} + F_{\text{CONTACT}} - F_{\text{EXTERNAL}} = \{0\} \quad (2)$$

The above equation contains an additional, interaction term, but is otherwise like a geometrically nonlinear FE equation of motion. This interaction kernel is built-up by evaluating interaction four-integrals of the form

$$F_{\text{CONTACT}}^p = \sum_{se_p} \sum_{se_q} \sum_{\text{nodes}_{se}} \int_{se_1} \int_{se_2} \rho_1 \rho_2 S_I \left(\bar{r}_{pq} \cdot (f_p^{-T} N_p) \right) \cdot (f_q^{-T} N_q) v(s) dA_2 dA_1; p \neq q \quad (3)$$

Where, ρ is the symbol for particle density, S_I represents shape function matrix, f is deformation gradient, N denotes the surface outward normal in the reference configuration, \bar{r}_{pq} is

a vector pointing from a point in body p to a point in body q . se_p and se_q represents the total no. of elements on surface se_1 in p and surface se_2 on q .

For simplicity, quasi-static conditions are assumed, and inertial force is neglected.

3. Numerical Test Case

The validation of the in-house code based on MIBCFE (see Figure 1) is performed against the examples reported in Fan et al. [5] and Fan and Li [6]. A cylinder of radius R adhering to a body of size $10R \times 10R$ is considered as a model problem for validation. Both bodies are modeled as Neo-Hookean material. Plane strain conditions are assumed. Particle density is chosen as ρ_0 in the reference configuration. The initial Young's Modulus and Poisson's ratio of the material are assumed as $E = 1000 \rho_0 \varepsilon$ and 0.2 respectively. A Lennard-Jones 12-6 potential is considered as the interaction potential. The Lennard-Jones parameters are assumed to be $\sigma_0 = 0.1R$, $\varepsilon = 1.5 \rho_0^2 R^3$. The bodies are meshed using 4-noded (Q4) elements with a 5×5 grid of Gauss points. Each body has about 1000 of these elements. Preliminary results show a considerable deviation from the results reported in Fan et al. [5] and Fan and Li [6]. The cause for this deviation is being investigated, but differences in the interaction-based contact stiffness seem to be a likely cause. A complete validation program for the in-house code is currently under development.

Figure 1. Mesh of the adhesive test system.

4. Conclusion and Ongoing Work

An interaction-based continuum FE algorithm for micro contact (MIBCFE) is aimed to be developed in this ongoing work. Currently, the framework is being validated using the test cases reported in Fan et al. [5] and Fan and Li [6]. In the next phase, MIBCFE will be tested to simulate micro scale contact problems. MIBCFE will attempt to address the computational difficulties found in those micro contact simulations.

5. References

- [1] Johnson KL, Kendall K, Roberts AD, 1971, Surface energy and the contact of elastic solids, Proceedings of the Royal Society A, 324(1558), 301-313.
- [2] Derjaguin BV, Muller VM, Toporov YP, 1975, Effect of Contact deformations on the adhesion of particles, Journal of Colloid and Interface Science, 53(2), 314-326.
- [3] Maugis D, 1992, Adhesion of spheres: the JKR-DMT transition using a Dugdale model, Journal of Colloid and Interface Science, 150(1), 243- 269.
- [4] Sauer RA, Li S, 2007, A contact mechanics model for quasi-continua, International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, 71(8), 931-962.
- [5] Fan H, Ren B, Li S, 2015, An adhesive contact mechanics formulation based on atomistically induced surface traction, Journal of Computational Physics, 302, 420-438.
- [6] Fan H, Li S, 2016, A three-dimensional surface stress tensor formulation for simulation of adhesive contact in finite deformation, International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, 107(3), 252-270.
- [7] Argento C, Jagota A, Carter WC, 1997, Surface formulation for molecular interactions of macroscopic bodies, Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 45(7), 1161-1183.
- [8] Jagota A, Argento C, 1997, An intersurface stress tensor, Journal of Colloid and Interface Science, 191(2), 326-336.

Application of Embedded Element Approach to Nanostructure of Bone

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Abstract

Embedded element (EE) approach is one of the several approaches dealing with fiber-reinforced composites (FRC). Bone's nanostructural element called microfibril can also be considered as FRC of tropocollagen molecules reinforced into organic matrix. In this research work, the EE approach has been applied in modeling the microfibril and further compared with its full three-dimensional model. The EE model was found to cut the computational cost significantly while maintaining the accuracy in prediction of mechanical properties. The results of EE microfibril model were also found to be comparable to the experimental study by van der Rijt et al. [4].

1. Introduction

Bone's nanostructural element consists of three hierarchical length scales namely 1) Tropocollagen (TC) molecules; 2) Microfibril; and 3) Fibril. The global response of a hierarchical material depends on its nanoscale deformation mechanism. The structure of microfibril can be considered as a fiber-reinforced composite (FRC) whose matrix phase consists of non-collagenous proteins (NCPs) and water; and TC molecules as reinforcing phase. The hierarchical arrangement of these constituents at different length scales makes the microfibrillar and fibrillar structures. The application of embedded element (EE) approach in FRC problems combined with asymptotic homogenization technique has been proven to be quite efficient [1, 2]. In the present work, a simplified two-dimensional (2D) EE model of microfibril model coupled with asymptotic homogenization technique was developed and compared with its three-dimensional (3D) model which is similar to the microfibril model of Hambli et al. [3]. The EE model not only reduces the mesh complexity problems but also cuts down the computational cost drastically.

2. Material and Method

The structure of microfibril consists of five TC molecules arranged in a staggered fashion along their length. Each TC molecule is displaced axially by 67 nm called D-Period (D) relative to its surrounding molecules, thus making a 'quarter staggered' structure. This structure creates periodic gap ($\sim 0.6D$) and overlap ($\sim 0.4D$) regions between two TC molecules. Staggered arrangement of TC molecules in the homogenized matrix of NCPs and water makes a microfibrillar structure which is 4 nm in diameter and of unknown length. Hence, for the present study, a periodic and repetitive unit cell of microfibril has been considered. The TC molecules have been modeled as one dimensional (1D) beam element and the matrix as 2D plane stress element. The length and width of the 2D model are taken as 340 nm and 12.6 nm ($2\pi R$) respectively (where, 'R' is the radius of microfibril). Figure 1 shows the 3D and 2D microfibril models.

Figure 1. The 3D and 2D models of microfibril (All dimensions are in nanometers).

The TC molecules and matrix phase have been modeled as elastic materials with Young's modulus of 2.8 GPa and 0.5 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.28 and 0.3 respectively. The TC molecules were embedded into the matrix phase using the 'Embedded Region Constraint' feature of ABAQUS 2017. Both models have been simulated under periodic boundary conditions for tensile loading under small strain (<2%) regime.

3. Results and Discussion

The predicted Young's moduli from 3D and EE microfibril models were found to be very close to each other. A mesh convergence study on the EE model suggested an elemental edge length of 0.5 nm for matrix as well as embedded elements for the minimization of numerical error. The comparison between EE and 3D microfibril models based on different parameters has been presented in Table 1. The parameters consist of computational time (in seconds) to solve the models, total number of elements and the elastic modulus (GPa). The elastic modulus from EE model was found to be very close to the one from the experimental study by van der Rijt et al. [4].

Table 1. Comparison between EE and full microfibril model.

Parameter	EE Model	Full Model
Computational time (sec)	40	2375
Number of elements	20000	823137
Young's modulus (GPa)	1.89	1.887

4. Conclusion

A simplified 2D model of microfibril was studied using EE technique. The model not only reduced the computational cost but was also found to be comparable in terms of Young's modulus. The advantage of using embedded approach is that it significantly reduces the degrees of freedom for a particular model and hence cuts the computational cost. The 2D EE model however lacked in some of the nanostructural details, such as cross-links connecting two TC molecules, the interface between the matrix and TC molecules etc., as compared to the full 3D model. But comparing the overall properties, the EE technique came out to be a robust approach which can be extended further to 3D.

5. References

- [1] Liu Hui, Danielle Zeng, Yang Li, Liying Jiang, 2016, Development of RVE-embedded solid elements model for predicting effective elastic constants of discontinuous fiber reinforced composites, *Mechanics of Materials*, 93, 109–123.
- [2] Sharma Rajneesh, Bhagat Atul Ramesh, Mahajan Puneet, 2016, Finite element analysis for mechanical characterization of 4D inplane carbon/carbon composite with imperfect microstructure, *Latin American Journal of Solids and Structures*, 11(2), 170-184.
- [3] Hambli Ridha, Barkaoui Abdelwahed, 2012, Physically based 3D finite element model of a single mineralized collagen microfibril, *Journal of theoretical biology*, 301, 28-41.
- [4] van der Rijt Joost A. J., van der Werf Kees O., Bennink Martin L., Dijkstra Pieter J., Feijen Jan, 2006, Micromechanical testing of individual collagen fibrils, *Macromolecular bioscience*, 6(9), 697-702.

Flutter Suppression of Glass/Epoxy Composite Wing Embedded with SMA

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Abstract

The present work focuses on the numerical investigation of Unswept Cantilever lifting surface made of Glass/Epoxy embedded with SMA for Flutter suppression. The Aeroelastic Static & Dynamic analysis & Vibration control of Composite surface for an Unsteady Aerodynamic air flow in subsonic regime are studied. The present work emphasizes on understanding the Flutter problem in the SMAHC (Shape Memory Alloy based Hybrid Composite) wing system. The FE modelling of Cantilever wing is carried out in Nastran using quadrilateral elements. The wing is modelled as Transversely Orthotropic Shell elements with corresponding temperature dependent properties. Efforts are made to capture the complex Thermo-Mechanical behavior of SMA in Composite layup using Nastran cards. The SMA embedded in Glass/Epoxy composite is modelled as SMAHC. The constitutive SMAHC model to capture Thermo-Elastic behavior is developed as ECTE (Effective Coefficient of Thermal Expansion) model. The model is capable of capturing the temperature dependent non-linear behavior of SMA and also more accurately represents the Mechanics of Composites embedded with SMA as Actuator. Nastran Flutter codes are developed and solved for different thermal conditions. The *P-K* Method Flutter Solution is used for the analysis. Parametric studies are performed for Flutter instability to study the effect of number of SMAs & temperature. The results are correlated with the variation in Real Eigen values from Normal Mode analysis.

1. Introduction

In the present highly competitive aircraft industries, main focus of aircraft manufacturers is to achieve better performance in terms of fuel efficiency and flight speed range. Use of Composite materials in the aircraft industry has assisted in achieving the desired performance but with an added cost in terms of Aeroelastic stability. The Aeroelastic stability analysis of Composite wing structure is one such area which has greater influence on the performance and functional aspects of aircrafts.

Inclusion of Smart Materials i.e., Piezo-electric materials and Shape Memory Alloys into the aircraft structure in the recent years has helped in achieving Vibration control, suppressing Dynamic instabilities and to get good maneuverability [1, 2]. Use of SMA's as Actuator for the Composite wing structures for suppressing the Dynamic instabilities is found feasible in many practical applications [2, 3].

2. General Specifications

The numerical model is built in Nastran, is a Cantilever model consists of 16 layers of either Glass-Epoxy or Ni-Ti layups transversely divided as four strips which are modelled as 2-D orthotropic quad elements. The SMA is embedded in the middle two strips are modelled as SMAHC. The temperature dependent material properties of Glass/Epoxy and SMAHC are defined using MAT8 and PCOMP cards. Sufficient numbers of Vibration and Flutter runs are carried for different temperatures and models.

3. Equations

The Thermo-elastic constitutive relations [4] for Transversely Orthotropic lamina is given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \int_{T_0}^T \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_1(\tau) \\ \alpha_2(\tau) \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} d\tau \quad (1)$$

The governing equations for the Thermo-Mechanical response of SMAHC panel [4] is given by

$$[M]\{\ddot{A}\} + \left([k] - [K_{\Delta T}] + \frac{1}{2}[N1] + \frac{1}{3}[N2] \right) \{A\} = \{F(t)\} + \{P_{\Delta T}\} \quad (2)$$

4. Results

Figure 1. Sensitivity plots and V-G plots.

5. Summary

The current work shows the numerical modeling of smart structure for aeroelastic analysis and potential use of SMA in aircraft structures for the postponement of Flutter instability. Two Flutter modes i.e. first bending & 2nd bending are observed and will remain same for all the cases. The Flutter Boundary is the function of both Temperature and Number of SMA layers. From the plots in Figure 1, it is observed that the increase in number of SMA layers as well as in temperature have favorable effects on flutter boundary. The V-G plot results for six and nine SMA layered cases are shown in results.

6. References

- [1] Feng-Ming Li, Active Aeroelastic Flutter Suppression of a Supersonic plate with Piezoelectric material, International Journal of Engineering Science 51, 2012, 190-203.
- [2] Changho Nam, Aditi Chattopadhyay, Youdan Kim, Application of Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) Spars for Aircraft Maneuver Enhancement, Proceedings of SPIE Vol. 4701, 2015.
- [3] D.J. Hartl, D.C. Lagoudas, Aerospace applications of Shape Memory Alloys, Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part G: Journal of Aerospace Engineering, 2007, 221- 535.
- [4] Travis L. Turner, A New Thermoelastic Model for Analysis of Shape Memory Alloy Hybrid Composites, Journal of Intelligent Material systems and Structures, Vol. 11—May 2000.

Structural Assessment of Polyurea Coated Materials for Armed Personal Vehicles

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Abstract

The application of composite structural systems to protect the main structure during vehicle collisions, blast loading and other high impact applications has been a major focus of interest in the modern design industry over the last few decades. Enhancing the energy absorption, minimizing force transmission and improving the dynamic fracture resistance of metallic plate structures have been the main challenges in those studies. In the present study, a relative assessment has been made between metal plates with polyurea coated metal plates. As the weight also one of the critical parameter in the vehicle design, Titanium alloy plates were used and compared with the steel plates for both with and without coatings.

Keywords: Layered materials, Polyurea Coatings, Mild Steel, Titanium Alloy, Blast Loading, Energy Absorption.

1. Introduction

Coating the metal plates with a polyurea layer has proven to significantly affect the survivability of such structures under high intensity impulsive loads [1-5]. Polyurea is a coating material that has received extensive research interest due to its effective energy absorption property, withstand to high impact loads and many other physical & mechanical properties. It can also serve in retarding the occurrence of fracture in the metal plates due to its hyperelastic behavior. Viscoelastic behavior of polyurea offers excellent rate sensitivity to use under high impact applications i.e., strain rates in the order of 10^6 S^{-1} . In the design of protective of Army vehicles, which are subjected to high impulsive loads, people have been using steel as base material irrespective of some of its minor drawbacks in terms of weight and corrosion. The main reasons for this are that steels have high absolute strength and hardness combined with high ductility, low price compared to most other armor materials. But, Titanium and Titanium alloys are excellent materials which are having superior properties than steel in terms of their brilliant properties like high tensile strength to density ratio, high corrosion resistance, fatigue resistance, high crack resistance, and ability to withstand moderately high temperatures without creeping.

2. General Specifications

Blast is the rapid expansion of hot gases resulting from the detonation of an explosive charge gives rise to a highly compression wave called a shock wave, which propagates through the air. The experimental work for blast load in the laboratory level has developed with help of Shock-Tube Set-up. Numerical validation has done by using Abaqus Explicit scheme. The detonation, shock wave propagation and interaction with structure can be considered as ConWep problem and the standard solution can be obtained, from finite element based numerical simulation.

The pressure time variation can be expressed as Friedlander equation (typical for any blast wave):

$$p(t) = (p_s - p_a) \left[1 - \frac{t - t_d}{t_d} \right] e^{-\frac{(t-t_d)}{\theta}} \quad (1)$$

3. Results and Conclusion

In the present study, relative assessment of Polyurea coated Steel & Polyurea Coated Titanium Alloy has been made under various strain rates.

From Figure 2, it has been observed that Titanium Alloy coated with Polyurea is deflecting less than Steel coated with Polyurea at a pressure of 160 bar. Also, the energy absorbed by polyurea coated plates are less when compared with bare plate so that the chance of failure can be minimized.

Figure 1. Pressure vs Time plot for blast loading.

Figure 2. Deflection vs Time for different combinations by Shock-Tube.

4. References

- [1] Szafran, J., and A. Matusiak. Polyurea Coating Systems: Definition, Research, Applications. parameters 2: 3.
- [2] Xue, Liang, Willis Mock, and Ted Belytschko. Penetration of DH-36 steel plates with and without polyurea coating. Mechanics of materials 42.11 (2010): 981-1003.
- [3] Amini, M. R., J. B. Isaacs, and S. Nemat-Nasser. Experimental investigation of response of monolithic and bilayer plates to impulsive loads. International Journal of Impact Engineering 37.1 (2010): 82-89.
- [4] Boyer, R. R. An overview on the use of titanium in the aerospace industry. Materials Science and Engineering: A 213.1-2 (1996): 103-114.
- [5] Ackland, Kathryn, Christopher Anderson, and Tuan Duc Ngo. Deformation of polyurea-coated steel plates under localised blast loading. International Journal of Impact Engineering 51 (2013):13-22.

Assessment of Impact Strength of Rotationally Molded Products: An Alternative Approach

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Abstract

Rotational Molding is a polymer processing method used to produce hollow domestic and engineered plastics parts by melting and subsequent solidification of polymer. Linear Low-Density Polyethylene (LLDPE) is a widely used raw material for this process. Impact strength is one of the crucial quality parameter of rotationally molded products. Generally, the RM products are characterized for their impact strength using a low temperature falling dart type impact test. In this paper we propose an alternative approach that uses true stress - true strain behavior of LLDPE to characterize the impact strength. The investigations are done on samples molded at different process conditions and their effect on impact performance of samples has also been analyzed. The observations obtained were compared with the data obtained from the conventional impact tests like falling Dart and notched Izod impact tests. Apart from impact properties, this approach also gives significant information on the mechanical properties of the products.

1. Introduction

Rotational molding (RM) is a melt polymer processing method. Herein polymer powder is heated in a convective heating environment till it melts completely in a mould that rotates at very low speeds either bi-axially or in a rock and roll type of motion. It is then allowed to solidify to acquire the shape of the mould. This process is used to manufacture engineered and domestic products at competitive costs. Storage tanks, transportation equipment, medical products, marine industry essentials are a few examples of rotationally molded products. Considering crucial quality requirements of the products, characterization of the material becomes very important.

LLDPE is widely used raw material for this process. Its density ranges from 935 kg/m³ to about 940 kg/m³ and has a crystallinity of 65%-70% at room temperature. It has better stiffness, chemical resistance, and tensile strength, but somewhat poorer impact strength as compared with LDPE and MDPE [1]. Apart from this it has a broader processing window. It has been observed that although high-density polymers show higher impact resistance, the other factors like crystalline morphology plays more vital role than density in the impact performance. In real time application, the impact performance of the plastic is very important. Pick *et al* observed that at a particular test temperature (-60 to 20 °C) the impact resistance of metallocene polyethylene is higher, typically by 1 to 4 J/mm than the LLDPE. It was also observed that for the metallocene polyethylene, the impact strength was highest when the failure mode was brittle, but for the linear low-density polyethylene the best impact resistance was observed when the failure mode was ductile. [2-4]. For RM applications generally falling dart type of impact test is preferred which varies according to the thickness. Also it is carried out at low temperature (-40°C). Conventional impact tests like Izod and Charpy are also done to get an idea of the impact characteristics. It is a well-known fact that area under the stress-strain plot gives an idea about the toughness of the material. Since the plastics deformation of this material is considerable, area under the true stress strain curve can give the toughness of the material. Thus the plasticity of the material can be explored to for its characterization impact in particular. In this paper, we have reported how the area under the true stress-true strain curve of the LLDPE can give meaningful information.

2. General Specifications

RM was carried out at M/s GMI Zarak molders Pvt. Ltd. Verna Goa in a biaxial CACCIA machine. The oven conditions used for a typical RM process were followed. The various tests done include Tensile and Flexural tests performed using a UTM, Impact tests performed using Izod test machine. For tensile test, Type 4 samples of the ASTM D638-02a were used. These were prepared by shear cutting the sheets. For flexural test, specimen was prepared according to ASTM D790 standards. For Izod test, samples from flexural test were used after cutting a notch at the center of each piece. The observations of the tensile tests were processed to obtain the true stress –

true strain graphs. The area under the true stress strain graphs were found out and compared to the impacts strength values from the Izod tests.

3. Observations

The plot given in Figure 1 is the comparative true stress vs true strain plot of the median sample of each type of LLDPE samples. The table below the plot calculates the toughness as area under the curve and also given is the impact strength obtained from Izod test.

Figure 1. True stress vs true strain plots.

Table 1. Toughness of all sample types.

Sample Code	Toughness	Impact strength (Izod test)
A	43.7433 MPa	0.354 J
B	12.9722 MPa	0.139 J
C	34.9303 MPa	0.246 J
D	22.3967 MPa	0.175 J

4. Summary

Toughness for each sample was found and compared to the izod impact strength (Table 1). Trends observed in toughness obtained from true stress strain plots are comparable to the trends shown by impact strengths of the samples.

5. References

- [1] R. J. Crawford and J. L. Throne, Rotational Molding Technology. 2002.
- [2] Pick E L T and Eileen Harkin-Jones, An Investigation in to relationship between the impact performance of rotationally moulded polyethylene products and their dynamic mechanical properties J. Polym. Eng. Sci. 43:905–918. 2003.
- [3] Pick E L T and Harkin-Jones, Understanding the impact behavior of rotomoulded linear low density polyethylene. J. Rotation 13:26–30. 2003.
- [4] Pick L, Harkin-Jones E, Kearns M P and Crawford R J, A Comparison between the impact performance of rotationally moulded linear low density polyethylene with metallocene polyethylene. J. Rotation 9:21–25. 2003.

Hygrothermal Nonlinear Static Analysis of Laminated Composite Skew Plates

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Abstract

In the present work, non-linear static response of skew sandwich plates under hygrothermal environment is presented. Using higher order shear deformation theory and von-Karman's non-linearity, the equations of motion are derived. These equations are then transformed from physical to computational domain using linear transformation and chain rule of differentiation. Fast converging finite double Chebyshev series is used for spatial discretization. The non-linear terms are linearized using quadratic extrapolation technique.

1. Introduction

Skew plates are subjected to different types of transverse and in plane loading conditions during their service period. At the obtuse corners of the skew plates stress singularity is developed. Because of these reasons, the analysis of skew plates becomes difficult. In present study skew plates made up of the composite material is used, but composites are susceptible to heat and moisture when operating in harsh and changing environmental conditions. This moisture absorption changes the thermo-physical, mechanical and chemical characteristics of the composite structure.

2. Mathematical Formulation

For the present work, laminated composite panel with length a , width b , and thickness h is used. Geometry of plate is as shown below.

Figure 1. Geometry of Laminated Composite Plate.

A third order shear deformation theory [1] is used to present the displacement fields of the panel. Based on the TSDT, the displacement field at a point is assumed of cubical order and can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + z\psi_x(x, y) + z^2u_1(x, y) + z^3\phi_x(x, y) \\ v(x, y, z) &= v_0(x, y) + z\psi_y(x, y) + z^2v_1(x, y) + z^3\phi_y(x, y) \\ w(x, y, z) &= w_0(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where u_0 , v_0 represents the in-plane displacements and w_0 is the transverse displacement of a point (x, y) . The functions ψ_x , ψ_y denotes the rotations of the normal to the middle surface about y and x axis respectively. The parameters u_1 , v_1 and ϕ_x , ϕ_y are the higher order terms in the Taylor's series expansion and represents higher order transverse cross-sectional deformation modes. The mapping of the physical domain (skew plate) to computational domain (square plate) is required for implementation the proposed solution methodology. Linear mapping technique is utilized for the transformation of physical domain to computational domain. The mapping functions used for the transformation of a skew plate of sides ' a ' and ' b ' and thickness ' h ' with skew angle ' θ ' into computational domain ($-1 \leq r \leq 1$) are:

$$r = \frac{2x - (2y \cot \theta + a)}{a} ; s = \frac{2y}{b \sin \theta} - 1 \quad (2)$$

The fast converging finite double Chebyshev series [2] is used for the spatial discretization of the differential equations along with appropriate boundary conditions, thus the coupled partial differential equations are transformed to a system of algebraic equations. The displacement function $\eta(r, s)$ and the loadings are approximated in space domain in terms of finite double Chebyshev series and expressed as:

$$\eta(r, s) = \sum_{i=0}^M \sum_{j=0}^N \delta_{ij} \eta_{ij} T_i(r) T_j(s); \quad -1 \leq r, s \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

3. Results

For coding the solution methodology FORTRAN 77 is used. Different combinations of moisture content (%C) and temperature rise (T °C) are employed. The material properties of the laminated composite plate are given as [3]:

$$E_f = 230 \times 10^3 G_f = 9 \times 10^3, \nu_f = 0.34, \rho_m = 1200 \text{ Kg/m}^3$$

$$\beta_m = 0.268, \alpha_f = 0.54 \times 10^{-6}, \alpha_m = 45 \times 10^{-6}, \quad V_m = 0.4, \rho_f = 1750 \text{ Kg/m}^3$$

Figure 2. Effect of temperature, moisture concentration and their combination on the non-dimensional bending moment (M_x) of clamped, laminated composite skew plates ($a/h=10$, $a/b=1$) having ply orientation $[0/90/90/0]$ subjected to uniform transverse loading under hygro-thermal condition.

From the above graph percentage change in moments with respect to no hygrothermal conditions can be calculated. Percentage changes are 1.80%, 5.89%, 9.96% and 15.10% for (1%, 0°C), (1%, 100°C), (5%, 0°C) and (5%, 100°C) cases, respectively.

4. Summary

The effects of temperature, moisture concentration and their combination on the non-dimensional displacement response and non-dimensional bending moment of the symmetric cross ply and anti-symmetric cross ply are studied.

5. References

- [1] B. N. Pandya, T. Kant (1988), Higher-order shear deformable theories for flexure of Sandwich Plates-Finite Element Evaluations, *Int. J. Solids Structures* Vol 24, No. 12, pp. 1267-1286.
- [2] R. Pandey, K.K. Shukla, A. Jain (2008), Nonlinear flexural analysis of laminated composite plates, *Int J ApplMechEng*, 13 707–733.
- [3] A.K. Upadhyay, Ramesh Pandey, K.K. Shukla (2010), Nonlinear flexural response of laminated composite plates under hygro-thermo-mechanical loading, *Commun Nonlinear Sci Numer Simulat* 15 2634–2650.

Vibration Suppression in Metamaterials with the Aid of Viscoelastic Inserts

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Abstract

Metamaterials are artificial materials that are designed to offer desired responses that are not possible with naturally occurring materials. Vibration suppression phenomenon in acoustic metamaterial beams with embedded local resonators made up of viscoelastic characteristic material is presented in detail here. It is shown that the metamaterial structure exhibits better damping characteristics compared to plain beam without sacrificing its strength and stiffness.

1. Introduction

What is a “metamaterial” may be understood from the following definitions available in the literature. In one such definition metamaterial is understood as engineered composites. Metamaterial have properties that are derived from their physical properties but not the chemical properties. Metamaterial are materials, which exhibit properties which are not observed in nature. Metamaterials are also defined as material which has properties not found in constituent materials. Consolidating all these definitions, a metamaterial may be understood as a composite material that is purposely engineered to provide material properties that are not attainable with ordinary materials.

Damping is an inherent property of a material. In some practical applications the damping is desirable and where as in some application damping is completely undesirable. Increase in damping often leads to a compromise on stiffness. That is, a material with higher damping has reduced stiffness compared to a material with normal damping. Higher damping implies higher levels of energy dissipation and low values of stiffness. So fabrication of such material with enhanced energy dissipation without the compromising on stiffness lead to the development of metadamping criterion.

2. Metamaterial Beam

Material often behaves differently under static conditions compared to dynamic conditions. The dynamic characteristic of a material is always a point of discussion and needs an understanding of wave propagation. Materials under dynamic environment often act as mechanical filters for wave propagation. The waves propagate only for specific set of frequency band termed as “pass band” [1]. The frequency bands for which the waves are completely blocked are termed as stop bands. “The whole is greater than sum of its parts” which implies periodic acoustic metamaterials which are basically mass-in-mass consisting of masses, springs and viscous damping exhibit enhanced properties than mass and mass statically equivalent periodic chains generally termed as phononic crystals. The design of a metamaterial often realized based on below mentioned objectives.

- a) Metamaterial should exhibit stop bands for low as well as high frequencies.
- b) Provide broadband reduction of amplitude of propagating waves beyond stop bands due to damping constituent.
- c) The metamaterial should be exhibiting higher dissipative properties without compromising on stiffness and load bearing characteristics.

3. Design for Vibration Suppression

The damping of structural components and materials is often a significantly overlooked criterion for good mechanical design. The damping can be either active or passive damping. Devices such as electronic actuators are used to dissipate energy in active damping. Passive damping methods include add-on solutions such as viscoelastic materials. Viscoelastic materials are unique in the characteristic of dissipating system energy when deformed in shear. Typical applications of passive damping include aerospace, marine, transport, engine mounts, machine components such as rotating shafts and many other structural applications. Viscoelastic materials are used in the form of inserts in beams, which are called as mass-in-mass structures or phononic crystals or

sandwiched with two layers of base structure [2]. Usage of viscoelastic materials at the junction of the structure results dissipation of vibrational energy of the structure due to cyclic shearing of the viscoelastic material without compromising on stiffness.

4. Viscoelastic Material and Its Characteristics

Viscoelasticity is a material behavior characteristic possessing a mixture of perfectly elastic and perfectly viscous behavior. The viscosity property of a viscoelastic material imparts the substance a strain rate dependence on time and the phase angle between stress and strain is always 0° to 90° . If we load an elastic material and release, we observe no energy dissipation that is all the energy stored in a material during loading is recovered when the load is removed. Contrary to an elastic material there exists purely viscous behavior. The viscous material does not recover any of the energy stored during loading after the load is being removed and the phase angle between stress and strain is always 90° , that is all energy is lost due to pure damping. Unlike elastic material, for a viscous material, stress is proportional to the rate of strain.

Figure 1. Elastic behavior versus viscoelastic behavior.

5. Damping Design Using Viscoelastic Materials

Damping is often introduced to dissipate energy or to perform vibration suppression. In structural problems the damping is enhanced by introducing viscoelastic cores [3]. The reduced vibration is achieved by converting the vibration energy into heat energy dissipated by the viscoelastic material to the surroundings. As the structure is subjected to cyclic forced/free vibrations shearing action is imparted to the viscoelastic core material. This mechanism creates the damping effect as these shear strains are converted to heat energy with in viscoelastic material.

6. Summary

The properties of metamaterial and the themes of its definition are discussed in the paper. Meta damping characteristics of a metamaterial is discussed briefly. Comparison of elastic, viscous and viscoelastic material is done. Meta damping characteristics of a metamaterial and mathematical formulation of the same is provided. Paper also discusses the different configurations of local resonators like mass-in mass and mass and mass in metamaterial beam to achieve maximum dissipative properties.

7. References

- [1] M. I. Hussein, M. J. Frazier, 2013, Metadamping an emergent phenomenon in dissipative metamaterials, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 332, 4767–4774.
- [2] M. Nouh, O. Aldraihem, A. Baz, 2014, Vibration Characteristics of Metamaterial Beams with Periodic Local Resonances, *ASME Journal of Vibration and Acoustics*, Vol. 136 / 061012-1.
- [3] X. Q. Zhoua, D. Y. Yu, X. Y. Shao, S. Q. Zhang, S. Wang, 2016, Research and applications of viscoelastic vibration damping materials: A review, *Composite structures*, Volume 136, Pages 460-480.

Buckling of Laminated Composite Plates Using IHSDT Subjected to In-Plane Arbitrary Loads

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Abstract

This study focuses on the analysis of buckling response of composite plates subjected to in-plane arbitrary load using inverse hyperbolic shear deformation theory for the symmetric and anti-symmetric composite laminates. The principle of virtual work is used for deriving the governing equations and the boundary conditions. The Navier-type closed form solution is incorporated for solving the governing equations for simply supported conditions. The effect of number of layers on the biaxial buckling load characteristics is observed.

1. Introduction

Laminated composites are increasingly used in engineering applications such as aeronautical, marine and mechanical industries as well as in other fields of technology because of its advance mechanical properties. Composite materials have increased the performance and reliability of structural systems. Buckling is one of the important mode of failure thus the need to study the buckling in composite plate arises. An inverse hyperbolic shear deformation theory is used to study the buckling response in symmetric and anti-symmetric laminated composite plates subjected to in-plane arbitrary loads. In order to derive the governing equations, the principle of virtual work is employed. The simply supported cross-ply laminates are considered and Navier type closed form solution is implemented to solve the governing equations for such laminates.

2. Mathematical Formulation

In this study, a plate is assumed, which is composed of N number of orthotropic layers of uniform thickness h , length a , and width b . The material properties are used as follows: $E_1 / E_2 = 2.5$, $G_{12} / E_2 = 0.5$, $G_{13} / E_2 = 0.5$, $G_{23} / E_2 = 0.2$, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$ [1]. The fiber orientation (θ) and material properties of each layer define the reduced stiffness matrix which is in turn employed in generalized Hooke's law to depict the material behavior. The governing equations are obtained using the principle of virtual work. The cross ply plates for simply supported conditions are analyzed and governing equations are solved using the Navier type closed form solution. The following displacement field for the laminated plates based on the IHSDT [2] is considered to derive the mathematical model.

$$u(x, y, z) = u_0(x, y) - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \left(\sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{rz}{h} \right) - z \frac{2r}{h\sqrt{r^2 + 4}} \right) \theta_x \quad (1)$$

$$v(x, y, z) = v_0(x, y) - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} + \left(\sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{rz}{h} \right) - z \frac{2r}{h\sqrt{r^2 + 4}} \right) \theta_y \quad (2)$$

$$w(x, y, z) = w_0(x, y) \quad (3)$$

where u, v and w are the displacement functions in terms of mid-plane displacements (u_0, v_0, w_0) and shear rotations (θ_x, θ_y) and r has a constant value of 3 [2].

3. Results and Discussion

On the basis of the developed mathematical model, various numerical examples are solved to predict the buckling characteristics of the composite plates. The buckling load parameter of symmetric as well as anti-symmetric cross ply plates subjected to varying in plane loads is examined. The non-dimensional buckling load parameter given by

$P_{cr} = \lambda(a^2 / E_2 h^3)$ is evaluated and presented in the results. Table 1 presents the buckling results of symmetric cross ply plate having span to thickness ratio as 10 subjected to various in plane arbitrary loads. It is observed that with the increase in K value (ratio of in-plane load in y-axis to the load in x-axis) the buckling load parameter is decreasing. It should be noted that the negative values of K represent the tensile forces acting on the laminates in y-direction. Thus, increment in the tensile forces in the y-axis increases the buckling load parameter.

Table 1. Non-dimensional buckling load of cross ply symmetric plate.

K	Buckling load (P_{cr})			
	[0/90/0]	[0/90/90/0]	[0/90/0/90/0]	[0/90/0/90/0/90/0/0]
-0.8	69.128	81.408	82.791	83.526
-0.6	34.564	40.704	41.395	41.763
-0.4	23.042	27.136	27.597	27.842
-0.2	17.282	20.352	20.698	20.881
0	13.825	16.281	16.558	16.705
0.2	11.521	13.568	13.798	13.921
0.4	9.875	11.629	11.827	11.932
0.6	8.641	10.176	10.349	10.440
0.8	7.680	9.045	9.199	9.280
1.0	6.912	8.140	8.279	8.352

Further, the analysis is performed for anti-symmetric plates with increase in number of layers. The variation of non-dimensional buckling load with respect to the different values of loading (K) for anti-symmetric cross ply can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Variation of Non-dimensional buckling load parameter (P_{cr}) with in plane arbitrary load.

4. Summary

The buckling response of simply supported symmetric and anti-symmetric cross ply is analyzed using IHSST. The laminates are subjected to in plane arbitrary loads. The generalized governing equation and boundary conditions are derived using principle of virtual work. The Navier-type closed form solution is used to solve the governing equations. The results are obtained for both symmetric and anti-symmetric plate for simply supported conditions. It is observed that for lower value of K the buckling load is having a higher value.

5. References

- [1] Reddy J.N. (1984). A simple higher-order theory for laminated composite plates. Journal of Applied Mechanics 51:745-52.
- [2] Grover N., Maiti D.K. and Singh B.N. (2013). A new inverse hyperbolic shear deformation theory for static and buckling analysis of laminated composite and sandwich plates. Composite Structures 95:667-75.

Deformation Characteristics of Functionally Graded Plates Using a Non-Polynomial Shear Deformation Theory

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Abstract

In this study, the static response of FGM plates is studied using secant function-based shear deformation theory (SFSDT). The generalized displacement equations are derived using the principle of virtual work and solved by Navier type exact solution method. The results are then compared with other shear deformation theories in order to validate the accuracy of the theory.

1. Introduction

During recent decades, Functionally Graded Material (FGM) is popular due to its gradually changing properties across the thickness. The FGM is an advance class of composite material whose properties vary continuously according to power law. The FGM plates are being used in different engineering sectors such as automotive, military, medical, construction, chemical industries. In the present work, static analysis of FGM plate is examined using a shear deformation theory which is based upon secant function. The governing equations are developed using the principle of virtual work. The Navier type exact solution is implemented to obtain the response.

2. Mathematical Formulation

The FGM plate of dimension $a \times b \times h$ is considered where 'a' is the length, 'b' is the width and 'h' is the thickness. The gradation of the FGM material properties depends on the power law. The effective properties are arithmetic average of constituent properties and are given by Kulkarni et al. [1]. In this work, the SFSDT originally developed for composite plates [2] is applied for the modelling of FGM plates. The theory consists of mid-plane displacements (u_0, v_0, w_0), shear rotations (θ_x, θ_y) and shear strain shape function of thickness coordinate. In terms of these, the in-plane (u, v) and transverse (w) displacements are expressed as [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} u(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) &= u_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) - \xi_3 \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial \xi_1} + \left[\xi_3 \sec(r\xi_3/h) + (-\sec(r/2)[1 + (r/2)\tan(r/2)]) \right] \theta_x \\ v(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) &= v_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) - \xi_3 \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial \xi_2} + \left[\xi_3 \sec(r\xi_3/h) + (-\sec(r/2)[1 + (r/2)\tan(r/2)]) \right] \theta_y \quad (1) \\ w(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) &= w_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) \end{aligned}$$

The stiffness matrix is calculated which depends on the material properties such as Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio. The value of r is optimized to 0.1 [2]. The governing equations for analysis are obtained by principle of virtual work in the terms of stress and moment then converted into generalized displacement equations. Navier type exact solution is used to obtain the solution of governing differential equations.

3. Results and Discussion

In order to demonstrate the developed approach, the results are presented for FGM plate under sinusoidal transverse load. The generalized code is generated in MATLAB for static response of FGM plate having properties of Aluminum/Alumina. $E_m = 70GPa$, $E_c = 380GPa$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ [1]. The non-dimensional deflection [1] is obtained and given as $W = [10E_c h^3 w(a/2, b/2)] / [q_0 a^4]$.

The non-dimensional deflection of FGM plate under sinusoidal load with varying power index and span thickness (a/h) is taken as 10 is presented in Table 1. The results are compared with existing theories and it is observed that present results are in well agreement with the published results. Further, the effect of a/h ratio and power law index are observed on FGM plate and the results are depicted in Figure 1.

Table 1. Non-dimensional deflection of FGM plate with $a/h=10$ and varying power index.

Theory	N=1	N=2	N=4	N=8
Present	0.5890	0.7573	0.8815	0.9746
ITSDT [1]	0.5884	0.7569	0.882	0.9747
SSDT [3]	0.5889	0.7573	0.8819	0.975
TSDT [4]	0.589	0.7573	0.8815	0.9747
HSDT [5]	0.588	0.7564	0.8814	0.9737

Figure 1. Static response of FGM plates with varying a/h ratio and power law index (N=0, 1, 3).

4. Conclusion

The static response of functionally graded material plates is analyzed using secant function based shear deformation theory. The theory is based on the shear strain function which satisfies the traction free boundary conditions and also satisfies the criteria of continuity and differentiability. The governing differential equations are obtained using principle of virtual work and solved via Navier type exact solution methodology. The obtained results indicate the applicability and accuracy of SFSDT for the prediction of transverse deformation characteristics of FGM plates.

5. References

- [1] Kulkarni K., Singh B.N., and Maiti D.K. Analytical solution for bending and buckling analysis of functionally graded plates using inverse trigonometric shear deformation theory. *Composite Structures* 134 (2015): 147-157.
- [2] Grover N., Singh B.N., and Maiti D.K. New nonpolynomial shear-deformation theories for structural behavior of laminated-composite and sandwich plates. *AIAA journal* 51.8 (2013): 1861-1871.
- [3] Zenkour A.M. Generalized shear deformation theory for bending analysis of functionally graded plates. *Applied Mathematical Modelling* 30.1 (2006): 67-84.
- [4] Wu, Chih-Ping, and Hao-Yuan Li. An RMVT-based third-order shear deformation theory of multilayered functionally graded material plates. *Composite Structures* 92.10 (2010): 2591-2605
- [5] Mantari J.L., Oktem A.S., and Soares C.G. Bending response of functionally graded plates by using a new higher order shear deformation theory. *Composite Structures* 94.2 (2012): 714-723.

A Comparative Study of Strain Sensing Characteristics of Intrinsically Conducting Polymers

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Abstract

Electromechanical response of intrinsically conducting polymers (ICPs) such as polyaniline composites and PEDOT:PSS having different microstructures is studied. The strain-sensing capabilities under uniaxial strain and cyclic loading conditions were also monitored. It was found that among these materials, PANI-DBSA/EVA showed higher strain sensitivity. The causes for the observed behaviour is explained.

1. Introduction

Conductive films made from various intrinsically conducting polymers (ICPs) are useful for applications such as strain sensing, pressure sensing and flexible displays [1]. Strain sensing with such ICPs or its composites have been reported already. However, a study to investigate the best possible ICP that could give the highest strain sensitivity is yet to be done. This paper compares the strain sensing characteristics of various conducting polymers such as polyaniline and PEDOT:PSS. Since these ICPs do not form free-standing films, it needs to be either blended with composites or coated on a substrate [2]. Such flexible films, which have good stability under uniaxial cyclic strain and biaxial strain in the linear elastic limit, these can be used as sensors for health monitoring of structures even upon small deformation. In this study, it was observed that a composite of PANI doped with DBSA and blended with a copolymer, ethylene-vinyl acetate showed the highest strain sensitivity. This is explained using the mechanism of strain sensing.

2. Experimental Methods

Polyaniline (emeraldine base, EB) was synthesized and doped separately with hydrochloric acid (HCl) and dodecyl benzene sulfonic acid (DBSA). PANI-HCl/PVA and PANI-DBSA/EVA composite films were prepared by solution blending and casting of films. This was made into free-standing films and for the purpose of comparison, samples were also made by coating onto PET substrate. Commercial samples of PEDOT:PSS coated on PET substrate were purchased. Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on a biaxial tensile testing machine (BiSS Ltd., Bangalore, load cell capacity 1kN) using ASTM D882 standard sample. Video-based displacement recording system was used to determine the strain. The electrical resistance was simultaneously measured using a 2-probe conductivity meter (Agilent 34972A). From the measured resistance values (R), the conductivity (σ) is obtained as

$$\sigma = \frac{\lambda^2 l}{RA} \quad (1)$$

where l is the distance between the electrodes, and A is the cross sectional area, $\lambda=l/l_0$, l_0 is the initial distance between electrodes (all in SI units). Strain sensitivity or gauge factor (GF) is obtained from,

$$GF = \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta l/l_0} \quad (2)$$

where ΔR is the change in resistance and $\Delta l/l_0$ is the mechanical strain (all in SI units).

3. Results and Discussion

Electromechanical response upon uniaxial tensile loading of PANI-HCl/PVA, PANI-DBSA/EVA (both free-standing and coated on PET substrates) and PEDOT:PSS coated on PET substrates is shown in Figure 1. Upon uniaxial tensile strain, the electronic conductivity increases. This is attributed to the re-arrangement of microstructure of the ICP [3]. Among all the films, PANI-DBSA/EVA showed the highest sensitivity. Upon cyclic loading, the conductivity follows the same trend as that of mechanical strain. The strain sensitivity for various conductive composites are

given in Table 1. PANI-DBSA/EVA (40/60) shows highest strain sensitivity among the composites studied. Further studies on the determination of response time, cyclic response for 1000 cycles, etc. were also studied for PANI-DBSA/EVA.

Figure 1. Electromechanical response of various ICPs films.

Table 1. Strain sensitivity of various ICP films.

Sensor film	Measurable range (% strain)	Strain sensitivity (Gauge factor)
PANI-HCl/PVA	19	-12
PANI-HCl/PVA on PET	3	-2
PANI-DBSA-EVA	13	-66
PANI-DBSA-EVA on PET	5	-24
PEDOT:PSS on PET	14	-20

4. Summary

Conductive PANI composites PANI-HCl/PVA, PANI-DBSA/EVA, films of PEDOT:PSS showed strain sensing property. On uniaxial tensile loading, the conductivity increased. PANI-DBSA/EVA showed the maximum strain sensitivity.

5. References

- [1] Forrest, S.R., 2004. The path to ubiquitous and low-cost organic electronic appliances on plastic. *Nature*, 428(6986), p.911.
- [2] Barra, G.M., Leyva, M.E., Soares, B.G., Mattoso, L.H. and Sens, M., 2001. Electrically conductive, melt-processed polyaniline/EVA blends. *Journal of applied polymer science*, 82(1), pp.114-123.
- [3] Akhilesan, S., Rao, C.L. and Varughese, S., 2014. Electromechanical behavior of polyaniline/poly (vinyl alcohol) blend films under static, dynamic and time-dependent strains. *Smart Materials and Structures*, 23(7), p.075016.

Response of Polyurea: Coating and Sandwich Structured Steel Plate in Blast Application

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Abstract

In the present study, we will discuss the numerical analysis of response of metal plates coated with polyurea as well as polyurea sandwiched with metal plates which are subjected to the blast loads keeping the areal density constant. The numerical analysis is done using inbuilt blast function code, ConWep available in ABAQUS/Explicit and the results are validated with experimental data. The relative assessment of the above plates showed that polyurea coated on back face of monolithic plates as well as the sandwiched panels showed a significant reduction in deflection and impulse transmitted to the structures with sandwich panels giving slightly better response.

1. Introduction

Recent experiments show that when coated on steel plates with enough adhesion, polymers can increase the overall impact resistance of steel armors when applied on the back side i.e., the side opposite to where load is applied. The numerical analysis of blast response of various shapes of hull plates used in APV was done in literature. The blast resistant and damage behavior of plain woven, layered and sandwich composite fabricated using polyurea glass fiber composite was evaluated experimentally using a shock tube for applying a shock blast loading on simply supported rectangular plate. Traditionally the armor materials such as ultra-high hardness steels are being used for providing the occupant protection at the expense of payload and mobility. Therefore, there is a need of lightweight armor material that would reduce the payload and enhance the mobility at the same time ensure occupant safety. In recent years, composites are being used in military application.

2. Background

The dynamic behavior of structures subjected to blast loading as well as high impact has been the subject of considerable research effort in recent years. Coating the structures with a polyurea layer has proven to significantly affect the survivability of such structures under high intensity loading conditions such as blast and impact. Polyurea is a coating material that has received extensive research interest due to its effective energy absorption property, withstand to high impact loads and many other physical & mechanical properties. Recently a number of studies are being done to explore use of polyurea coatings to enhance blast protection. Initially polyurea was applied to concrete masonry wall units. These studies showed that the polymeric material effectively hold together the fragments after breaking off the back surface of the wall during blast loading. In recent studies, industries are using polymeric materials to enhance the blast protection of metallic structures and composite structures [1]. Many researchers have been exploring blast effects on the concrete structures by different reinforcing and mixing addition, such as steel, fiber, carbon and nylon into the concrete mold. To protect the civilian buildings in a war or terrorist attack area, concrete structures are extensively used as protective structures.

The concerns regarding vehicle integrity, safety of military personnel is critical when the AFVs are exposed to mine blast. In such condition, the vehicle's hull might get ruptured due to applied loading and the vehicle occupant would be exposed to mechanical effects such as shock, structural deformation and vertical impulse loading. The effect of mine on vehicle occupant can be categorized into three types namely primary, secondary and tertiary. The primary injuries are related to pressure and duration of blast wave, secondary injuries are related to fragments and other debris and tertiary injuries are occurred when a body suffers significant acceleration or decelerations resulting in spine injuries, traumatic brain injuries, abdominal injuries etc. Composite materials are considered as effective materials in applications involving blast and ballistic impacts, for absorbing the energy of blast. Also, the application of polyurea as a coating and sandwiched with metals, as a shock mitigation material is a relatively new idea. In the present study the objectives are:

- a) To develop a numerical model for simulating the response of metallic plates with polyurea coating to facilitate designing a blast resistant steel component.
- b) To investigate the response of Sandwich Plates under Blast loading by keeping Areal Density Constant.

3. Experimental Results

The experimental results for scaled down model using Crazz-Hopkinson scaling law for Cassipir was achieved. The specimen was scaled down to 8.33:1. The dimension of specimen was 300 X 300mm, it was subjected to a blast loading of 5, 10, 14.5, 19, 21 and 23 gm of TNT at a standoff distance of 34mm with model dimension shown in Table 1. The corresponding displacement and impulse were noted down and were compared with the experimental results obtained by Yuen et al. [2] (Figures 1 and 2). A close correlation between experimental and numerical simulation were obtained. The maximum error in impulse was found to be 13.6% and for deflection the error was 33.7 %. The difference between experimental and numerical results may be due to reflection of pressure and shock wave from uneven geometry. The validated numerical model was further used for prediction of back face coatings and sandwich structures.

Table 1. Model Dimension.

Parameters	Parameters of scaled down model	Parameters of the full scale model
Dimensions of projected area	300x300mm ²	2500x2500mm ²
Standoff distance	34mm	410mm
Plate thickness	2mm	16.66mm
Material	Domex 700steel	Mild steel

Figure 1. Variation in predicted and measured value of impulse.

Figure 2. impulse vs. mass of pE4.

The response of monolithic plate, polyurea coated on back side of monolithic plate and sandwich panel showed that impulse transmitted to the structure is maximum in case of monolithic plate. The impulse transmitted decreases with the increase in polyurea coating on back side of monolithic plate and similar observation is seen for sandwich panel. However, in case of sandwich panel the impulse transmitted to the structure is similar for lower mass of explosives as compared with that of polyurea coated on back face of monolithic plate while for higher mass of explosives sandwich panel performs better as compared to that on polyurea coated plate.

4. Summary

The bare plate is more effective than back coated plate in terms of reduction in deformation & impulse transmission when areal density is kept constant. Both the back face polyurea coating and sandwich panels were found to be useful in blast mitigation. However, the sandwich panel appeared to provide slightly more blast mitigation especially at higher mass of explosives.

5. References

[1] Ackland, K., Anderson, C. and Ngo, T.D., 2013. Deformation of polyurea-coated steel plates under localised blast loading. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 51, pp.13-22.
 [2] Yuen, S.C.K., Langdon, G.S., Nurick, G.N., Pickering, E.G. and Balden, V.H., 2012. Response of V-shape plates to localised blast load: Experiments and numerical simulation. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 46, pp.97-109.

Numerical Implementation of Welding Residual Stresses in AISI Type 316LN Stainless Steel using Mapping Technique

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Abstract

Welding residual stress is one of the main concerns in the process of fabrication and operation which cause failures in welded steel joints due to its potential effect on structural integrity. This work focuses on the numerical implementation of measured welding residual stress using X-ray diffraction technique in welded CT specimens of AISI 316LN. Two-dimensional plane strain model has been used to simulate the CT specimen. This technique contains an iterative procedure to equilibrate the pre-stress input to the FE model. With residual stresses, the crack is propagated using GTN model. Results show that this method can numerically implement the measured residual stresses with good accuracy and the effect of the residual stress for a given crack length on ductile crack propagation is also studied.

1. Introduction

The ductile crack growth behavior seen in many of the steel structure play a vital role in fracture analysis. The ductile fracture process is effected by the presence of high stress triaxiality and plastic strains [1] and influences the near tip stress/strain field. The influence of weld residual stresses on the behavior of the weld joint characterizes the failure of weld structures and welded components. The presence of residual stresses can influence the stress fields due to loading at the crack tip and cause additional constraint [2]. This paper focuses on the numerical implementation of measured welding residual stress using X-ray diffraction technique in welded CT specimens of AISI 316LN. Two-dimensional plain strain models have been modelled to simulate the crack present in CT specimen. Welding residual stresses were mapped on to FE-model using residual mapping technique [3]. The GTN model is used to estimate the crack behavior due to loading and develop load bearing behavior.

2. Material Properties, Geometry and GTN Model

The material studied is the austenite stainless steel grade 316LN (316LN SS), used for the primary and secondary sodium systems of Prototype Fast Breeder Reactor (PFBR). Shield metal arc welding is performed to fabricate 316LN SS weld joints. In this process, SS 316L electrode sticks are used. Tensile specimens used for material properties testing are extracted perpendicular to the weld seam. The compact tension (CT) specimen is used to study the fracture behavior of 316LN SS material. The main dimensions of the CT specimen are the crack length a is 30 mm, width W is 50mm, thickness B is 14mm and weld width is 14mm.

Ductile fracture in metals is a result of void nucleation, growth and coalescence of the existing and newly born micro voids due to loading. The modified GTN model consists of additional parameters (q_1 , q_2 , q_3) and modified damage variable f^* . The yield function of the GTN model is shown below:

$$\phi(\sigma, f, \bar{\sigma}) = \frac{\sigma_{eq}^2}{\sigma} + 2q_1 f^* \cdot \cosh\left(\frac{3}{2} q_2 \frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma}\right) - 1 - (q_1 f^*)^2 \quad (1)$$

3. Residual Mapping Technique

The measured residual stress value for weld 316LN SS was taken from X-ray diffraction report performed on dissimilar metal weld joint of 316LN - Inconel 182 - P91. Some important test parameters used for residual stress measurement by the XRD technique for 316LN SS are X-ray radiation used Chromium $K\beta$, operating voltage is 30 kV, Current is 7mA, Wavelength is 2.0848. The value of residual stress is 153MPa measured at 7mm away from the interface of 316LN SS and Inconel 182. The residual stress was introduced into the FE-model of the CT-specimen at weld zone as pre-stress, but without a crack. Since the introduction of pre-stress causes the FE-model

to be in the non-equilibrium state, a self-equilibrated step was performed to distribute and relax the defined pre-stresses to the adjacent elements of the FE-model before applying loads or displacements. This step results in a difference between the initial pre-stress and equilibrium stresses developed. To minimize the difference, an iterative process is chosen to modify the input values of the pre-stress to emulate a desired residual stress. The following equation defines the iterative process:

$$[\sigma]_{input}^{i+1} = [\sigma]_{input}^i + \alpha \{ [\sigma]_{Measured} - [\sigma]_{Output}^i \} \quad (2)$$

where $[\sigma]_{input}$ is pre-stress input into the FE-model, $[\sigma]_{measured}$ is the measured residual stress from experiments. $[\sigma]_{output}$ is the resultant stress obtained after equilibrium step. The superscript i , in the Eq. (2) represents the i^{th} step in the iterative process and α is a constant and taken as 1. This iteration process starts with $i = 0$ and $[\sigma]_{input} = [\sigma]_{measured}$. $[\sigma]_{input}$ for $i = 1$ is calculated from the Eq. (2) and using the value of $[\sigma]_{output}$ obtained from previous analysis. The iterative process runs till the values of $[\sigma]_{output} = [\sigma]_{measured}$ are approximately equal.

4. Results

The procedure discussed in the previous section is implemented numerical using Abaqus FEA package. The image shown below details the residual stress distribution in CT specimen with a pre-crack. Figure 1. clearly shows the pre-stress distribution to the base metal regions during equilibrium step. The graph shown below details the effect of residual stresses on the load bearing capacity of the structure. The graph compares the load vs displacement of the welded CT specimen with and without residual stresses. From the figure, it is evident that the residual stresses affect the plastic region of the welded structure. Since the magnitude of the residual stresses does not exceed the yield stress of the weld metal, the elastic region remains identical.

Figure 1. Residual stress distribution with pre-crack.

Figure 2. Load vs Load line displacement.

5. Summary

In this paper, the numerical implementation of residual stresses is discussed. The procedure is implemented using 2-D plain strain CT specimen model and successfully distributed stresses over the elements adjacent to weld zone due to equilibrium step. The difference between measured residual stress and output residual stresses is less than 5%. The effect of residual stresses on load bearing capacity is discussed and compared with the weld joint FE model having no residual stresses.

6. References

- [1] Sherry A H, Wilkes M A, Sharples J K, and Budden P J. The assessment of residual stress effects on ductile tearing using continuum damage mechanics. Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology Vol. 130 No. 4 (2008): p.041212.
- [2] Liu J, Zhang Z L, and Nyhus B. Residual stress induced crack tip constraint. Engineering Fracture Mechanics Vol. 75 No.14 (2008): pp 4151–4166.
- [3] Tvergaard V, and Needleman A. Analysis of the cup-cone fracture in a round tensile bar. Acta metallurgica Vol. 32 No. 1 (1984): pp.157-169.

Study of Crack Propagation Using Finite Element Methods

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Abstract

In this paper, we study the crack propagation in 2-D materials using finite element methods (FEM). Two types of boundary conditions are considered: displacement boundary condition (Dirichlet) and traction boundary condition (Neumann). Two modes of crack propagation are also considered: namely, crack opening and crack sliding. For each of them, the crack propagation and region of stress concentration are determined using the free open source software FreeFem++ with great accuracy.

1. Introduction

The theory behind the crack propagation is the solution of steady state elastostatic problem which is govern by

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + b_i = 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} denotes the stress tensor in 2 dimensions with four components and b_i denotes the body forces acting on the object. Here, i and j can take values 1 and 2 denoting x and y directions, respectively. Elaborating, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial y} + b_x = 0 \quad (2)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{yx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial y} + b_y = 0 \quad (3)$$

It is obtained as a consequence of force equilibrium. We solve the elastostatic problem by expressing the stress in terms of displacement of particles of the materials. The transformation is done using the constitutive relations and it leads to a second order elliptic partial differential equation (PDE) in two variables.

The traction boundary condition is given by:

$$\sigma_{ij} \cdot n_j = t_i \quad (4)$$

Similar transformation of the traction boundary condition leads to Neumann boundary condition.

The two variables u_1 and u_2 are solved for x and y values of displacement. The weak formulation is derived for both the directions separately and then combined to obtain a single weak formulation for the problem. The traction boundary condition becomes the Neumann condition for the solution and the whole equation is solved by using FreeFEM++ which is an Open source FEM software.

Finally, this technique is applied to two separate materials namely,

- Aluminium with $E = 68.9$ GPa and $\nu = 0.34$ and
- Nylon with $E = 28.3$ GPa and $\nu = 0.4$,

where E is the Young's modulus and ν is the poison's ratio.

2. Equations

The strain-displacement and constitutive relations are given by: $e_{ij} = 0.5(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})$ and $\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}e_{kl}$, where e is the strain tensor, σ is the stress tensor and C is the modulus of elasticity tensor.

The governing equations finally become:

$$(\lambda + 2\mu)\frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2} + \mu\frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial y^2} + (\lambda + \mu)\frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x\partial y} + b_x = 0 \quad (5)$$

and

$$(\lambda + 2\mu)\frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial y^2} + \mu\frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x^2} + (\lambda + \mu)\frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x\partial y} + b_y = 0 \quad (6)$$

where λ and μ are material constants present in the modulus of elasticity tensor. The equations are multiplied by test functions, shear and tensile loads are applied and the weak formulation is derived for each case separately.

3. Results

Figure 1. Aluminium under tensile load.

Figure 2. Nylon under tensile load.

Figure 3. Aluminium under shear load.

Figure 4. Nylon under shear load.

Crack propagation and stress concentration zones are accurately plotted using FreeFEM++ software.

4. Summary

We have studied crack propagation by using FEM. The weak formulation and the method adopted to solves the problem and this technique can be applied to solve more complex crack domains, and further, can also be extended to three dimensions.

5. References

- [1] T. Belytschko., and T. Black, 1999, Elastic Crack Growth in Finite Elements with minimal Remeshing, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 45, 601-620.
- [2] J. S. Daily, and N. W. Klingbeil, 2010, Plastic dissipation energy at a biomaterial crack tip under cyclic loading”, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 32(10), 1710-1723.
- [3] D. M. Tracey, 1976, Finite element solution for crack-tip behavior in small scale yielding, *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, 98(2), 146-151.
- [4] F. Hecht, 2012, New development in FreeFem++. *J. Numer. Math.*, 20, 251–265.

Micro Inertia Driven Entropy Based Damage Evolution for Polycrystalline Metals Under High Strain Rate

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Abstract

A general continuum mechanics based framework using the principles of irreversible thermodynamics and statistical mechanics for the quantification of damage in polycrystalline metals, subject to high strain rate deformations has been developed. Nonlinearities associated with micro-structural defects in polycrystalline metals under high strain rate deformations are homogenized by introducing meso-level intrinsic length scale. Micro-structural linear momentum balance is done to incorporate inertial effects of dislocations using mesoscopic length scale so that continuum principles hold true.

1. Introduction

Current non-local plasticity theories do not explicitly consider inertial effect at microscopic level while micro-structural defects are in motion [1] especially during high strain rate deformations. Classical metal plasticity considers homogeneous plastic flow since they consider only statistically stored dislocations in to account. Experimental investigations on strength of materials [2] reported intrinsic length scale in determining inhomogeneous plastic deformations. In order to account inhomogeneous plastic flow, one has to consider geometrically necessary dislocations to have deformation compatibility in gradient visco-plasticity theories. Kinematics of deformation assumed here are state of small strain deformations, and Irrotational plastic flow of dislocation motion under the assumption of plastic incompressibility.

2. Balance of Linear Momentum at Microscopic Level

Intrinsic microscopic length scale can be considered as characteristic distances between defects (dislocations) and/or their characteristic sizes (dislocation cells). Inertial effects have been demonstrated by considering the acceleration of dislocations in the equation of motion with a proper definition of dislocation mass and in a phenomenological way, that can be written as follows [3],

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left[\int \rho_m l_m^2 \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} \right] d\Omega = \int \zeta \cdot n d(\partial\Omega) + \int (\Lambda - \Pi) d\Omega \quad (1)$$

Consequently, the meso-level energy balance incorporating kinetic energy contribution of dislocation motion is expressed as,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\rho \left(\frac{1}{2} v^2 + \frac{1}{2} l_m^2 \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}^2} + \psi \right) \right] = -\nabla \cdot \left(\rho e v - \sigma v - \zeta \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} \right) + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r - \frac{\partial \rho h}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

Combining the above Eqs. (1) and (2) upon application of principle of local state, final form of specific internal energy rate is given by expressing N^p as the plastic strain direction tensor and D as the symmetric part of velocity gradient after imposing balance of angular momentum,

$$\rho \frac{dh}{dt} = \sigma : D + \zeta \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} - \sigma : N^p \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r \quad (3)$$

It is hypothesized that Helmholtz free energy is dependent on elastic strain, gradient of equivalent plastic strain and temperature. To be consistent with irreversible thermodynamics, Clausius-Duhem inequality is imposed to get dissipation function and constitutive expressions,

$$\rho T \frac{ds}{dt} = \left(\sigma - \rho \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial E^e} \right) : E^e + \left(\zeta - \rho \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}}} \right) \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r - \rho \left[\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial T} + s \right] \dot{T} \quad (4)$$

and decomposing $\zeta = \zeta^e + \zeta^d$, energetic and dissipative components, consequently Eq. (4) is modified as follows

$$\rho T \frac{ds}{dt} = \zeta^d \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r \quad (5)$$

The above expression is further modified using the differential form of Fourier's law of thermal conduction to get the entropy evolution equation as

$$\frac{ds_i}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho T} \zeta^d \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \frac{1}{\rho T} \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^{\dot{p}} + \frac{1}{\rho T^2} k \nabla T \cdot \nabla T + \frac{1}{T} r \quad (6)$$

3. Evolution of Damage

Damage evolution is defined by a relationship between damage and entropy for solids undergoing plastic deformation [4].

$$D_\alpha = D_{cr} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{m_s}{R}(s-s_0)} \right) \quad (7)$$

In time integration scheme, change in entropy $\Delta s = s - s_0$ can be evaluated from the evolution Eq. (6) and can be used to compute total damage from Eq. (7).

4. Summary

General framework developed for gradient based plasticity in polycrystalline metals, proven to have thermodynamic consistency in the context of unified mechanics which relates entropy with damage. This approach is robust in a way that all kinds of dissipation in any material under external, internal or combined energy transfer can be physically quantified by damage parameter. By incorporating a meso-level length scale, it is made possible to couple nonlinearities associated with dislocations and could incorporate micro-structural inertia effects. This evolution equation may be further investigated in the future to quantify mesoscopic conjugate forces and a workable entropy evolution equation may be developed for high strain rate deformations in polycrystalline metals. In addition to that, a healing configuration can be postulated to map damaged configuration to investigate the effect of crack closure mechanism observed in certain materials.

5. References

- [1] Wang, L., Teng, J., Liu, P., Hirata, A., Ma, E., Zhang, Z., Chen, M. and Han, X., 2014. Grain rotation mediated by grain boundary dislocations in nanocrystalline platinum. *Nature communications*, 5, p.4402.
- [2] Ma, Q. and Clarke, D.R., 1995. Size dependent hardness of silver single crystals. *Journal of Materials Research*, 10(4), pp.853-863.
- [3] Rahaman, M.M., Roy, P., Roy, D. and Reddy, J.N., 2017. A peridynamic model for plasticity: Micro-inertia based flow rule, entropy equivalence and localization residuals. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 327, pp.369-391.
- [4] Basaran, C. and Yan, C.Y., 1998. A thermodynamic framework for damage mechanics of solder joints. *Journal of Electronic Packaging*, 120(4), pp.379-384.

Active Buckling Control Studies on Columns Using Equivalent Force Model as Piezoelectric Actuators

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Abstract

In the present study numerical analyses are carried out on column structures to see the feasibility of enhancement in buckling load. The analyses are carried out on a column having aluminum material properties. Force-displacement plots are used for finding the effect of actuators on the buckling characteristics of the column.

1. Introduction

The main reason for the failure of thin structures like columns is buckling. If buckling is controlled by any external actuation, the load-bearing capacity of a structure can be improved. Berlin [1] has pointed out that when compared to man-made structures, the structures built by nature (animals) are more flexible when acted upon different loading conditions. He conducted experiments in which buckling effect on the composite columns was minimized by using piezoelectric actuators. It was demonstrated that multiple buckling modes can be stabilized simultaneously. He found that loadbearing capacity of a controlled column was increased by 5.6 times. Cohen [2] pointed that active control of buckling leads to stronger and lighter structures which can dynamically adapt to the change in the environment. Simulation the active buckling control on columns using ABAQUS FEM solver has been done and the results are analyzed.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the Feedback loop created in Abaqus.

2. Problem Formulation

It is assumed that the force produced by the piezoelectric actuator concentrates at the center of the actuator, when the voltage is applied across it. Thus the force is applied directly on the column for this investigation. The force is applied in such a way that the column is pushed towards the equilibrium direction. The force value is calculated proportionally to the stress value at the center of the column in the axial direction and the formula taken is given below.

$$F = K \times S_{11} \quad (1)$$

where F is the equivalent force, S_{11} is the stress the axial direction and K is the control gain.

A column is modelled using Aluminum material properties. The dimensions taken for the column are 250mm×25mm×1mm. FEM Model consists of shell elements having 4 nodes with reduced integration and hour glass control were used for the modelling of column structure. Motion in X, Y, Z directions are restricted at the base and motion in the Y direction is allowed at the top edge of the column.

3. Numerical Studies

Numerical studies are carried out using ABAQUS. Python code is used to create a feedback loop. The restart option available in ABAQUS is utilized to achieve the feedback loop. The stress at a particular location is measured and a proportional force is applied if the stress is greater than the desired value. In this way the control of buckling has been achieved. Force-displacement plots are obtained for with buckling control and without buckling control of column. It is observed that the behavior of the column with control is showing better load bearing capacity.

Figure 2. Deformed shape of the column when subjected to a load and control force.

Figure 3. Load bearing capacity when the force is applied proportionally to the stress value.

4. Summary

FEA analysis for a column on which control forces are applied to prevent buckling is carried out. Investigation has been done using equivalent force model. It is observed from the results that the load-bearing capacity of the column has increased when a force is applied perpendicular to the column. The force applied tries to push the column towards the equilibrium. In effect, this action increases the buckling load carrying capacity of the column.

5. References

- [1] Andrew A. Berlin, Towards Intelligent Structures: “Active Control of Buckling”, Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, May 1994.
- [2] Natalya Cohen, Active Control of Buckling: “Centralized and Decentralized Approaches”, Master’s Thesis, Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, May 1996.
- [3] ABAQUS Manuals, Retrieved from <http://abaqus.software.polimi.it/v6.14/index.html>.

Fatigue Life Estimation of Welded Joints

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Abstract

Fatigue life of welded joints of mild steel plates is studied under uniaxial and biaxial loading conditions. Mild steel plates of 3mm thickness are welded by SMAW process. Uniaxial fatigue testing is conducted for different values of maximum stress keeping the Stress Ratio of 0.1 at 15 Hz. Failure is found to occur at the Heat Affected Zone. Biaxial tests are also conducted on specially made cruciform samples with the same stress ratio. Residual stress developed due to welding process was estimated using Finite Element Method. An attempt is made to estimate fatigue life by simulating crack growth using Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. The experimental and simulation results are compared.

1. Introduction

Many factors including residual stress, geometry, presence of cracks and voids etc. contribute to the mechanical behavior of welded joints [1]. Study of the behavior of welded joints under fatigue loading is important since most of the real life situations include biaxial or multiaxial loading. This work mainly aims to compare the behavior of butt welded joints under uniaxial and biaxial fatigue loading conditions. Weld joints of 3mm thick Mild Steel (0.18% C, 0.73% Si, 0.64% Mn, 0.84% W) plates with two pass Submerged Arc Welding are investigated. The samples were machined to required size/shape using water-jet machining in order to minimize the modification of residual stress.

2. Uniaxial Fatigue Testing

Uniaxial fatigue tests are conducted on a total of 11 dog-bone weld samples prepared according to ASTM E466 standard [2] keeping the maximum stress applied at 80%, 70% and 60% of the yield stress of the base material. The yield strength was obtained as 483 MPa from static tests. The higher yield strength of the mild steel was due to the cold processing used for manufacturing the plates. For fatigue tests the ratio of minimum to maximum stress was maintained at 0.1 by keeping the frequency at 15 Hz. In all cases, the failure occurred at Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) and was sudden without any noticeable crack growth. The photograph of a typical failed sample is shown in Figure 1a.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. (a) Photograph of a typical failed sample under uniaxial loading; (b) Stress Range – Cycles to Failure Plot.

The Stress Range versus Cycles to Failure plot obtained from the uniaxial tests is shown in Figure 1b. The curve indicates decrease in cycles to failure with increase in the applied stress.

3. Biaxial Fatigue Testing

Standards for biaxial fatigue testing are not available and hence cruciform samples designed using finite element analysis are used for the testing. The specimen dimensions are optimized according to the available biaxial test system in the Department of Applied Mechanics, IIT Delhi. A set of specimen made in cruciform shape from welded plates were tested and found to fail at the clamping locations which indicates requirement of modification in specimen. The photograph of a typical failed biaxial sample is shown in Figure 2. Another set of cruciform specimen made from steel plates are slotted in the middle and welded for the testing. The test is ongoing.

Figure 2. Photograph of a failed biaxial sample.

4. Finite Element Simulations

Finite element simulations of welding in ANSYS is carried out in order to estimate the residual stress generated after the welding process. Goldak Double Ellipsoidal heat source [3] model used to determine temperature history and then thermo-elasto-plastic analysis [4] is carried out for determining residual stress. Element birth and death technique is employed to simulate material deposition while welding. It revealed that residual stress is tensile in the weld region and compressive in the adjacent regions. The maximum residual stress generated found to be of the order of yield stress of the material.

Fatigue crack growth is simulated following Modified Elbers' Method [5] based on Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. 3D surface crack is modelled in ANSYS APDL. LEFM equations are used to find out the crack extension. The crack is regenerated with new dimensions for simulation of crack growth. The simulation results are being compared with experimental results.

5. Summary

Weld joints are usually stronger compared to base metal under static loading and Heat Affected Zone is weaker under Fatigue Loading. They behave differently under loading along and across the weld. Residual stress is tensile in the weld region and is compressive in the adjacent regions.

6. References

- [1] Alam MM, Barsoum Z, Jonsén P, Kaplan AF, Häggblad HÅ., 2010, The influence of surface geometry and topography on the fatigue cracking behaviour of laser hybrid welded eccentric fillet joints, *Applied Surface Science*, 256(6), 1936-1945.
- [2] Designation AS. E466-07, 2007, Standard practice for conducting force controlled constant amplitude axial fatigue tests of metallic materials, ASTM International.
- [3] Goldak J, Chakravarti A, 1984, Bibby M. A new finite element model for welding heat sources, *Metallurgical transactions B*, 15(2), 299-305.
- [4] UEDA Y, Nakacho K, 1980, Theory of Thermal Elastic-Plastic Analysis with A More General Workhardening Rule (*Welding Mechanics, Strength & Design*), *Transactions of JWRI*, 9(1), 107-114.
- [5] Liu H, Shang DG, Liu JZ, Guo ZK., 2014, Fatigue life prediction of laser welded 6156 Al-alloy joints based on crack closure, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, 74, 181-187.

Analysis of Resonant Fatigue Testing System

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Abstract

This work addresses the modelling of resonant fatigue testing of pipes using transfer matrix method and frequency response of the system for different operating conditions. The modeling of pipes is carried out using Timoshenko beam theory considering rotational and gyroscopic effects. The interaction between different spans is simulated using Transfer matrix of joints. The natural frequencies, mode shapes and forced vibration response are analysed.

1. Introduction

Study of dynamic response of rotating machinery is important for design and failure prevention of machinery. It is necessary to improve the fatigue resistance of pipes subjected to dynamic loading e.g. oil exploration lines. The most common method of loading for estimating fatigue life are axial, multi-point and rotating resonant bending. In resonant fatigue testing system, fatigue life is calculated by exploiting the resonance condition. A pipe is excited by a rotating eccentric mass, and the excitation frequency is controlled using external motor. Two bearings are used to hold the rotating pipe [1]. It is assumed that the stress-strain behavior of bearings is linear for small displacement.

2. Methodology

Transfer matrix method is used for analyzing free and forced vibration. In this method, we relate the state variables from one end of the system to another end by developing point and field transfer matrices. Further, with the help of point and field matrices we form an overall transfer matrix to get the vibration response by applying the boundary conditions. The governing equations for the rotating pipe element are given as [2]:

$$\frac{\partial^4 X}{\partial Z^4} - \left(\frac{\rho}{KG} + \frac{\rho}{E} \right) \frac{\partial^4 X}{\partial Z^2 \partial t^2} + \frac{\rho^2}{KGE} \frac{\partial^4 X}{\partial t^4} + \frac{\rho A}{EI} \frac{\partial^2 X}{\partial t^2} + \frac{2\rho\omega}{E} \left(\frac{\partial^3 Y}{\partial Z^2 \partial t} - \frac{\rho}{KG} \frac{\partial^3 Y}{\partial t^3} \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^4 Y}{\partial Z^4} - \left(\frac{\rho}{KG} + \frac{\rho}{E} \right) \frac{\partial^4 Y}{\partial Z^2 \partial t^2} + \frac{\rho^2}{KGE} \frac{\partial^4 Y}{\partial t^4} + \frac{\rho A}{EI} \frac{\partial^2 Y}{\partial t^2} - \frac{2\rho\omega}{E} \left(\frac{\partial^3 X}{\partial Z^2 \partial t} - \frac{\rho}{KG} \frac{\partial^3 X}{\partial t^3} \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Governing equations of motion are used to drive the transfer matrix of a continuous segment of a pipe.

3. Results and Discussion

A rotor-bearing system [3] as shown in Figure 1a is considered for validation.

Figure 1. (a) Rotor-bearing system [3]; (b) Comparison of the frequency response of system.

The frequency response of the system is obtained using MATLAB code developed based on the transfer matrix method. For comparison, rotor-bearing system is modelled in ANSYS and harmonic analysis is carried out. The frequency response of the system obtained using TMM found to be in good agreement with that obtained using ANSYS (Figure 1b). We modelled the resonant fatigue testing system with the help of the bearing, mass and pipe elements. Different system parameters (Table 1) are varied to obtain the stress charts.

Table 1. Details of resonant fatigue testing system for aluminium pipe section [4].

Pipe			Bearing		Unbalance	
Parameter	span	Joint	$K_{xx} = K_{yy}$	1000 N/m	Mass	7 Kg
Length (mm)	3700	500				
Do, Di (mm)	147, 121	157, 131	$C_{xx} = C_{yy}$	10000 Ns/m	eccentricity	0.05 m
E (GPa)	73	73	$C_{xy} = K_{xy}$	0	Phase angle	0

For the stress variation with unbalance mass other parameter values are kept constant (Table 1). The maximum bending stress versus rotational speed curves for different unbalance mass are shown in Figure 2. As expected, the stress amplitude increases with the increase in unbalance without any significant change in resonance frequencies. These charts are expected to be useful for the design of resonant fatigue testing system.

Figure 2. Stress variation with the unbalance m^*e .

4. Summary

The parametric study is carried out to investigate the variation of stress amplitude with variation of length, thickness and unbalance. This study can be used to design resonant fatigue testing system according to the field operating conditions.

5. References

- [1] Miscow GF, De Miranda PE, Netto TA, Plácido JC, 2004, Techniques to characterize fatigue behavior of full size drill pipes and small scale samples, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 26(6), 575-84.
- [2] Ghasemalizadeh O, Mirzaee M, Sadeghi H, Taghi Ahmadian M, 2008, Rotor Bearing System Analysis Using the Transfer Matrix Method with Thickness Assumption of Disk and Bearing, *International Journal of Mechanical, Aerospace, Industrial, Mechatronic and Manufacturing Engineering*, 2(5), 607 - 614.
- [3] Kang Y, Lee AC, Shih YP, 1994, A modified transfer matrix method for asymmetric rotor-bearing systems, *Journal of vibration and acoustics*, 116(3), 309-17.
- [4] Bertini L, Beghini M, Santus C, Baryshnikov A, 2008, Resonant test rigs for fatigue full scale testing of oil drill string connections, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 30(6), 978-88.

Crack Growth Analysis of a Homogeneous Plate in the Presence of Defects Using Extended Isogeometric Analysis

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Abstract

In this work, extended Isogeometric analysis (XIGA) is successfully extended to evaluate the fatigue life of a homogenous finite plate in the presence of defects (cracks and holes) under cyclic loading condition. In isogeometric analysis (IGA), same basis functions, i.e. non uniform rational B-splines (NURBS), are used for defining the geometry and solution. In XIGA, the crack faces are modeled by discontinuous Heaviside jump functions, whereas the singularity in stress field at the crack tip is modeled by crack tip enrichment functions. The modeling of holes is performed by jump function. A new criterion has been used to model the different type of discontinuities within the element by imposing additional degrees of freedom at the control points, intersected by a discontinuity. These simulations show that the defects/discontinuities, distributed near to the main crack have significant effect on the SIF values whereas the defects/discontinuities away from the main crack have got very small effect on the SIFs.

Keywords: Extended isogeometric analysis (XIGA), Fatigue life, Paris law, Edge crack, Holes, Inclusions, Stress intensity factor (SIF).

1. Introduction

The analysis of static and propagating cracks becomes important to ensure the reliability of components under cyclic loading condition. In general, the fatigue life of the components is evaluated using strength of material based failure theories without accounting the effect of discontinuities, developed either at the manufacturing stage or during application. Therefore, fracture based numerical simulations have extensive applications in predicting the life of components in presence of defects. To simulate cracked structures, a number of methods such as element free Galerkin method [1], reproducing kernel particle method [3], meshless local petrov Galerkin method [4] and extended finite element method [1] have been used. In these methods, the approximation of geometry introduces some error in the solution since different basis functions are employed for defining the geometry and solution. To cope-up with this issue, in 2006, Hughes et al. [5] introduced a powerful numerical method, known as isogeometric analysis (IGA). In IGA, the error associated with the domain discretization/approximation is totally removed as the same basis functions (NURBS) are employed for defining the geometry as well as the solution. In recent years, IGA has been successfully applied in the various fields of engineering and sciences. Therefore, in the present work, the XIGA will not only be extended further to simulate the life estimation of fatigue crack growth with multiple flaws but also will be extended to simulate the multiple flaws lying in the same element. The modeling of various discontinuities passing through one element is performed by imposing additional degrees of freedom at selected control points. The discontinuities located far away from crack have less influence on the SIFs value. Therefore, the discontinuities are modeled in a specific area near the plate. The plane crack problems are taken, and solved by XIGA in the presence of multiple discontinuities.

2. Isogeometric Analysis

Non-uniform rational B-splines (NURBS) are used in computer aided design (CAD) because of their ability to represent complex geometries exactly. Isogeometric analysis uses same basis functions for performing the analysis. Hence, there is no error present due to the geometric discretization.

3. Numerical Simulation and Discussion

In this paper, the fatigue life of an edge cracked finite sized plate is simulated by XIGA in the presence of holes. A finite plate of size 100mm×200mm along with an edge crack of initial length $a = 25$ mm is taken for the simulation as shown in Figure 1. In XIGA and XFEM, the domain is discretized with a uniform control net and uniform mesh of 30×60 respectively. The fatigue life obtained by both XIGA and XFEM are depicted in Figure 2. The cross mark indicates the fatigue life of the plate. The failure fatigue life for finite plate obtained using XIGA and XFEM are found to be 17908 cycles and 18835 cycles respectively. The results obtained by XIGA are found in good agreement with XFEM.

Figure 1. Edge crack plate with dimensions, loading and boundary conditions.

Figure 2. Fatigue life variation with crack length for left edge cracked plate.

4. Conclusion

In present work, XIGA has been successfully extended to evaluate the fatigue life of an edge cracked plate in the presence of holes, inclusions and minor cracks. The modeling of multiple discontinuities passing through an element is performed by adding additional degrees of freedoms at the selected control points. The proposed domain size (radius at crack tip) is taken as function of element diagonal length for fatigue crack growth. The optimum value of domain size is taken as 75% of element diagonal length. On the basis of present simulations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- a) The multiple discontinuities lying in an element can be accurately and easily simulated by XIGA.
- b) The fatigue life of plate is significantly affected due to presence of defects i.e. holes, inclusions and minor cracks.
- c) The discontinuities (holes) located away from the major crack has negligible influence on the SIFs value.
- d) The presence of discontinuities behind crack has got negligible influence on the SIFs.

5. References

- [1] Belytschko, T., and Black, T. (1999), Elastic crack growth in finite elements with minimal remeshing, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 45, pp. 601–620.
- [2] Belytschko, T., Lu, Y.Y. and Gu, L. (1994), Element-free Galerkin methods, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 37, pp. 229–256.
- [3] Atluri, S.N. and Zhu, T. (1998), A new meshless local Petrov–Galerkin (MLPG) approach in computational mechanics, *Computational Mechanics*, Vol. 22, pp. 117–127.
- [4] Liu, W.K., Jun, S. and Zhang, Y.F. (1995), Reproducing kernel particle methods, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 20, pp. 1081–1106.
- [5] Hughes, T.J.R., Cottrell, J.A. and Bazilevs, Y. (2005), Isogeometric analysis: CAD, finite elements, NURBS, exact geometry and mesh refinement, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, Vol. 194, pp. 4135–4195.

Influence of Water Cooling on Stresses in DC Casting of Aluminum Alloys

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Abstract

Startup phase of direct chill casting is very critical due to the origin of hot tearing at the surfaces in case of rectangular ingots. To identify the possibility of occurrence of defects, thermomechanical behaviors of the ingot is studied. Boiling curve is the only mode of thermal loading which is different in the impinging and free falling region of the secondary water cooling. Hot casting due to complete water ejection, cold casting due to immediate wetting, and the real situation which is the combination of hot and cold cast are studied in the aspect of stress evolution at the surfaces. It is identified that all components of stresses are tensile and relatively high for the wetting front propagating case than the cold casting case.

1. Introduction

Direct Chill (DC) casting process is used to produce aluminum and magnesium ingots for the subsequent rolling process. The schematic view of DC casting process and the simplified mathematical representation of thermal and mechanical computational domain are shown in Figure 1. When the bottom block starts moving downwards, the water jet first strikes the ingot below the Electromagnetic slit. In the start-up phase, casting speed and water flow rate are generally ramped for the optimized product quality.

Figure 1. Direct chill casting – Process schematics and Computational domain.

Maximum heat flux, Leidenfrost temperature, and rewetting temperature are the parameters influencing the boiling curve which depends on amount of water flow rate. Based on the ingot temperature, surface quality, amount of water flow, and water quality, the Leidenfrost effect occurs which changes the cooling kinetics in the impinging region. Rewetting temperature controls the front movement in the free falling region.

2. Thermal Solution

Thermal modeling of DC casting includes the domain growth and boiling curve for two regions [1-3]. The thermal solution for hot casting, cold casting and water flow regulating case (experimental) at a position of 25 mm from the bottom are shown in Figure 2a. For the cold casting case, since the water flow rate is sufficient, wetting of the ingot surface occurs at the impingement region itself and so there is no wetting front propagation. In the hot casting

case, due to low water flow rate, film boiling occurs at the impingement region. This results in permanent water ejection and there is no wetting front propagation and no further cooling in the free falling region. For the experimental case, initially the low water flow rate promotes ejection in startup phase and the water flow rate is increased for the occurrence of wetting and followed by front propagation.

3. Mechanical Solution

Plane strain situation in the direction of ingot width is used to recover the 2-D modelling [4]. The maximum stress occurs at the surface of the ingot. Maximum stress in 'z' direction of the ingot surface with respect to ingot height is shown in Figure 2b. For the water flow regulating case, σ_{zz} reaches a maximum of around 165 MPa in the bottom region of the ingot. Even in the immediate wetting case (cold cast), stresses are not critical in the bottom region. For hot cast, the maximum stresses are very low due to film boiling at the impingement region.

Figure 2. (a) Temperature evolution at 25 mm from bottom; (b) Maximum out of plane stress along the ingot height for the three cases [* - casting speed and water flow rate is ramped in the simulation which is called as experimental situation].

4. Summary

Thermal and mechanical fields of DC casting process is modeled. For the wetting front propagation case, the maximum stresses for all components are high and tensile at the surface in the bottom region of the ingot, which is the one of the major reasons for the origin of surface cracks.

5. References

- [1] J. Sengupta, S. L. Cockcroft, D. M. Maijer, and A. Larouche, 2005, Quantification of temperature, stress, and strain fields during the start-up phase of direct chill casting process by using a 3D fully coupled thermal and stress model for AA5182 ingots, *Materials Science and Engineering A* 397(1-2), 157–177.
- [2] E. Caron, M. A. Wells, 2012, Film boiling and water fil ejection in the secondary cooling zone of the direct chill casting process, *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B*, 43(1), 155-162.
- [3] P. Pavan Kumar, A.K. Nallathambi, E. Specht, A. Bertram, 2012, Mechanical behaviour of mushy zone in DC casting using a viscoplastic material model, *Technische Mechanik* 32(2), 342-357.
- [4] A. K. Nallathambi, 2010, Themomechanical Simulation of Direct chill casting, PhD thesis, OVGU, Magdeburg.

Thermal Stresses in Quenching of Moving Plate by Array of Jets

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Abstract

It is important to understand the origin of distortion and residual stresses in the quenching of moving plates. This kind of situation arises in the direct chill casting process where the water jet impinges on the hot region where the film boiling exists and the jet gets deflected away from the surface. It is attempted to simulate the residual stresses in rigidly moving plate which is fixed at the top surface. It is identified that the curvature is maximum for the initial ejection followed by rewetting situation when compared to immediate wetting, and static plate. Out of plane stresses (σ_{zz}) attains its maximum at the wetting front which is lower for the ejection and rewetting situation. At the bottom edge of the plate σ_{zz} is relatively high for all cases except the static plate.

1. Introduction

When the thin plate is kept vertically stationary, the water jet is assumed to fall on the top. Upper region of the plate is always colder when compared to the lower region. Heat flow from bottom of the plate to top in upward direction. In the case of moving situation, the water jet initially falls on the bottom edge of plate, and the heat flow direction is reversed when compared to static plate situation. In the impinging region, if the film boiling situation arises, the jet gets deflected away from the plate. From that point along the downward region (Free Falling Region, FFR), there is no possibility of water cooling until the wetting front arrives. Leidenfrost temperature controls the film collapse and wetting condition in the impinging region whereas the rewetting temperature influences the wetting front speed and ejection situation in free falling region.

2. Model Description

Figure 1a shows the moving water mold when the plate is kept stationary which is similar as in mold gets fixed and the plate moves downward. The impingement region has both horizontal and vertical momentum of water jet whereas the free falling region has only vertical momentum of water jet. The boiling curves in the Figure 1b are incorporated for impingement region and the free falling region. Based on the speed, possible situation arises at the quenching surface: (a) Immediate wetting, (b) Ejection. In case (a), there is no wetting front movement. However, in case (b), rewetting temperature controls the front speed.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic diagram.

Figure 1. (b) Boiling Curves for impingement and Free falling region.

3. Mathematical Model

Plain strain situation in the plate width direction is assumed due to the negligible temperature gradient in that direction. Elasto-Viscoplastic material model is implemented to capture the rate dependency of thermal loading. The Garofalo law best describes the aluminum alloy's mechanical behavior and is given as in Eq. 1. Garofalo creep is also a deviatoric creep model with a creep rate proportional to the hyperbolic sine function. The exponential term can be augmented by an Arrhenius type temperature dependency.

$$\dot{\epsilon}^{cr} = A \sinh\left(\frac{\sigma_{eff}}{\sigma_0}\right)^n \exp\left(\frac{-Q}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

where Q is the activation energy (SI unit: J/mol), R is the gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature (SI unit: K). A is the creep rate (SI unit: 1/s), n is the stress exponent (dimensionless), and σ_0 a reference effective stress level (SI unit: Pa).

In-house MATLAB based finite element code is used to model the thermal and mechanical fields of the moving and static plate conditions where the boundary conditions are appropriately formulated. The flow chart of the MATLAB code can be seen in the Appendix below.

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 2. (a) Curvature and Max Stress-Velocity graph.

Figure 2. (b) Max Stress-Length graph.

Figure 2a shows the final mean curvature and mean maximum stress (occurs at wetting region) of σ_{zz} component for the various casting speed.

- It can be observed that the maximum curvature and minimum stress occurs at 20 mm/s speed, due to the water ejection at the lower region and following by the moving wetting front.
- At the higher speed, the situation is similar to the static condition where the wetting front steadily moves at 10-11 mm/s. Results should be the same for moving plate and static plate around that speed.
- In the experimental observation, the cracks originate at the edge of the plate as shown in Figure 2b. Therefore, at the end of the complete quenching process the stresses at bottom region of the plate are plotted. It is shown that the ejection situation is more favor for the occurrence of cracks.

5. Summary

Quenching of moving hot plate is modeled. It is found that the maximum curvature and vulnerability of crack originates at the edge of the plate is high for the water ejection situation.

6. References

[1] Nallathambi A.K., Kaymak Y, Specht, E., Bertram, A, 2010, Sensitivity of material properties on distortion and residual stresses during metal quenching processes, Journal of Materials Processing Technology, 210(2), 204-211.
 [2] Etienne Caron, Mary A. Wells, 2011, Film Boiling and Water Film Ejection in the Secondary Cooling Zone of the Direct-Chill Casting Process, Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B, 43(1), 155-162.

Numerical Analysis on Controlling the Post Buckling Behavior of Cylindrical Shells Using Mode Splitting

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Abstract

In this study, controlling the post buckling behavior of cylindrical shells using piezoelectric actuator is investigated. A novel method based on mode splitting is attempted in this study. Piezoelectric actuators are placed at discrete asymmetric location to destroy the symmetry of the system. The analysis results show that mode splitting can be used as an effective technique for controlling the post buckling behavior of cylindrical shells.

1. Introduction

Buckling control of structures is one of the promising applications of piezoelectric materials. Berlin [1] has shown that buckling load carrying capacity can be increased up to 5.6 times the load carrying capacity for a column structures. These studies were further extended to more complicated structures like plates and shells by other researchers. One of the key challenges in the buckling control of cylindrical shell is the placement of actuators. Jose and Tangirala [2] has shown that buckling wavelength can be used as a criterion for placing the actuators for enhancing the buckling load carrying capacity of cylindrical shells. Closely spaced eigenvalues (The eigenvalues of the structure will be very close to each other) of cylindrical shells are a major challenge in the buckling control of shell like structures. It is well established that the closely spaced nature of the eigenvalues is a result of the symmetry in the system.

In the present study piezoelectric actuators are placed at non symmetric locations to destroy the symmetry of the system. The resulting load axial shortening plots are compared with that of symmetric placement of actuators to study the effect of actuator placement. The effect of asymmetry on the eigenvalues of the cylindrical shell is compared for the different configurations tested. It is to be noted that the present study is limited to studying the effect of actuator configurations on the eigenvalues of the structure. No attempt has been made to optimize the actuator locations in this study.

2. Problem Formulation

The post buckling behavior of a cylindrical shell is highly influenced by mode jumping phenomenon which is the result of closely spaced eigenvalues. From a bucking control point of view this is undesirable as the placement of actuators and sensors are complicated if the system possesses closely packed eigenvalues. Primary reason for closely spaced eigenvalues is the symmetry in the system under consideration. The effect of mode jumping can be nullified if the system is modified appropriately such that the eigenvalues are well separated. The effect of placing piezoelectric actuators at appropriate locations so as to tailor the eigenvalues of the system is investigated through numerical experiments in this study.

3. Finite Element Model

Numerical analyses are carried out using the commercial software Abaqus. Shell elements having 4 nodes with reduced integration and hour glass control were used for the modelling of shell structure. The cylinder is assumed to be simply supported and is subjected to axial compressive loading. Piezoelectric actuators are modelled using piezoelectric element. These elements exhibit a coupling between their electrical and mechanical behavior. The interaction between the cylindrical shell and the piezoelectric actuator are modelled using 'Tie constraint' in Abaqus.

4. Numerical Study

The cylindrical shell chosen for carrying out the analysis were of dimension 54 x 80 x 0.1 mm (Diameter, Height and thickness respectively). The piezoelectric actuators had dimension 14 x 28 x 0.4 (Length, Width and thickness respectively). The different configurations tested and some sample analysis results are shown in Figure 1 below. In the configuration 1, the actuators are placed at symmetric locations whereas in the configuration 2, asymmetry

is introduced in the placement of the second actuator. The shape of the buckling waves for a nonlinear analysis carried out is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Development view of cylindrical shell configurations tested (a) Configuration1: Symmetric configuration; (b) Configuration 2: Asymmetric configuration.

Figure 2. Comparison of post buckling behavior of configurations tested.

5. Summary

In the present study the effect of asymmetric placement of piezoelectric actuators on the closely spaced nature of eigenvalues of the cylindrical shell is investigated. The results obtained indicate that the eigenvalues of the system can be modified by placing the actuators at appropriate locations.

6. References

- [1] Andrew A. Berlin, Towards Intelligent Structures: “Active Control of Buckling”, Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, May 1994.
- [2] Sandeep, Jose, Arun K., Tangirala. A novel approach toward actuator placement for cylindrical shells undergoing axisymmetric buckling. Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures 27.11 (2016): 1425-1439.

A Zigzag Theory Based Quadrilateral Element for the Analysis of Laminated Shells Containing Delaminations

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Abstract

In this work, we present a four-node facet shell element based on the third order zigzag theory for the analysis of laminated shells containing delaminations. A region-wise approach is employed at the delamination front and a novel hybrid technique is used to enforce the continuity of in-plane displacements. The free mode model is adopted. Results for natural frequencies of composite spherical shells with a central cutout containing delaminations are presented and compared with available FE results.

1. Introduction

Delamination which is debonding or separation between adjacent plies is one of the most significant and severe modes of damage in laminated structures [1]. It may occur during manufacturing due to, e.g. incomplete wetting, air entrapment, large out-of-plane interlaminar stresses near free edges etc. or during service due to low velocity impact etc. Delaminations, generally embedded within the laminate, may not be visible at all, but their presence may significantly reduce its strength and alter its dynamic response, even leading to a catastrophic failure. The region approach is adopted here for modeling the delaminations, wherein the delaminated and the integral segments are divided into individual laminates. The delaminated layers are assumed to have no mutual interaction/contact between them during the deformation and they are called as the *free mode* models. A four-node facet shell element based on the third order zigzag theory is employed for the analysis. The continuity of the inplane displacements and rotations at the delamination front is implemented using a transformation approach and the relation between the degrees of freedom (DOFs) of the intact and delaminated segments is obtained using the proposed hybrid method.

2. Third Order Zigzag Theory Approximations

Consider a multilayered composite laminate having delaminations both across the laminate thickness and along the spans. The intact laminate and delaminated sublaminates are assumed to have a global third order variation in z combined with a layerwise linear variation of the in-plane displacements, u_x and u_y , whereas, the transverse displacement, w is independent of z . For a sublaminates shown as in Figure 1a, the displacement field approximations according to the third order zigzag theory are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_x(x, y, z) \\ u_y(x, y, z) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{0x}(x, y) \\ u_{0y}(x, y) \end{bmatrix} - z \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{R}^k(z) \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0x}(x, y) \\ \psi_{0y}(x, y) \end{bmatrix}, \quad w(x, y, z) = w_0(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where w_0 is the transverse displacement of the middle plane. u_{0x} and u_{0y} are the translation components and ψ_{0x} and ψ_{0y} denote the shear rotation components of the middle plane, respectively. $\mathbf{R}^k(z)$ is a matrix of layerwise functions of z reported in Kapuria and Kulkarni [2] which is obtained by satisfying conditions of zero transverse shear stresses at the free surfaces and equal transverse shear stresses at layer interfaces. The nodal DOF vector is given by:

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{0x} & u_{0y} & w_0 & -w_{0,x} & -w_{0,y} & \psi_{0x} & \psi_{0y} & \theta_{0z} & \psi_{0z} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where θ_{0z} and ψ_{0z} correspond to the drilling degrees of freedom, included for local to global transformation.

3. Results and Discussion

The results for a simply supported composite spherical shell with cutout and delamination as shown in Figure 1 is presented and compared with TOT FE [3] results in Table 1. The spherical shell is thin ($a/h=100$) and shallow ($R/a=5$) with a square cutout of size $c = 0.1a$ at the center and the delamination around the cutout is located at the middle interface. The lay-up of its laminate is $(0/90)_s$. The shell is modeled with a mesh size of 20×20 . The results for the first four nondimensional natural frequencies $\bar{\omega} = \omega_n a^2 \sqrt{\rho / Y_2} / h$ of the shell without delamination and with delamination sizes of 30%, 50% and 70% are presented here. The % delamination is computed as $100x(c + 2d)/a$. The present results agree well with the available FE results for all the modes. For the smaller delamination size of 30%, the frequencies do not change significantly from those of the undelaminated shell but, for the delamination sizes of 50% of 70% there is a significant reduction in the natural frequencies, particularly for the higher modes.

Figure 1. Sublaminates and a composite spherical shell with cutout and delamination.

Table 1. Nondimensional natural frequencies of composite spherical shells with cutout and delamination.

Mode	Delamination size in %							
	Intact		30%		50%		70%	
	ZIGT FE	TOT FE	ZIGT FE	TOT FE	ZIGT FE	TOT FE	ZIGT FE	TOT FE
1	29.042	28.640	28.936	28.539	28.262	27.924	27.639	27.367
2	38.211	37.879	37.755	37.513	38.178	38.069	34.344	34.227
3	50.196	48.928	45.524	45.424	38.167	38.022	34.920	34.593
4	52.824	52.136	52.064	52.025	45.628	45.293	37.605	34.593

4. References

- [1] Garg, A. C., Delamination damage mode in composite structures, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 29, 557-584, 1988.
- [2] Kapuria, S., Kulkarni, S. D. An improved discrete Kirchhoff quadrilateral element based on third-order zigzag theory for static analysis of composite and sandwich plates, *International journal for numerical methods in engineering* 69, 1948-1981, 2007
- [3] S.-Y. Lee, D.-S. Chung, Finite element delamination model for vibrating composite spherical shell panels with central cutouts, *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design* 46, 247-256, 2010.

Stability of Plates with Cut-outs Subjected to Partial Edge Loading

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Abstract

Many engineering structures comprise of plates and shell as their basic element; hence analysis of plates and shells is of paramount important. Moreover, under working condition these plates are subjected to many types of external loads. In plane compression is one of the types of loading which buckles the plate which leads to instability. Also, plate with cutout is an important element of various structures. These kinds of structures behave differently than the ones without cutouts hence studying the structures with cavities is also of importance. The present work focuses on the study of rectangular plate with and without circular hole subjected to in-plane partial edge loading. The study includes analysis of buckling load factor, deformations and various stresses for various sizes of holes and boundary conditions. The results have been obtained by NASTRN (2017.0.1) - an FEA tool, which can be successfully employed to study these kinds of structures.

1. Introduction

In the field of Aerospace, Naval, civil, and Mechanical Engineering, structural systems consist of stiffened panels and thin walled structures, which are subjected to uniform and non-uniform in-plane edge loading. The aircraft structural members such as skins, ribs, spars and stiffened panels, which are subjected to mechanical and aerodynamic loading cause the buckling instability due to axial compressive force. Very few published literature deals with the buckling behavior of isotropic and composite plates subjected to in-plane partial edge loading. The effect of loading on thin plates with simply supported and clamped edge conditions have been studied by Singh et al. [1], Sundaresan et al. [2], and Shakerley and Brown [3]. These authors have studied the elastic buckling of plates with eccentrically positioned rectangular perforations and concluded that orientation of the perforation to loading axis has major effect on buckling load. Shanmugam et. al. [4] proposed the formula for predicting cutout dimension with respect to slenderness ratio for perforated rectangular plates with different boundary conditions and loading condition i.e. axial and biaxial by using finite element method. El-Sawy and Nazmy [5] studied the effect of aspect ratio on the elastic buckling off uniaxial loaded plates with eccentric hole at different location. The present work deals with the study of rectangular plates with and without circular holes subjected to in-plane partial edge loading. The results have been validated against corresponding result by Singh et. al. [1] and Sundaresan et al. [2].

Figure 1. (a) Loading type 1.

Figure 1. (b) Loading type 2.

2. General Specifications

Plate considered for the present analysis has dimensions as 100 mm by 100 mm by 1 mm. For cut out section, the aspect ratio is defined as 'd/a' where, 'd' is diameter of the cut-out section and 'a' is the minimum side length of the plate. In the present analysis aspect ratio (d/a) of 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 have been considered. It is assumed that the mid plane of the plate is coinciding with XY plane. The plate is considered to be comprised of steel with modulus of elasticity (E) 210GPa and Poisson ratio (μ) 0.30. Shell type of plate with 2D is considered with thickness 1mm. Two types of partial edge loads have been considered (Figures 1a and 1b) and their intensity have been varied such that total load remains constant. If the intensity of the load applied per unit length on the whole length of the plate is assumed to be N_x , then for 20% of loaded edge length, the intensity of load will be $5N_x$ in magnitude. Meshing used for model is paver mesh with QUAD4 elements of size 1 unit. Both simply supported

and clamped plates have been considered for the analysis. Buckling analysis of sequence 105 using solver NASTRAN version 2017.01 is carried out to determine the Eigen values for load factor of fundamental mode.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of rectangular plates without circular holes subjected to in-plane partial edge loading are obtained and validated with available results by Sundaresan et. al. [2] and Singh et. al. [1] presented in Table 1. From above case it is observed that critical buckling load for square plate is mainly influenced by partial edge loading. Simply supported and clamped plate are found stronger in their uniaxial partial edge loading of Type 1 as compared to plate subjected to uniaxial uniform loading Type 2.

Table 1. Result and validation of analysis of plate with pervious literature for loading type 1.

Sl. No.	Initial Applied Load (N/mm)	Length Of Loaded Edge (%)	Loading Type-1					
			Buckling Load Factor For Plate					
			All Edges Simply Supported (SSSS)			All Edges Clamped (CCCC)		
			Present	Singh et al. [1]	Sundaresan et al. [2]	Present	Singh et al. [1]	Sundaresan et al. [2]
1	1000	100	3.59	3.57	3.61	9.08	9.08	9.106
2	1250	80	4.058	4.04	3.97	9.96	9.96	10.01
3	1666	60	4.72	4.71	4.69	11.01	11.06	10.92
4	2500	40	5.4	5.35	5.41	11.96	11.96	11.83
5	5000	20	5.77	5.74	5.77	12.48	12.48	12.35

4. Conclusion

The present work focuses on the investigations of the elastic buckling behavior of simply supported and clamped thin rectangular isotropic plates subjected to uniaxial partial edge loading. The analysis is carried out for the plates with and without cut-outs. From the analysis, it can be concluded that for simply supported and clamped plates with Type 1 edge loading condition, the plate buckling load factor decreases for aspect ratio 0.1 to 0.3 and then increases for the aspect ratio 0.4 and 0.5. For loading Type 2, the behavior of plate changes and the buckling load factor decreases continuously as aspect ratio increases. The stress profiles of these plates also changes drastically for various aspect ratios and boundary conditions.

5. References

- [1] Singh, S., Kulkarni, K., Pandey, R. and Singh, H., 2012. Buckling analysis of thin rectangular plates with cutouts subjected to partial edge compression using FEM. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 10(1), pp.128-142.
- [2] Sundaresan, P., Singh, G. and Rao, V., 1998. Buckling of moderately thick rectangular composite plates subjected to partial edge compression. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, 40(11), pp.1105-1117.
- [3] Shakerley, T.M. and Brown, C.J., 1996. Elastic buckling of plates with eccentrically positioned rectangular perforations. *International journal of mechanical sciences*, 38(8-9), pp.825-838.
- [4] Shanmugam, N.E., Thevendran, V. and Tan, Y.H., 1999. Design formula for axially compressed perforated plates. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 34(1), pp.1-20.
- [5] El-Sawy, K.M. and Nazmy, A.S., 2001. Effect of aspect ratio on the elastic buckling of uniaxially loaded plates with eccentric holes. *thin-walled structures*, 39(12), pp.983-998.

Fatigue Creep Interaction Through Continuum Damage Mechanics

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Abstract

Damage due to fatigue, creep and ratcheting is modelled using continuum damage mechanics. Fatigue life is drastically affected by the interaction of ratcheting and creep phenomena. For modelling of ratcheting at room temperature, Chaboche model [4] is adopted. Elastic predictor and plastic corrector method is adopted for local integration of constitutive equations. The developed formulation is employed to study the elasto-plastic response of a cylindrical rod under axisymmetric conditions in load control mode. For simulation, a FORTRAN code is developed. The present results are found to be in fairly good agreement with those available in literature.

1. Introduction

Components of fossil fuel power plants, nuclear power reactor etc. are subjected to high cycle thermal load (fatigue-creep interaction) and progressive deformation with loading cycles (ratcheting). Date et al. [1] found through experimental observation that when these three phenomena simultaneously take place, the rate of deterioration of the material is very high. Kang et al. [2] considered the uniaxial ratcheting and fatigue failure under the frame work of visco-plasticity coupled with damage. Zheng et al. [3] modeled ratcheting-creep interaction by Ohno-Wang model but they did not consider damage effect. Ratcheting-fatigue-creep interaction has not been investigated by the unified damage coupled visco-plastic model in the literature. The main aim of the present paper is to formulate constitutive model considering damage due to fatigue creep and ratcheting based on the framework of continuum thermodynamics. Based on the formulation, a computationally efficient finite element code in FORTRAN is developed.

2. Methodology

Chaboche unified visco-plastic constitutive model is adopted. For correct prediction of ratcheting behavior, dynamic recovery term in the Armstrong-Fredrick model [5] is modified with the threshold. Static recovery term is added to Armstrong-Fredrick [5] model to capture creep behavior. Lemaitre [6] approach is adopted to couple visco-plastic model to damage. For local integration of constitutive relations, elastic predictor and plastic corrector method (return mapping algorithm) is adopted. For plastic corrector, implicit backward Euler difference method is used.

3. Results and Discussion

The developed formulation and code are employed for the study of elastoplastic response of a cylindrical rod under unsymmetrical cyclic loading. This axisymmetric bar is modeled using 4 (radial) × 2 (axial) elements mesh of rectangular elements. 3×3 Gauss- Quadrature integration order is used for integration over an element. The present simulation results are compared with those of Chaboche [4]. Range of cyclic loading as 400 MPa is kept constant throughout the loading history. But mean stress is increased for first four levels then decreased for last level. Stress versus strain curves are plotted at mid position on the longitudinal axis. Material coefficients are adopted from Chaboche [4].

Results of this simulation are shown in Figures 1a and 1b. It can be observed that ratcheting (accumulation of plastic strain) occurs as expected due to non-zero mean stress during cyclic loading. The ratcheting is correctly predicted for the first three mean stress levels but underestimated for the fourth mean stress level as compared to Chaboche prediction (Figure 1b). Negative ratcheting is also predicted when the mean stress is decreased in the last level but in this case ratcheting prediction is little overestimated as compared to Chaboche prediction (Figure 1b). From Figure 1b we observe that at the low mean stress levels, saturation in the strain happens very frequently but at the high mean stress levels it happens after certain amount of accumulated plastic strain.

Figure 1. (a) Stress versus strain curve for increasing mean stress level depicting ratcheting; (b) Maximum plastic strain versus number of cycles for increasing mean stress level depicting ratcheting.

4. Summary

The Chaboche model for ratcheting description under infinitesimal deformation is implemented successfully. Overall prediction is in fairly good agreement with Chaboche [4].

5. References

- [1] Date, S., Ishikawa, H., Otani, T. and Takahashi, Y., (2008). Effect of ratcheting deformation on fatigue and creep-fatigue life of 316FR stainless steel, *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 238(2), 336–346.
- [2] Kang, G., Liu, Y., Ding, J. and Gao, Q., (2009). Uniaxial ratcheting and fatigue failure of tempered 42CrMo steel: Damage evolution and damage-coupled visco-plastic constitutive model, *International Journal of Plasticity*, 25(5), 838–860.
- [3] Zheng, X. T., Xuan, F. Z. and Zhao, P., (2011). Ratcheting-creep interaction of advanced 9-12% chromium ferrite steel with anelastic effect, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 33(9), 1286–1291.
- [4] Chaboche, J. L., (1991). On some modifications of kinematic hardening to improve the description of ratchetting effects, *International Journal of Plasticity*, 7, 661-678.
- [5] Armstrong, P.J. and Frederick, C.O., (1966). A mathematical representation of the multiaxial Bauschinger effect. Report RD/B/N731, CEGB, Central Electricity Generating Board, Berkely, UK.
- [6] Lemaitre, J., (1984). How to use damage mechanics, *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 80 (1984) 233-245.

Residual Stress Analysis of Under Water Welded Vessels

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Abstract

Underwater vessels find applications in offshore structures, underwater vehicles, submarines etc. At the time of assembly of these large structures, welding process is employed. The welded joints are subjected to different internal/external operating loading conditions including changing hydrostatic pressure superimposed with welding residual stresses. In this work finite element analysis is carried out to evaluate the transient temperature and residual stress fields during welding considering longitudinal and circumferential welds.

1. Introduction

Under water pressure vessels are manufactured by welding curved plates longitudinally and circumferentially. Residual stress analysis of circumferential or longitudinal weld joints needs to be carried out for estimation of operational life [1]. Due to the intense concentration of heat in the welding, the regions near the weld line undergo thermal cycles. The thermal cycles cause non-uniform heating and cooling in the material, thus generating inhomogeneous plastic deformation and residual stresses in the weldment [2].

2. Methodology

Residual stresses are highly sensitive to a transient temperature distribution therefore, for determination of realistic temperature profile, Goldak's double ellipsoidal heat source model [3] is used for thermo-mechanical analysis. In the double ellipsoidal heat source model depending on whether an element lies in front or rear quadrant relative to heat source, the heat flux value is calculated as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Double ellipsoidal heat source model [3].

3. Finite Element Simulations

Finite element simulations of welding in ANSYS are carried out in order to estimate the residual stress generated after the welding process using Goldak Double ellipsoidal heat source and thermo-elasto-plastic analysis for determining residual stress field. Thin cylinder is considered so that biaxial state of stress exists [4]. Element birth and death technique is employed to simulate material deposition while welding. Finite element simulation of both longitudinal and circumferential joint is considered separately. The maximum residual stress generated is found to be of the order of yield stress of the material.

4. Results

For Von Mises, hoop and axial residual stress distribution for longitudinal joint are plotted for both inner and outer surfaces in Figure 2. For longitudinal weld, the distribution characteristic of the axial stress for outer surface is more or less similar to that of the inner surface whereas the distribution of hoop residual stress for outer and inner

surfaces are of opposite nature due to radial contraction. In case of circumferential weld, the distribution of axial residual stress for outer and inner surfaces is of opposite to nature.

Figure 2. Variation of residual stress along transverse direction of the longitudinal weld at the mid-point of (a) inner surface and (b) outer surface.

For Von Mises, hoop and axial residual stress distribution for circumferential joint are plotted for both inner and outer surfaces in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Variation of residual stress along transverse direction of the circumferential weld at the mid-point of (a) inner surface and (b) outer surface.

5. References

- [1] Deng D, Murakawa H, Numerical simulation of temperature field and residual stress in multi-pass welds in stainless steel pipe and comparison with experimental measurements, *Computational Materials Science*, 2006, 37, 269-277.
- [2] Karlsson R, Josefson B, Three-dimensional finite element analysis of temperatures and stresses in a single-pass butt-welded pipe, *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, 1990, 112, 76-84.
- [3] Goldak J, Chakravarti A, Bibby M, A new finite element model for welding heat sources, *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions*, 1984, 15, 299-305.
- [4] Dong P, Brust F, Welding residual stresses and effects on fracture in pressure vessel and piping components, *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, 2000, 122, 329-338.

Dynamic Response of Composite Laminates

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Abstract

The analytical deduction and experimental validation of Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymers (GFRPs) is performed to check for the effect of laminate ply orientation on dynamic response. The Finite element method investigates natural frequencies and mode shapes with the block Lanczos method since there is a static correction built into the algorithm. Computed modes are experimentally validated through Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC) test. A code is developed on ZAERO and G method of extraction is used to analytically derive complex Eigen values. The generated values predicting dynamic response is validated experimentally using Low speed wind tunnel and eventuates a close correlation.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Flutter, MAC, Wind Tunnel, ZAERO, G-Method, GFRP.

1. Introduction

There is a lack of literature involving tantamount scrutiny into the outcome of using inexpensive and insulating Glass Fibers in an aerodynamic environment. This paper seeks to thereby conform to the need for the utilisation of such a rectangular Uni-Directional GFRP of dimensions 315mm x 75mm x 1.2mm in testing it for its response toward dynamic instability over a range of velocities, with fibre orientations known to affect elastic properties as seen in Bledzki et al. [1]. The interaction between inertial, elastic and aerodynamic forces which are the machineries involved in aeroelasticity as noted from Fung [2], is delved into with an intention to determine the structure's behaviour while approaching dynamic instability.

2. Methodology

The numerical determination of system characteristics subjugates the necessary Eigen values which are extracted through the block Lanczos method. These modes are experimentally verified on a vacuum bag moulded Unidirectional Laminate (UDL) through the MAC test. The Linear Averaged Frequency Response Spectrum obtained is implemented in MEScope, which supports Data Acquisition for rigorous extraction and processing. The comprehensive behaviour of the UDL is seen to be explained by the first five major natural frequencies which thereby have been the focus of attention in all successive calculations and experimental analysis for this paper.

Figure 1. Velocity vs. damping factor for 5 modes generated using ZAERO.

ZAERO, an aeroelastic analysis software is used to build a simulation model for the laminate in a relevant environment and envisions the application of the G method. The G technique involves the use of a reduced frequency allotment process to generate a damping perturbation method for flutter solution. The behaviour of mode 1 corresponds to a post-critical static response called divergence which is seen at the onset of instability. This activity is benign and does not lead to life cycle fatigue. The torsional mode which attributes to the flutter

phenomenon is revealed to pose steep increase in value alongside the damping obtained through the half power bandwidth method as shown in Figure 1. The software is used to analytically determine the flutter velocity of an aluminium cantilevered plate as 21 m/s as a reference value to compare with the effects of GFRP.

The analytically derived values are validated experimentally using a low speed suction type wind tunnel. The dynamic stability analysis is prolonged to obtain a vibration response of the UDL with the time domain acceleration data processed into the frequency domain. The variations in frequency and damping have been checked against a spectrum of velocity values to develop characteristic curves as practiced by Lin et al. [3] and clearly indicates that an instability is prompted at 31.25 m/s.

3. Results

The comparison between analytically derived and experimentally obtained dynamic instability velocities show a close correlation as shown in Figure 2. It is therefore inferred that the conducted MAC and modal analysis which are the forerunners for the dynamic instability analysis are the accurate proponents for the comprehensive calculation involved.

Figure 2. Comparison of V-G plot of Numerical and Experimental Results at Mode-2.

4. Conclusion

A close agreement between analytically deduced and experimentally observed results indicates the presupposition of fibre orientation on the onset of flutter. The detailed framework characterising the appropriate conditions and calculations would influence future analysis more efficient and accurate thereby closely monitoring the dynamic instability in Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymers.

5. References

- [1] A.K. Bledzki, A. Kessler, R. Rikards and A. Chate, Determination of elastic constants of glass/epoxy unidirectional laminates by the vibration testing of plates, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 59, pp.2015-2024, 1999.
- [2] YC Fung, *An Introduction to the Theory of Aeroelasticity*, Dover Publications, New York City, 1993.
- [3] Kuo-Juin Lin, Pong-Jeu Lu and Jiann-Quo Tarn, Flutter Analysis of Cantilever Composite Plates in Subsonic Flow, *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 27, No. 8, pp. 1102-1109, 1989.

Estimation of Leak in Elastomeric Seals

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Abstract

Flexible elastomeric seals are important devices used in storage and transport of fuels like Hydrogen, oil & gas. Apart from this, they are also employed in critical applications of industries such as defense, nuclear, space and aerospace industry. In spite of their widespread usage, leakage of seals has remained to be a poorly understood phenomenon forcing engineers to rely on empirical relations and field/test data to design seals. This paper discusses a new simulation procedure developed based on Darcy's law for flow through porous media to estimate leak rate and hence failure of elastomeric seals.

1. Introduction

Flexible elastomeric seals are widely used to seal liquids and gases. They are of critical importance in industries such as defense, nuclear, space, oil & gas industry and are commercially available for use in various household and industrial equipment such as air tight containers, pressure cookers, cryogenic liquid tanks, high pressure pipe joints and industrial gas storage tanks. In spite of their widespread usage, leakage of seals has remained to be a poorly understood phenomenon forcing engineers to rely on empirical relations and field/test data to design seals. A mathematical model that relates seal design to its failure (leak at a rate beyond an acceptable limit) under a given set of environmental and loading conditions can be very useful in improving the quality and reducing the expenditure in designing seals, as well as their integrity for safety in critical applications.

2. Background

Although elastomeric seals leak due to damage caused by variety of environmental and loading conditions, there are only two mechanisms by which a seal can leak. The sealing fluid can leak through the elastomer-metal interface or it can leak by permeating through the elastomer. Understanding and modeling these mechanisms can greatly help in seal design and failure (leaking beyond an acceptable rate) estimation. Few researchers have attempted to understand leak by analyzing at a sub-micron length scale where the surface roughness characterizes the interface through which leak occurs. For example, Persson and Yang [1] and Lorenz and Persson [2] suggested that leak occurs due to flow of liquid at the sealing interface through small leak paths that exist from the high-pressure side to the low-pressure side due to uneven rough elastomeric and metal surfaces at the interface. This theory uses Persson's contact and percolation theory to estimate the size and the number of leak. The size of these channels is thus used in predicting the leak rate of the seals at different fluid pressures. The model finally predicts the rate of leak of sealing fluid as a function of roughness spectrum of the surface, fluid viscosity and pressure.

Although models like these have a robust analytical formulation they suffer from the limitations that arise from several inherent assumptions made while modeling the surface, modeling the material and solving the flow through the leak channels. Several of these assumptions in this case have made Persson's model applicable only for liquid media and seals made of linearly elastic materials at low pressures applications (~10kPa). However, most engineering applications use seals made of hyper-elastic, elastomeric materials at much pressures (100 kPa – 10000 MPa). This makes them unsuitable for daily use in practical engineering problems that deal with moderate pressures.

To circumvent the problems that arise due to detailed modeling of the interface, we have developed a suitable experimental setup that can provide sufficient leak data to characterize leak through the given interface. This is augmented with flow modeling using Darcy's law for porous media to describe leakage of gas. While the experimental setup is described in our previous works, in this paper, we focus on flow model that describes leak through elastomer- metal interface.

3. Flow Model

We propose that the interface of elastomer and metal can be considered as a porous media of small thickness through which gas flows as leakage. Depending on the contact pressure at the interface and the gas pressure,

both the size of pores and the permeability of the porous media change thus affecting the rate of leakage of gas. To describe this, we now write the Darcy's law for flow through porous media

$$q(x) = -\frac{k(x)A(x)}{\mu} \frac{dp}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where q is rate of flow of fluid, k is permeability, μ is dynamic coefficient of viscosity, dp is change in gas pressure p over the length dx . We now propose that both permeability and area of cross section can be related to contact pressure and gas pressure by

$$A(x)k(x) = 2\pi x k_1 e^{k_2 p - k_3 \sigma} \quad (2)$$

where σ is contact stress at the interface, p is gas pressure and k_1, k_2 & k_3 are parameters that only depend on the geometry of the pores and mechanical properties of the elastomer/metal. For a given pair of elastomer, metal with a given surface roughness, they however remain constant. Using these and integrating appropriately, we finally arrive at the equation

$$\frac{k_1}{k_2^2 e^{k_3 \sigma}} \left[\frac{2\pi M}{\mu RT \rho_o \ln\left(\frac{x_o}{x_i}\right)} \right] [(k_2 p_i - 1)e^{k_2 p_i} - (k_2 p_o - 1)e^{k_2 p_o}] - q_o = 0 \quad (3)$$

The unknown constants k_1, k_2 and k_3 are fit by using data available for several values of p_i, σ and q_o . The resultant equation is now plotted against the rest of the data to verify its applicability. In Figure 1, scattered circular points are experimental data and solid lines are from model. Note that in Figure 1, as expected, the first three curves fit well as the equation is trained with that data. The other curves also seem to fit fairly well if not really well. This shows that the model works quite well.

Figure 1. Leak rate v/s Absolute gas pressure at different contact pressures.

Each solid line is at a particular contact pressure that is labelled at the end of the curve. Solid lines are predicted by the model. Scattered circles are data from experiment.

4. Summary

This extended abstract discusses the need to have a predictive model to estimate leak and failure in elastomeric seals. It briefly discussed the drawbacks of the existing methods like Perrson's method and Liu's method in describing leak. A new method that uses both experimentation and simulation effectively is proposed. The conference paper shall discuss this simulation technique in detail.

5. References

- [1] Persson, B.N.J. and Yang, C., 2008. Theory of the leak-rate of seals. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 20(31), p.315011.
- [2] Lorenz, B. and Persson, B.N.J., 2009. Leak rate of seals: Comparison of theory with experiment. *EPL (Europhysics Letters)*, 86(4), p.44006.

Influence of Boundary Conditions on Linear & Nonlinear Periodic Response of Laminated Composite Plates

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Abstract

The excellent directional properties and low specific weight of composites have made their use extensive in structural applications particularly in aerospace, automobile and biomedical fields. These structural components during service are exposed to dynamic loading. The forced vibration response obtained without including geometric non-linearity lead to erroneous results particularly for thin structural components. The present work is intended to explore the influence of boundary conditions on the nonlinear steady state forced vibration response of laminated composite plates. The analysis has been carried out in time domain using modified shooting method along with arc-length/pseudo arc-length continuation schemes.

1. Introduction

The use of laminated composites in industrial application has been increasing day by day due to their excellent directional property and low strength to weight ratio. These structural components are often in the form of thin plates which are subjected to dynamic load during service. The forced vibration response analysis becomes important for their safe and efficient design. The linear forced vibration analysis gives a conservative estimate and the inclusion of geometric nonlinearity in the strain displacement relation becomes important for the accurate prediction of cyclic stresses and strains which is necessary for their optimal design.

The present analysis is carried out using FEM based on displacement field of first order shear deformation theory. The geometric nonlinearity is included in the analysis using von Karman's assumption for small strains and moderately large rotation. The governing equations have been obtained in time domain. The nonlinear steady state forced vibration analysis is complex and computationally challenging. The direct time integration method fails to predict the complete response curve and significantly large time marching is required even to predict the response in the stable regime. The frequency domain methods such as harmonic balance and incremental harmonic balance methods suffer from the drawback that they require a priori assumption on the participating mode which may lead to erroneous results. The method employed for the present analysis is based on modified shooting method [1] where the banded nature of the matrices is preserved unlike shooting method resulting in computationally efficient scheme. Newmark's time marching approach coupled with modified shooting technique along with arc-length/pseudo arc-length continuation for prediction of forced periodic response is used in the present analysis.

The finite element method has been extensively used in the nonlinear analysis of beams and plates. One of the first attempt to apply FEM to the large amplitude vibration was integrated by Mei [2]. Chia and Prabhakara [3] presented an analytical multi-mode approach of free flexural vibrations of orthotropic plates. Mei and Decha-Umphai [4] presented a finite element formulation for the large amplitude vibration of thin plates subjected to harmonic loading. The p-version finite element method has been employed to study the influence of higher harmonics on the non-linear vibration of unimodular isotropic plates by Ribeiro [5]. A methodology based on shooting technique and Newmark's time integration scheme is proposed for predicting the periodic responses of non-linear systems directly from solution of second order equations of motion without transforming to double first order equations by Ibrahim et al. [6]. Khan and Patel have investigated the nonlinear forced vibration response of bimodular plates [1] and cylindrical panels [7] and it has been observed in their analysis that for bimodular structures the positive and negative half cycle response amplitudes are different.

It is evident from the literature that the influence of boundary conditions on the nonlinear forced vibration response of laminated plates has not been adequately addressed and requires attention. The method employed in this paper is computationally efficient and does not require *a priori* assumption on the participating modes. This present work explores the effects of boundary conditions on the linear and non-linear steady state forced vibration response of laminated composite plates. Significantly large difference in the peak displacement amplitudes have been obtained

between linear and non-linear analysis. The non-linear dynamic behaviour has been explored using phase plane plots, temporal response history and modal participations.

2. Typical Results

A laminated composite plate of length ' l ' and width ' b ' is considered with the co-ordinates x, y along the in-plane directions and thickness ' h ' along z the direction. The influence of boundary conditions on linear as well as nonlinear steady state forced vibration response of laminated plate is presented. The plate is subjected to a uniformly distributed harmonic force with frequency in the vicinity of first natural frequency of the plate. The linear and nonlinear frequency response curves corresponding to the centre of the plate are shown in Figures 1a and 1b respectively. It is revealed from the plots that linear analysis predicts significantly large response amplitude compared to the corresponding nonlinear analysis. It can also be seen that flat plates reveal hardening nonlinearity with degree of hardening nonlinearity greater for CCCC (all edges clamped) plates followed by CSCS (Long edge clamped), SCSC and SSSS plate respectively for $l/b = 2$. The nonlinear response amplitude is smallest for CCCC plates and is greatest for SSSS plates. The difference between the linear and nonlinear amplitude is greatest for SSSS plates with linear response amplitude being approx. 7 times the nonlinear amplitude.

The material properties considered in the analysis are:

$$E_1/E_2 = 25, E_2 = E_3 = 1 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}/E_2 = G_{13}/E_2 = 0.5, G_{23}/E_2 = 0.2, \nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{13} = 0.25, \rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

Figure 1. Steady state frequency response curves of laminated cross-ply plate ($0/90^\circ$, $l/b = 2$, $b/h = 100$, $b = 0.5 \text{ m}$).

3. References

- [1] A. H. Khan, B. P. Patel, Nonlinear forced vibration response of bimodular laminated composite plates. *Composite Structures* 108 (2014) 524-537.
- [2] C. Mei, Finite element displacement method for large amplitude free flexural vibrations of beams and plates, *Composite & Structures*, 3(1), (1973), 163-174.
- [3] C. Y. Chia and M. K. Prabhakara, A General Mode Approach to Nonlinear Flexural Vibration of Laminated Rectangular Plates, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 45(3), (1978), 623-628.
- [4] C. Mei, K. Decha-Umphai, A finite element method for non-linear forced vibrations of rectangular plates, *American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Journal*, 23 (1985) 1104–1110.
- [5] P. Ribeiro, Nonlinear vibrations of simply-supported plates by the p-version finite element method, *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design* 41(2005) 911-924.
- [6] S.M. Ibrahim, B. P. Patel, Y. Nath, Modified shooting approach to the non-linear periodic forced response of isotropic/composite curved beams, *International Journal of Non-linear Mechanics*, 44 (2009), 1073-1084
- [7] A. H. Khan, B. P. Patel, Periodic response of bimodular laminated composite cylindrical panels with and without geometric nonlinearity. *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics* 67, (2014) 209- 217.

Modeling of Cyclic Electromechanical Response of PVDF

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Abstract

Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is a piezopolymer, PVDF exhibits viscoelasticity for mechanical cyclic loads. In this study, we attempt to model cyclic mechanical and electromechanical behavior using thermodynamically consistent models. Cyclic experiments and stress relaxation tests have been carried out for uniaxial PVDF.

1. Introduction

Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is well-known for its strong piezoelectricity. Strong piezoelectricity was first discovered in PVDF by Dr. Kawai, in 1969 [1]. It is capable of exhibiting piezoelectricity both as a sensor (detect electrical voltage when perturbing with mechanical forces) and as an actuator (observe mechanical deformation when perturbing with electrical voltage) [2]. Polyvinylidene fluoride is a piezopolymer and widely used as sensor in different applications such as locomotion sensors, tactile sensors, customized sensors, etc. It is essential to model the cyclic behavior of mechanical and electromechanical responses for these applications.

In this paper we attempt to model the experimental cyclic plots, we have used our past outputs of mechanical and electromechanical cyclic test results. We used the displacement control mode option during the experiments. Tests are done for first 1000 cycles. Theory and identical modeling results are discussed in the next section.

2. Theory

From literature [3, 4], using the constraints and maximizing the rate of dissipation with the constraints Ramkumar et al. arrive with the following evolution expression

$$\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{k_p(t)} = 2 \left\{ \frac{\mu_1^{1/(2\beta-1)}}{2\nu} \left[\text{tr} \left(\mathbf{B}_{k_p(t)} - \frac{9}{\text{tr}(\mathbf{B}_{k_p(t)}^{-1})} \right) \right]^{\frac{1-\beta}{2\beta-1}} \right\} \times \left[\frac{3}{\text{tr}(\mathbf{B}_{k_p(t)}^{-1})} \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{k_p(t)}^{-1} \right] \quad (1)$$

By assuming suitable deformation tensors and substituting in the above equations,

$$\frac{dB(t)}{dt} = 2 \left[\frac{\mu_1}{2\nu} \right]^{\frac{1}{(2\beta-1)}} \left[\frac{2+B(t)\sqrt{B(t)}}{\sqrt{B(t)}} - \frac{9B(t)}{2B(t)\sqrt{B(t)+1}} \right]^{\frac{(1-\beta)}{(2\beta-1)}} \times \left[\frac{3B(t)}{B(t)\sqrt{B(t)+1}} - B(t) \right] + 2B(t) \frac{\dot{\lambda}}{\lambda} \quad (2)$$

One needs to solve the above differential equation with the model stress or model piezo tensor equations.

Figure 1. Stress vs time predictions for first five cycles.

3. Implementation and Results

We have implemented the theory using the MATLAB 2016a software. The stress vs. time data and voltage vs time data are available for 1000 cycles. Fminsearch function and ODE45 solver was used to optimize the parameters by satisfying the above differential equation. Sum of the squares of the error was chosen as the objective function. First, five cycles for mechanical response are simulated and showed in this paper (as shown in Figure 1). Both mechanical and electromechanical reactions for 1000 cycles will be showed in the full article.

4. Summary

An attempt made to model the cyclic response of the PVDF. The more detailed explanations will be presented in the full paper.

5. References

- [1] Kawai, H., 1969. The piezoelectricity of poly (vinylidene fluoride). *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 8(7), p.975.
- [2] Dargahi, J., Sokhanvar, S., Najarian, S. and Arbatani, S., 2012. *Tactile Sensing and Displays: Haptic Feedback for Minimally Invasive Surgery and Robotics*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [3] Ramkumar, A., Kannan, K. and Gnanamoorthy, R., 2010. Experimental and theoretical investigation of a polymer subjected to cyclic loading conditions. *International Journal of Engineering Science*, 48(2), pp.101-110.
- [4] Rajagopal, K.R. and Srinivasa, A.R., 2007, February. On the response of non-dissipative solids. In *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* (Vol. 463, No. 2078, pp. 357-367). The Royal Society.

Computational Modeling of Ballistic Impact on Body Armor

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Abstract

There has been a growing need for high performance composite panels, suitable for modern body armor development. HB26 DSM Dyneema is 0/90° laminate of Ultra High Molecular Polyethylene (UHMWPE). It comprises SK76 fibres of volume fraction of 83% in a polyurethane (PU) matrix. The laminates are designed to prevent the bullet penetration by dissipating kinetic energy. The present computational study is carried out for 5mm thick Dyneema sheet at impact velocity of 400m/sec and its effect on, back face signature and residual velocity considering the effect of shock.

1. Introduction

A finite element modelling technique using Autodyn is chosen to perform numerical simulation on Dyneema grade HB26. The model is shown in the Figure 1 which shows the uniform meshing throughout in composite. The composite is modeled with 5mm thick plate with equivalent material property taken from literature [1]. The projectile used is 9mm FMJ that consist of lead core and brass jacket. The shear response of the brass jacket and the lead core were modelled using Johnson-Cook (1983) and the Steinberg - Guinan (1991) strength models respectively. The composite and bullet were modelled using hexahedral brick elements. Two separate model is run with or without shock keeping other parameter same in both simulations to see the effect of shock in ballistic impact. FE model employed was well validated with numerical and experimental results given in the literature [2].

2. General Information

The material properties used for doing the simulation are taken from the literature [1]. There the longitudinal and transverse stiffness values were obtained by performing the tensile tests and the in-plane compression tests were performed to find the through-the-thickness stiffness. Poisson's ratio values were obtained from the tensile tests using an extensometer. The Young's modulus values in the E_{11} and E_{22} directions were averaged and the Shear modulus was calculated using the empirical relation formula. The failure model used is maximum strain criteria.

3. Equation of State

The total pressure can be expressed in terms of the volumetric and deviatoric strain increments [3] resulting in the following orthotropic constitutive relation:

$$P = -\frac{1}{9}[C_{11} + C_{22} + C_{33} + 2(C_{12} + C_{23} + C_{13})]\varepsilon_{vol} - \frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + C_{12} + C_{13})\varepsilon_{11}^d - \frac{1}{3}(C_{12} + C_{22} + C_{23})\varepsilon_{22}^d - \frac{1}{3}(C_{13} + C_{23} + C_{33})\varepsilon_{33}^d \quad (1)$$

The Mie-Gruneisen equation of state defines the material pressure – volume and energy - volume relation along a reference curve usually taken to be shock Hugoniot, the Gruneisen gamma, Γ , allows extrapolation to material states off the reference curve and is a thermodynamic property of material:

$$P = P_r \varepsilon_{vol} + \Gamma(vol) \frac{\Gamma(vol)}{\varepsilon_{vol}} [e - e_r(\varepsilon_{vol})] \quad (2)$$

Where the reference material states denoted by a subscript r correspond to the Hugoniot shock states of the material. These reference states are obtained by solving a system of equation which will be covered in the Hugoniot Jump equations.

The additional contribution to the total stress that is attributed to the material shock effect can be calculated by subtracting Eq. (2) from Eq. (1) as

$$P_{NL} = P - P_L \quad (3)$$

The final total elastic stress by combining Eq. (3) and Eq. (1)

$$\sigma^T = [\sigma_{11} - P_{NL}, \sigma_{22} - P_{NL}, \sigma_{33} - P_{NL}, \sigma_{23}, \sigma_{31}, \sigma_{12}] \quad (4)$$

The polynomial equation of state that can also be used to define the shock effect is defined as:

$$P = [K\varepsilon_{vol} + A_2(\varepsilon_{vol})^2 + A_3(\varepsilon_{vol})^3 + (B_0 + B_1\varepsilon_{vol})\rho_0 e] \quad (5)$$

Where the constants A_2, A_3, B_0, B_1 are also obtained from inverse flyer plate tests while the compression ratio, μ ,

$$\mu = \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right) - 1 \quad (6)$$

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the back face deformation of 5mm HB26 plate with respect to time. Back-face signature is one of critical parameter in ballistic impact, which should be within allowable limit of 22 mm to avoid any serious injury.

Figure 1. Armor response with shock.

Figure 2a shows the effect of shock wave in ballistic impact and undermining this may lead to oversized armors. Without shock and with shock bullet residual velocity is 330 m/sec and 290 m/sec respectively. Figure 2b shows that the back face signature is higher in case of shock which is opposite to the residual velocity trend. The trend clearly indicates that, with shock back face signature is critical and residual velocity is under predicted. So, for residual velocity without shock, result is more conservative and for back face deformation with shock is more conservative. Thus simulations with shock and without shock are important.

Figure 2. Comparison of (a) residual velocity with shock and without shock effect; (b) back-face signature with shock and without shock.

5. References

- [1] Lässig, T., Nguyen, L., May, M., Riedel, W., Heisserer, U., van der Werff, H. and Hiermaier, S., 2015. A non-linear orthotropic hydrocode model for ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene in impact simulations. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 75, pp.110-122.
- [2] Bandaru, A.K., Ahmad, S. and Bhatnagar, N., 2017. Ballistic performance of hybrid thermoplastic composite armors reinforced with Kevlar and basalt fabrics. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 97, pp.151-165.
- [3] Lakshmana Rao, C., Narayanamurthy, V., Simha, K. R. Y. *Applied Impact Mechanics*. John Wiley & Sons 2016.

Finite Element Analysis of Nonlinear Second-order Strain Gradient Kirchhoff Plate

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Abstract

The weak form of the governing equation of equilibrium of isotropic Kirchhoff nanoplate with von Kármán geometric nonlinearity is derived for the first time using second-order negative strain gradient nonlocal theory. An improved 4-noded sub-parametric quadrilateral finite element having 12 degrees of freedom per node is developed to discretize the plate and its performance is assessed by analyzing the nonlinear static bending problems for different boundary conditions.

1. Introduction

The classical continuum theories do not include any internal length scale parameter; hence they lack the capability of capturing small-scale effects at micro/nano sizes. A number of nonlocal continuum theories have been proposed to address these shortcomings. The negative higher-order strain gradient theory [1] captures the nonlocal effects consistently independent of boundary conditions. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the finite element formulation of nanoplates incorporating von Kármán geometric nonlinearity and nonlocal effect through strain gradient theory is not available in the literature. In this paper, a refined quadrilateral finite element formulation is developed to study the bending of nonlinear isotropic Kirchhoff nanoplates using second-order negative strain gradient model.

2. Formulation

The constitutive relation for negative second-order strain gradient nonlocal theories can be expressed as [1]:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} (\varepsilon_{kl} - l^2 \varepsilon_{kl,mm}) \quad (1)$$

where l is the nonlocal parameter. Isotropic rectangular Kirchhoff nanoplate subjected to transverse UDL q with the length along the x -axis as a , the width along the y -axis as b and the thickness h is modelled considering von Kármán geometric nonlinearity. The weak form of the equations of equilibrium can be written as [2]:

$$\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_0^b \int_0^a \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} \left[\varepsilon_{xx} \delta \varepsilon_{xx} + \nu (\varepsilon_{xx} \delta \varepsilon_{yy} + \varepsilon_{yy} \delta \varepsilon_{xx}) + \varepsilon_{yy} \delta \varepsilon_{yy} + \frac{1-\nu}{2} \gamma_{xy} \delta \gamma_{xy} + l^2 \left\{ \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial y} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \nu \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{1-\nu}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial x} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \delta \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial y} \right\} \right] dx dy dz - \int_0^b \int_0^a q \delta w dx dy - \oint_S \left(N_{mn} \delta u_{0n} + N_{ns} \delta u_{0s} + Q_n \delta w - M_{mn} \frac{\partial \delta w}{\partial n} - M_{ns} \frac{\partial \delta w}{\partial s} \right) dS = 0 \quad (2)$$

where E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively; u_0 , v_0 and w are mid-plane displacements along the x -, y - and z -directions, respectively. Along with the classical boundary conditions, two additional boundary conditions ($\partial u_0 / \partial x$ and $\partial^2 w / \partial x^2$ (or their conjugates) on the x -constant edges; $\partial \delta v_0 / \partial y$ and $\partial^2 \delta w / \partial y^2$ (or their conjugates) on the y -constant edges) are also obtained due to the gradient effect.

An improved 4-noded sub-parametric quadrilateral finite element having 12 degrees of freedom per node (Eq. 3) is developed to tackle the nonlinear bending problem. In Figure 1, \mathbf{d}_i and δ_i are the degrees of freedom at each node in the physical coordinate space and natural coordinate space, respectively.

$$\mathbf{d}_i = \left\{ u_0, \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y}, v_0, \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y}, w, \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}, \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right\}_i^T \quad (3)$$

where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are elemental node numbers. The shape functions are derived by following a procedure similar to the one given by Lachemi and Lahoud [3].

Figure 1. 4-noded element in (a) physical coordinate space; (b) natural coordinate space.

3. Results and Discussion

A numerical code is developed in Fortran to implement the proposed FE model. The data for the rectangular single-layered graphene sheet, subjected to transverse point load F at the center, are taken as [4]: $a = 15.1$ nm, $b = 13.13$ nm, $h = 0.088$ nm, $E = 3.75$ TPa and $\nu = 0.33$. A mesh size of 8×8 is found to be sufficient for all analyses carried out in this study. The code is validated for movable all edges simply supported (SSSS1) plate (normal in-plane displacement is nonzero, tangential in-plane displacement is zero at the edges) by comparing the present results with those from the lattice model [4] (Figure 2a). Parametric study on immovable all edges clamped (CCCC2) plate (both normal and tangential in-plane displacements are zero at the edges) and movable/immovable SSSS plates (SSSS1/SSSS2) are shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 2. Nondimensional force versus nondimensional transverse displacement (a) comparison with lattice model [4]; (b) parametric study.

4. Summary

Parametric study depicts decrease in the flexural deflection with the increase in the nonlocal parameter depicting the hardening nature of the negative strain gradient theory. The appropriate choice of the nonlocal parameter (l) for different materials/configurations/geometries can be obtained by minimizing the difference between the FE results and the results obtained from experiments/molecular mechanics simulations.

5. References

- [1] Aifantis EC, 1992, On the role of gradients in the localization of deformation and fracture, International Journal of Engineering Science, 30(10), 1279-1299.
- [2] Papargyri-Beskou, S, Beskos, DE, 2008, Static, stability and dynamic analysis of gradient elastic flexural Kirchhoff plates, Archive of Applied Mechanics, 78(8), 625-635.
- [3] Lachemi M, Lahoud AE, 1991, A refined quadrilateral element for the finite-element analysis of plates, International Journal for Numerical Methods in Biomedical Engineering, 7(7), 527-537.
- [4] Scarpa, F, Adhikari, S, Gil, AJ, Remillat, C, 2010, The bending of single layer graphene sheets: the lattice versus continuum approach, Nanotechnology, 21(12), 125702.

Effectiveness of Polyurea Coated Steel Plates in Blast Mitigation in Vehicles

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Abstract

Shaped plates are being used as blast mitigation structures in armored personal carriers (APC). These shaped plates either deflect or absorb the energy imparted to them. An optimally designed plate should absorb the energy as much as possible and transmit the least impulse to the vehicle structure. In this context polyurea coated steel plates have recently attracted a lot of interest. Experimental studies have shown that steel plates coated with polyurea are more capable of mitigating the blast load. Hence a numerical study can be conducted on the polyurea coated V-shaped steel plates for finding its response. The objective of this study is to conduct FE based failure analysis of V-shaped steel plates coated with polyurea. The important parameters which affect the response of the plate are the mass of the explosive, the included angle of the V shape and thickness of polyurea layer and its interface characteristics. The response variables under consideration are the deflection of the plate and imparted impulse. A numerical procedure validated for flat plates coated with polyurea, has been used for the above study. The results are helpful in identifying an optimal structure design for resisting blast loads.

1. Introduction

New and improvised explosive devices in the form of land mines are widely used in war affected zones. The armored personal vehicles (APV) which are the only means of transportation under those situations are always under threat from those landmines. The effectiveness of the APV to resisting blast loads depends on the metallic plates used as blast mitigation structures as shown in Yuen et al. [1]. These coated metallic plates can deflect away and absorb a major part of the blast load. Hence net impulse transferred to the vehicle crew is significantly reduced thus enhancing their security. APV like south African CASSIPR are known to use V shaped plates as blast mitigation structures. Traditionally the plates are made from the armored steel. Latest research has also highlighted the use of sandwich structures, using hyperplastic coating materials like polyurea for the above purpose as given in Amini et al. [2] and Ackland et al. [3]. Polyurea coatings have been found to have resistance to fragmentation, impact loads, and ballistic loads along with blast mitigating capacity. These materials when applied as an external coating on the, metals plate are seen to improve the blast resistant property of the shaped plates.

2. Objectives

One of the objective of this work is to develop numerical methods for blast loading of structures using Abaqus explicit and validate the results against published results. These validated models can be used for assessing the effectiveness of protective structures like V-plate with polyurea coating under blast loading.

3. Summary

In this work the main focus is on numerical simulation of the mechanical response of the full scale V shaped plate by using the commercially available software Abaqus Explicit. This covers the geometric part modelling, mesh convergence studies, material modelling and blast load modelling. The initial studies consist of blast load modelling and its interaction with flat plates with and without polyuria coatings and its validation with results reported in literature Ackland et al. [3]. For this purpose, numerical work was carried out for a scaled down flat plate made of BlueScope XLERPLATE 350 grade steel (and having a dimensions of 1000mm x 1000mm), having polyurea coatings of 4mm thickness. It is observed that blast functions used in the simulation can adequately model the deformation in the plates. The later part studies the impulse transmitted and deformations of a full scale polyurea coated model (of 2500mm x 2500mm) and a V included angle of 145°. A mesh convergence study was performed and the mesh sizes of 0.02m for steel and 0.03m for polyurea was found adequate. The impulse transmitted to the base structure was compared with a V-plate without coating and reduction in the transmitted impulses were observed and presented in Figure 1. It can be observed that the variation in impulse is nonlinear and the reduction is about 22% for 21kg of explosive. Reduction in deformation was also observed in the case of coated plates and presented in Figure 2. It is

observed that the reduction in deformation is nonlinear and has a maximum value of 13% for 21 kg of explosive. It is assumed that the above results may be helpful in obtaining optimized plate designs.

Figure 1. Deformations for a bare plate and coated steel plate (5mm steel plate +7.7mm coating).

Figure 2. Impulse transmitted for full scale plate with and without coating.

4. References

- [1] Yuen, S.C.K., Langdon, G.S., Nurick, G.N., Pickering, E.G. and Balden, V.H., 2012. Response of V-shape plates to localised blast load: Experiments and numerical simulation. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 46, pp.97-109.
- [2] Amini, M.R., Simon, J. and Nemat-Nasser, S., 2010. Numerical modeling of effect of polyurea on response of steel plates to impulsive loads in direct pressure-pulse experiments. *Mechanics of Materials*, 42(6), pp.615-627.
- [3] Ackland, K., Anderson, C. and Ngo, T.D., 2013. Deformation of polyurea-coated steel plates under localised blast loading. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 51, pp.13-22.
- [4] Markose, A. and Rao, C.L., 2017. Mechanical response of V shaped plates under blast loading. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 115, pp.12-20.
- [5] Roland, C.M., Twigg, J.N., Vu, Y. and Mott, P.H., 2007. High strain rate mechanical behavior of polyurea. *Polymer*, 48(2), pp.574-578.

Mitigation of Secondary Blast Effects Using Tubular Structures

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Abstract

Mitigation of secondary blast effects on occupants in armored vehicles when subjected to mine blast has been explored by conducting numerical, analytical and experimental on circular as well as square aluminum (Al 6061) tubes. A parametric efficiency study on effect of cross-sectional geometry, obliquity of impact, boundary condition as well as relative rigidity of top plate connected to the tube were investigated and the results are reported only for two different cross sectional geometries due to space constraint. Modes of failure as well as performance matrices of crush efficiency were found to be consistent with the experimental observations.

1. Introduction

Armored vehicles which are subjected to mine blasts poses serious threats at different scales to occupants. Armor plating a vehicle is insufficient to protect the occupant against land mine explosions. Johnson and Reid [1] have reviewed a large number of investigations pertaining to the subject of collapse of tubes and other structures. From the point of view of energy-absorption capacity. Abramowicz and Jones [2] conducted a series of axial crushing tests on steel square tubes and observed three failure modes. These works have been revisited to investigate the dynamic crushing load capacity under secondary blast effects. Experimental study has been conducted to investigate the impulse transmitted and the average strain, strain rate.

2. Numerical Investigation

A dynamic analysis using explicit time integration scheme employed in Abaqus 6.11, a commercially available FEA package is used to simulate impact events and interpret the response of single as well as multiple tube sandwich type structures. Johnson-Cook material model has been adopted for both the failure as well as plastic model.

Figure 1. Effect of boundary conditions: Combined mode of bending and asymmetric lobe failure in 0.9 mm thick, 20 cm long, four tube sandwich system tied with rigid plate at bottom and thin plate at top.

Figure 2. (a) Relative Impulse Transmission..

Figure 2. (b) Efficiency Plot for 20 cm Tube.

3. Analytical Investigation

Analytical expressions for crush force proposed by Abramowicz and Jones [2] has been modified with popular Cowper-Symond expression for dynamic yield stress. Results were close to the experimental as well as numerical counter parts. Theoretical dynamic modulus based on average strain rate has been calculated from experimental observations.

$$\text{Asymmetric mode A [2]: } P_m = 11.48 * \sigma_y^{dyn} * t^{\frac{5}{3}} b^{\frac{1}{3}} + 0.44 * \sigma_y^{dyn} * t^{\frac{4}{3}} b^{\frac{2}{3}} + 0.26 * \sigma_y^{dyn} * t^2 \quad (1)$$

4. Experimental Investigation

Samples were tested using drop weight test facility and the reaction force history is recorded to find the average strain rate, impact duration, impulse transmission, peak crush force and mean crush force. Deformation modes were closely matching with numerical observations. Impact duration which governs the identification of impact event and further impulse calculations, was found to be 0.059 sec and very near to the numerical simulation results (0.056 sec) in case of 20cm long square tube. Apart from conventional performance matrices as shown in Table 1, impulse transmitted (Figure 2a) is observed to be an additional key parameter which can be correlated with regular NATO HFM-090 standards.

Table 1. Parametric evaluation of energy absorption efficiency (N-Numerical, A-Analytical, E-Experimental).

Parameters defining efficiency	20cm Long Square Tube			15cm Long Circular Tube		
	N	A	E	N	A	E
Total Energy absorption (J)	1320	1087.01	-	1203	1089	-
Peak crushing load (N)	10396	8104.74	12713.5	15600	8013	18821
Mean crush force(N)	7300.00	8104.74	7982.45	9630	8013	8977
Specific Energy Absorption(J/kg)	34878.64	29699.75	-	27548	24937	-
Crush Force Efficiency (%)	70.29%	-	62.79%	61.73%	-	47.70

Figure 3. Diamond mode failure in 15 cm long circular tube (a) Experimental observation; (b) Numerical observation.

5. Summary

Consolidated results are shown in Table 1. It is observed that variation in total energy absorption between numerical and analytical was not significant in each case. Mean Crush Force (MCF) was in similar ranges for both the square and circular tube case in analytical, Numerical and experimental studies. Variation in Specific Energy Absorption (SEA) between analytical and numerical studies reveals that the simplified assumptions used in analytical model may not be fully satisfied in the numerical simulation. The Crush Force Efficiency (CFE) clearly reveals that the circular cross sections are better in handling the energy absorptions. Further study in controlling the variations in crushing force can be done by introducing imperfections in the tubes by kinks, serrations, holes, composites/foam filling, etc.

6. References

- [1] Johnson W., Reid S. R., 1978, Metallic Energy Dissipation Systems. Applied Mechanics Reviews 31(3):277-288.
- [2] Abramowicz W., Jones N., 1984, Dynamic axial crushing of square tubes. International Journal of Impact Engineering 2(2):179-208.

Impact Resistance of Polyurea Backed Steel Materials by Izod Impact Test

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Abstract

In the present work, impact resistance of Steel specimens with and without Polyurea backing were measured in terms of energy absorption. The standard specimen dimensions taken in the present study are 8x8x75 mm with 1.6mm V-notch which is scaled down with respect to ASTM standards for Izod Specimen. A relative study has been made between two kinds of above mentioned specimens by Izod Impact setup and validated numerically by Abaqus CAE (6.14). The important parameters like energy absorption, reaction force, and equivalent plastic strain were investigated. The results indicate that the specimen backed with Polyurea coating behaves well in terms of greater energy absorption and showing low plastic strain, which reduces the chances of failure of materials.

Keywords: Izod Impact, Impact Resistance, polyurea backed Steel Specimens, Equivalent plastic strain, Energy Absorption.

1. Introduction

Failure of the materials during impact loading is one of the major problems in the engineering for several reasons. Absorption of impact loads or effect mitigation has drawn attention of researchers and several techniques using sacrificial layers, coatings etc. have emerged as solutions. Many impact testing techniques were established over the years to study the fracture behavior of engineering materials. Izod and Charpy are two such techniques which are primarily used to find the impact strength of a specimen under impact conditions. Steel is a ductile material under room temperature conditions and polyurea behaves like hyperelastic. Polyurea is a special material which has good sensitivity towards strain rate. Many authors have studied the behavior of materials by using Izod and Charpy techniques. Ghaith et al. investigated the non-linear behavior of steel alloys at different temperatures [1]. Bhasavakumar et al. studied the impact toughness of Aluminum Copper alloy materials by Charpy test [2].

In the present study, we discuss the detailed analysis of response of metal specimens backed with polyuria sheets, subjected to the impact loads. The relative assessment has been made along with bare metal plate both numerically and experimentally for getting the dynamic response as well as failure modes. The impact analysis is modelled numerically in Abaqus/Explicit (ver.6.14). The experimental work for this study in the laboratory level is accomplished with the help of Izod Impact Set-up, which works on the principle of energy absorption by the specimen.

2. General Specifications

The Izod test renders qualitative measure of toughness of material on the basic principle of absorption of energy in a notched sample under high rate of loading. Dropping a heavy weight from certain height (also called as angle of fall, α) which hits the specimen and rises to certain angle (also called as angle of rise, β) depending upon strength of the specimen. The difference in energies of two positions gives the energy absorbed by the specimen.

$$\text{Initial energy} = E_i = m g R (1 - \cos \alpha) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Energy after the rupture} = E_r = m g R (1 - \cos \beta) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Energy absorbed by the specimen} = E_{\text{abs}} = m g R (\cos \beta - \cos \alpha) \quad (3)$$

Here, R is arm length of setup.

3. Results and Conclusion

Below figure indicates the effect of Polyurea backing to the steel specimen in terms of energy absorption. The comparison of polyurea backed specimen with the bare specimen has been assessed by studying various parameters like notch end displacement history, building up of equivalent plastic strain near notch area, reaction

force history, von-mises stress variation with time, and energy absorption. The numerical results obtained by Abaqus are shown below.

Figure 1. Deformed and undeformed specimens of bare and back coated metal specimens.

From simulation it is observed that Polyurea backed specimen exhibit more impact absorption compared to bare plates and there is reduction in all aforementioned parameters. Also, the final deflection of polyurea coated plates are less when compared with bare plate so that the chance of failure can be minimized.

4. References

- [1] Ghaith, F.A., 2010. Nonlinear finite element modeling of Charpy impact test. In *Advanced materials research* (Vol. 83, pp. 182-189). Trans Tech Publications.
- [2] Basavakumar, K.G., Mukunda, P.G. and Chakraborty, M., 2008. Impact toughness in Al–12Si and Al–12Si–3Cu cast alloys—Part 1: Effect of process variables and microstructure. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 35(4), pp.199-205.
- [3] Silberstein, M.N., 2005. *Mechanics of Notched Izod impact testing of polycarbonate* (Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology).
- [4] Szafran, J. and Matusiak, A., *Polyurea coating systems: definition, research, applications. parameters*, 2, p.3.
- [5] Rao, C.L., Narayanamurthy, V. and Simha, K.R.Y., 2016. *Applied Impact Mechanics*. John Wiley & Sons.

SH-Wave Propagation in a Viscoelastic Sandy Layer Over a Heterogeneous Half-Space

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Abstract

This paper investigates the propagation of SH-wave in a viscoelastic sandy layer overlying a heterogeneous half-space in which rigidity and density are linearly varying. As mathematical tools, such as the method of separation of variable and Whittaker's function are applied to obtain the required displacement components. The analytical expression of dispersion equation has been derived in closed form by using the appropriate boundary conditions. The dispersion equation perfectly matched with standard dispersion equation of SH-wave in a particular case. The effect of various parameters namely sandy parameter, viscoelastic parameter, inhomogeneity parameter and non-dimensional wave number on phase velocity of SH-wave has been discussed analytically and demonstrated graphically. Moreover, some notable points of the problem have been observed about the nature of wave propagation.

1. Introduction

Viscoelastic property consists with two significant physical properties namely viscous and elastic. Viscoelastic materials can retain the vibrational energies by damping them. Sandy layer is one of those layers present underneath the Earth which may sometimes be found to be acted upon by viscosity with considerable internal friction. The heterogeneity inside the Earth is caused by variation in density and rigidity with depth. Wave propagation through viscoelastic sandy medium is one of the most important topics due to its wider applicability in various areas such as soil mechanics, geophysics, seismology etc.

2. Formulation

We consider a model for the propagation of SH-wave in viscoelastic sandy medium with finite width H overlying an inhomogeneous semi-infinite medium. We have taken origin at the interface between the upper layer and lower semi-infinite medium. The x -axis is taken as in the direction of wave propagation along the interface and z -axis chosen vertically downwards in the lower medium (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Geometry of the problem.

The only non-vanishing equations of motion in the absence of body forces for the propagation of SH-wave is given as:

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}^{(i)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}^{(i)}}{\partial z} = \rho_{(i)} \frac{\partial^2 v_{(i)}}{\partial t^2}; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

where ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the density of upper layer and semi-infinite medium, respectively.

3. Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions for the problem is defined as:

$$\tau_{yz}^{(1)} = 0 \text{ at } z = -H \quad (2)$$

$$v_1(x, z, t) = v_2(x, z, t), \tau_{yz}^{(1)} = \tau_{yz}^{(2)} \text{ at } z = 0 \quad (3)$$

The dynamical equations of motion are solved by the boundary conditions and eliminating the constants, we get the dispersion equation of SH-wave propagating in the proposed model.

4. Results and Conclusion

The displacement components of both the proposed layer and semi-infinite medium have been derived separately in close form. Using suitable boundary conditions and variable separation method is used to obtain the frequency equation of SH-wave and some results are well matched with previous results in particular case. Phase velocity is computed numerically and impacts of various parameters are examined graphically. We concluded that phase velocity of SH-wave has been surprisingly affected by various parameters. Some graphs are presented which shows the variation of phase velocity as well as damped velocity (as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2. Variation of dimensionless (a) phase velocity; (b) damped velocity of SH wave versus dimensionless wave number for different values of viscoelastic parameter, when inhomogeneity parameters are fixed.

5. References

[1] Singh AK, Mistri KC, Das A, 2016, Propagation of SH-wave in a corrugated viscous sandy layer sandwiched between two elastic half-spaces, *Waves in Random and Complex Media*, 27(2), 213-240.
 [2] Dhua S, Chattopadhyay A, 2016, Wave propagation in heterogeneous layer of the Earth, *Waves in Random and Complex Media*, 26(4), 626-641.

Effect of Polymer Foam on Car Stiffness Beams in Case of Lateral Impact

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Abstract

Modern cars are equipped with stiffness beams in the doors which help in preventing a direct side impact collision with the passengers. In case of impact the reaction forces on car get a huge peak and time of impact is little. To study the force profile, time of impact and maximum displacement a scaled down model of both rear and front car doors, as one entity, is created and impacted with a cuboidal impactor in DWT facility. Tests were also conducted with layers of foam on the stiffness beams. A scaling analysis is presented to correlate forces, time of impact and other parameters between model and prototype. Simulations were also conducted to analyze the trend.

Keywords: Lateral Impact, Car Stiffness Beams, Scaling Analysis, Drop Weight Testing.

1. Introduction

From statistics available in public domain it is known that side impacts are more fatal than front and rear impacts. This is because of lack of space available to stop the impacting object. In recent research by Yin et al. [1] analysis on Functionally Graded Foam Filled Cellular Structure (FGFCS) in B-Pillars has been done. Park et al. [2] looked into complexity and sensitivity analysis of structural composite inserts in vehicle structures. The stiffness beams in the car reduce the intrusions into the passenger compartment upon collision. The path of the energy transfer is from the hinges to the floor to the seats and ultimately, the passengers. The stiffness beams can resist the impacting object but with very small time of impact. As a result, the passengers experience an intense shock. To prevent this, we bring in a novel idea of placing an energy absorber (flexible foam) between outer sheet metal and stiffness beams so that some energy is absorbed before hitting the structure. In contrast, Marsavina et al. [3] conducted three-point bending tests on rigid foams like polyurethane. Injuries in cars happen due to sudden very high force experienced by the passenger. Peak force in cases of with and without foam and with different thicknesses was measured.

2. Scaling Analysis

In the model all dimensions, reduced by a factor α with respect to prototype (real car), were calculated similar to the work of Alves et al. [4]. We assume the door to be a beam, doubly clamped, and impactor as a uniformly distributed load. Then on mathematically deriving following is found:

$$\text{Forces} \quad P_m = \alpha^2 P_p \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Time of Impact} \quad T_{o,m} = \alpha \gamma T_{o,p} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Acceleration} \quad a_m = \frac{a_p}{\alpha} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Velocity} \quad v_m = \gamma v_p \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Displacement} \quad s_m = \alpha \gamma^2 s_p \quad (5)$$

where m is subscript for model, p is subscript for prototype, P is force, T is time of impact, a is acceleration, v is velocity, s is displacement, α is scaling factor and γ is ratio of prototype impactor velocity to model impactor velocity.

3. Simulations

The simulations were done using Abaqus and LS Dyna. There are broadly four model components to be analyzed, namely, the specimen (car door), foam, impactor and base, out of which impactor and base are taken rigid. For

steel, impactor elasticity and rate dependent plasticity models (Johnson Cook plasticity model) were used and for foam, Ogden model (hyper-elastic) and Fu_Chang_foam material model were used. The parameters obtained from simulations are maximum deflection, peak force, time of contact/impact.

4. Experimental Setup

A specimen in our experiment is a steel structure comprising stiffness beams and pillars joined by welding. In few specimen, foam is also pasted on the steel structure. Drop weight test (DWT) facility was used for impactor to attain certain velocity before impact. Electromagnet system was used to hold the impactor at the height of 2 meters. Specimen is placed on a metal base mounted vertically above the load cell. A special arrangement to hold the load cell in place was used. The impactor is dropped from a certain height onto the specimen and response on oscilloscope was recorded. The images and videos of impact process were also captured using a professional camera.

5. Results

The load cell data (Voltage vs. Time) collected by oscilloscope was analyzed in spread sheet software and data was plotted. Only the relevant portion of data, where impact happened, was selected and rest was truncated. An unusual trend is seen that the curve starts with some fluctuations followed by two consecutive combinations of peak and valley. But since both the graphs show same pattern it can be believed that experiment is repeatable.

Figure 1. Voltage vs. Time graph for specimen without foam.

Figure 2. Voltage vs. Time graph for specimen with 6 mm foam thickness.

The time of impact was measured from the graphs. For specimen without foam time of impact is 47 ms as shown in Figure 1 and with a 6 mm sheet of foam the time of impact is 54 ms as shown in Figure 2. Since time of impact increased in latter case, average force is believed to be decreased.

6. Summary

An analysis has been done on the scaled down model of lateral impact on car. Influence of foam on the structure has been studied to know the reduction in peak force and increase in time of impact. Scaling analysis, simulations and experiments have been done. From experiments it is observed that the time of impact increases on applying sheet of foam on steel structure.

7. References

- [1] Yin, H., Chen, C., Hu, T. and Wen, G., 2017. Optimisation for bending crashworthiness of functionally graded foam-filled cellular structure. *International Journal of Crashworthiness*, pp.1-15.
- [2] Park, C.K.C., Kan, C.D.S., Reagan, S.W., Deshpande, B.R. and Mohan, P.K., 2011, May. Crashworthiness and Sensitivity Analysis of Structural Composite Inserts in Vehicle Structure. In *Eighth European LS-DYNA Users Conference* (pp. 23-24).
- [3] Marsavina, L., Sadowski, T., Kneć, M. and Negru, R., 2010. Non-linear behaviour of foams under static and impact three point bending. *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, 45(10), pp.969-975.
- [4] Alves, M. and Oshiro, R.E., 2006. Scaling the impact of a mass on a structure. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 32(7), pp.1158-1173.

Numerical Analysis of Bat and Ball Impact in Cricket

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Abstract

In the present study, the behavior of the cricket bat impact under various ball speeds is conducted. The aim of our project was to develop and validate a finite element model of a cricket ball/bat impact. For numerical simulation orthotropic wood material is impacted with ball having hyper-elastic properties. The hyper elastic model is based on Mooney-Rivlin parameters. The stress and deflection induced due to impact are presented.

1. Introduction

Cricket is a popular sport with a rich history, and the first rules were laid down in 1788 but development in the cricket equipment has not been adequate. One of the main reason is the law of cricket which limits the material composition of the cricket blade to wood. This is contrary to other sports such as tennis and squash where rackets have evolved significantly and numerous materials such as Aluminium-based alloys, carbon and Kevlar fiber composites and titanium-based alloys have been utilized. The performance of cricket bats depends upon the properties of cricket balls, bat swing speed, and the nature of the wood.

2. Numerical Modelling

In present study ABAQUS CAE is used for Finite Element Analysis of the ball bat impact scenario. The geometry of the cricket bat used for numerical simulation is shown below:

Figure 1. Dimensions of the Cricket Bat.

Table 1. Orthotropic Properties of Willow Wood.

	Young's Modulus (MPa)			Shear Modulus (MPa)			Poisson's Ratio		
	E_x	E_y	E_z	G_{xy}	G_{yz}	G_{zx}	ν_{yx}	ν_{zx}	ν_{xy}
Willow	3301.17	219.85	1757.41	330.12	33.012	330.12	0.015	0.16	0.16

Table 2. Hyperelastic properties of Cork.

Material parameters	Value
C10	3.10 MPa
C01	-1.50 MPa
d	0.004MPa ⁻¹

Cricket bat has two parts blade and cane, the Blade, where the impact between the ball and bat happens, is made up of the willow wood material. For numerical simulation the bat material is taken as homogeneous orthotropic material. Orthotropic properties of willow wood are shown in Table 1. Cricket ball is made up of three layers. A central cork-rubber core, cork-and-twine packing, and a stitched leather cover usually constitute the three major layers of a cricket ball. The materials used in manufacturing cricket balls are highly rate-dependent and, accordingly, impact-speed dependent. For the present study the inner cork is taken as the ball material. The cork is modelled as hyper elastic material. Strain-energy density function based Mooney-Rivlin hyper elastic model is used to model the cricket ball. The material constants for cork is shown in Table 2.

C3D8R, an 8-node linear brick elements with reduced integration and hourglass control were used in the simulations. Impact loading is applied by the high velocities of the ball (in our case 100 kmph and 150 kmph), impact force is acting on the top surface of bat at certain distance from the bottom. Encastre boundary condition is applied on the cane part of the bat to simulate the real practice of ball bat impact.

3. Results

Figure 2a shows Von Mises stress distribution through the bat, it is found that Von Mises stress is about 45.67 MPa and 83.74 MPa for ball speed 100 kmph and 150 kmph respectively. Figure 2b shows deformed shape of the bat after impact. The values of coefficient of restitution (COR) is found by calculating ratio of velocity after impact and before impact.

Figure 2. (a) Von Mises stresses for 100 kmph; (b) Deformed shape of the bat after impact.

4. Summary

Impact analysis and vibration analysis of the cricket bat has been done. The increase of 83% in stress values has been found out for increase in velocity from 100 kmph to 150 kmph. The value of Coefficient of restitution is 0.52 which is slightly higher than the experimental value 0.48.

5. References

- [1] Ning Cheng, Development of a Universal FE Model of a Cricket Ball, School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University, July 2008.
- [2] Harsimranjeet Singh, Experimental and computer modeling to characterize the Performance of cricket bats, Washington State University, School of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, December 2008.
- [3] John, S., Li, Z.B. Multi-directional vibration analysis of cricket bats. The engineering of Sports, 2002.
- [4] C.Lakshmana Rao, V.Narayanamurthy, K.R.Y. Simha, Applied Impact Mechanics, ISBN: 978-1-119-24180-5, 2016.

Effects of Height Variation on Impact Force and Stress Waves in *Shirodhara*

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Abstract

Shirodhara is an Ayurvedic therapy that has been used extensively as a treatment for neurological disorders like mental stress, paralysis, depression, anxiety and insomnia. It utilizes the flow impact of medicinal fluid on forehead of the subject at controlled temperature for cure. The impact force of fluid falling from *Shirodhara* pot is measured using an integrated circuit piezoelectric (ICP) force sensor. This study also includes the analytical approach to the problem to assess the relative performance of impact force generated by traditional wick used in the *Shirodhara* treatment.

1. Introduction

Shirodhara is an ancient Ayurvedic therapy. An ayurvedic oil pours in a continuous stream over the forehead or *ajna marma*, an area where nerves are highly concentrated. This study investigates the effects of height variation on Impact force due to milk drop impact on the forehead skin by mimicking the dripping of essential oil in the ayurvedic process of *Shirodhara* through experiment, simulation and analytical approaches. A simple experimental setup was designed to measure the impact force at 4 *angulas*, 6 *angulas* and 8 *angulas* height (units from ancient text) equivalent to 0.075 m, 0.1125 m and 0.15 m respectively.

2. General Specifications

Size of the human forehead = 0.158 mm * 0.076mm

Thickness of skin+ muscle= 1mm

Young's modulus of human skin, $E = 4.2 \times 10^5$ Pa

Density = 1020 kg/m³

Skull and fat layers in the human forehead is neglected in the analysis.

Table 1. Fluid parameters of the model.

S. No	Fluid	Density (kg/m ³)	Viscosity (centipose)	Surface Tension (N/m)
1	Milk	1027	3	0.05102

3. Experiment

Figure 1. Experimental setup to measure the impact force due to fluid flow.

Figure 1 is the experimental setup to measure the impact force associated to *Shirodhara*. Recent studies didn't investigate the effects of height variation on impact force in *Shirodhara*. In this study we are trying to understand the effects of impact height due to the fall of fluid in *Shirodhara*. Density and viscosity of the fluid is measured experimentally. The impact height between wick to the sensor is varied by an adjustable stand. The fluid flow impacts the sensor due to gravity. Hence the impact force of the continuous flow of fluid is measured using the ICP

force sensor at room temperature.

4. Analytical Modeling of the Fluid (Oil)-Skin Interaction in *Shirodhara* Process

The proposed model adopts linear elasticity theory with small deformations for the skin [1]. By solving the 1D wave equation, Navier-Stokes equation and D'Alembert's solution for wave equation [2], the impact pressure on the contact surface is given below:

$$\text{Impact pressure: } p|_{x=0} = 1.58 \times (V_0 - V_s) \text{ MPa} \quad (1)$$

where V_0 is the velocity of impact and V_s is the velocity of elastic solid. $V_0 - V_s$ is due to cushioning effect of the elastic solid. V_s is given by solving the wave equation for elastic solid to get the impact pressure on solid:

$$p_s|_{x=0} = \rho_s \times c_s \times V_s \quad (2)$$

where ρ_s is the density of the elastic solid and c_s is the fundamental velocity of wave propagation is given by:

$$c_s = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho_s}} \quad (3)$$

Solving the above equation, we get $c_s = 20.29$ m/s.

From force balance, we get

$$\rho_0 \times c_0 \times (V_0 - V_s) = \rho_s \times c_s \times V_s \quad (4)$$

which gives

$$V_s = \frac{\rho_0 c_0 V_0}{\rho_0 c_0 + \rho_s c_s} \quad (5)$$

5. Results

For various impact height, the measured impact force and the Impact Parameters for drop-elastic solid from analytical approach of impact pressure on solid and liquid medium is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Impact parameters for drop-elastic solid.

Sl. No.	Impact Height (m)	Force (N)	Impact Pressure on solid (MPa)	Impact pressure on liquid (MPa)
1	0.075	0.2542	0.025	0.032
2	0.115	0.3914	0.03	0.032
3	0.15	0.432	0.035	0.032

6. Summary

The extended abstract discusses the experimental setup and effect of height variation on Impact force in *shirodhara*. It briefly discussed the analytical Modeling of the fluid (oil)-skin interaction in *Shirodhara* Process. The paper shall discuss the correlation between experimental, numerical, simulation and analytical results in detail and the stress waves associated to *Shirodhara*.

7. References

- [1] N. Li, Q. Zhou, X. Chen, T. Xu, S. Hui and D. Zhang, Liquid drop impact on solid surface with application to water drop erosion on turbine blades, Part I: Nonlinear wave model and solution of one-dimensional impact, International Journal of Mechanical Sciences, vol. 50, no. 10-11, pp. 1526-1542, 2008
[2] C. L. Rao, V. Narayanamurthy and K. R. Y. Simha, Applied Impact Mechanics, Ane Books Pvt. Ltd.

Determination of Load Point Displacement of 3-Point Bend Specimen Under High Strain Rate

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to evaluate the load point displacement (LPD) of notched 3-point bend specimen under impact loading condition. A modified Hopkinson bar (MHPB) was used to generate impact loading at different velocities (11-18 m/s). Notched 3-point bend specimens were prepared from an Aluminum Alloy Al6063-T6 10mm thick plate. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and strain gauge measurement have been used to determine the load point displacement of the specimen. Strain gauge and one-dimensional stress wave theory were employed to get the load point displacement and force. Explicit finite element (ABAQUS) software was used for the numerical simulation of the impact experiment. Results acquired from numerical simulations were compared with the experimentally obtained data (DIC & Strain Gauge measurement). A good agreement was found between the numerical and experimental data.

1. Introduction

Aluminum alloys are very useful materials in the aerospace and automotive industry. Excellent combination properties such as high strength to weight ratio, high fracture toughness and corrosion resistance are the main reason behind this. During the collision of vehicles, different types of fracture or failure occurred in the different components. To ensure the safety of human life during these type of accidents load point displacement (LPD) is an important parameter to determine the various fracture property under the dynamic loading condition [1]. Dynamic 3-point bend experiments were performed on MHPB to determine the LPD by using the two-point strain measurement [2] technique along with 3D DIC technique. As an accurate constitutive material model is needed in order to predict the plastic deformation and fracture behavior of metals through FEM simulation during impact loading. From different constitutive models that are available, Johnson-Cook constitutive model was selected [3]. The basic idea in the calibration of J-C constitutive model is to isolate the effect of strain hardening, strain rate hardening and thermal softening on the plastic behavior of the material.

2. Experiments and Results

The three-point bend experiments were performed on MHPB, is shown in Figure 1, under the dynamic loading at different velocities in between 11-18m/s. Here we discussed only one experiment conducted at 15.1m/s velocity (Aprox. 1890/s strain rate) in detail.

Figure 1. Whole Experimental Set-up.

Figure 2. Un-fractured and fractured specimen.

The specimens were prepared from aluminum sheet of Al6063-T6 material and sprayed with white paint and a random speckle pattern marked on it for DIC analysis as shown in Figure 2. Strains are recorded at two points with

the help of strain gauge measurement known as incident (ε_i) and reflected (ε_r) strain. These strains are used for determine the Load point displacement (LPD) by using Eq. (1).

$$u(t) = C_0 \int_0^t (\varepsilon_i(t) - \varepsilon_r(t)) dt \quad (1)$$

Where C_0 is wave propagation speed of the Hopkinson pressure bar.

Transient load point displacement (u) measured on the specimen surface by digital image correlation process is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that the good agreement between MHPB and DIC results and displacement shows a continuous increase during dynamic loading as expected. From Figure 3, it is cleared that displacement is very less because only one wave is being considered. The reason behind considering only one wave is that fracture initiate with in the one wave traveling across the specimen, as shown in Figure 4.

Numerical analysis has been done in ABAQUS by using the Johnson-cook material model and its material constants value has taken from H. Zhu et al. [4] paper.

Figure 3. Variation of LPD with time.

Figure 4. Profile of LPD at 15.1m/s velocity.

3. Summary

The LPD was calculated using two different techniques (1) strain measurement technique, and (2) DIC. Results from both were found to be in good agreement with each other. A numerical result has confirmed the experimental results validity.

4. References

- [1] L. Rubio, J. Fernandez-Saez and C. Navarro, Determination of dynamic fracture-initiation toughness using three-point bending tests in a modified Hopkinson pressure bar, *Experimental Mechanics* 43 (2003), 379–386.
- [2] C. Bacon, J. Farm and J.L. Lataillade, Dynamic fracture toughness determine from load point displacement, *Experimental Mechanics* 34 (1993), 217-223.
- [3] Johnson G R and Cook W H, A constitutive model and data for metals subjected to large strains, high strain rates and high temperatures, *Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Ballistics* 21(1983), 541-547.
- [4] H. Zhu, C. Qin, J. Q. Wang, and F.J. Qi, Characterization and Simulation of Mechanical Behavior of 6063 Aluminum Alloy Thin-walled Tubes, *Advanced Materials Research* 197-198 (2011), 1500-1508.

Droplet Impact for Various Dripping Condition Falling from Different Height

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Abstract

Fluid impact has its wide application in civil, biomedical engineering and applied mechanics. This paper focus on one of the biomedical application for fluid impact is *Shirodhara*. *Shirodhara* is a medical therapy that has been used extensively as a treatment for neurological disorders like mental stress, paralysis, depression, anxiety and insomnia. It utilizes the laminar flow impact at low velocity of medicinal liquid on forehead of the human at controlled temperature, which leads to the tranquillity of mind. In preliminary study of experiment, the impact force of continuous falling liquid is of order 10^{-2} N is measured for all the liquids. A detailed investigation of variation of force generated for a liquid droplet falling from various fixed height is presented.

1. Introduction

Impact is the force which occurs in short time duration. Fluid impact is encountered in several engineering fields from high velocity impact to low velocity impact [1]. One of the biomedical applications of fluid impact at low velocity on human forehead is *Shirodhara* [2]. This medicinal therapy involves the low velocity impact of medicinal liquid on the forehead from a specific height of approximately 7.5cm at a controlled temperature, creates a vibration on the forehead [3]. A scientific explanation of the mechanics of this treatment is a challenging task and has not been attempted by many investigators. The vibration impulse generated by the mechanical impact has a soothing effect on the body and mind [4]. When there is a fluid impact on a solid surface, a transient impact will be developed at the interface in short time duration as vibration on forehead. The preliminary studies have indicated that the fluid impact force of continuous fall of *Ksheerabala* and *Mahanarayanan* oil which is used in *Shirodhara* treatment is compared with the impact force of water. The measured impact force of continuous dripping liquid is of order 10-2N in 5 milliseconds, is almost same for different liquids used in the experiment. In the current study, a detailed investigation of the fluid impact under various tapping condition of vibration is studied. The fluid impact of the liquid falling from the beaker at controlled flow rate is measured using an integrated circuit piezoelectric (ICP) force sensor for various tapping condition. The time-dependent response of the sensor is acquired using data acquisition system which is connected to the computer. The force is determined by measuring the voltage output from the piezoelectric force sensor [5].

2. Experiment

The experimental setup consists of *Shirodhara* pot made of earthen mud is kept on a height adjustable designed stand. The schematic diagram for the experimental setup for measurement of impact force is shown in Figure 1. *Gaurda* cloth is used as wick for uniformity of fluid flow from the pot and to ensure the continuous and laminar flow of fluid. The flow rate of the fluid falling is maintained approximately constant by visual observation, providing the required diameter of wick. Fluid impact force measurement is the primary component in our understanding of *Shirodhara*. An Integrated Circuit Piezoelectric (ICP) force sensor is used for measuring the impact force. Battery powered signal conditioners are used for conditioning the output signals from the sensor to the readout instrument and also to provide power to drive the sensor. The output voltage is measured with the data acquisition card and all the data are collected through a custom written LabVIEW program and processed in MATLAB [5]. The data is collected at 200Hz and filtered using 10Hz low pass Butterworth filter.

The impact experiment is done for single tap, intermittent tap a liquid droplet falling from a various fixed height. The impact from single drop to continuous flow of fluid is varied by changing the volume of fluid in the pot. In the medicinal treatment, from the ancient empirical rules, the distance between the wick and the forehead is always maintained at 0.075 m approximately. A detailed investigation of impact force is carried out, by varying the height from the wick to the sensor as 2 angulas, 4 angulas, 6 angulas and 8 angulas (units in ancient language) which is approximately calculated as 0.038 m, 0.075 m, 0.113 m and 0.15 m respectively. The impact force for a continuous

fluid falling at a constant height of 0.075 m is taken from the literature and compared [5]. The continuous flow is ensured to be laminar without any turbulent effect.

3. Results

The typical impact force measured at the surface of the sensor is shown in Figure 2 for a single drop impact of *Mahanarayanan* oil falling from various impact heights. The impact force duration is approximately five milliseconds for the fluid fall from all the impact height. The impact duration is observed to be same for all the fluids. The impact force is found to be increasing with increasing the impact height. Impact force of 0.02144 N is the highest when a liquid falling from higher impact height of 0.15 m. The lowest impact force generated is 0.01353 N which is fluid drop falling from a height of 0.038 m.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of experimental setup for measuring fluid impact force.

Figure 2. Impact Force (N) vs Time (ms) for single drop impact of Mahanarayanan oil falling from various heights.

4. Summary

The fluid impact force when a single drop, intermittent flow of drops and continuous flow of fluid falling from different heights for *Mahanarayanan* oil, *Ksheerabala* oil and water is studied in this paper. There is only small variation of impact force for different liquids under different condition. The following conclusions can be stated:

- The height of impact considered in the experiment are 0.038 m, 0.075 m, 0.113 m and 0.15 m and the velocity are 0.86 m/s, 1.21 m/s, 1.49 m/s and 1.72 m/s relatively. The impact force increases as the impact height and velocity of impact increases.
- The measured impact force is of range from 0.03907 N to 0.01305 N. The highest impact force is observed for water, which is a reference fluid and the lowest impact force is measured for the *Ksheerabala* oil. The impact force is same for *Mahanarayanan* oil, *Ksheerabala* oil when the impact height is 0.075 m, which is the approximate height used in the treatment procedures.

5. References

- [1] Rao, C. Lakshmana, Narayanamurthy, V., and Simha, K. R. Y., 2016, Applied Impact Mechanics, John Wiley & Sons, pp.1, 22.
- [2] Uebaba, K., Xu, Feng-Hao., Tagawa, M., et. al., 2005, Using a healing robot for the scientific study of Shirodhara. IEEE engineering in medicine and biology magazine, Vol. 24.2, pp. 69-78.
- [3] Dhuri, Kalpana D., Prashant V. Bodhe, and Ashok B. Vaidya., 2013, Shirodhara: A psycho-physiological profile in healthy volunteers, Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine, Vol. 4.1, pp. 40-44.
- [4] Chapara Aparna, Kavya, N., Vasan Satish, S and Lohith, B. A., 2017, Critical Analysis of Shirodhara: A Review, International Ayurvedic Medical Journal, Vol. 5(4), pp.1190-1197.
- [5] Swathika, M., Lakshmana Rao, C., Balasubramanian, V., 2016, Measurement of Impact Force associated with Shirodhara (Ayurvedic) Treatment, The Indian Society of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, International Conference, pp.11-14.

Torsional Wave Propagation in a Viscoelastic Functionally Graded Orthotropic Overlying Inhomogeneous Half-Space

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Abstract

The present work deals with the propagation characteristics of torsional waves in a functionally graded material plate over the inhomogeneous half-space under the effect of initial stress. The equations of motion have been derived separately for layer and half-space under suitable boundary conditions. A closed-form frequency relation for the torsional surface waves under the considered geometry is obtained. In particular, some cases have been deduced to validate with previously known results. To show the effect of proposed parameters on the torsional surface waves, some graphical representation has been illustrated.

Keywords: Torsional wave, FGM layer, inhomogeneity, anisotropy, phase velocity, group velocity.

1. Introduction

Functionally graded materials (FGM) are a class of composites that have a dynamic assortment of material properties beginning with one surface then onto the following. FGMs play an important role in astronautics and aerodynamic designing because these materials change its properties gradually. At high temperatures these materials show creep and stress relaxation, therefore, FGMs are highly useful in structural building and automotive or aviation ventures [1, 2].

In the present article, the frequency relation of torsional waves in an orthotropic viscoelastic functionally graded layer over initially stressed inhomogeneous half-space has been carried out. The numerical computations have been performed with the help of MATHEMATICA. Graphical representations show that the proposed parameters are highly affecting the torsional wave velocity.

2. Formulation of the Problem

A finite thickness (H) of FGM plate overlying inhomogeneous half-space is considered. An initial stress is applied in the half-space. We consider a 3D Cartesian coordinate system. The origin is assumed at the plane $Z=0$. Let r and θ are radial and circumferential co-ordinates respectively. We consider the propagation direction of wave along the radial direction. Let (u_1, v_1, w_1) denotes the particle displacement along r , θ and z direction, respectively.

Figure 1. Geometry of the problem.

Condition of torsional waves: The torsional surface wave is characterized by the displacement components $u_1(r, z, t) = 0 = w_1(r, z, t)$ and $v_1 = v_1(r, z, t)$.

3. Boundary Conditions and Frequency Equation

The boundary conditions has been considered for both cases

$$(i) \tau_{\theta z}^{(1)} = 0 \text{ at } z = -H; (ii) v_1 = v_2 \text{ at } z = 0; (iii) \tau_{\theta z}^{(1)} = \tau_{\theta z}^{(2)} \text{ at } z = 0.$$

Using the boundary conditions (i), (ii) and (iii), we get

$$\tan[\xi H] = \frac{\xi(\mu_2 + i\omega\mu_2')(\gamma_2 + \sqrt{\gamma_2^2 + 4M})}{(C_{44} + i\omega M_{44})\left(2\xi^2 + \frac{m^2}{2}\right) - \frac{m}{2}(\mu_2 + i\omega\mu_2')(\gamma_2 + \sqrt{\gamma_2^2 + 4M})} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) gives the wave velocity equation of Torsional waves in a Voigt-type viscoelastic orthotropic functionally graded material layer overlying an inhomogeneous half-space. When the upper medium as well as lower half-space be isotropic then then Eq. (1) can be reduced as a classical equation of Love wave [3] which validates with the proposed model.

Figure 2. Variation of dimensionless phase velocity and dissipation function against dimensionless real wave number for different values of initial stress $S (= P'/2\mu_2')$.

4. Conclusion

It has been observed by numerical computation that the phase velocity decreases with increasing nature of wave numbers. The proposed parameters have very significant effect on the phase velocity in lower range of wavenumbers. The dissipation function increases initially up to a certain value then it is stable for higher wavenumbers. The current study may be helpful for young researchers or seismologist for predicting the nature of torsion wave in these Earth structures.

5. References

- [1] Altenbach H, Eremeyev VA, 2008, Analysis of the viscoelastic behavior of plates made of functionally graded materials, ZAMM J. Appl. Math. Mech., 88, 332-341.
- [2] Altenbach H, Eremeyev VA, 2008, Direct approach-based analysis of plates composed of functionally graded materials, Arch. Appl. Mech., 78, 775-794.
- [3] Love AEH, 1920, Mathematical theory of elasticity, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Linearly Consistent One-Point Integration Rule Over Star Convex Polytopes

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Abstract

We propose a linearly consistent one-point integration scheme (LS-1p) which inherits the properties of the LS-3n. This is done by the Taylor's expansion of the weak form which facilitates the evaluation of the smoothed nodal derivatives acting as stabilization terms. The salient feature of the proposed technique is that it requires only one integration point as opposed to 3n in [1] and 13n integration points in the conventional approach over n-sided polytopes, which translates to 50% and 30% reduction in the overall computational time in two and three dimensions, respectively. The efficacy of the proposed method is demonstrated by solving few benchmark problems.

1. Introduction

The polygonal and polyhedral finite element method (PFEM) relaxes the constraints on the element topology by allowing n-sided/faced arbitrary polytopes in the finite element analysis. The recent advancement of the PFEM in the engineering application have demonstrated the efficacy of arbitrary polytopes over the classical finite elements. The flexibility provided by polytopes comes with challenges. The construction of approximation functions over arbitrary polytopes is not unique. This has led to different approaches to construct approximation functions over arbitrary polytopes. These approaches include: Wachspress basis functions, mean value coordinate, harmonic shape functions, Laplace basis functions and maximum entropy basis functions, to name a few. Moreover, the computation of the integrals over polytopes poses some difficulties. One approach to integrate over arbitrary polytopes is to sub-divide the region into triangles (in two dimensions) or tetrahedra (in three dimensions) and then employ conventional quadrature schemes. Although, the approach is simple, it requires "many" integration points to integrate even simple functions. Typically, higher order quadrature rules involving 13 integration points per triangle are employed. Moreover, the associated approximations do not pass the patch test.

Inspired by the smoothing technique originally proposed for meshfree methods [1], a smoothing technique was proposed for the polygonal elements in Natarajan et al. [2]. However, it was shown that the direct application of the smoothing technique with average shape functions does not pass the patch test and yields less accurate results [2]. Within the framework of the smoothed finite element method (SFEM), Francis et al. [3] proposed a linear smoothing (LS) technique. The Linear smoothed (LS) scheme [3] ameliorates linear and quadratic approximations over convex polytopes by employing a three-point integration scheme (LS-3n).

In this paper, we present a new one-point quadrature rule over arbitrary star convex polytopes which can reproduce linear strain. In order to achieve this characteristic, the Taylor's expansion of the stiffness matrix and the strain-displacement matrix is employed around the center of the element. The modified derivatives are calculated at the geometric center of each element and a conventional assembly procedure is adopted to calculate the stiffness matrix. The robustness, the accuracy and the convergence properties are studied with a few benchmark problems in elastostatics. The Wachspress basis functions are employed in this formulation which overlays a limitation on using strictly convex polytopes but the proposed approach of quadrature technique can be used for arbitrary polytopes using appropriate basis functions.

2. Linear Smoothing (LS)

Within the SFEM framework, the discrete modified strain field $\widetilde{\varepsilon}_{ij}^h$ that yields the modified strain-displacement matrix \widetilde{B} which is then used to build the stiffness matrix is related to the compatible strain field ε^h by :

$$\widetilde{\varepsilon}_{ij}^h(x) = \int_{\Omega_c^h} \varepsilon^h(x) q(x) dV \quad (1)$$

where $q(x)$ is the smoothing function. On writing Eq. (1) at the basis functions derivative level and invoking Gauss-Ostrogradsky theorem, we get:

$$\int_{\Omega_c^h} \phi_{l,x} q(x) dV = \int_{\Gamma_c^h} \phi_l q(x) n_j dS - \int_{\Omega_c^h} \phi_l q_{,x}(x) dV \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_l is the Wachspress basis functions and n_j is the outward normal to the boundaries. In the proposed method the $q(x) = \{1, x, y\}$ in two dimensions and $q(x) = \{1, x, y, z\}$ in three dimensions.

3. Results and Discussion

The three dimensional L-shaped quarter model as shown in Figure 1 is discretized with arbitrary polytopes as shown in Figure 2. From Figure 3, we infer that the strain energy convergence to the reference solution for both the method. Also an optimal convergence rate in strain energy can be seen in figure 3 for the proposed method. The equivalent von-Mises stress distribution obtained is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 1. L-shaped quarter model: Geometry and boundary conditions.

Figure 2. L-shaped quarter model: Sample mesh with 320 elements.

Figure 3. Convergence and convergence rate of the strain energy with mesh refinement.

Figure 4. Equivalent von-Mises stress distribution.

4. References

- [1] Chen JS, Wu CT, Yoon S and You Y, 2001, A stabilized conforming nodal integration for Galerkin mesh free methods, *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 50, 435-466.
- [2] Natarajan S, Ooi ET, Chiong I, Song C, 2014, Convergence and accuracy of displacement based finite element formulations over arbitrary polygons: Laplace interpolants, strain smoothing and scaled boundary polygon formulation. *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, 85, 101-122.
- [3] Francis A, Bernardin AO, Bordas SPA, Natarajan S, 2017, Linear smoothed polygonal and polyhedral finite elements, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 109(9), 1263-1288.

Corrected and Stable eXtended Finite Element Method for Hyperelastic Materials

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Abstract

This paper presents Corrected eXtended Finite Element Method (CXFEM) and Stable eXtended Finite Element Method (SXFEM) for hyperelastic materials. As hyperelastic material include both material and geometric nonlinearities, Total Lagrangian formulation is combined with CXFEM and SXFEM. To enable the adaptive meshing, quadtree mesh is implemented.

1. Introduction

eXtended Finite Element method (XFEM) is well established method to solve the solid mechanics problem having a non-smooth solution in linear regime. The best advantage of XFEM is that mesh can be independent of the morphology of the discontinuity. In XFEM, standard FEM approximation is augmented by the enriched part of approximation. This enriched part is governed by enrichment function. Enrichment function captures the jump in displacement or its derivative and allows the discontinuity to pass through the element. Basically through this enrichment function we try to induce the analytical information of the solution which is priori known. As this enrichment is localized, the transition elements between standard and enriched elements stay partially enriched and do not satisfy the partition of unity property. This issue is called as blending issue and it causes the loss of accuracy and convergence. To alleviate the blending issue Fries [1] gave Corrected eXtended Finite Element method (CXFEM) by modifying the enrichment function. Modified enrichment function is produced by multiplying the standard enrichment function such that it varies linearly on blending elements. One more variant of XFEM, Stable eXtended Finite Element method (SXFEM) is proposed by Babuška & Banerjee [2]. Stable XFEM also uses the different enrichment function.

Hyperelastic materials can handle large deformation and large strain, in addition to that most of the hyperelastic material models are nonlinear. The problem involving hyperelastic material should be solved by nonlinear finite element method.

In this paper, we present the CXFEM and SXFEM for hyperelastic materials with uniform mesh and quadtree mesh. We used the Total Lagrangian formulation with XFEM. Quadtree meshing technique is highly celebrated meshing technique for adaptive meshing. To handle the elements with hanging nodes considering them as the polygons, polygonal shape functions are used [3].

2. Numerical Section

Weak form of the Total Lagrangian formulation is given by,

$$\int_{V^0} \mathbf{E}^T \mathbf{S} dV^0 - \int_{V^0} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b}_0 dV^0 - \int_{S^0} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{t}_0 dS^0 = 0 \quad (1)$$

Displacement field is approximated by

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i(\mathbf{X}) \mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j=1}^m N_j(\mathbf{X}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{X}) \mathbf{a}_j(t) \quad (2)$$

where enrichment function for CXFEM is: $\varphi_{CXFEM}(\mathbf{X}) = R(\mathbf{X}) \varphi_{XFEM}(\mathbf{X})$

and that for SXFEM is: $\varphi_{SXFEM}(\mathbf{X}) = \varphi_{XFEM}(\mathbf{X}) - \sum_i N_i(\mathbf{X}) \varphi_{XFEM}(\mathbf{X}_i)$

3. Results and Discussion

A circular inclusion at the center of the square plate of length is taken as the domain under consideration. Boundary conditions are as shown in Figure 1 is applied. Matrix and inclusion both are considered as compressible Neo-Hookean material. Results are compared with Abaqus using very fine mesh. Relative displacement error and the relative Cauchy stress error in the L_2 norm are compared as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively. It can be

inferred that the corrected XFEM and the stable XFEM yields optimal results and that stable XFEM is slightly accurate than the corrected XFEM.

Figure 1. The problem domain.

Figure 2. L_2 norm displacement error comparison.

Figure 3. L_2 norm Cauchy stress error comparison.

4. Summary

CXFEM and SXFEM are compared for hyperelastic materials using uniform and quadtree mesh. L_2 norm for both displacement and Cauchy stress is shown for comparison. From the plot we can say that SXFEM outperforms the CXFEM, but the difference between them becomes smaller with refinement. Also using proper discretization criteria, we can get better results through quadtree meshing.

5. Reference

- [1] Fries, T. P. (2008). A corrected XFEM approximation without problems in blending elements. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 75(5), 503–532.
- [2] Babuška, I., & Banerjee, U. (2012). Stable Generalized Finite Element Method (SGFEM). *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 201, 91–111.
- [3] Tabarraei, A., & Sukumar, N. (2005). Adaptive computations on conforming quadtree meshes. *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design* 41(7–8), 686–702.

Stress Diffusion Interactions in an Isotropic Elastic Medium: Effect of External Loading

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Abstract

In this paper, the effect of loading conditions and the presence of geometric discontinuities on the stress and concentration distribution in an isotropic medium are investigated. A fully coupled chemo-mechanical framework, wherein the stress depends on the local concentration and the flux on the gradient of the hydrostatic stress, is employed. The resulting transient, non-linear coupled differential equations are solved using Galerkin framework. Two different loading conditions are studied: (a) linear pull and dwell loading (LPDL); and (b) equivalent step loading (ESL). From the detailed numerical study, it is observed that the dwell time has a significant influence on the distribution of the concentration, which in turn influences the critical stress locations.

1. Introduction

The presence of diffusion species, either as an external gas or resulting from electrochemical reactions, lead to the severe degradation in the material properties and failure [1]. These interaction behaviors depend on several factors such as geometric feature of the particle, operations and the presence of geometric discontinuities [2]. However, the effect of different loading in the presence of geometric discontinuities is still unexplored. In this study, we solve the fully coupled chemo-mechanical interactions using FEniCS software to investigate the effect of loading in the presence of geometric discontinuities. We have also investigated the coupled phenomena between stress and diffusion i.e., the competition between the evolved stresses and diffusion of the species. This viewpoint is especially important in elucidating the mechanics of stress-diffusion interactions in the presence of geometric discontinuities.

2. Numerical Formulation and Model

The coupled stress-diffusion interactions in the absence of body force are defined by:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \quad (1) \quad \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \text{ in } \Omega, \quad (2)$$

subjected to the boundary conditions:

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_u, \quad c = \bar{c} \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_c, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_t, \quad \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{J}} \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_J \quad (3)$$

and constitutive relations:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = C \left(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - [c - c_o] \frac{\bar{\Omega}}{3} \mathbf{I} \right), \quad \mathbf{J} = -D \left[\nabla c - \frac{\bar{\Omega}}{RT} c \nabla \sigma_h \right] \quad (3)$$

To study the stress diffusion interactions, a model boundary value problem is chosen as shown in Figure 1a. The influence of these interactions is reported at points A, B, C, D, E and F, when the system is subjected to the loading conditions as shown in Figure 1b.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the concentration with respect to time for same pulling and dwell time ($\bar{t}_p = \bar{t}_d$). During the pull, the system is elongating in the direction of applied displacement under the continuous inflow of the species to the system from the left edge. For the pure elasticity problem, upon pulling in the x-direction, points C and D is found to be in tensile state of stress whereas points E and F are in compressive state of stress. But in contrast, for the chemo-mechanical problem, points E and F are in tensile state of stress and points C and D are in compressive state of stress initially. Regions of tensile stresses experience a concentration influx while

compressive regions experience concentration outflux. This allows concentration to build up more at points E and F than points C and D initially. It is observed that the drop in the hydrostatic stress gradient is more dominant than the concentration gradient. Hence the reason for observation in decrease of the concentration level. On the other hand, at points C and D hydrostatic stress gradient increases after the initial slump and concentration gradient decreases with continuous pulling, resulting in a gradual increase in the concentration level after the initial slump.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic representation of the geometry and boundary conditions of plane strain domain with geometric discontinuities; (b) Loading history.

Figure 2. Concentration evolution as a function of normalized time for (a) linear pull and dwell loading (LPDL); and (b) equivalent step loading (ESL).

4. References

- [1] Oriani, R.A., 1972. A mechanistic theory of hydrogen embrittlement of steels. *Berichte der Bunsengesellschaft für physikalische Chemie*, 76(8), pp.848-857.
- [2] Swaminathan, N., Balakrishnan, S. and George, K., 2016. Elasticity and size effects on the electrochemical response of a graphite, Li-ion battery electrode particle. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 163(3), pp.A488-A498.

Evaluation of Fracture Parameters by Coupling the Edge Based Smoothed Finite Element Method and the Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method

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Abstract

This paper presents a technique to evaluate the fracture parameters by combining the edge based smoothed finite element method (ESFEM) and the scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM). A semi-analytical solution is sought in the region close to the vicinity of the crack tip using the SBFEM, whilst, the ESFEM is used for the rest of the domain. As both the methods satisfy the partition of unity and the compatibility condition, the stiffness matrices obtained from both the methods can be assembled as in the conventional finite element method. Crack propagation study is carried out with minimal remeshing locally to show the robustness of the proposed technique.

1. Introduction

In fracture mechanics, analysis of cracked bodies includes evaluating the stress intensity factors (SIFs) which characterize the near crack-tip stress field. Though analytical solutions are available to evaluate the SIFs for several cases, when it comes to unconventional geometries, numerical methods are the only choice. Several methods have been developed such as the finite element method (FEM), the boundary element method (BEM), the extended finite element method (XFEM), meshfree methods, the scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM), the smoothed finite element method (SFEM) and the iso-geometric analysis (IGA). In the lot, the SFEM is a versatile method which was introduced to the FEM framework by Liu et al. [1] after being successfully used with meshfree methods. The method eliminates the requirements of the derivatives. Here we propose to use the SFEM which is found to be advantageous compared with the regular FEM. In particular, we use the edge based smoothed finite element method (ESFEM) which has been shown to be superior both in terms of accuracy and convergence than the conventional FEM [2]. However, in order to better capture the solution in the singular region we propose to use the SBFEM which was proved to better capture singularity near the crack tip by Song and Wolf [3].

2. Coupling of the ESFEM and the SBFEM

Figure 1. Smoothing domain: (a) Default domain when the ESFEM is used; (b) current case.

The effect of the singularity is limited only to a small region around the crack tip, hence, it is sufficient to treat this small region via the SBFEM. In the present study triangular meshes are used since they can be easily generated even for complex structures. Triangular meshes are also less accurate due to the low order of approximation of the field. Hence, we use the ESFEM over triangular meshes which has been shown to be more accurate than the other SFEM techniques. It can be seen in Figure 1a that the support domain for the edges along the SBFEM domain boundary partly overlaps with the SBFEM domain. Hence, care should be taken in evaluating the gradients in the ESFEM. Only the domain shown in Figure 1b should be considered as contributing to the stiffness matrix computed via the ESFEM. The stiffness matrix of the SBFEM domain is computed based on the linear boundary elements and

the ESFEM is used elsewhere. The stiffness matrices are then assembled as per the corresponding degrees of freedom indices and solved for the unknown displacements.

3. Numerical Section

To show the efficiency and the robustness of the technique proposed, a plate with an edge crack under mixed mode loading condition is chosen. The geometry and the loading conditions of the domain are as shown in Figure 2. The crack propagation for the problem is simulated with the proposed technique. The domain is discretized with three node triangular elements. In the vicinity of the crack tip, a square domain is identified from the base mesh. The stiffness matrices of the triangular elements are computed by using the ESFEM and the stiffness matrix of the square domain is computed by using the SBFEM. The maximum circumferential stress criterion is used to predict the crack propagation angle. The crack incremental length is chosen as 0.5. After the crack kinks, the domain is discretized again and a square SBFEM domain is identified from the new mesh such that it aligns to the crack tip. The length of the SBFEM domain is taken as twice the crack incremental length and the scaling center is chosen at the crack-tip. To obtain the crack path, the scaling center corresponding to each incremental step of the SBFEM domain is chosen and plotted. Figure 2 shows the crack path obtained from the proposed technique with 7 incremental steps. It is observed that the crack path from the present technique is consistent with that reported by Rao and Rahman [4].

Figure 2. Edge crack under mixed mode and crack propagation with present technique.

4. Summary

A technique to evaluate the fracture parameters combining the ESFEM and the SBFEM is discussed. The presented technique doesn't require any knowledge of asymptotic behavior near crack-tip fields a priori. Crack propagation is carried out to study the versatility of the proposed method. The predicted crack trajectories agree well with that reported in literature.

5. References

- [1] Liu GR, Dai KY, Nguyen TT, 2007, A smoothed finite element method for mechanics problems, *Computational Mechanics*, 39(6), 859-877.
- [2] Liu GR, Nguyen TT, Lam KY, 2009, An edge-based smoothed finite element method (es-fem) for static, free and forced vibration analysis of solids. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 320(4), 1100-1130.
- [3] Song C, Wolf JP, 1997, The scaled boundary finite-element method-alias consistent infinitesimal finite-element cell method-elastodynamics, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.*, 147(3-4), 329-355.
- [4] Rao BN and Rahman S, 2001, A coupled meshless-finite element method for fracture analysis of cracks, *International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping*, 78, 647-657.

Isogeometric Analysis for Acoustic Scattering

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Abstract

In this paper the performance of Isogeometric analysis with Finite Element Method is compared. The domain is truncated using the absorbing boundary condition. The comparison is based on the L2 error for higher order basis functions. The pollution error for increasing wave numbers is studied for both these methods.

1. Introduction

The wave propagation phenomena can be modelled using the Helmholtz equation. The solution to this equation becomes tedious when the solution is desired on a complex geometry. The solution to the wave equations using Finite Element Method (FEM) suffers from inaccuracies due to the presence of dispersion and the dissipation effects; this becomes more prominent with the increasing wave numbers. To capture this effect, the high mesh requirement is needed [1]. The use of higher order polynomials in FEM results in higher oscillations. These shortcomings of the FEM can be overcome by the Isogeometric analysis (IGA) which employs the Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines (NURBS) to exactly represent the geometry and the field variables. Refinement in the IGA can be performed analogous to the FEM, while maintaining higher continuity across the elements. Apart from possessing higher order continuity across the elements, the IGA has other desirable properties like homogeneity, non-negativity and compact support. The refinement of the geometry in the IGA can be performed without altering the exact geometry and also the oscillations occurring at the higher polynomial orders can be eliminated due to the non-negativity properties of the NURBS [2]. The problems in case of exterior scattering are of unbounded nature, to obtain a finite computation domain the domain is truncated using the fictitious boundary conditions. Absorbing Boundary Condition (ABC) [3] is one of the most commonly used artificial boundary condition. The aim of this paper is to present the comparison between the Isogeometric analysis and FEM for higher wave numbers.

2. Numerical Section

The Duct domain is shown in the Figure 1. Equation (1) is solved for acoustic pressure p subjected to the boundary condition as shown in the Eqs. (2)-(4). Equation (3) represents the absorbing boundary condition at the outlet, Eq. (4) is a rigid boundary condition on the walls of the duct, where m denotes the mode number, n denotes the outward normal and k is the wave number.

$$\Delta p + k^2 p = 0 \text{ in } \Omega_b \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = \cos(m\pi y) \text{ on } x=0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial n} + ikp = 0 \text{ on } x=2 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = 0 \text{ on } y=0 \text{ and } y=1 \quad (4)$$

The exact solution of the above problem can be given as Eq. (5). The calculation of k_x and the constants A_1 and A_2 are shown in the Eqs. (6) and (7), respectively.

$$p_{exact}(x, y) = \cos(m\pi y)(A_1 e^{-ik_x x} + A_2 e^{ik_x x}) \quad (5)$$

$$k_x = \sqrt{(k^2 - (m\pi)^2)} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} k_x & -k_x \\ (k - k_x)e^{-2ik_x} & (k + k_x)e^{2ik_x} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -i \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The cut off frequency is given as $m_{\text{cut-off}} = \frac{k}{\pi}$. If the mode m is such that, it is less or equal to the cut off frequency then it represents propagating wave and for the case when m is greater than cut off frequency it represents evanescent wave. The L_2 errors with respect wave numbers for $m=2$ are shown in Figure 2. The result shows that in case of IGA the error does not depend on the wavenumber.

Figure 1. The Duct Domain.

Figure 2. Evolution of L_2 norm with respect to the wave number.

3. Summary

The pollution error is evaluated for IGA and FEM for different frequencies. It is seen that the error does not increase with the increasing the wavenumbers in case of IGA.

4. References

- [1] M. Dinachandra, Sethuraman Raju, Plane wave enriched Partition of Unity Isogeometric Analysis (PUIGA) for 2D-Helmholtz problems, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 335 (2018), pp. 380-402.
- [2] Hughes T., Cottrell J., Bazilevs Y, Isogeometric analysis: CAD, finite elements, NURBS, exact geometry and mesh refinement, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 194 (39–41) (2005), pp. 4135-4195.
- [3] Bjorn Engquist, Andrew Majda, Absorbing Boundary Conditions for the Numerical Simulation of Waves, *Mathematics of Computation*, Vol. 31, No. 139 (Jul., 1977), pp. 629-651.

Stochastic Scaled Boundary Finite Elements for Equations with Uncertain Material Parameters

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Abstract

This paper addresses the problem of quantifying the stochastic structural response of an engineering structure under the influence of stochastic material properties using the Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method (SBFEM). The discretization and the representation of the random material fields are accomplished through the Karhunen-Love (KL) expansion using only the major Eigen pairs of the covariance function extracted using the conventional Galerkin approach. The solution domain is discretized with arbitrary polygons. Instead of projecting the non-homogeneous material property from the stochastic domain first to the element nodes of solution domain and then to the Gauss quadrature points, our approach is to fit the Eigen function directly at the Gauss quadrature points. Using such an approach, the issue of coupling the information between the solution and the stochastic domain subjected to different meshing criteria could be seamlessly addressed. The proposed concept is applied to the study of stochastic structural response of a Cooks membrane under shear loading with spatially varying random material properties. The computational cost savings using our proposed concept when compared against the conventional finite elements and Monte Carlo simulations are also highlighted.

1. Introduction

Computational stochastic mechanics have drawn considerable attentions in engineering practice as it is expected to efficiently reflect the inevitable features of uncertainty in structures. In real engineering applications, the random variations of structural parameters are more appropriate to be simulated as continuous random fields if their randomness in space domain is considered to be smooth fluctuations. This consideration led to the development of ad hoc numerical methods techniques that could efficiently deal with the stochastic partial differential equations (PDEs) wherein uncertainty parameters in terms of stochastic input data vary spatially. However, it is worth to be noted that there still doesn't exist any proficient strategy based on these techniques to handle random-field uncertainties for the stress singularity problems, as a fine mesh is required around the stress singular point. Scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM) is a semi-analytical algorithm, mostly used in structural algorithm, which discretizes only the boundary of domain to be analysed without the need of fundamental solutions. Such features make SBFEM much useful for problems pertaining to stress singularity or unbounded media. This method was initially proposed by Song and Wolf. For simple domains, a single SBFEM element would be sufficient enough to capture the structural response, with meshing done only along the boundary of analyzed domain. However, for complex geometries, the interior may need to be discretized into further sub-domains so as to satisfy the scaling requirements. In SBFEM, the stress singularities at crack tips are analytically represented, so that accurate stress intensity factor (SIFs) can be determined. In recent years, though many researchers have been focusing on structural response studies using SBFEM technique with deterministic input parameters, very limited work exist in literature that deals with stochastic SBFEM studies. In real structures, many input parameters such as material properties, loads and geometry of the domain exhibits certain degree of uncertainty. Hence, it is pertinent for structural analysis and design that one identifies and quantifies these uncertainties in input parameters and study its effects on the stochastic structural response of the domain.

In this work, the scaled boundary finite element method is used to address the problem of quantifying the stochastic structural response of 2D plate with a hole under plane stress under the influence of stochastic material properties in the form of random material Young's modulus. The discretization and the representation of the random material fields is accomplished through Karhunen-Loeve (KL) expansion technique using conventional Galerkin approach. The solution domain is solved using SBFEM. In order to capture the eigenfunction representation within a subdomain, we use the technique developed by Irene Chiong, wherein the eigenfunctions are locally represented in each sub-domain by a polynomial surface in Cartesian coordinates. The coefficients of polynomial surface fit are determined by using a least square fit over each sub-domain. The location used to fit the surface are chosen

to be the Gaussian/ Gauss-Lobatto integration points. Such an approximation is made under the assumptions that the sizes of the sub-domains remain sufficiently small and the order of polynomial surface fit should be sufficiently large to accurately represent the randomness in material fluctuations. The fit used doesn't affect the properties of SBFEM. The perturbation in the stiffness matrix for each KL term is computed from the corresponding fit of eigenfunctions corresponding to each KL term. Meanwhile Polynomial Chaos expansion is used to represent the stochastic nodal displacement, as its covariance function is not known apriori. Following section details the implementation of the above method to study the stochastic structural response of a 2D plate with a hole under tensile loading in plane stress conditions, with Young's modulus being modelled as a random variable.

2. Numerical Example

Figure 1a shows the schematic of a Cooks membrane. The mean value of Young's modulus is taken to be 20000 with an exponential correlation function having a correlation length of 50 units and coefficient of variation (defined as the ratio of standard deviation to mean) in the range of 5% to 30%. Poisson ratio is 0.3. A shear traction, q of 10 units is applied at the right end. The KL terms of 5 was found to be sufficient enough to represent the random field while the maximum order of Hermite polynomials (optimal stochastic basis functions for Gaussian random variable) is taken to be 2.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of Cooks membrane; (b) Covariance of stochastic output displacement at the top rightmost point against the input CoV values.

Figure 1b plots the covariance of stochastic displacements at the top rightmost node for both X and Y displacements against the input variance of Young's modulus. Moreover, an excellent agreement between the mean and standard deviation of stochastic displacements obtained using our stochastic SBFEM formulation with Monte Carlo simulations using a sample size of 10,000, accurate to the 3rd decimal place.

3. References

- [1] Do, D.M., Gao, W., Saputra, A.A., Song, C. and Leong, C.H., 2017. The stochastic Galerkin scaled boundary finite element method on random domain. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 110(3), pp.248-278.
- [2] Long, X.Y., Jiang, C., Han, X. and Gao, W., 2015. Stochastic response analysis of the scaled boundary finite element method and application to probabilistic fracture mechanics. *Computers & Structures*, 153, pp.185-200.
- [3] Long, X.Y., Jiang, C., Yang, C., Han, X., Gao, W. and Liu, J., 2016. A stochastic scaled boundary finite element method. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 308, pp.23-46.
- [4] Long, X.Y., Jiang, C., Han, X., Gao, W. and Zhang, D.Q., 2015. Stochastic fracture analysis of cracked structures with random field property using the scaled boundary finite element method. *International Journal of Fracture*, 195(1-2), pp.1-14.

Computational Analysis of a Low Head Francis Turbine Draft Tube for Varying Load Conditions

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Abstract

Flow pattern in draft tube of a reaction turbine plays a very important role in overall performance of the turbine. In present work, a thorough analysis of draft tube of a mixed flow Francis turbine is performed computationally by using Ansys CFX. For the analysis, complete assembly of the turbine consisting spiral casing, stay vanes, guide vanes, runner and draft tube is considered. Performance of the draft tube is evaluated for varying load conditions as partial loads of 60 % and 80 %, full load and overload of 120%. It is observed that draft tube efficiency is maximum at full load condition. At part load of 60 %, draft tube swirl is found maximum. For validation purpose, efficiency of the turbine is computed for different loads and compared with experimentally calculated values. A fair agreement between the two is observed.

1. Introduction

Draft tube is an integral part of a reaction turbine which recovers pressure from kinetic energy of the high velocity fluid coming out from runner and allows the turbine to be set above the tail race. Thus the main function of the draft tube is to minimize kinetic energy loss at runner exit and setting the turbine at a certain height above the tail race. The purpose of providing draft tube is fulfilled without any loss of net available head as a vacuum pressure is maintained at runner exit. It is clearly understood from the functioning of draft tube that it makes the turbine more susceptible for cavitation. So, designing a draft tube is a critical job as it affects the overall performance to a great extent [1-4]. Moreover, functioning of draft tube is extensively dependent on the flow pattern coming out from runner exit which further depends upon the regime of operation. This work is an attempt to find the performance of draft tube of a 48m head horizontal axis mixed flow Francis turbine at different load conditions. Efficiency and loss values for draft tube have been calculated.

2. Model Specifications

In the present work a conical draft tube is considered. Its specification is clearly shown in Table 1. For the Analysis a complete assembly of the Francis turbine is considered which consists of a spiral casing, 18 stay vanes, 18 guide vanes, runner with 13 blades and a draft tube. Below Figure 1 shows the draft tube model with its grid.

Table 1. Draft Tube specification.

Sr. no.	Attribute	Value
1	Inlet diameter	1.0198m
2	Outlet diameter	2.47m
3	Divergence angle	8.51°
4	Height	4.36m
5	Bend Angle	90°

Figure 1. Draft tube.

3. Results

For validation, performance of the Francis turbine is evaluated at full load, part load of 60% and 80 % and over load operation of 120%. A very close resemblance is found between experimental and computational results (Figure 2).

Net available head across the turbine is found 53.3m for full load operation. At this regime, head loss in draft tube is calculated as 1.26m (2.366%). Finally, the draft tube efficiency is determined as 75.8 % for 100% load.

Figure 2. Comparison of experimental and computational results.

Figure 3. Pressure contour and velocity streamlines at 100% load.

4. Summary

It is found that the performance of the draft tube is maximum at full load operation with minimum swirl. The efficiency of the draft tube is calculated as 75.8% at BEP. There is no vortex rope seen for full load operation. At part load operation (60 % load), draft tube losses are found maximum with minimum pressure recovery. It is clearly observed that the pressure distribution in draft tube is more uniform for full load operation than other regimes of operation.

5. References

- [1] McNabb J, Devals C, Kyriacou S A, Murry N, Mullins B F, 2014, CFD based draft tube hydraulic design optimization, IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science 22 (2014) 012023.
- [2] Tian Xiaoqing, Pan Huachen, Hong Shuli, Zheng Yuan, 2015, Improvement of hydro-turbine draft tube efficiency using vortex generator, Advances in Mechanical Engineering, Vol. 7(7) 1–8.
- [3] Dyke SJ, Spencer BF Jr., Sain MK, Carlson JD, 1996, Seismic response reduction using mangetorhelogical dampers, Proceedings of IFAC World Congress, San Franscisco, California, June 30 – July 5.
- [4] Lewis FL, Syrmos VL, 1995, Optimal Control, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 359-370.

Effect of Twisted Tape on Bend Erosion

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Abstract

Erosion is a severe problem for the different types of industries such as thermal power plant and oil refineries. In the present work, the twisted tape is inserted in the upstream of the pipe at different axial locations using commercial CFD software ANSYS- FLUENT. The effect of average particle size and inlet velocity on the erosion behavior for all different locations of twisted tape have been investigated. It is found that due to the twisted tape, the swirling motion occurs in the upstream of the pipe which reduces the maximum penetration ratio in the elbow and consequently reduces the erosion rate in the elbow.

Keywords: Standard elbow, twisted tape, elbow erosion.

1. Introduction

Erosion is defined as the impact of erodent particles on the solid surface caused by the removal of mass from the solid surface [1]. Slurry transportation through pipelines is one of the modern technology to transport the great amount of slurry over a long distance [2]. A number of ways such as insertion of a twisted tape or a spiral wire inside the pipe at the upstream of the bend, can be employed to reduce the bend erosion due to solid particles [3]. The twisted tape is used to minimize the erosion rate in pipelines and it is also reported that due to the twisted tape [4]. The present work emphasizes on the reduction of the erosion rate by the insertion of twisted tape at different positions from the inlet of the elbow. Validation of the computational results in the form of penetration ratios is done with the results of Santos et.al. [5] for the standard elbow.

2. Modelling of Geometry

2.1. Geometrical Configuration of Bend Pipe with Twisted Tape

Table 1. Geometry Specifications.

Pipe diameter(d)	25.4 mm	Twisted tape thickness	25.4 mm
Inlet pipe length	1220 mm	Twisted tape length	76.2 mm
Outlet pipe length	101.6 mm	Tape twisted angle	180°
Elbow curvature & bend angle angle	38.1 mm & 90°	Twisted tape position from elbow	0d, 1d, 2d, 3d

Figure 1. Standard pipe; Figure 2. Twisted tape in inlet pipe; Figure 3. Twisted tape at inlet of bend pipe; Figure 4. Meshing of geometry.

2.2. Mesh Generation

Table 2. Detail of Meshing.

Grid type	Structured grid	Element size	1.00 mm
Nodes	1371774	Min. skewness	0.008
Elements	1314862	Max. skewness	0.554

2.3. Boundary Conditions

Table 3. Parameters used for CFD simulations.

Pipe material	Aluminum (6061-T6)	Inlet velocity	34.10 m/s
Fluid	Air	Avg. particle size	182 μm (mean dia.)
Erodent particle	Silica sand	Outlet pressure	Atm. gauge pressure
Turbulent model	Standard k- ϵ turbulence	Erosion model	Discrete phase model(DPM)

3. Results and Discussion

Figures 5 and 6 show that the erosion rate in the standard elbow is reduced with the twisted tape inserted in the inlet pipe. The erosion rate is found to be maximum at 0d upstream of elbow and minimum erosion rate is found to be at 3d upstream of elbow. Figure 7 shows that the erosion rate in the elbow with twisted tape is lower than that of the standard elbow.

Figure 5. Erosion rate for standard elbows.

Figure 6. Erosion rate for twisted tape inserts at 0d.

Figure 7. Erosion rate variation of standard bend with twisted tape inserted in bend pipe.

4. Summary

concludes that the insertion of twisted tape helps in reducing the erosion rate. It is also observed that the farther the tape is placed, upto 3d, from the inlet of the bend the better the results are. Placing the tape farther than 3d yields no improvement in reduction of erosion rate.

5. References

- [1] Baker, P.J. and Jaobs, B.E.A., A guide to slurry pipeline systems, BHRA, Fluid Engineering, 1979.
- [2] Avi Uzi, Yaron Ben Ami, Avi Levy, Erosion prediction of industrial conveying pipelines, Powder Technology 309 (2017) 49–60.
- [3] D. Mills, Pneumatic Conveying Design Guide, Butterworth-Heinemann, 2003.
- [4] R. Wood, T. Jones, N. Miles, J. Ganeshalingam, Upstream swirl-induction for reduction of erosion damage from slurries in pipeline bends, Wear 250 (1–12) (2001) 770–778,
- [5] Vinicius Fagundes dos Santos, Francisco José de Souza, Carlos Antonio Ribeiro Duarte, Reducing bend erosion by inserted of twisted tape in elbows, Powder Technology 301 (2016) 889–910.

Selection of Suitable Mesh for Simulation of a Trapezoidal Microchannel Heat Sink with Different Fluids

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Abstract

In the present work, numerical simulations are carried out to estimate flow behavior and heat transfer performance of trapezoidal microchannel heat sink using three meshes viz. hexahedral mapped mesh, tetrahedral mesh with hexahedral elements in fluid domain and a pure tetrahedral mesh. The study aims to figure out the suitable mesh to carry out further simulations. Simulations are carried out using distilled and deionized water as working fluids. Grid independence is carried out for the meshes and are used to carry out the simulations. It is observed that deionized water shows a better heat transfer performance compared to distilled water but suffers a higher pressure drop.

1. Introduction

Cutting edge research in the development and use of micro-devices in many applications such as MEMS, lab-on-chip, etc. is encountering the problem of effective removal of high heat flux from them. Non-effective cooling in these devices can lead to formation of hot-spots and may jeopardize the reliability of device operation. Microchannels owing to their large surface area to volume ratio, less working fluid demand have been effective in removal of high heat fluxes from these devices in the past. The use of various heat transfer fluids for increasing effectiveness of heat removal through micro-channels has been one of pioneering works in the past. Still many improvements like modification of geometry or use of a suitable working fluid in micro-channels can be carried out for enhanced heat transfer characteristics. This work aims to study the heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics of a trapezoidal microchannel using distilled water and deionized water.

2. General Specifications

The geometry of trapezoidal microchannel made up of copper having hydraulic diameter 0.315 mm is modelled on Solid-works. Length of micro-channel is 44.8mm. ICEM CFD is employed for meshing the prepared model. Three types of meshes are utilized to analyze the heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics. The first mesh is hexahedral mapped mesh, while second is tetrahedral mesh with hexa-core for fluid domain and the third one is a pure tetrahedral mesh. FLUENT is employed for solving the governing equations. This work focusses on single phase laminar flow of working fluid through the microchannel. Inlet velocity is given as a boundary condition at the microchannel inlet which decides the flow Reynolds number and mass flow-rate. Pressure outlet condition of zero-gauge pressure is specified at the microchannel outlet. No-slip condition is deployed at the micro-channel walls. A constant heat flux condition of 100 W/cm² is given at the base of the copper block which mimics the heat flux from electronic device, with all other walls of the block being adiabatic.

A pressure based solver is selected to solve the flow equations using the semi-implicit method for pressure linked equations (SIMPLE) algorithm for pressure velocity coupling. Second order discretization scheme was employed for pressure equation whereas momentum and energy equations were discretized using second order upwind scheme. Absolute convergence criterion for the residuals of the continuity, momentum equations was set below 10⁻⁴ and for energy equation it was set below 10⁻⁷. The minimum quality obtained for the pure tetrahedral mesh is very less and hence the mesh is discarded. Grid independency test is carried out on the remaining cases to ensure an effective mesh for further simulations.

Grid independence is obtained at 30 lakh nodes (approximate) for hexahedral mapped mesh and 18 lakh nodes (approximate) for tetrahedral mesh with hexa-core. O-grid scheme was tried at the microchannel walls to obtain fine mesh but was discarded due very high aspect ratio (around 10⁴) in the region.

3. Equations

Flow is considered incompressible, laminar and viscous. No-slip is employed at the walls. The influences of radiation and gravity are considered negligible. Both solid and fluid properties are considered constant. The effect of viscous dissipation of fluid flow is considered negligible. Variation of viscosity with temperature is not considered.

The governing equations:

$$\nabla V = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_f V \cdot \nabla V = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\mu \nabla V) \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_f c_{p,f} (V \cdot \nabla T) = k_f \nabla^2 T_f \quad (3)$$

$$k_s \nabla^2 T = 0 \quad (4)$$

The equations used for calculating heat transfer coefficient and Nusselt number are as follows:

$$Re = \rho V_{in} D_h / \mu \quad (5)$$

$$h(x) = q''(x) / (Tw(x) - Tm(x)) \quad (6)$$

$$Nu(x) = h(x) D_h / k_f \quad (7)$$

Where, Tm is Bulk mean temperature, Tw is Wall temperature, q'' heat flux at wall, k_f is Thermal conductivity of working fluid, ρ_f is Density of working fluid, μ is Dynamic Viscosity of working fluid, D_h is Hydraulic diameter of channel, V_{in} is inlet velocity, V is Velocity vector, $c_{p,f}$ is Specific heat capacity of fluid, and k_s is Thermal conductivity of solid.

4. Table

Table 1. Variation of pressure drop in trapezoidal microchannel with Reynolds number.

Reynolds Number	150	400	600	800
Pressure Drop	0.0783977	0.20636	0.31848	0.4420689

5. Summary

Three meshes, hexahedral mapped mesh, tetrahedral mesh with hexahedral elements in fluid domain and a pure tetrahedral mesh are used for simulation of flow and heat transfer characteristics of trapezoidal heat sink. Due to low quality for the pure tetrahedral mesh, grid independency test is done on the remaining meshes. A suitable mesh for further simulations is selected with the help of results obtained. Grid independence is obtained for the meshes. It is observed that deionized water provides better heat transfer performance compared to distilled water but at the expense of higher pressure drop.

6. References

- [1] Wang H., Zhihua Chen, Jianguo Gao, 2016, Influence of geometric parameters on flow and heat transfer performance of micro-channel heat sinks, *Applied Thermal Engineering* 107 (2016) 870–879.
- [2] Andrei G. Fedorov, Raymond Viskanta, 1999, Three-dimensional conjugate heat transfer in the microchannel heat sink for electronic packaging, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 43 (2000) 399–415.
- [3] Amirah M. Sahar, Mehmed R. Özdemir, Ekhlal M. Fayyadh, Jan Wissink, Mohamed M. Mahmoud, Tassos G. Karayiannis, 2015, Single phase flow pressure drop and heat transfer in rectangular metallic microchannels, *Applied Thermal Engineering* 93 (2016) 1324–1336.

Selection of Suitable Mesh for Simulation of a Rectangular Microchannel Heat Sink with Different Fluids

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Abstract

In the present work to estimate flow behavior and heat transfer performance of a rectangular microchannel heat sink, three meshes are employed viz. hexahedral mapped mesh, tetrahedral mesh with hexahedral elements in fluid domain and tetrahedral mesh with hexahedral elements in fluid domain with prism elements at the wall. The study aims to figure out the suitable mesh to carry out further simulations. Distilled and de-ionized water used as working fluids for the simulations. Deionized water shows a better heat transfer performance compared to distilled water at the expense of higher-pressure drop.

1. Introduction

With rapid increase in the development and use of micro devices in many applications such as MEMS, bio-medical, photovoltaics, electronic devices, air conditioning, nuclear, automotive, aerospace and lab on chip related applications, etc. the problem of effective heat removal from these devices has become an alarming issue. Non-effective heat removal from these devices may lead to formation of hot spots at different locations in the device that later on can jeopardize the reliability of device operation. In the past micro-channels have been known for their effective heat removal owing to high surface area to volume ratio, smaller sizes, and less working fluid demand. Channels with hydraulic diameter less than 1 mm referred to be as micro-channels. The present work aims to study the heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics of a rectangular microchannel using various fluids such as distilled water and de-ionized water.

2. General Specification

The geometry of rectangular microchannel made up of copper having hydraulic diameter 86.58 μm [1] is modelled in Pro E. Length of the microchannel is 10 mm. ICEM CFD is employed for meshing the prepared model. Three types of meshes are utilized to analyze the heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics. The first mesh is hexahedral mapped mesh with very fine meshing closer to the wall for accurate prediction of temperature close to the wall [2], while second is tetrahedral mapped mesh with hexa-core for fluid domain and the third one is a tetrahedral mapped mesh with hexa-core for fluid domain and prism elements at the wall. Hexahedral mesh gives better mesh quality and takes less computation time so we choose it for further simulations. After meshing FLUENT is employed for solving the governing equations. This work focusses on single phase laminar flow of working fluid through the microchannel. Inlet velocity of 3.4823 m/s is given as a boundary condition at the microchannel inlet, which decides the flow Reynolds number ($Re=300$) and mass flow-rate. Pressure outlet condition of zero-gauge pressure is specified at the microchannel outlet. No-slip condition is deployed at the micro-channel walls. A pressure based solver is selected to solve the flow equations using the semi-implicit method for pressure linked equations (SIMPLE) algorithm for pressure-velocity coupling. Second order discretization scheme is employed for pressure equation whereas momentum and energy equations were discretized using second order upwind scheme. Grid independency test is carried out for hexahedral mesh to ensure an effective mesh. Mesh with 579025 cells is then chosen to plot graphs and find results.

3. Equations

The major assumptions are:

- a) Steady fluid flow and heat transfer,
- b) Incompressible fluid,
- c) Laminar flow,
- d) Constant viscosity.

Continuity equation for fluid region is

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Momentum equation for fluid region is:

$$\rho_f (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla \vec{v}) = -\nabla P + \mu_f \nabla^2 \vec{v} \quad (2)$$

Energy equation for the fluid region is

$$\rho_f C_{p,f} (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla T) = k_f \nabla^2 T \quad (3)$$

Energy equation for the solid region is

$$k_s \nabla^2 T = 0 \quad (4)$$

The following equation is used to calculate Nusselt number,

$$Nu(x) = \frac{q''(x)d_h}{k_f(T_w(x) - T_m(x))} \quad (5)$$

where d_h is hydraulic diameter, $q''(x)$ is local heat flux, $T_w(x)$ is average temperature at the boundary, $T_m(x)$ is fluid bulk temperature, $Nu(x)$ is Nusselt number, and k_f is thermal conductivity of the fluid.

4. Summary

Three meshes, hexahedral mapped mesh, tetrahedral mesh with hexahedral elements in fluid domain and tetrahedral mesh with hexahedral elements in fluid domain with prism elements at the wall are used for simulation of flow and heat transfer characteristics of rectangular heat sink. Grid independency test is done on all the three meshes. A suitable mesh for further simulations is selected with the help of results obtained. For de-ionized water, average Nusselt number varies from [11.61, 57.08] against distilled water [11.37, 56.72]. Pressure drop obtained is 1.64 atm for distilled water and 1.73 atm for de-ionized water. Thus, De-ionized water provides better heat transfer performance compared to distilled water but at the expense of higher pressure drop.

5. References

- [1] Weilin Q., Mudawar, I., 2002, Analysis of three-dimensional heat transfer in micro-channel heat sinks, Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer, 45, 3973–3985.
- [2] Fedorov, A.G., Viskanta, R., 2000, Three-dimensional conjugate heat transfer in the microchannel heat sink for electronic packaging, Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer, 43, 399–415.

Effect of Inlet Design parameters of a Cyclone Separator on Fluid Dynamics Characteristics

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Abstract

The objective of this project is to design and study the change in fluid characteristics by modifying the inlet shape of a Stairmand's High-Efficiency Cyclone Separator. This paper focuses on the comparison between a normal a Stairmand's High-Efficiency Cyclone Separator and an inlet modified cyclone separator. To compare and validate the results standard data is used from different references. The inlet velocity and flow rate parameters are taken from a standard data and then according to standard geometry model is designed in SOLIDWORKS 2017, Mesh in ICFM CFD 15.0 and simulations are done in ANSYS FLUENT 15.0.

1. Introduction

A cyclonic separation is a method of removing solid particulates from air or gas, without the use of filters, using vortex separation. Cyclone separators are generally used in kitchen ventilation to separate grease from exhaust hoods, Portable vacuum cleaners, production plant exhausts to control air pollution and many more. The basic principle in a cyclone separator is that it separates solid and gaseous particles through two different outlets. The project aims to improve the collection efficiency by modifying the inlet. Solid coal particles of 1-10 μm diameter are separated from the air which is collected at the bottom of the cyclone separator. The main objective of the research was to analyze the change in collection efficiency by altering the inlet of the cyclone separator.

Figure 1. Stairmand high-efficiency model.

2. General Specifications

Stairmand's High-efficiency model as shown in Figure 1 has been chosen and dimensions are calculated based on the relationships given by Stairmand and after modelling pressure plots are simulated in ANSYS Fluent and they are compared with actual results. This is followed by changing the inlet dimensions and to study the change in efficiency. The main motivation of this study is due to the fact that cyclone separator has many industrial applications. This study mainly focusses on the change in efficiency only due to geometric parameters.

3. Equations

Since it is a turbulent flow only two models can accurately predict this behaviour, they are RANS (Reynold's average Navier Stoke) equation and LES (Large eddy simulation). The RSM model calculates all RANS equations and gives accurate results.

$$\rho \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = \rho \bar{f}_i + \frac{\partial \left[-\bar{p} \delta_{ij} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} \right]}{\partial x_j} \quad (1)$$

4. Summary

This project shows the variation of fluid characteristics due to the addition of circular inlet over the standard square inlet of the cyclone separators. This project helps in understanding real-life problems faced in industries due to varying shapes of the inlet.

5. References

- [1] Oliveira, R.A.F., Justi, G.H. and Lopes, G.C., 2017. Grid convergence study of a cyclone separator using different mesh structures. *Chemical Industry & Chemical Engineering Quarterly*, 23(3).
- [2] Khairy Elsayed, 2011. Analysis and Optimization of Cyclone Separators Geometry Using RANS and LES Methodologies, Thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel.
- [3] Ithape, P.K., Barve, S.B., Pande, S.S. and Nadgire, A.R., 2017. Effect of Geometric Parameters on the Performance of Cyclone Separator using CFD. *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology*.

Effect of Slot Area on the Performance of Conical Self-Entraining Ejector Diffuser

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Abstract

Numerical study has been conducted on a conical self-entraining ejector diffuser to establish the flow characteristics with heat transfer and effect of slot area has been investigated. Ejector diffusers are used as exhaust assemblies downstream of gas turbine engines and form an important component for infrared suppression system (IRSS) in helicopters, ships, aircrafts, etc. Their ability to entrain ambient air helps in reducing infrared signature levels. Thus, higher mass entrainment is desirable for suppression of infrared (IR) signature levels which in turn depends on the design of ejector diffuser. Present investigation focuses on slot along the diffuser rather than a step slot. Further effect of slot area on the performance of ejector diffuser is investigated. It has been found that increasing slot area ejector diffuser offers better cumulative mass entrainment compared to a constant slot area and decreasing slot area ejector diffuser. Study also reveals that increasing slot area shows better cooling capabilities and hence a better IRSS device.

1. Introduction

The presence of infrared (IR) energy levels on the defense vehicles acts as a source to heat seeking missiles which make these vehicles extremely vulnerable when operating in enemy lines. There is a need to improve infrared suppression systems (IRSS) against evolving heat seeking missiles. One of the IRSS device is exhaust ejector diffuser whose primary aim is to cool the hot exhaust gases before exiting into environment. The cooling ability of ejector diffuser is critical to escape locking onto heat seeking missile. Further the cooling capability of an ejector diffuser depends upon the geometric and dynamical parameters. Previous studies with focus on mass entrainment have emphasized on diffuser shapes such as conical stepped ejector diffuser [1], rectangular stepped ejector diffuser [2] and oblong stepped ejector diffuser [3]. Most of the studies reported in literature is with a step (sudden increase in area) at the slots but hardly any study has been reported with no step at the slots. The present study attempts to investigate conical ejector diffuser with slots but without step increase and the effect of slot area on the performance.

2. Problem Formulation

The ejector diffuser under investigation is shown in Figure 1. From the nozzle, exhaust jet leaves and enters into the mixing tube and then into the diffuser and then exit into the environment through tailpipe. Using the symmetrical nature of geometry, a 2-dimensional axisymmetric domain has been selected. The dimensions of the domain are defined in terms of nozzle diameter D_{nz} . Values of standoff distance, mixing tube and area ratio between mixing tube to nozzle, diffuser length, diffuser cone angle, diffuser area ratio, plenum size are adopted from literature [1-4]. Current study is conducted at fixed Reynolds number $Re=2 \times 10^5$. Evaluation of the choice of turbulence model and grid convergence studies have been performed using experimental results (conical stepped ejector diffuser) of Sen [1]. Based on these comparisons we find that the performance of the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model is the best in conjunction with a mesh size of 0.9 million cells. Slot area is varied in three ways (i) constant slot area, (ii) increasing slot area and (iii) decreasing slot area as shown in the Table 1. A_0 being area of first slot (same for three cases), Table 1 shows factor values by which area increases or decreases for Case I and Case III.

Figure 1. Schematic of increasing area conical ejector diffuser.

Table 1. Slot area details (A_0 represents area of Slot 1).

Slot area	Slot 1	Slot 2	Slot 3	Slot 4	Slot 5
Increasing slot area (Case I)	A_0	$1.26A_0$	$1.51A_0$	$1.77A_0$	$2.02A_0$
Constant slot area (Case II)	A_0	A_0	A_0	A_0	A_0
Decreasing slot area (Case III)	A_0	$0.87A_0$	$0.75A_0$	$0.62A_0$	$0.49A_0$

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2a shows the cumulative mass entrainment ratio (Φ) for three cases and the presence of variations in Φ for the three cases indicates that change in slot area affects mass entrainment. At the end of Slot 5, Case I shows maximum $\Phi = 4.12$ compared to $\Phi=3.95$ for Case II and $\Phi=3.57$ for Case III. Study of local mass entrainment rate reveals that entrainment through slots increase downstream of the diffuser. The nature of mass entrainment can be explained by static pressure distribution.

Figure 2 (a). Cumulative mass entrainment comparison for three cases.

Figure 2 (b). Temperature variation plot at the exit of diffuser for three cases.

Figure 2b is a plot of normalized temperature variation (Ψ) near the exit of ejector diffuser for three cases. We observe that Case I offers better thermal mixing profile as large annular zones from the wall towards axis has lower Ψ values. Thus Case I is a better IRSS device.

4. Conclusion

Three cases of slotted ejector diffuser were numerical investigated where the slot area was varied while keeping other parameters fixed. It has been found that increasing slot area ejector diffuser offers better cumulative mass entrainment as well as better cooling capabilities.

5. References

- [1] Sen S, 2008, Studies on Flow Characteristics of a Stepped Conical Diffuser with Passive Suction. PhD thesis, Department of Applied Mechanics, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi.
- [2] Singh P, 2009, Studies on Non Circular Stepped Ejector Diffuser, PhD thesis, Department of Applied Mechanics, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi.
- [3] Chen Q, 2008, Performance of air-air ejectors with multi-ring entraining diffusers. PhD thesis, Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, Queen's University.
- [4] Singh L, Singh SN, and Sinha SS, 2017, Effect of standoff distance and area ratio on the performance of circular exhaust ejector using computational fluid dynamics, IMech E Part G: Journal of Aerospace Engineering, page 0954410017717287.

Energy and Second Law Analysis of Shower Cooling Tower with Variation in Inlet Water to Air Mass Flow Ratio for Industrial Application

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Abstract

Hot water is cooled down with the help of conventional cooling tower in industries, the performance of conventional cooling tower decrease due to fouling on the fill surface. To overcome this difficulty, a new type of cooling tower called shower cooling tower (SCT) is designed where fill is removed entirely. The two-dimension (2-D) MATLAB mathematical model is developed and validated with the help of experimental results. From the results, it is cleared that SCT thermal efficiency decrease and SLE of SCT increase with increasing the water to air mass flow ratio (RLG).

1. Introduction

The forced draft parallel flow cooling tower used to remove the heat of hot water when it comes in contact with atmospheric air. The air removes heat by the help of convective and evaporative heat transfer. The working of the conventional cooling tower has deteriorated due to decomposition of salt on the fill of cooling tower. To overcome this problem, a new type of tower called SCT (Figure 1) has been developed which replaced the fill. In SCT small size nozzles disintegrate water into a smaller droplet and increase heat transfer between water and air. Milosavljevic and Heikkilä [1] have studied a mathematical model for a counter flow wet cooling tower and found that exit air temperature is decreased with decreased the inlet air velocity. Ardekani et al. [2] said inlet and outlet water temperature difference for the wind facing sector was about twice that of the peripheral sectors. Kumar and Pant [3] investigated as Reynolds number increase flow pattern changes. Heydarinezhad and Delfani [4] studied that Reynolds number changed with a variation in changes the geometrical and physical perimeters of flow. Reuter [5] have analyzed cooling tower by using FLUENT; he suggested that the performance of a cooling tower can be improved by reducing droplet size. Viljoen [6] studied the performance of cooling tower using FLUENT. He reported the collision of water droplets has no major impact on water distribution pattern in the cooling tower. Hawlader and Liu [7] analyze evaporative cooling tower and said exit water droplet temperature increases with increase the inlet water droplet temperature. Zunaid et al. [8] reported total exergy of air controlled by its convective and evaporative exergy, and evaporative exergy of air are major component present in total exergy of air.

Figure 1. Parallel flow SCT.

2. Experimental Facility, Mathematical Model and Validation

Schematic diagram of downdraft parallel flow SCT used for experimental work is shown in Figure 1. The atmospheric air and hot water come in contact of SCT at the top. The hot water is cooled down when it come in contact of atmospheric air. The cold water collected at the bottom of the tower and hot air expelled into the atmosphere. The detail mathematical model of SCT is given in Zunaid et al. [8]. The experimental data of a parallel flow down draft SCT has been used for validation of 2D MATLAB results. It is noticed that error between experimental and predicted exit water temperature are less than $\pm 10\%$.

3. Effects of Variation in RLG

This study based on the variation of inlet RLG in 2D MATLAB mathematical model from 0.5 to 2.0. Table 1 shows changes in outlet parameters at constant inlet air DBT (36 °C), air relative humidity (65 %), water temperature (56 °C), and droplet diameter (250 µm). Table 1 also shows as RLG increases exit air DBT, air specific humidity and droplet temperature increases because of the mass of water at inlet increases. Maximum and minimum water droplet temperature reduction is 17.11 °C and 10.02 °C which obtained at 0.5 and 2 RLG respectively. The range of SCT decreased by increased RLG hence the thermal efficiency of SCT also decreased simultaneously increased in the RLG. Total exergy of air, exergy of water increased with increase in the RLG because exit air and water droplet temperature and mass of water increased with increased RLG. As the amount of water in RLG increased destruction in exergy of the system along tower height increased because the amount of exergy release by water is more than the amount of exergy gain by air. SLE of SCT increased with increase in the RLG.

Table 1. Effect of variation in inlet RLG.

RLG _{in}	$T_{a,out}$ (°C)	$\omega_{a,out}$ (kg _w /kg _a)	$T_{d,out}$ (°C)	$m_{d,t}$ (kg/s)	η_{th} (%)	$X_{c,out}$ (W)	$X_{e,out}$ (W)	$X_{a,out}$ (W)	$X_{d,out}$ (W)	$X_{t,out}$ (W)	I_t (W)	η_{II} (%)
0.5	38.90	0.044	38.89	0.0023	68.19	1.52	103.72	105.24	3757.68	3862.92	871.33	81.60
1	42.14	0.0543	42.13	0.0035	55.28	8.16	219.75	227.91	7855.08	8082.99	1385.35	85.37
1.25	43.30	0.0583	43.29	0.004	50.66	11.75	273.11	284.86	9969.48	10254.34	1581.03	86.64
1.5	44.27	0.0615	44.26	0.0044	46.79	15.21	322.89	338.10	12114.93	12453.03	1749.38	87.68
2	45.99	0.065	45.98	0.0045	39.94	21.47	412.23	433.70	12898.49	13332.19	1817.03	88.01

4. References

- [1] Milosavljevic, N. and Heikkilä, P., 2001. A comprehensive approach to cooling tower design. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 21(9), pp.899-915.
- [2] Ardekani, M.A., Farhani, F., Mazidi, M. and Ranjbar, M.A., 2014. Study of degradation of dry cooling tower performance under wind conditions and method for tower efficiency enhancement (research note). *International Journal of Engineering-Transactions C: Aspects*, 28(3), p.460.
- [3] Kumar, N. and Pant, A., 2009. A computational approach to the flow of walter's liquid b' through annulus of coaxial porous circular cylinders for high suction parameter (research note). pp.119-124.
- [4] Heydarinezhad, G. and Delfani, S., 2000. Direct numerical simulation of the wake flow behind a cylinder using random vortex method in medium to high Reynolds numbers. pp.33-50.
- [5] Reuter, H.C.R., 2010. Performance evaluation of natural draught cooling towers with anisotropic fills (Doctoral dissertation, Stellenbosch: University of Stellenbosch).
- [6] Viljoen, D.J., 2006. Evaluation and performance prediction of cooling tower spray zones (Doctoral dissertation, Stellenbosch: University of Stellenbosch).
- [7] Hawlader, M.N.A. and Liu, B.M., 2002. Numerical study of the thermal-hydraulic performance of evaporative natural draft cooling towers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 22(1), pp.41-59.
- [8] Zunaid, M., Murtaza, Q. and Gautam, S., 2017. Energy and performance analysis of multi droplets shower cooling tower at different inlet water temperature for air cooling application. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 121, pp.1070-1079.

Linear Stability of a Shear Imposed Falling Film

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Abstract

A linear stability of a gravity-driven thin film flow on an inclined plane is studied in the presence of an imposed shear stress. The base flow velocity is computed analytically for different values of the imposed shear stress. It is observed that base flow is intensified in the presence of imposed shear stress. The fourth order Orr-Sommerfeld boundary value problem is derived by using the perturbation method along with the normal mode decomposition. Further, the critical Reynolds number is determined analytically, which decreases in the presence of imposed shear stress and results in a destabilizing effect. On the contrary, the critical Reynolds number increases in the presence of surface tension and results in a stabilizing effect.

1. Introduction

Hydrodynamic stability is one of the fascinating topics of fluid mechanics because of its several applications in industry and technology [1]. For example, thin films are used as lubricant layers for the flow of crude oil in pipes and channels [2]. In addition, thin film plays a crucial role in coating technology. In fact, the formation of wave on the surface of a coating film degrades the quality of the final coated product [3]. The study of stability of thin liquid film flowing down an inclined plane was initiated by Yih [4] based on the long-wave asymptotic expansion. He derived the Orr-Sommerfeld equation by using the perturbation technique. Later, the physical mechanism of the instability was discussed in detail by Smith [2]. He also introduced the constant shear stress at the free surface and computed the critical Reynolds number based on the first order asymptotic expansion. Here our purpose is to extend the work of Smith by considering the higher order terms in the asymptotic expansion.

2. Formulation and Methodology

Consider a gravity-driven 2-D viscous incompressible liquid film flowing down an inclined plane having an inclination angle θ , in the presence of a constant shear stress τ_r , acting parallel to the plane at the free surface $y=h(x, t)$ (Figure 1). The origin is located at the plane and the co-ordinate axes x and y are placed along the streamwise and crosswise directions respectively. Here g is the gravitational acceleration, d is the constant film thickness for base flow solution and $U(y)$ is the base flow velocity. The governing equations are mass and momentum conservation equations. After applying the boundary conditions, the base flow solutions are determined analytically.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a falling film in the presence of an imposed shear stress.

Using the perturbation method along with the normal mode decomposition, the governing equations can be reduced to the well-known Orr-Sommerfeld (OS) equation.

$$(D^2 - k^2)^2 \varphi = ikRe[(U - c)(D^2 - k^2)\varphi - D^2 U \varphi] \quad (1)$$

where $D = d/dy$ is the differential operator, φ is the amplitude of stream function of disturbance, k is the wave number, c is the complex wave speed, Re is the Reynolds number and U is the base flow velocity.

Using the long wave analysis, the OS equation is resolved and the growth rate is computed up to third order asymptotic expansion.

Figure 2. The growth rate kc_i as a function of wavenumber k for different values of the imposed shear stress τ when weber number $We = 0$, $Re = 3$, and $\theta = 45^\circ$. The points are result of Pascal [5].

Figure 3. Variation of critical Reynolds number (Re_c) with the imposed shear stress τ when inclination angle θ varies. Solid points are results of Yih [4].

3. Results and Conclusion

Critical Reynolds number reduces with the increasing value of the imposed shear stress as shown in Figure 3. This fact indicates that imposed shear stress has a destabilizing effect on the long-wave mode. Critical Reynolds number increases with the decreasing value of the inclination angle as shown in Figure 3. This fact indicates that inclination angle has a stabilizing effect on the long-wave mode. Growth rate enhances with the imposed shear stress as shown in Figure 2 and results in a destabilizing effect.

4. References

- [1] Drazin, P.G. and Reid, W.H., 2004. Hydrodynamic stability. Cambridge university press.
- [2] Smith, M.K., 1990. The mechanism for the long-wave instability in thin liquid films. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 217, 469-485.
- [3] Samanta, A., 2014. Shear-imposed falling film. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 753, 131-149.
- [4] Yih, C.S., 1963. Stability of liquid flow down an inclined plane. *The physics of Fluids*, 6(3), 321-334.
- [5] Pascal, J.P., 1999. Linear stability of fluid flow down a porous inclined plane. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 32(4), 417.

Study of Ship Airwakes Characteristics at Different Cross Wind Conditions

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Abstract

This study is related to the numerical estimation of ship airwakes characteristics at different cross-wind conditions faced by frigate ships. The combined ship-helicopter operation nearby small naval vessels is one of the most challenging tasks. The complexity of this task arises due to complex flow structures on helodeck and these flow structures are developed due to ship superstructure, helicopter aerodynamics, and cross-wind flow conditions over the helodeck. In an attempt to study cross-wind effects on the helodeck region, we present Reynolds-averaged-Navier-Stokes (RANS) modelling of turbulent flow over a wide range of WOD angles over a simple frigate ship.

1. Introduction

The landing and take-off of helicopters from small naval frigate ships is very challenging due to the complex flow structure and smaller size of deck. This complexity again increases with WOD angle. Ship helicopter operational limit charts (SHOL) are used to determine whether it is safe to land in the prevailing wind conditions. To develop these charts test flights are conducted which is very time consuming and expensive. With advancement in computing power and more efficient flow modelling techniques, it has become possible to generate the airwake data without conducting actual tests. Using that data in virtual flight simulator these SHOL charts are developed reducing the cost and time of the process. In present work the flow is studied over a wide range of WOD angles using RANS approach. Generic SFS2 geometry of the frigate ship is used.

2. Computational Approach

Commercial CFD tool FLUENT is used to carry out this study. Due to bluff body structure of helohanger the flow gets separated on the helodeck. The flow over bluff bodies is considered as Reynolds number independent after significantly high Reynolds number (3×10^5). All the numerical simulations are carried out on 1/100th scale 3D model of SFS2 geometry with 21.33m/s free stream velocity. The flow domain is meshed using unstructured approach. To capture the boundary layer effects prism layers are grown on the ship surface with exponential growth factor of 1.2. In the region of interest, i.e. the helodeck the mesh density is increased to ensure necessary effects of separated flow are captured. Standard K - ϵ model is used with enhanced wall functions. The grid independence is achieved at 4 million cell count. During the wind tunnel experiment the SFS2 model is placed above the ground and boundary layer suction is used to reduce boundary layer effects from sea surface and to ensure uniform free stream. Thus in the numerical approach as well the sea surface is treated as frictionless boundary.

3. Mathematical Formulation of K - ϵ Turbulence Model

Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) approach based turbulent models are one of the most used models to study such kind of flow due to their less resource requirements while maintaining the required accuracy. The RANS approach is based on modelling the terms originating from averaging the non-linear term in the instantaneous Navier Stokes equations. The modelled k and ϵ equations are as follows:

$$\text{Eddy viscosity : } \mu_t = \rho C_u \frac{K^2}{\epsilon} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Turbulent Kinetic Energy } \kappa: \frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho k u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\mu_t}{\sigma} \right) \right] + 2\mu_t E_{ij} E_{ij} - \rho \epsilon \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Dissipation } \epsilon: \frac{\partial(\rho \epsilon)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho \epsilon u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\mu_t}{\sigma} \right) \right] + C_{1\epsilon} \frac{\epsilon}{k} 2\mu_t E_{ij} E_{ij} - C_{2\epsilon} \rho \frac{\epsilon^2}{k} \quad (3)$$

where $\rho =$ Density of fluid.

4. Results and Discussion

The flow data generated is compared with the experimental data reported in literature by Forrest et al. [1] in Figure 1 for validation of the computational approach. The flow features are analyzed in 5 different planes. Figure 1 shows the variation of the normalized velocity components with respect to normalized distance from the centerline on helodeck.

Figure 1. Variation of normalized U, V, W components of velocity along a lateral line on helodeck at 50% deck length and at hanger height.

Figure 2. (a) Velocity magnitude contours in 3 Transverse planes; (b) difference in normalized average T.K.E of two halves of helodeck w.r.t increasing WOD angle.

From Figure 2, it can be seen that there is recirculation of flow just after the hanger creating a low velocity zone near hanger. As the WOD angle increases the symmetrical flow structure in helodeck starts becoming assymetrical due to cross wind component which can be seen from Figure 2b. The increase in difference in normalized average turbulent kinetic energy with increasing WOD angle shows that the flow has become assymetrical creating a differential loading of helicopter rotor which in turn increases pilot workload.

5. References

- [1] Forrest, J.S. and Owen, I., 2010. An investigation of ship airwakes using Detached-Eddy Simulation. *Computers & Fluids*, 39(4), pp.656-673.
- [2] Shukla, S., Singh, S.N. and Srinivasan, B., 2015. A Computational Study of Modified TTCP/SFS Ship Airwakes. *Conference on Ship and Offshore Technology ICSOT 2015 December 10-11, 2015, IIT Kharagpur, India.*
- [3] Dooley, G., 2017. Ship Airwake Computational Modeling Method Verification.

Numerical Investigation of Ship Airwakes Interaction with Helicopter Fuselage

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Abstract

The ship-helicopter combined operation creates a tremendous amount of workload even for the most experienced pilots. The primary reason for this workload is the flow dynamics over the helo deck which alters the helicopter aerodynamics during launch and recovery operation. Numerical study has been performed with NASA Rotor Body Interaction (ROBIN) helicopter fuselage and TTCP Simple Frigate Ship (SFS2) geometry to investigate the helicopter aerodynamics under ship airwakes. A parametric study has been performed at different wind-over-deck (WOD) conditions and Fuselage Yaw with steady RANS approach. Results are presented for a range of onset parameters, and these results highlight the characteristic force and moment experienced by the fuselage during ship-helicopter combined operation.

1. Introduction

The shipborne helicopter is one of the dominant tools for any naval fleet which facilitates aerial operation/surveillance at sea. In general, the ship-helicopter combined operation is very challenging and demanding in nature. The overall ship-helo activity is dominated by several crucial factors namely, ship airwake, large vortices, WOD condition, helodeck space, helo-downwash, and harsh sea/weather conditions [1-3]. These factors reduced flight margin and drastically increase pilot workload. Experiencing such complex flow conditions by pilots is considered to be a most challenging task, especially during the recovery stage, i.e. when the helicopter comes into the ship superstructure airwake [4]. Thus, the gravity of overall problem demands a systematic study of helicopter aerodynamics under the ship airwakes.

Several experimental and numerical research has been reported on ship-helicopter dynamic interface (DI) phenomena. Literature findings show that WOD conditions, helicopter approach angle and ship size are the critical parameters which affect the helicopter aerodynamics.

2. Study Methodology

Details of ship and helicopter geometry including dimensions, parameters and WOD speed are presented in Table 1. The computational domain size and the ship-helo superstructure model have been taken from literature (as shown in Figure 1). The accuracy of current prediction is verified by performing simulations on different grids with a suitable turbulence model and comparing against available experimental results from literature. Unstructured grids generated by ICEM and general purpose commercial CFD code ANSYS fluent 15.0 are used for simulation.

Table 1. Details of geometries, selected parameters and WOD speed.

Geometry Type	Dimension	Parameters	WOD Speed
SFS2	1.38 x 0.138 x 0.168 (L x B x H) m ³	0°, ±5°, ±10°, ±15°, ±30° (WOD angles)	21 (40.8) m/s (knots)
ROBIN FUSELAGE	0.55 (Xmax.) m.	0°, +30° (Yaw angles)	

3. Results and Discussion

It is found from the study that the high WOD condition (> 15°) affects the helicopter aerodynamics significantly. The appearance of such flow condition at high WOD conditions increase force and moment coefficients experience by fuselage. The reason behind such drastic increment is due to the exposed area of fuselage body to free stream flow, free shear layer, high turbulence intensity and large recirculation zone over the helodeck. More details regarding the results and pertinent discussion will be presented in the full paper.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of Computational Domain and Geometries.

Figure 2. Variation of coefficients at 0° Yaw and different WOD angles.

Figure 1. (b) Zoomed view of ROBIN fuselage (placed at the marked location over the helodeck).

4. References

- [1] Lee, R.G. and Zan, S.J., 2002, September. Wind tunnel testing to determine unsteady loads on a helicopter fuselage in a ship airwake. In ICAS 2002 Congress (pp. 3111-1).
- [2] Forrest, J.S., Owen, I., Padfield, G.D. and Hodge, S.J., 2012. Ship-helicopter operating limits prediction using piloted flight simulation and time-accurate airwakes. *Journal of Aircraft*, 49(4), pp.1020-1031.
- [3] Shukla S., Makkar I., Singh S. N., Suman S.S., and Vijiyakumar R., 2017. Numerical Studies of Coupled Flow Effects Due to Ship Airwake and Rotor Downwash Interaction on Warship Helo-Decks. In 5th International Conference on Ship and Offshore Technology, pp 1-17.
- [4] Healey, J., 1987. The Prospects for Simulating the Helicopter Ship Interface. *Naval Engineers Journal*, 99(2), pp.45-63.

Combustion Characteristics of an Array of Energized Flames

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Abstract

This investigation emulates the exhaust gas interactions of the solid rocket through concurrent ignition of an energized candle and sparklers, with systematic analysis of their behaviors. The work emphasizes on three main parameters, distance, orientation, and the number of heat sources (sparklers). An in-depth study is carried out on the burning interactions between an energized candle and sparklers as external heat sources in the immediate vicinity.

1. Introduction

Solid Rockets are the earliest form of rocket propulsion and forms an integral component of rocket propulsion. Rockets propelled by solid propellants utilizes a combination of a solid oxidizer and a solid Fuel. As widely known, success in Solid Rocket Motor design and development depends significantly on human understanding of burning rate behavior of the selected solid propellant under all motor operating conditions and design limit conditions. In recently, Most of Solid Rocket Motors consist of the Main Engine, along with multiple Boosters that provide an additional thrust to the space bound vehicle. Though widely used, they have been eclipsed by Liquid Propellant Rockets, because of their better performance characteristics. The addition of a catalyst such as Iron Oxide, on the other hand, can drastically enhance the performance of a Solid Rocket. Literature incorporates that experimentation with the energized fuels resulted in enhanced regression rates demonstrating the influence of adding energetic materials into the conventional propellant mixture. Following the appreciable work of Grant and Jones [1], reporting experimental observation that the low-frequency oscillation dominates the flame plume at the high flow rates required to lift the flame far above the burner. Omata [2], studied that the various conditions of parameter values and initial condition result in various states of entrainment. The hysteresis is one of the characteristics in the patterns of entrainment. Saxena et. al. [3], showed that the Amplitude Death is a general outcome in coupled nonlinear oscillator systems, occurring in a wide variety of dynamical models and for different forms of coupling. Forrester [4], examined the relative distance between the tip of the visible flame and the wax pool surface using the frame analysis features of Media Player Classic, to better understand the dynamics of fire, particularly the proximity effects of individual flames that arise and are perpetuated by a fuel source, arrays of candles. The dynamics of the flames were recorded using a Nikon J1 camera in the slow-motion mode, enabling 400 fps to be captured. Paraffin candles, as well as those made from bees wax, were used - both demonstrating the phenomena, ruling out possible impurity effects. Shadowgraphs were recorded in slow motion as a beam of light was shone through the oscillating flames against a white background in a darkened room. In the light of above mentioned works, present work attempts to investigate the effect of Solid Rocket Motors using Sparklers in vicinity of an Energized Candle.

2. General Specifications

An experimental setup was upraised comprising of a central Energized Candle acting as the main Engine and surrounding Sparklers acting as the Booster. When the Main Engine and Boosters of a Solid Rocket ignite simultaneously, their exhausts at the nozzle interact with each other. The Energized Candle contains Magnesium, while the Sparklers contain Aluminium, both of which act as catalysts and enhance the burn rates of both materials, thus increasing their performance. Figure 1 illustrates the experimental setup which was constructed for conducting the experiments. The regression rate was calculated using linear formulation.

$$r = l/T_{av} \quad (1)$$

where, r = regression rate in centimeters per second, l = the portion of the candle which has been utilized, T_{av} = the time taken to burn that portion.

Figure 1. (a) Energetic candles; (b) A simple double-sided scale for taking the measurements; (c) Experimental Setup; (d) Setup bed.

3. Summary

The Regression Rates are calculated by taking time intervals for burning of successive markings on the candle, in units of cm/minute. The results are noted with the cases of combustion rates of a normal candle and an energetic candle (Figure 2). A Magic candle burns 114.6% faster than a normal candle. The role of high energy materials in propellants, their combustion and resultant propulsion for diverse applications is investigated.

Figure 2. Variation of average regression rates for Normal fuel and an energized fuel.

Figure 3. Variation of average regression rates with separation distance for Energetic fuel in presence of a single sparkle.

Figure 3 shows the variation of regression rate for pilot fuel (Magic candle) in presence of a single sparkle (External influence) with separation distance. The maximum regression rate for the case with one sparkle occurs when the fuel and the source are placed attached to each other. At zero cm distance, the rate is 708.69% than the regression rate in the absence of sources.

The work is motivated by the need to enhance combustion performance and minimization of related hazards using energy transfer prediction.

4. References

- [1] Grant, A., and Jones, J., 1975, Low-frequency diffusion flame oscillations. *Combust. Flame* 25, 153–160, 1975.
- [2] Omata, S., 1988, Entrainment among coupled limit cycle oscillators with frustration. *Physica D*, 31, 397–409.
- [3] Saxena, G., Prasad, A., and Ramaswamy, R., 2012, Amplitude death: The emergence of stationarity in coupled nonlinear systems. *Phys. Rep.* 521, 205–228.
- [4] Forrester, D. M., 2015, Arrays of coupled chemical oscillators. *Sci. Rep.* 5, 16994.

Laser Induced Combustion

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Abstract

Enhanced energy requirement has necessitated active research efforts to fundamentally understand combustion behavior in presence of alternative energy sources. A recent area of research emphasis includes the Direct Energy Weapons (DEWs). The governing principle of DEW is transmission of high energy with the use of lasers and/or microwaves introducing uneven heat stresses and leading to the failure of structural integration eventually causing its destruction. Present work is motivated by the need to have better combustion-oriented applications and enhanced fire safety. The investigation is carried out to explore the laser-combustion interactions and identification of the significant implications. The presence of an effective alternate energy source is expected to induce effect in the form of stability, Instability and extinction.

1. Introduction

Combustion is critically important as it provides for about 80% of the energy requirement of the world. In the last five decades, emphasis on combustion focuses two aspects viz., Improving quality of combustion and addressing the risks/hazards. With recent advancement, an aspect which is researched upon is the combustion behavior in the presence of laser flow. Lasers are well known as potential, cheaper, point-precise and high-speed energy sources. Their applications pertain to propulsion, energy generation, artillery, fire safety and defence support systems. Lasers are going to play a huge role in the future in many fields especially in the national security as they have high potential in defense energy systems (DES). Following the classical work of Hickling and Smith [1] on Combustion Bomb Tests of Laser Ignition and Dale et. al., [2] on Laser-ignited internal combustion engine. Significant experimental, computational, analytical contributions have been made. In recently, Mulla et. al., [3] investigated the early stages of flame-kernel development in laser-induced spark ignited mixtures issuing out of a Bunsen burner. A CH_4/air mixture was studied as a base case and compared with $\text{CH}_4/\text{CO}_2/\text{air}$ and $\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2/\text{air}$ mixtures for nearly the same adiabatic flame temperature. Larger flame-kernel spread was found in the case of CH_4/H_2 mixtures. The effects were stated to be due to two competing effects, namely, increase in the strain rate that causes local extinction, and increase in the turbulence levels. Present work focusses on understanding the effect of laser on solid fuel burning.

2. General Specifications

A simple experimental setup was upraised comprising of varying intensity lasers, paraffin wax candles, incense sticks, concave and convex lenses, optical setup (shadowgraph) and stopwatch (Figures 1 (single laser) & 2 (Three laser) configurations).

Figure 1. Single laser configuration.

Figure 2. Three laser configurations.

The effect was simplified by quantification of flame spread rate (candle) and smoldering regression rate (incense stick) variation with key controlling parameters. Spread rate were measures using linear formulation. The parametric variations include external energy source (laser), separation distance, laser intensity, different source (laser)

configurations. Systematic experimentation was carried out under normal gravity conditions and results were compared with the base case of combustion without any external source.

3. Summary

The predictions of experimental setup were matched with the conventional heat transfer theory. Results indicate that lasers significantly affect the combustion process in both modes - flaming and smoldering which project lasers as a potential futuristic energy source to test and analyze combustion systems and design laser induced combustion systems. For flaming combustion (Figure 3), laser(s) placed far away from the pilot fuel were noted to result in drop in flame spreading rate however, nearby placement largely resulted in rise. For smoldering (Figure 4), single laser configuration depicts maximum regression rate rise of 45.29% for 320 nm, and minimum rise of 2.76% for 650 nm.

Figure 3. Effect of varying laser intensity on opposed flame spread rates.

Figure 4. Effect of varying laser intensity on reverse smoldering regression rates.

The results indicate dual nature of laser-combustion interactions. As a potential application, the unique properties of DEW include travelling at the speed of light with no complicated trajectory calculations (ensuring the target is in the line of sight), not being affected by gravity, its invisibility and its ability to take on multiple targets from a stand-off distance. Hence, by studying and performing experiments on LIC, it is possible to enhance the national security.

4. References

- [1] Robert Hickling, William R. Smith, 1974, Combustion Bomb Tests of Laser Ignition, Proceedings of Automotive Engineering Congress and Exposition, February 1974, DOI10.4271/740114.
- [2] J. Douglas Dale, P. R. Smy, D. Wayne, R.M. Clements, 1977, Laser-ignited internal combustion engine, Combustion and Flame, 30:319-320.
- [3] Irfan Mulla, Satyanarayanan R Chakravarthy, N. Swaminathan, Ramanarayanan Balachandran, 2015, Evolution of flame-kernel in laser-induced spark ignited mixtures: A parametric study, Combustion and Flame, 164:303-318.

Thermoacoustic Effects on Unstable Premixed Flames

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Abstract

Present work attempts to establish instabilities associated with lifted premixed flames in gas burners. The lifted premixed flame signifies higher normal flow rate velocity than the flame speed. An experimental setup was upraised to address the present issue. Experimentation was conducted on lifted flame using butane gas lighters surrounded by impinging acoustics. The novelty of the work is investigating combustion noise and instability by impinging sound on an already unstable lifted flame.

1. Introduction

Combustion is an exothermic chemical reaction that brings in transfer and transformation of mass, heat and momentum. The generation of large amount of energy from a small volume relates mostly to the flaming combustion. Flaming combustion is broadly classified as premixed and diffusion flames. Premixed flames are generated when the fuel and oxidizer are mixed before the combustion zone. Combustion forms the most reliable and basic form of propulsion for ground and space applications. The urge to get better combustion and fire safety propels study on combustion sciences. Combustion instabilities in premixed flames occurs in a reacting flow in which some perturbations, even very small ones, grow and then become large enough to alter the features of the flow in some way. These phenomena can be classified into the following three types: thermoacoustic combustion instabilities; static instabilities or flame blowoff; and intrinsic flame instabilities. However, the term combustion instabilities usually refer to the thermoacoustic type. The combustion instability explored the work is 'Flame lift off phenomena' when the unstable rises above the burner to a certain distance (Figure 1). This occurs when the flame spread rate S_L is less than the incoming mass flow rate of the fuel U , i.e. $U > S_L$. The fuel flow rate lifts off the flame from the burner. Although combustion science is being extensively studied, its effectiveness accompanied with acoustic is a special domain yet to be completely explored. Chiu and Summerfield [1] proposed a unified theory of noise generation and amplification by turbulent combustion of premixed fuel and liquid fuel droplets, within the framework of the fluid mechanics of the reacting gas. Lieuwen and Yang [2] presented, the case studies section for specific manufacturer and user experiences with combustion instabilities in the development stage and in fielded turbine engines. The work then goes on to examine, the fundamental mechanisms, the combustor modeling, and control approaches. Matalon [3] worked on intrinsic combustion instabilities in both premixed and non-premixed systems, identifying the roles of differential and preferential diffusion, thermal expansion, and heat losses. Results stated that, for premixed flames, the hydrodynamic instability resulting from thermal expansion plays a central role and is particularly dominant in large-scale flames. It is responsible for the formation of sharp folds and creases in the flame front and for the wrinkling observed over the surface of expanding flames.

Figure 1. Schematics of fuel flow rate and flame speed.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. (a) Experimental setup; (b) Base Premixed lifted flame.

2. General Specifications

A small scale experimental setup was upraised to investigate the acoustic energy implications on an unstable lifted premixed flame. The setup comprises of (a) Household butane lighter, (b) High characterization audio speakers, (c) camera, (d) Dark background for optical shadowgraph, and (e) A firm thermocol board that mounts all other components with angles marked on it. The experiments were carried out by impinging acoustic waves on the flame front by two notable speakers placed diametrically opposite and 200 mm apart to the flame (Figure 2a). The sound waves of varying frequency were impinged from both the speakers on the lifted flame (Figure 3). The instability induced in the flame due to this can be measured by the distance the flame rises on the burner. To quantify the magnitude of instability induced in the flame we define a parameter called as the GFL (Gross flame length). Where GFL is the algebraic sum of FL (flame standoff distance) and FH (flame height) (Figure 4). The phenomenon was probed in terms of GFL (Gross Flame Length), Flickering Frequency, variation in flame specifications and flame extinction or stabilization time.

Figure 3. Schematic of impinging acoustic on unstable lifted flame.

Figure 4. Schematic GFL, FL and FH for the lifted flame.

Figure 5. Variation of the flame variation time with acoustic frequency the lifted flame.

3. Summary

Acoustic energy brings alteration in inter energy conversion which varies with frequency. The following cases are observed due to these conversions viz., Acoustic neutralizes (No change), Acoustic tries to stabilises the unstable premixed flames, Acoustic further installs instability. The cases of acoustics frequency causing flame stabilization and extinction varies with time, so the values of T_{ex} (flame extinction time) and T_s (flame stabilization time) are different (Figure 5), this defines a zonal acoustics frequency system which has significant effect on existing unstable flame. The longest t extinction time noted was for 9000 Hz (59sec) and the lowest being 0 if the flame doesn't extinguish. The longest stabilization time noted was for 2000 Hz (50 sec) and the lowest being 0 if the flame remains unstable. The lower zone frequencies from 100 Hz to 750 Hz either restabilize viz. 500 Hz or neutralizes the flame. The mid zone frequencies between 750 Hz to 2000 Hz also stabilize (2000 Hz) and neutralizes (750, 1000 Hz). The high zone frequencies from 2000 to 10000 Hz is characterized to have either extinguish or neutralize the flame (Figure 5).

4. References

- [1] Chiu, H. H., and Summerfield M., 1973, Theory of combustion noise, aerospace and mechanical sciences report, Princeton University, Princeton, New Jersey.
- [2] Lieuwen, T. C. and Yang, V., 2005, Combustion instabilities in gas turbine engines. AIAA.
- [3] Matalon, M., 2007, Intrinsic flame instabilities in premixed and non-premixed combustion. Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics 39, pp.163-191.

An Experimental Insight on the Forced Forward Smoldering Combustion

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Abstract

In forward smoldering, the air moves in the same direction as smoldering front whereas in reverse smoldering air moves in direction opposite to smoldering front. The rate at which fuel regresses in flameless combustion is an important parameter of practical and functional significance. An important aspect in attention is the existence of air flow at certain velocities (forced flow) in combustion processes along with varying the separation distance. The forced flow over the combustion process is very likely to affect the ignition and the process propagation. The study of smoldering is primarily driven by the need to have better fire safety and greater skillful applications. The specific objectives of the study are:

- a) To study the forced flow effects on the forward smoldering regression rates.
- b) To study the effect of key controlling parameters.

1. Introduction

Smoldering is of many uses however, if not controlled it is also a source of unlimited damage. The subject involving mass and heat transfer and is broadly encountered in nature covering wide range of engineering and industrial applications. Smoldering essentially is well known as slow combustion and unlike flaming combustion (with flames) is a surface phenomenon. Heat transfer from burning to unburnt surface is attributed with propelling the ignition front normal to the fuel surface. The phenomenon is studied under two classes as: Opposed (Reverse Smoldering) and Concurrent (Forward Smoldering) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic of smoldering with different zones together with the direction of propagation.

Figure 2. Schematic of Experimental setup.

2. General Specifications

An experimental setup was upraised for the present study (Figure 2) comprising of a hard thermocol with protractor fixed on it and firmly supported in front of a table. The forced air flow effect is generated with a fan having 3 different speed levels, 4 m/s, 4.5 m/s, 5 m/s (measured at the surface of the fan) and is placed at 4 different distances, 100 cm, 75 cm, 50cm, 30cm with respect to the fuel. The experiments were thoroughly carried out in a quiescent room under normal gravity conditions. Dark sheets were used for flow visualization to capture the smoke pattern. The solid fuel assembly comprised of dried incense sticks in 5 cm × 0.20 cm specification. The incense sticks composition is sawdust (30 %), charcoal (30 %) and cow dung (38.5%) and incense chemical (1.5%). The fuel strips were marked at regular intervals of 1 cm to track the smoldering front propagation with time.

3. Summary

According to classical heat transfer theory over thin solid fuels, the propagating front spreads by the heat feedback (forward heat transfer) from the burning to the unburnt solid fuel upstream. The extent of heat feedback is reflected in regression rates. In the last five decades, appreciable work had been carried out to prevent and control smoldering aiming primarily at understanding the fuel regression rates under varying operating conditions and the reviews can be found in Kinbara et al. [1] and Ohlemiller [2]. Following the classical work of Kinbara et al. [1] on downward

propagation of smoldering combustion through solid materials, appreciable research efforts have been made in the form of experimental, numerical, analytical, theoretical studies. Ohlemiller [2] studied the propagation rate of smoldering through porous horizontal fuel layers for a variety of materials along with the structure of the smolder reaction zone and the factors controlling it. Investigations comprises of a thick (18 cm) layers of wood-based fibers in the form of cellulosic insulation smoldering under natural convection air supply conditions. Two-dimensional profiles of temperature, oxygen mole fraction, and residual organic material were measured both for unretarded insulation and for insulation having 25 wt.% of the smolder retardant. It was inferred that the overall wave structure is dominated by oxygen diffusion from above. The heat release chemistry was noted to involve both oxidative pyrolysis and char oxidation in a shifting balance depending on depth in the layer. The experimentation shows that there is major effect on smoldering with the change in orientation, change in velocity and as well as change in distance. Prior to the main study, experimental predictions were corroborated with the well-established smoldering studies (Figure 3) by Tiwari et. al. [3]. The effect of surface orientation on regression rates at selected orientations for reverse mode was assessed. The predictions of the experimental setup matched reasonably well. It is likely to offer a good physical insight into the forced forward smoldering phenomenon and the articulation of the role of the key controlling parameters.

Figure 3. Variation of reverse smoldering regression rate with surface orientation.

At present, systematic experimentation is being carried out to investigate the effect of varying flow field, separation distance coupled with surface orientation on forward smoldering combustion.

4. References

- [1] Kinbara, T., Endo, H., and Sega, S., 1967, Downward propagation of smoldering combustion through solid materials. Symposium (International) on Combustion 11, (1), 525–531.
- [2] Ohlemiller, T.J., 1990, Smoldering combustion propagation through a permeable horizontal fuel layer. Combustion and Flame 81, 3-4 (9), 341–353.
- [3] Pratik Tiwari, Vikram Ramanan and Vinayak Malhotra., 2017, Thermoacoustic smoldering, Journal of Space Exploration.

Enclosure Phenomenon in Varying Flow Forced Convection

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Abstract

Systematic experimentation was carried out on forced convection heat transfer apparatus under varying non-linear flow conditions. Plate orientations, types of enclosures (solid, meshed, perforated), flow velocity variations etc. are taken as governing parameters to effect convective heat transfer phenomenon which is perceived as deviations in value of heat transfer coefficient. R-V zonal system is utilized to simplify the fundamental understanding of heat transfer coefficient variation with surface orientation under varying flow field. The objectives of this work are as follows:

- 1) To establish relative effectiveness of forced convective heat transfer under varying flow field.
- 2) To investigate the implications of varying shapes and sizes of perforations on confined forced convective heat transfer.
- 3) To understanding the controlling mechanism and role of key controlling parameters.

1. Introduction

Forced convection covers wide range of practical, functional, industrial, engineering and scientific applications. Convective heat transfer behavior in presence of forced flow is broadly studied and understood under uniform flow conditions. However, a large domain of applications sustains to the convection heat transfer under varying flow conditions. Inconsistent flow results in nonlinear heat transfer, therefore it is imperative to understand response of flow in coupling of external inconsistent forced flow with confined convective heat transfer.

2. General Specifications

Following the incubating work of Goshayeshi and Safaiya [1] on turbulence mixed convection in air filled enclosures. Tiwari et al. [2] experimented on forced convection over a rough flat plate and related implications. Bhatia and Malhotra [3] studied the enclosure phenomena in confined natural convection. However, an aspect yet to be comprehensively worked upon is variation of convective heat transfer under forced domain in varying flow conditions.

Figure 1. Experimental setup.

Figure 2. Enclosures (a-h) utilized in the study.

Present work details systematic experimentation conducted with an objective to provide a good physical insight into heterogeneous heat transfer phenomena of forced convection over a flat plate.

An existing forced convection experiment setup (Figure 1) was utilized for the present study. The study primarily intends understanding of the enclosure effect under varying flow field in aid of governing parameters viz., plate orientation, enclosure shapes and enclosure size (Figure 2) on convective heat transfer coefficient. Experiments were performed on an existing forced convection experimental setup comprising of an aluminium flat plate with five

equidistant thermocouples embedded in it. The heat transfer characteristics were analyzed for smooth surface facing upward in a confined passage.

3. Summary

Results show that heat transfer coefficient behaves significantly diverse with varying surface orientation and heat input (Figure 3). The heat transfer rates monotonically rise radically with varying surface orientation and drops with heat input, both followed by a gradual descent. Increased heat supply transmits more heat transfer and hot surfaces are predicted to lose heat faster when oriented more in horizontal state however, heat transfer rates are found to be sensitive to a critical value after which the varying rate drops. The effect of enclosure is established to enhance reduction in the transfer of heat with orientation. Results indicate that enclosures significantly affect heat transportation from the source under varying conditions (Please see Figure 4).

Figure 3. Convective heat transfer coefficient variation with the surface orientation.

Figure 4. Convective heat transfer coefficient variation with the surface orientation for the cases of with (solid plate) and without enclosure.

The compiled results are noted to provide excellent physical insight in the phenomena of heat transfer. The proposed work is intended to explore science behind change in convective heat transfer to explain significant effects on its wide range applications.

4. References

- [1] Hamid Reza Goshayeshi and Mohammad Reza Safaiya, 2011, Investigation of turbulence mixed convection in air filled enclosures. *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science* 2(6), pp. 87-95.
- [2] Pratik Tiwari, Shitiz Sehgal, Ajay Babusekar and Vinayak Malhotra, 2014, Experimental investigation on forced convection over a rough flat plate and related implications. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management* 3(9), pp. 234-238.
- [3] Ribhu Bhatia and Vinayak Malhotra, 2016, Enclosure Phenomena in Confined Natural Convection, *American Journal of Engineering Research* 5(11), pp. 166- 179.

On the Role of Acoustic Bass in Premixed Flame Combustion

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Abstract

Aviation industry comprises of several acoustic noises created by various sources i.e. from aircraft airframe, engines, ground power units etc. The related acoustics is reported to have resulted in significant losses. This necessitates active research efforts to study thermoacoustics as an important aspect of the aviation industries. Present work establishes the interrelation between the acoustic effect of bass as a potential parameter in understanding premixed flame behavior. The study is primarily driven by the need to have better combustion and fire safety. The specific objectives of the study are:

- a) To study the acoustic bass effects on the stable premixed flame.
- b) To study the effect of key controlling parameters.

1. Introduction

Flame represents a chemical reaction between the fuel and oxidant called combustion accompanied by the release of heat and covers wide range of practical, industrial, functional, scientific applications. Flames are broadly classified as the premixed and diffusion. This classification is based on the way, fuel and oxidizer mixture are formed for combustion with premixed flames arising from the fuel gas and air being mixed prior to entering the burner. Premixed hydrocarbon flame burning in air are identified with the blue light emitted if the mixture is fuel lean and a yellow soot-producing flame, if the mixture entering the flame is fuel-rich, known as a luminous flame. In addition, they can also be categorized into stationary flames or propagating (travelling) flames, the former being the most widely used in domestic or industrial burners, the latter being involved in explosions. Figure 1a shows the simplified structure of a premixed flame comprising of a *Preheat zone* involving heating up the reactants, *Inner-layer* relating radical formation, *oxidation-layer* for finishing the remaining reactions and *Post-flame zone* for hot products, NO_x formation. Simplification of most of the organized combustion are premixed, from the rocket motors to the burners which are used in the kitchen. An important aspect of premixed flames is that they create lesser pollutants and combustion can be held in a lesser volume as compared to the diffusion flames. Most of the flaming operations in industries viz., Aviation are accompanied by the acoustics representing a pressure wave involving molecules compression and expansion. The acoustic spectrum is well known to comprise of Infrasound (0-20 Hz), Acoustics (20-20000 Hz) & Ultrasound (>20 kHz). Acoustics is further sub-classified into Sub-Bass, Bass, Low Midrange, Midrange, Upper Midrange, Presence and Brilliance. Acoustic bass describes tones of low frequency and range from 60-250 Hz.

Figure 1. Schematic of (a) premixed flame structure; (b) premixed flame and acoustic interaction.

Acoustic energy in interaction with the thermal energy is likely to affect the combustion process thus the operational objective. The Flame - Sound Interaction is likely to alter the forward heat transfer and intrinsically the reaction mechanism thus resulting in the altered flame behavior and flammability (please see Figure 1b).

The applications can be noted in significant fire prevention, detection, suppression and resourceful combustion utilization. Following the classical work of Chiu and Summerfield [1] on the theory of combustion noise. Lieuwen and Yang [2] systematically investigated the combustion instabilities in the gas turbine engines. Matalon [3] focused on the Intrinsic flame instabilities in premixed and non-premixed combustion. Appreciable work had been done but a

comprehensive solution is yet to be established owing to non-linear behavior and adapted occurrence. Present work attempts to understand the role of acoustic bass on the flame acoustic interaction and related energy transfer for better combustion and minimization of the hazards.

2. General Specifications

An experimental setup (Figure 2) was upraised and the effect of acoustic bass on the premixed flames was assessed. Butane lighter was used as fuel source. The role of key controlling parameters, namely, frequency and flutter of flames in horizontal and vertical direction, was extensively examined in terms of maximum and minimum flame height and flickering frequency conforming to the experimentation time for selected case. The bass frequency was divided into different ranges and each range were thoroughly inspected. The data obtained is used for a bass flammability curve and henceforth a significant change in the flames were found out when bass was impinged to the flame.

Figure 2. Experimental setup.

Figure 3. Variation of premixed flame flickering frequency with and Acoustic interaction.

3. Summary

Result state that for flame interaction with low frequency, low pitch tune there is a change in the flickering frequency, hence changing the burning properties of the flame, by only changing one properties i.e. bass. Figure 3 shows the variation of flickering frequency with acoustic bass frequency. Maximum flickering was observed at 40 Hz with a flickering frequency of 1.15 Hz whereas minimum flickering was observed at 100 Hz with a flickering frequency of 0.166 Hz. Maximum flickering frequency defines the flame is unstable and the minimum flickering frequency outlines the relatively stable flame at the frequency range.

The outcomes could be of immense contribution to the scientific community and industries. The methodological awareness is reasonable, efficient, cost-effective and will be very helpful in future aerospace industries by contributing in enhanced success rate. The results can be effectively utilized in several applications ranging from fire extinguish to enhancing the jet engine performance and reducing the pollution caused from aircraft using acoustics.

4. References

- [1] Chiu H. H., Summerfield, M., 1973, Theory of combustion noise, aerospace and mechanical sciences report, Princeton University, Princeton, New Jersey.
- [2] Lieuwen, T. C., and Yang, V., 2005, Combustion instabilities in gas turbine engines. AIAA.
- [3] Matalon, M., 2007, Intrinsic flame instabilities in premixed and non-premixed combustion. Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics 39, pp.163-191.

Jet Impingement Heat Transfer on Flat and Ribbed Surfaces

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Abstract

A computational study was carried out for turbulent slot jet impingements on flat and ribbed surfaces to investigate heat transfer and flow characteristics using OpenFOAM 4.1. It was observed that the flow and heat transfer properties were significantly affected by the ribbed plate compared to that on a flat plate. The detached rib configuration showed augmentation in the local Nusselt number in the area of clearances between ribs and plate due to a sudden flow acceleration. However, the stagnation point Nusselt number was observed to be the maximum with the flat surface as compared to that on a ribbed surface.

1. Introduction

Jet impingement heat transfer has the highest heat transfer rate among all possible single-phase heat transfer arrangements [1]. Some of its industrial applications are cooling of turbine blades and electronics chips, heating and cooling of food products and rapid cooling or heating in glass manufacturing industries, etc. Jet impingement configuration looks quite simple geometrically but it involves some flow complexities, such as, free jet, free shear-layer, potential core, stagnation point, wall jet region and flow separation with ribbed impingement surface, etc. Two kinds of conventional arrangements are possible for cooling of an impingement surface, i.e., jet impingement on a flat surface or surface with some kind of roughness. The latter represents an appropriate physical situation where this type of cooling is required in actual practice [1, 2]. Recently many researchers [1-3] have considered jet impingement on a flat surface and performed RANS computations. They observed that the computations with the standard $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence were in close agreement with the experimental data [4]. In the present study we have also considered the standard $k-\varepsilon$ model for computation of both the cases.

2. General Specifications

Figure 1. Computational domain and boundary conditions used in the present study.

In the present study, a 2D computational domain (Figure 1) was considered and computations were performed using OpenFOAM 4.1, which is an open source customized CFD solver. No-slip boundary conditions were applied at all walls and the impingement plate was kept at a constant temperature ($T = 320$ K). However, all the other walls were considered adiabatic. Almost a flat nozzle exit velocity profile ($T = 300$ K) was specified at the nozzle outlet. Outflow boundary conditions were specified at the outlet. Both the outlets were located at a sufficiently large distance from the nozzle centerline to avoid any reversed flow situation ($x/B = +60B$). Grids were made finer at critical locations, such as, near impingement plate, ribbed walls, stagnation region, etc.

3. Equations

The standard $k-\varepsilon$ model is a most commonly used turbulence model to obtain mean flow characteristics of a turbulent flow. In this model the eddy viscosity is given as $\mu_t = \rho C_\mu (k^2 / \varepsilon)$, where C_μ is an empirical constant.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho k \bar{u}_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + P_k - \rho \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \varepsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho \varepsilon \bar{u}_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} P_k - C_{2\varepsilon} \rho \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} \quad (2)$$

The values of the model constants are [3] $C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.44$, $C_{2\varepsilon} = 1.92$, $C_\mu = 0.09$, $\sigma_k = 1$ and $\sigma_\varepsilon = 1.3$.

4. Results and Discussion

We have validated our code for jet impingement on a flat plate and observed that the standard $k-\varepsilon$ showed good agreement with the reported experimental data [4] similar to that of other reported computational results [1, 3]. From Figures 2, 3 and 4 it can be observed that the flow and heat transfer characteristics are different for jet impingement on flat and ribbed surfaces. Flow acceleration and good mixing can be seen in clearances between rib and plate (Figures 2 and 3). The stagnation point Nu is lower for a detached rib configuration compared to the flat plate for the same values of H/B and Re (Figure 4a), but in the region of rib clearances, a heat transfer enhancement can be observed due to a sudden flow acceleration in these regions. It can also be observed (Figure 4) that there is a drop in Nu between the ribs due to the formation of counter-rotating vortices and hence flow cannot effectively impinge at the heated plate.

Figure 2. Contours of (a, b) TKE and (c, d) velocity for flat and ribbed surfaces.

Figure 3. (a, b) Profiles of TKE and streamwise velocity close to flat and ribbed surfaces.

Figure 4. (a, b) Profiles of Nu and temperature for flat and ribbed surfaces.

5. Summary

Significant differences in heat and fluid flow behaviours were observed with the placement of ribs on a plate. Augmentation of heat transfer was observed in the regions of rib to plate clearances due to a good flow mixing and flow acceleration.

6. References

- [1] Shukla A K, Dewan A, 2017, Flow and thermal characteristics of jet impingement: comprehensive review, *Int. J. of Heat and Tech.*, 35, 153-166.
- [2] Shukla A K, Dewan A, 2017, Convective heat transfer enhancement using slot jet impingement on a detached rib surface, *J. of Applied Fluid Mechanics*, 10 (6), 117-126.
- [3] Dutta R, Dewan A, Srinivasan B, 2013, Comparison of various integration to wall (ITW) RANS models for predicting turbulent slot jet impingement heat transfer, *Int. J. of Heat and Mass Transf.*, 65, 750-764.
- [4] Ashforth-Frost S, Jambunathan K, Whitney CF, 1997, Velocity and turbulence characteristics of a semiconfined orthogonally impinging slot jet, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 14, 60–67.

Domain Size Effect for Computational Fluid Dynamics Modeling of Flow Past a Cylinder

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Abstract

Domain size affects the computation time and price, hence choosing a right domain size is of utmost importance. Different combinations of upstream (inlet), downstream (outlet) and sides are analyzed using commercial software ANSYS Fluent for turbulent flow past a circular cylinder. Initially 2-dimensional transition analyses are carried out to get the optimal distances. These dimensions are used for 3-dimensional domain. The results are validated using previous experimental as well as numerical studies comprising of a comparatively larger domain.

1. Introduction

Choosing the optimized domain size is one of the key parts of modeling. Flow past cylinder problem has been taken for the study because of author's interest in tall slender structures. As a starting point for choosing the domain size, recent CFD studies [1] are used. The blockage ratio was kept below 1.7% for all the cases which is well within the prescribed 3% [1, 2]. This paper intends to determine the sensitivity of flow field in the wake to the size of domain. It is not the objective of this work to study different turbulence models, boundary conditions, mesh sizes, etc but is to test the effect of distance of boundaries. The work is motivated by the fact that large domain size implies large numbers of cells which in turn implies expensive computation.

2. Computational Setup

A set of 2-D transient analyses were carried out in three combinations: varying sides, keeping other boundaries as constant; varying inlet distance from cylinder keeping rest of boundaries same and varying downstream while other boundaries remain unchanged. For all the cases, turbulent model used is SST k- ω , which is known for its capability of satisfactorily producing separated flows. The time step size corresponds to Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) number 10. Reynolds number based on cylinder diameter (d) of 30 mm is 20 000. Meshes are produced similarly with hexahedral cells for all cases maintaining y^+ as 1 near solid boundaries. Boundary conditions are: sides and top-symmetry; outlet: pressure outlet. Uniform velocity of 10m/s is applied at inlet.

3. Results and Discussion

Average of 30 cycles is taken after initial 30 cycles to ensure steady state for every case. Velocity is observed at a downstream distance of $5d$ from centre.

Figure 1. Velocity profile at $X=5d$ for different upstream distances.

Figure 1 shows the variation of distance of upstream boundary from 8d to 20d. Y is the transverse distance from centre of cylinder. For all the cases, centerline velocity is almost same but as the transverse distance increases, 8d and 10d cases show variable results while 12d and 20d matched satisfactorily. Hence, 12d upstream distance can be taken for inlet boundary. Similar analyses were done for downstream and side boundaries too after finalizing upstream direction. The chosen parameters are 12d for upstream, 20d for sides and 20d for downstream distances. To validate the same, a 3-dimensional model was created with domain height taken as 24d, similar to Afgan et al. [1]. Velocity profiles and coefficient of pressure (Cp) variation along the circumference are compared with numerical [1] as well as experimental [3] studies as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. (a) Velocity profile comparison at X/D=5; (b) Cp variation at mid height of cylinder.

Velocity profile matches well with previous experimental and numerical studies. While the maximum over-prediction with experimental study is 15%, it was under-predicted by 25% as compared to previous LES study but closer to experimental results hence better. Also, as can be seen by Cp profile, the present study has been able to capture separation point.

4. Summary

It is a usual practice to select the domain size based on experience and previous works but the present study clearly shows that predicting the right domain size plays a very important role in CFD study. For similar meshes, if previously used domains were used, the cell count would have been 2.53 million but for present study only 1.16 cells produce results even closer to the experiments consuming lesser time and computational effort. Hence, similar to grid independence study, it is worth to do domain independence study too.

5. References

- [1] Afgan I, Moulinec C, Prosser R, Laurence D, 2007, Large eddy simulation of turbulent flow for wall mounted cantilever cylinders of aspect ratio 6 and 10, International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow, 28, 561–574.
- [2] Zdravkovich M, 1997, Flow around circular cylinders. Oxford University Press.
- [3] Park CW, Lee SJ, 2002, Flow structure around a finite circular cylinder embedded in various atmospheric boundary layers, Fluid Dynamics research, 30, 197-215.

Numerical Study of Acoustics Flow in an Expansion Chamber

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Abstract

This work depicts the numerical study of acoustic flow through an expansion chamber including the effects of mean flow. The main objective of the study is to estimate the performance of an expansion chamber by calculating transmission loss of acoustical flow by using numerical simulation. The numerical computation involves two steps hybrid methodology. Firstly, the mean flow is calculated within the expansion chamber for a given inlet flow velocity, which is done by solving Navier-Stokes equation based flow solver. Second step is to determine the acoustics propagation in the chamber by using the Linearized Euler Equation (LEE). The results obtained show a significant reduction of sound level at exit than the level measured at inlet.

1. Introduction

Noise is an unwanted sound, which affects the comfort of human life. Noise generally which comes from automotive vehicles is also a major concern for the environment. To get rid from this problem, a number of computational and analytical studies have been carried to find out the acoustical flow of engine exhaust. The objective of the work is to compute the acoustical flow through an expansion chamber by imposing boundary conditions to attain specified geometry of the expansion chamber.

2. Test Model and Solution Methodology

Figure 1a shows the schematic of the geometry of the test model of an expansion chamber [1]. In addition, various boundaries as inlet, wall and exit boundaries are also shown in Figure 1a. To estimate the acoustic flow along with the mean flow, a two-step method. The flow chart of the adopted methodology is shown in Figure 1b.

Figure1. (a) Schematic of test model; (b) Numerical computation approach.

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho' u_0 + u' \rho_0) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\rho' v_0 + v' \rho_0) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial u'}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho_0 u_0 u') + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\rho_0 v_0 u') + \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x}(\rho_0 u' + \rho' u_0) + \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y}(\rho_0 v' + \rho' v_0) + \frac{\partial p'}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial v'}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho_0 u_0 v') + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\rho_0 v_0 v') + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x}(\rho_0 u' + \rho' u_0) + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y}(\rho_0 v' + \rho' v_0) + \frac{\partial p'}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(p' u_0 + \gamma p_0 u') + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(p' v_0 + \gamma p_0 v') + (\gamma - 1) p' \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} \right) - (\gamma - 1) \left(u' \frac{\partial p_0}{\partial x} + v' \frac{\partial p_0}{\partial y} \right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Eqs. (1)-(4) show the two-dimensional LEE, which are discretized using a low dissipative finite difference method [2]. Developed methodology is validated for sound propagation by a point source.

3. Results and Discussion

The results are calculated for an inlet sound of 120dB. First the mean flow velocity is calculated and then propagation of sound in the chamber is computed. Figures 2a-2c show the acoustic wave propagation in the expansion chamber at different time instances. Figures 2d and 2e indicate time history and frequency spectrum of sound measured at inlet and exit section of the chamber and a significant reduction in the sound level from 3 Pa to 0.6 Pa is observed.

Figure 2. (a, b, c) Sound wave propagation in chamber with respect to time; (d, e) time and frequency spectrum of sound measured at inlet and exit of the expansion chamber.

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5. References

- [1] Middelberg, J.M., Barber, T.J., Leong, S.S., Byrne, K.P. and Leonardi, E., 2004, November. Computational fluid dynamics analysis of the acoustic performance of various simple expansion chamber mufflers. In Proceedings of Acoustics (pp. 123-127).
- [2] Tam, C.K. and Webb, J.C., 1993. Dispersion-relation-preserving finite difference schemes for computational acoustics. Journal of computational physics, 107(2), pp.262-281.

Topology Optimization of Rotating Mechanical Members

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Abstract

Lightweight component offers numerous advantages for power and efficiency of a machine. Topology optimization is a versatile tool for mining the mass of components. However, components under motion cannot be directly optimized because of dynamic loading. In the present work, a methodology based on topology optimization is presented to design such components based on SIMP approach. A MATLAB routine is developed for obtaining the optimal topologies. The final topology is synthesized by presenting a method of the weighted density matrix. The obtained consolidated topology is simulated for deflection and Von-Mises stress. The results are validated through COMSOL based simulations.

1. Introduction

Topology optimization method helps to defined connections and holes in the initial material domain subject to the boundary condition, the objective function for minimum compliance and the optimality criteria algorithm. In this way, a novel shape and size of the structure or mechanical components can be obtained [1]. In order to apply topology optimization for a rotating mechanical member, parameters such as initial material domain, material properties, and loading conditions, need to be identified. For a rotating link, loading conditions are the most complicated and sensitive parameter to define.

2. Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP)

The SIMP approach implements straightforward densities to design domain which is discretized by square finite elements. The objective function for this problem is chosen as compliance, which represents flexibility or reverse of stiffness. The optimization of rotating mechanical member is resolved by means of a standard optimality criteria algorithm. The mathematical formulation of objective function reads as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\text{Minimum : } c(z) = D^T S D = \sum_{e=1}^N Y_e(z_e) d_e^T S_0 d_e \quad (1)$$

where c is the compliance, D and S are the global displacement, and global stiffness matrix respectively, S_0 is the element stiffness matrix, d_e is the element displacement vector, N is the total number of elements helpful to discretize the design domain, Y_e and z_e are the element stiffness and element design variable respectively.

3. Methodology

A methodology is proposed to optimize a rotating link. The link is supported on a hinge joint and the other end is carrying a vertical load of 10 N. Also, the self-weight and centrifugal force are considered. While rotation through the hinge joint, the applied force is dynamically changing. The optimal topologies for this link are obtained for various angular situations, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Optimal topologies at different force angles for a rotating link.

During the motion of link, forces are dynamic so superimposition of density matrixes corresponding to different force-angle is an obvious solution. Such obtained topology will suffice for all the angular values of the forces. However, it will have a high volume or mass, which is undesirable. The topologies obtained for certain angular value is non-optimal for other angular values of forces. Here a weighted density method is proposed. It helps to select the most common topology among all angular positions using appropriate weights. In such a way that, the

obtained mass will be minimal compared to superimposition approach. The formulation proposed is given in Eq. (2) which will be used to create weight density matrix.

$$[x] = w_1 ([x]) \theta_1 + w_2 ([x]) \theta_2 + \dots + w_n ([x]) \theta_n \quad (2)$$

where $[x]$ represents density matrix. The values of the weighted function (w_n) are selected such that it represents the highly sensitive element at a higher priority and less sensitive elements can be neglected.

4. Results and Discussion

The value of the deflection and the von-Mises stress for different volume fractions are obtained based on MATLAB routine and COMSOL are compared in Table 1. Due, to a limited number of pages, MATLAB code is not incorporated in manuscript only results are provided.

Table 1. Maximum Deflection and Von-Mises Stress comparison.

Volume Fraction	Maximum Deflection (mm)		von-Mises Stress (MPa)	
	MATLAB	COMSOL	MATLAB	COMSOL
0.4	6.581E-3			
0.5	6.012E-3			

Dropping the mass of the manipulator causes a considerable change in the torque to be generated by the motor. Subsequently, the energy delivered to the motor is reduced as shown in Table 2. If the volume fraction increases torque also increases. Consequently, the proposed methodology is used to develop the energy efficient mechanical systems [2].

Table 2. Volume fraction versus Torque.

Volume fraction	Torque (Nm)
0.4	0.5157
0.5	0.6943
1	1.4876

5. Summary

Topology optimization cuts down the material costs and declines the inertial force and hence the accuracy and precision are enhanced. However, reducing the mass increases the stresses on rotating mechanical member. Topology optimization is used here to minimize the stress as much as possible. The volume fraction to be chosen depends on the load acting on the component. The proposed topology optimization is not only restricted to rotating mechanical member but also applicable for other mechanical structural members like five-bar mechanism [3].

6. References

- [1] M. Bendsøe and O. Sigmund, 2003, Topology optimization. Berlin: Springer.
- [2] Chemnitz, M., Schreck, G., & Krüger, J., 2011, September, Analyzing energy consumption of industrial robots. In Emerging Technologies & Factory Automation (ETFA), 2011 IEEE 16th Conference on (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [3] Briot S., & Goldsztejn, 2018, Topology optimization of industrial robots: Application to a five-bar mechanism. Mechanism and Machine Theory, 120, 30-56.

Numerical Simulation and Optimization of Micromixer Performance

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Abstract

Micromixers are one of the vital components of a typical microfluidic system, employed for sample-dilution, homogenization, reactions, drug screening or toxicity analysis. Mixing of fluids becomes a challenging task at a micro level because of flow nature. This paper discusses some of the prominent design of passive micromixers, such as T, Y, and zig-zag micromixers. The mixing characteristics of these micromixers are simulated and compared based on mixing time, mixing length, and mixing index. Simulations are performed on multi-physics software, COMSOL. The present work will provide significant conclusions and guidelines to design and fabricate efficient and enhanced micromixers.

1. Introduction

A very low Reynolds number in microchannel flow results in laminar flow, which does not support mixing through flow. A better mixing can be achieved by proper control over the flow conditions or parameters such as velocity, pressure, and concentration etc. To change the flow parameters external forces are employed which are named as active micromixers, which are based on, acoustic, ultrasonic, dielectrophoretic, electro-kinetic, periodic electro-osmotic flow etc. [1]. Alternatively, to achieve better mixing the geometric shape of the channel is also modified which alters for flow pattern and helps in mixing. These types of micromixers are called as passive micromixers. The passive micromixers are suitable for remote and point of care devices. In this paper T, Y, and Zigzag mixer are compared based on their mixing performance. These mixers are generally used for their fabrication simplicity [2].

2. Methodology

The T, Y, and Zigzag mixers are simulated for their performances. The dimensions and flow conditions are mentioned in Table 1, below. The basic geometries of these mixers are given in Figure 1.

Table 1. Dimensions and flow conditions.

Parameter	Values
Dimensions (T- Mixer)	Length=10400 μ m, width=200 μ m, depth=200 μ m
Dimensions (Y- Mixer)	Length=10400 μ m, width=200 μ m, depth=200 μ m, angle=45 $^{\circ}$
Dimensions (Zigzag- Mixer)	Length=10400 μ m, width=200 μ m, depth=200 μ m, angle=90 $^{\circ}$
Reynolds's number	0.01, 10, 50, 100
Diffusion Coefficient	3.23 $\times 10^{-10}$ m ² /s
Concentration	Fluid1= 1, Fluid 2=0
Flow velocity at inlet (m/s)	5 $\times 10^{-5}$, 0.05, 0.25, 0.5
Density (kg/m ³)	Fluid1= 998, Fluid 2=1000

Based on aforesaid conditions the simulation is performed on COMSOL Multiphysics 5.3. The results are obtained for mixing efficiency. The expression for mixing efficiency is given by,

$$M = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{C_n - C}{C} \right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where C_n and C are normalized and expected concentrations. N is the number of mixing samples in the whole micromixer.

From Figure 1, the geometries of the T, Y and Zigzag micromixers can be visualized. In T and Zigzag mixers, the fluids are introduced through opposite faced channels, while in Y mixer, fluid is introduced at angular faced channels. The overall length along the straight axis is same; however, the total fluid traveling length is different in these mixers.

Figure 1. Geometries of (a) T-mixer; (b) Y-mixer; (c) Zigzag-micromixer.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2. Variations of (a) mixing index; (b) Pressure drop; and (c) velocity with different Re's and different mixers.

The comparisons of micromixers are made for pressure drop, mixing index and velocity values at different Re values. The overall mixing efficiencies of micromixers are presented in Figure 2a. Here, zigzag mixer shows high efficiency compared to T and Y-mixer. The mixing index of the zigzag mixer at Re of 0.01 is 99.99199% compared to T and Y micromixer, where mixing indexes are 99.999% and 99.99%. However, at Re of 10, 50 and 100, zigzag mixer's indexes are 99.7355%, 99.77688%, and 98.6958%, and for other mixer, it is below 80%. The reason for this difference is the different flow patterns created by the geometry of inlet. The pressure drop and velocity can be observed in Figures 2b and 2c, with respect to the distance along the width of the channel at different Reynolds numbers.

Table 2. Variations of mixing time for different Re's and different mixers at the exit of mixers.

S.No.	Reynolds Number(Re)	Mixing time solution for different micromixer (sec.)		
		T Mixer	Y Mixer	Zigzag Mixer
1	0.01	180	1530	192
2	10	0.9	0.54	0.41
3	50	0.31	0.13	0.1
4	100	0.07	0.08	0.04

Along with the concentration circulation, it is important to observe the mixing time for these mixers. Mixing time is simulated and results are presented in Table 2. The zigzag mixer is shown very less mixing time compared to others mixers at different Reynolds numbers. It is also evident from this table that mixing for very low Re value require high mixing time. In addition, at very low Re values, T mixer is faster compared to others.

4. Summary

In this paper, the performance of T, Y, and zigzag mixers are simulated based on mixing efficiency or mixing index and mixing time of micromixers at the exit of micromixer. It was observed that zigzag mixer is better than other mixers. The Numbers of sharp turns are more in zigzag micromixer; therefore, the magnitude of pressure drop gradient is more in zigzag micromixer compared to others micromixers. It is also observed, at very low Re values, T mixer is suitable for quick mixing.

5. References

[1] Lee, CY, Chang, CL, Wang, YN, Fu, LM, (2011), Microfluidic mixing: a review. International journal of molecular sciences, 12(5), 3263-3287.
 [2] Nguyen, NT, Wu, Z, (2004). Micromixers—a review. Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering, 15(2).

Synthesis of Epicyclic Gear Trains Using Spanning Trees

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Abstract

In this paper, a method is proposed to synthesize Epicyclic Gear Trains (EGTs) for a certain number of links, using the adjacency matrix of the spanning trees. When the adjacency matrix of possible EGT spanning trees for a certain order are obtained, an algorithm is run which assigns the required number of gear pairs in the adjacency matrix to make it a valid EGT graph. The adjacency matrices of possible EGTs are tested for displacement and rotational isomorphism, by hamming method for displacement isomorphism and separating graphs having more than one transfer vertex possible and need manual checking for rotational isomorphism.

Keywords: epicyclic gear train, isomorphism, adjacency matrix, transfer vertex, fundamental circuit, levels, spanning tree.

1. Introduction and Methodology

Different applications such as automobile transmissions, gas turbine engines, machine tool gear boxes, etc., use gear trains to obtain different speed ratios depending on the torque requirements of one or more driven shafts. Epicyclic gear trains (EGTs) are one such kind of gear train where the center of one gear revolves around the center of another gear. For an EGT of N links and 1 degree of freedom, there have to be $(N-1)$ turning pairs and $(N-2)$ gear pairs, according to the fundamental rules of EGTs [1]. For a given EGT, there are different ways of representing them, one being using graph theory [2]. In this, EGTs are shown as graphs using the linkages among various links of EGT; turning pairs as thin edges and gear pairs as thick edges. Representing an EGT by showing only its turning pairs following the above method is said to be the spanning tree of an EGT.

Graphs of EGTs can also be represented in form of linkage matrices, where each pairing is given a weightage and matrix is generated according to its linkage. Such matrices are called Linkage adjacency matrix (A) [3-5]. The rules of obtaining the linkage adjacency matrix are:

$A(i, j) = 2$ if link i and link j are connected by a gear pair;
1 if link i and link j are connected by a turning pair;
0 if there is no linkage between link i and link j .

While various possibilities of EGTs are possible, there is a chance of relabeling, which therefore needs an invariant to identify unique EGTs. Hamming method is used to eliminate the repeating graphs where hamming string acts as an invariant. Hamming distance between any two links is the number of digits at which codes differ. These hamming distances can be entered into a matrix which is said to be the hamming matrix of that chain. The sum of elements in each row of the hamming matrix is entered into a string called hamming string, which consists of the sums of all the elements of each row and sum of all elements in the string arranged in descending (or ascending) order [6].

With these hamming strings acting as invariants for displacement isomorphism, all non-unique hamming strings are declared as displacement isomorphic. Matrices with unique hamming strings go forward for rotational isomorphism test [7, 8].

These matrices are broken down into what are called fundamental circuits, which are spanning trees made into a closed loop by a gear pair. Every fundamental circuit has a vertex through which the level of turning pair changes from one side to another, called transfer vertex. In rotational isomorphism test, matrices with single transfer vertex possibility are considered as rotational non-isomorphic and the rest of the matrices are subjected to another iteration where they are manually checked for rotational isomorphism. Rotation graphs of these matrices are drawn and the transfer vertex of the EGT is found and linkage adjacency matrix is redrawn with modified linkages (pairing changes after transfer vertex is determined) accordingly. Graphs which pass the test are said to be rotational non-isomorphic and all the other matrices are rotational isomorphic.

Table 1. Number of EGTs for various links.

Number of links	Possible Spanning trees	Possible EGTs	Displacement Non-Isomorphic	Manual recheck need for Rotational Isomorphism	Non-Isomorphic EGTs after manual recheck
4	3	9	3	1	2
5	12	240	27	19	16
6	60	12600	176	68	120

2. Summary

The outcomes of the method proposed in the paper have been shown in Table 1 above. EGTs of order of up to 8 links are generated and displacement and rotational isomorphism tests are run and hence, the isomorphic EGTs are eliminated and only the unique EGTs are given as output. As a further work, automation of the manual work can be done, which improves the effectiveness of the method proposed.

3. References

- [1] Buchsbaum, F., and Fruedenstein, F., Synthesis of Kinematic Structure of Geared Kinematic Chains and Other Mechanisms, *Journal of Mechanisms*, Vol. 5, 1970, pp.357-392.
- [2] Dobrjanskyj, L., and Fruedenstein, F., Some Application of Graph Theory to the Structural Analysis of Mechanisms, *ASME Journal of Engineering for Industry*, Vol. 89, Series B, February 1967, pp.153-158.
- [3] Fruedenstein, F., An Application of Boolean Algebra to the Motion of Epicyclic drives, *ASME Journal of Engineering for Industry*, Vol. 93, Series B, February 1971, pp.176-182.
- [4] Uicker, J. J., Jr., and Raicu, A., A Method for the Identification and Recognition of Equivalence of Kinematic Chains, *Mechanisms and Machine Theory*, Vol. 10, 1975, pp.375-383.
- [5] Ravisankar, R., and Mruthyunjaya, T. S., Computerized Synthesis of the structure of Geared Kinematic Chains, *Mechanisms and Machine Theory*, Vol. 20, No. 5, pp. 367-387.
- [6] Rao YVD, Rao AC. Generation of Epicyclic Gear Trains of One Degree of Freedom. *ASME. J. Mech. Des.* 2008; 130(5):052604-052604-8. doi:10.1115/1.2890107.
- [7] Jae Kun Shin, Sundar Krishnamurthy, Standard code technique in the enumeration of epicyclic gear trains, *Mech. Mach. Theory* Vol. 28, No. 3, May 1992, pp. 347-355. 1993
- [8] Cheng-Ho Hsu, Jin-Jhu Hsu, An efficient methodology for the structural synthesis of geared kinematic chains, *Mech. Mach. Theory* Vol. 32, No. 8, July 1996, pp. 957-973.

Algorithm to Reduce the Number of Epicyclic Gear Trains for Isomorphism Test

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Abstract

An algorithm is used to reduce the number of Epicyclic gear trains of one degree of freedom (DOF) and with up to seven links. All possible Epi cyclic gear trains (EGT) of one DOF with a given number of links are generated from a set of EGTs of lower number of links. From the generated EGTs, structural isomorphic and rotational isomorphic ones are eliminated by assigning levels to turning pairs. An algorithm is proposed in this work, to reduce the number of EGTs to be handled to check for rotational isomorphism. Results for EGTs with seven links are presented.

1. Introduction and Methodology

In synthesis of EGTs assumptions made are EGTs are planar, have only binary joints, obey the general degree of freedom (DOF) equation and have unlimited rotatability for all links [1]. Each gear should have a turning pair on its axis and each link should have at least one turning pair to maintain constant centre distance between each gear pair. EGTs can be represented by Levai notations and in turn by graphs both structural and rotational [1-8].

In an EGT with 'n' number of links, there are 'n-2' number of gear pairs and 'n-1' number of turning pairs. The vertex incident with turning pairs is a transfer vertex (TV) [2, 3]. A subgraph with one gear pair and associated turning pairs is called as fundamental circuit (FC) [1-6]. All the turning pairs and gear pairs can be represented by edges and all the links by vertices in a graph of an EGT. Adjacency and rotational matrices are written from the graph of an EGT. Turning pairs and gear pairs are assigned values of '1' and '2' respectively while writing the adjacency matrix. Non-existence of connection is denoted by zero. From the adjacency matrix, transfer vertices for an EGT are determined using the algorithm proposed.

Higher order EGTs with 4, 5, 6, 7 links etc. are generated from EGTs of lesser number of links. Number of generated EGTs of one DOF with given number of links is listed in Table 1. All these generated EGTs are checked for structural isomorphism [3]. Using a suitable test for isomorphism like Hamming number method structurally isomorphic EGTs are eliminated. Hamming code for any two links is the number of digits at which the corresponding link codes differ in an adjacency matrix of an EGT [6]. Number of EGTs remaining after structural isomorphism are listed in Table 1.

Rotational isomorphism is tested using rotation graphs. Rotation graph of an EGT is drawn by knowing the TV for each gear pair in all the FCs of the EGT [6-13]. To locate the TV in each FC an algorithm proposed in this work. Levels are assigned to each of the turning pairs without violating the fundamental rules of EGTs [2-6]. TV in a particular FC is identified using the proposed algorithm. In any adjacency matrix of an EGT of given number of links, submatrices for 3-link, 4-link or higher number of links FCs are separated and using the proposed algorithm the TV for these FCs are identified. Once the TV is identified it is possible to write the rotational matrix for any EGT, using the same notation as used in the case of adjacency matrix. These rotational matrices are tested for rotational isomorphism. Number of EGTs remaining after isomorphism test are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Number of EGTs remaining after isomorphism test.

No of Links	EGTs Generated	EGTs remaining after structural isomorphism test	EGTs remaining after isomorphism test
3	1	1	1
4	6	3	2
5	72	19	6
6	1440	161	26
7	43200	2196	144

Let us consider a 5 link EGT as shown in Figure 1. Adjacency Matrix and Hamming code for it are shown in Figure 2. Hamming codes for all EGT's are compared for a particular number of links, similar hamming codes are discarded

there by eliminating structural isomorphs. Next TV's of each FC are identified and are shown in Figure 3. From these Rotation graphs are drawn, rotational matrix and rotational hamming are identified, these hamming codes are in turn compared and rotational isomorphs eliminated along with some special/not possible cases.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 & 2 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

128 [29 29 27 22 22]

Figure 1. Graph of 5-link EGT.

Figure 2. Adjacency Matrix and Hamming code for 5-link EGT in Figure 1.

Figure 3. FC's and levels of 5-link EGT in Figure 1.

2. Summary

Generation of all possible Epicyclic gear trains (EGT) of one degree of freedom (DOF) with a given number of links is done from a group of Epicyclic gear trains of lesser number of links using recursive method [3]. Tests for structural and rotational isomorphism are used to discard isomorphic EGTs. Before checking for rotational isomorphism, levels are assigned to turning pairs using fundamental rules [2-6]. Algorithm is proposed to reduce the number of EGTs to be checked for rotational isomorphism from a set of structurally non-isomorphic EGTs of one DOF and with up to seven links. The results for EGTs with 3 to 7 links are tabulated.

3. References

- [1] Buchsbaum, F., and F. Freudenstein. Synthesis of kinematic structure of geared kinematic chains and other mechanisms. *Journal of mechanisms* 5, no. 3 (1970): 357-392.
- [2] Ravisankar, R., and T. S. Mruthyunjaya. Computerized synthesis of the structure of geared kinematic chains. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 20, no. 5 (1985): 367-387.
- [3] Tsai, Lung-Wen. An application of the linkage characteristic polynomial to the topological synthesis of epicyclic gear trains. *Journal of mechanisms, transmissions, and automation in design* 109, no. 3 (1987): 329-336.
- [4] Kim, Jae Uk, and Byung Man Kwak. Application of edge permutation group to structural synthesis of epicyclic gear trains. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 25, no. 5 (1990): 563-574.
- [5] Shin, Jae Kyun, and Sundar Krishnamurty. Standard code technique in the enumeration of epicyclic gear trains. *Mechanism and Machine theory* 28.3 (1993): 347-355.
- [6] Rao, Y. V., and A. C. Rao. Generation of epicyclic gear trains of one degree of freedom. *Journal of Mechanical Design* 130.5 (2008): 052604.
- [7] Hsu, Cheng-Ho, and Kin-Tak Lam. A new graph representation for the automatic kinematic analysis of planetary spur-gear trains. *Journal of Mechanical Design* 114.1 (1992): 196-200.
- [8] Hsu, Cheng-Ho. A graph notation for the kinematic analysis of differential gear trains. *Journal of the Franklin Institute* 329.5 (1992): 859-867.
- [9] Hsu, Cheng-Ho, and Kin-Tak Lam. Automatic analysis of kinematic structure of planetary gear trains. *Journal of Mechanical Design* 115.3 (1993): 631-638.
- [10] Hsu, Cheng-Ho. Synthesis of kinematic structure of planetary gear trains by admissible graph method. *Journal of the Franklin Institute* 330.5 (1993): 913-927.
- [11] Hsu, Cheng-Ho. A graph representation for the structural synthesis of geared kinematic chains. *Journal of the Franklin Institute* 330.1 (1993): 131-143.
- [12] Hsu, Cheng-Ho. Displacement isomorphism of planetary gear trains. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 29.4 (1994): 513-523.
- [13] Hsu, Cheng-Ho, and Jin-Juh Hsu. An efficient methodology for the structural synthesis of geared kinematic chains. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 32.8 (1997): 957-973.

Design and Analysis of Missile Tail Fin

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Abstract

An improved version of a tail fin which can increase the stability of a missile is designed by modifying the previously proposed in literature. A right-angled trapezoidal fin and an isosceles trapezoidal fin which are most widely used in missiles are selected for this study. A double wedged aerofoil profile is given to reduce the drag. Computational fluid dynamics approach is used to find the lift on both fins and these results are compared to find the better fin among the both. Further, shear stresses are found on the selected fin in order to redesign for making pockets. Thus, a better design for the fin is proposed in the paper which increases the stability and endurances during operation.

1. Introduction

Defence is the effective strategy taken by any nation for their safety in today's scenario. And missiles have been the powerful tool to accomplish this strategy. If a missile is launched without fins, it would begin to wobble after leaving the launcher thus veering off from its flight path. The problem here is that the missile's Centre of pressure (C_p) would be ahead of its Centre of gravity (C_g), which increases the instability and the aerodynamic pressure acting on the missile body which starts to steer off the course. To reduce this problem fins are used to create the required lift force against the forces generated which disturbs the missile path.

There are different approaches used to evaluate the design of a fin in literature. August et al. gives a preliminary design of smart structure Fins for High-Speed Missiles. Design includes a light-weight, low-cost, smart missile fin which is capable of surviving the supersonic operating environment while providing performance comparable to existing missile fins of that time [1]. El-Mahdy et al. [2] used three different techniques for evaluating the design of fin namely, experimental, computational and engineering techniques. They also determined variation in lift and drag coefficients and centre of pressure location with the flight conditions for different design. Coming to the selection of the basic shape of fin, there are many shapes. From which trapezoidal shape is said to be have better aerodynamic qualities [3]. After selecting the basic shape, a previously proposed design is considered to modify it to get a better design. In this study an improved tail fin is proposed which can increase the stability of a missile. A right-angled trapezoidal fin and an isosceles trapezoidal fin that are most widely used in missiles are selected with double wedged aerofoil profile. Computational fluid dynamics analysis is performed on fins to determine the lift on both fins and are compared to find the better. Further, shear stresses are also determined to redesign for making pockets.

2. Model Generation

The model with the proposed design is generated using the SolidWorks programme. An adaptive design is generated from the previously proposed one which is of shape. The newly designed model is of right-angled trapezoidal shape as shown in the Figure 1. When simulations are performed on these fins with planar profiles, the induced drag is increased. To reduce this, drag an aerofoil profile is made on these fins as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. (a) Isosceles trapezoidal fin; (b) Right-Angled trapezoidal fin.

Figure 2. Fins with aerofoil profile.

3. Results and Discussion

The two designed fins models are used to calculate the lift force generated on them at various angles of attack through computational fluid dynamics analysis. The lift generated on the two fins are compared as shown in the Figure 3. These results show us that the tail fin 2 has got a greater lift than that of the tail fin 1. Therefore, the tail fin 2 is selected as the better one which is of shape right-angled trapezoid. Then the shear stresses are found on the fin face as in Figure 4. From these results pockets are made on the missile to decrease the mass-weight ratio.

Figure 3. Graph showing the variation in the lift generated on the two fin modals.

Figure 4. Shear stresses found on the fin.

Figure 5. Final Optimized fin.

4. Summary

Thus, the final optimized fin which is better than the previously proposed one is as in Figure 5. This fin design can be modified further for implementation in future missile systems.

5. References

- [1] August JA and Joshi SP, 1996, Preliminary Design of Smart Structure Fins for High-Speed Missiles, Smart Structures and Materials 1996: Industrial and Commercial Applications of Smart Structures Technologies, Volume 2721, DOI: 10.1117/12.239116.
- [2] El-Mahdy LA, Ahmed MY, Mahmoud OK, Abdel-Hameed OE, 2016, Experimental, Computational, and Empirical Evaluation of Supersonic Missile Aerodynamic Coefficients, In Proceedings of the 17th Int. AMME Conference 2016. Vol. 19, p. 21.
- [3] Peak of flight Newsletter. 2017, Issue 442, page 1-10.

Autonomous Dental Implant Robot

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Abstract

Dental arms are the most common equipment used by any dentist. This multi-tasking equipment has many sub-functionalities which include driller, water sprinkler and many more. But the problem with most of these is that they are still operated manually which not only reduces the efficiency by consuming more time but also can lead to inaccuracies while operating on teeth [1]. The surgeries that are performed are not easy either to demonstrate, learn or perform. Hence there is a requirement for a system which can provide solutions to these problems. This robot in development would be capable of demonstrating to medical students in dentistry and train them at initial stages. Also, once fully developed for commercial purposes this robot should perform surgeries on patients at later stages either controlled by a trained practitioner or making it completely autonomous. So, there is a crucial need to automate this machine [2]. Energy loss in vibration of drill while operating on the tooth during tooth implantation is to be kept at minimal value and this is studied in conjunction with all the links and joints of the robot which influence the tip of the end-effector. The results obtained from DAQ systems and accelerometer setup shows us the vibrational stability and need for improvement in the robot.

Keywords: dental robotic arm, vibration, accelerometer, image processing, end effector, signal filtering.

1. Introduction and Methodology

In the present work a code for a micro Controller has been developed to move the end-effector of the Indigenous Designed Dental Robotic Arm and to perform the drilling operations with specified accuracy. Initially a code is used for forward kinematics of the robot for thorough understanding of the motions. The code for forward Kinematics of RPP manipulator is tested successfully on the fabricated dental robot shown in Figure 1.

Before the actual design and fabrication of the dental robotic arm vigorous forward kinematics calculation are made. Manipulator Motion Control for Velocity, acceleration and Force is also verified [3]. Motion planning for drilling operation with open loop is implemented. Scope to extend this with Image Processing and Computer Vision to improve the accuracy and fully automate the motions is under consideration.

Efficiency of the robot is studied by considering the amount of energy loss during the operation of the drill. Energy loss in vibration of drill while operating on the tooth during tooth implantation is to be kept at minimal value and this is studied in conjunction with all the links and joints of the robot which influence the tip of the end-effector (the drill tip) [4]. To estimate the amount of energy loss we need to acquire the vibration and make an analysis of the vibration of the Dental Robotic Arm. Once the robot is repeatedly run with no errors, accelerometer is used to acquire the vibration. Data Acquisition system (DAQ) and Lab View software are used to analyze the vibration signals collected [5]. Since the data is collected is in raw form and has addition of noises in the form of surrounding disturbances, the signals collected must be filtered so that the useful main signal is isolated for analysis [6].

The results obtained are used to determine the efficiency of the robot fabricated and based on these results decisions are made with regard to system improvement.

Image processing can be implemented in order to increase the level of automation of the robot. While integrating image processing aspect thresholding has to be used to detect the shape of the object [7]. It is planned to detect only some small objects like a cube or a sphere and later algorithms will be developed to detect human face and teeth in order to make the dental surgeries fully automated [8-10].

2. Summary

A code has been developed to automate the existing dental robotic arm. Using accelerometer and DAQ systems the vibrational signals from the end effector are collected and analyzed. It is concluded that the moving motion does not cause a considerable disturbance, but the drilling motion constitutes for the most of the disturbance, and

has to be decreased, by using torsional dampers, increasing stiffness of material etc. Image processing can be later on integrated to make the setup completely automated.

Table 1. Vibration limits of different components of a general robot.

Figure 1. Dental Robotic arm.

Vibration Limits	Balance Condition Displacement, mils Peak to Peak at 1x rpm	Overall Velocity in/sec Peak 10 - 1,000 Hz	Overall Acceleration, g Peak 0 - 5,000 Hz
Electric Motors 1,000 – 2,000 rpm	2.0	0.2	0.5
> 2,000 rpm	1.0	0.2	1.0
Generators	2.0	0.2	0.5
Centrifugal Fans < 600 rpm	4.0	0.3	0.5
600 – 1,000 rpm	3.0	0.3	1.0
1,000 – 2,000 rpm	2.0	0.3	1.5
> 2,000 rpm	1.0	0.3	2.0

3. References

- [1] Y. V. D. Rao, Alivelu M. Parimi, D. S. P. Rahul, Dikshant Patel, Y. V. Nitin Mythreya, Robotics in Dental Implantation, International Conference on Advancements+ in Materials for Manufacturing (ICAAMM-2016), Materials Today Procedia, Elsevier.
- [2] Y. V. D. Rao, Alivelu M. Parimi, D. S. P. Rahul, Dikshant Patel, Y. V. Nitin Mythreya, Robotics in Dentistry, the 22nd Conference On Mechanical Engineering and Technology 2016, IIT (BHU), Varanasi.
- [3] Suyash Yeotikar, Alivelu M. Parimi, Y. V. D. Rao, Automation of end effector guidance of robotic arm for Dental Implantation using Computer Vision, IEEE International conference on Distributed Computing, VLSI, Electrical Circuits and Robotics (DISCOVER 2016), (NITK), Surathkal, 13-14, August 2016.
- [4] Y. V. D. Rao, Alivelu M. Parimi, An Understanding of construction of robotic arm for massaging, National Conference on Recent Advances in Manufacturing and Robotics-2016, April 16.
- [5] S. N. Das, Dr. Y. V. D. Rao and Dr. Sabareesh, A Review on Technological Trends in Vibration and Shock Isolation, National Conference on Recent Advances in Manufacturing and Robotics-2016, April 2016.
- [6] Reza N. Jazar, Theory of applied robotics Kinematics, Dynamics and Control, springer.
- [7] Robert J. Schilling, Fundamentals of Robotics- Analysis and Control. Pearson Education, Ed2008.
- [8] Jim Defranza and Deniel Gagliadi, Introduction to Linear Algebra with application. Tata McGraw Hill, Ed2012.
- [9] R. K. Mittal and I. J. Nagrath, Robotics and Control. McGraw Hill, ed2014.
- [10] John J. Craig, Introduction to Robotics mechanisms and Control. Pearson Education, Third Edition.

Design and Optimization of Single Speed Two-Step Reduction Gearbox

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Abstract

The objective of this project is to design, optimize and fabricate a single speed two-step reduction gearbox for an ATV (All-Terrain vehicle). The Gearbox is designed to couple with a CVT (Continuous Variable Transmission) to give maximum torque output to the wheels at different terrains. The objective of this research is to increase overall the performance of the transmission system, by reducing the overall size and mass of the gearbox and efficient with an engine up-to 350 cc. The Modelling part was carried out in SolidWorks 2017 and the analysis part was carried out in ANSYS 15.0. Different approaches were carried for designing, as well as calculating the parameters for bearings, and oil seals. The designs were optimized after the analysis.

1. Introduction

Gearbox is a part of a transmission system which consists of speed-changing gears and shafts for speed and torque conversion from a rotating power source (Engine) to another device – axle which rotates the wheels of the vehicle. Gearbox reduces the RPM of the engine to the tires and increases the torque output. It helps to drive the vehicle via different terrains and road conditions. In this project, a two stage-gearbox is designed, which will help in smooth running of an All-Terrain Vehicle. The design is such that it will not only help in longer and smoother functioning of all the parts that are coupled with it in the ATV but also ease the serviceability of the overall Gearbox.

2. General Specifications

The Gearboxes available in the market are bulkier, costlier and heavier. This Gearbox is designed in such a way that a single brake caliper can be mounted on it. This will facilitate the mounting of a single braking system for both the wheels in the rear, therefore reducing the un-sprung mass of the vehicle. Fins are added to the casing to increase the heat dissipation of the gearbox and increase the overall strength. Objectives are as follows:

- a. Reducing mass of the gearbox.
- b. Improving the torque output.
- c. Testing the Performance.

The structural analysis was done in ANSYS 15.0 and further optimization to reduce mass was done using Topology tool in ANSYS 18.0. The optimization further reduced the mass of the gears by 15.5% and shafts by 27.46%.

3. Equations

The required gear ratio for a vehicle with 210 kg was calculated as 11.86. A two-stage compound gear-train such as shown in Figure 1 was used to achieve this ratio. The equations given in ANSI/AGMA 2001-D4 were used to find the bending and contact stress on the tooth of the gears:

$$N_p = \frac{2k}{(1+2m)\sin^2\phi} \left(m + \sqrt{m^2 + (1+2m)\sin^2\phi} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $m = N_g / N_p$. The equation used to calculate the diameters of the shaft is:

$$d = \left\{ \frac{16n}{\pi} \left[\frac{2(K_f M_a)}{S_c} + \frac{\left[3(K_{fs} T_m)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{S_{ut}} \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2)$$

Following equation was used to calculate the load rating of the bearings:

$$C_{10} = F_D \left[\frac{x_D}{x_D + (\theta - x_D) [\ln(1/R_D)]^{1/b}} \right]^{1/a} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. Compound Gear-set.

4. Summary

This paper provides the entire design methodology for designing a single speed two-step reduction gearbox and ways to optimize it. The paper also focuses on ways to improve the performance of the gearbox.

5. References

- [1] Richard Budynas and Keith Nisbett, 2008. Shigley's Mechanical Engineering Design (Vol. 8). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [2] American Gear Manufacturers Association, 1994. Fundamental rating factors and calculation methods for involute spur and helical gear teeth. American Gear Manufacturers Association.
- [3] Calvin O'Brien, Erin Ebsch, Jenna Kudla and Bridget Quick, 2012. ME 450 Final Report Baja Gear Reduction. In: University of Michigan - Ann Arbor.

Design and Optimization of Wheel Assembly and Suspension Assembly

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Abstract

This paper states the complete designing and optimization process of a suspension assembly for an All-Terrain Vehicle. The assembly is designed keeping in consideration the rules laid by SAE BAJA 2018 and to achieve minimum weight possible to have the least unsprung mass. The suspension geometry was designed using LOTUS suspension analyzer and dynamic analysis was carried out using ADAMS Car. Modeling was done out in SolidWorks 2017 and the analysis part was carried out in ANSYS 15.0.

1. Introduction

The unsprung mass provides proper drive stability and load balancing of the vehicle while taking direct impacts from the ground. Therefore, it becomes imperative to reduce the mass of the wheel assembly and the rims and tires to increase the riding characteristics of an ATV. Also, a good wheel assembly is must sustain all loading forces during accelerating, braking, cornering and, tilting over a long period of time. Thus it is required to design the wheel assembly considering all these factors. A failure of any component of the suspension assembly can result in the breakdown of the automobile and in some cases, it might also be disastrous for the driver. Therefore, a proper structural analysis has to be done considering all possible loading conditions and optimization has to done to improve the design.

2. General Specifications

A dynamic analysis was done in Lotus Suspension Analyzer and hard points were obtained while keeping the toe and camber change minimum and caster and kingpin angle constant during the dynamic bump. The hard points obtained in a highly iterative process was exported to ADAMS Car Sim 2018 to get more accurate results. R10 rims in the front and R11.5 rims have been used in the rear. The front as to the rear mass distribution of the car is 40:60. The Weight of the vehicle is considered to be 215 kg along with the driver.

Table 1. Design parameters.

Specifications	Notations	Values
Wheel Base	B	1.7 m
Distance of rear axle from CoG	L	0.15 m
Height of CoG	H	0.545 m
Wheel track	J	1.4732 m
Coefficient of Adhesion	μ	0.45
The radius of curvature of shortest turn	c	1.69 m
Weight of car + driver	M	215 Kg
Acceleration	a	2.5 m ² /s

All the forces that are acting on components have been found out on the above basis and according to the abovementioned specifications which were pre-calculated based on the SAE BAJA Rulebook and preliminary CAD model of the complete vehicle.

The front wheel assembly consists of the following:

- a) Upright,
- b) Spindle,
- c) Taper Roller Bearing – 2,

- d) Wheel hub,
- e) Castle nut.

In order to finalize the wheel assembly, it is important to understand how each component is assembled and how are they connected to each other. The outer race of both the bearings is press-fitted into the hub. After that, the inner race of the bearings is press-fitted on the spindle. The nut is tightened onto one end of the spindle and a split pin is inserted into the hole made in the spindle for positively locking the wheel assembly and the other end is press-fitted to the upright and secured with the help of 4 Allen bolts.

While generating the mesh, proximity and curvature feature is more frequently used to generate more amount of nodes at fillets and cavities. This feature is helpful, as stress concentration tends to accumulate more in regions of bends and cavities. The analysis is done on ANSYS 15.0.

Figure 1. Exploded view of the wheel assembly.

Figure 2. Deformation due to bump on upright and spindle.

Figure 3. ADAMS Car simulation of front suspension.

Figure 4. Camber and Toe variation during jounce-rebound of rear suspension geometry.

3. Summary

This paper provides a way of preparing ideal suspension geometry for an All-Terrain Vehicle and the complete systematic methodology for designing and optimizing of the wheel assembly and its associated components.

4. References

[1] BAJA SAE INDIA Rule Book 2018.
 [2] Richard Budynas and Keith Nisbett, 2008. Shigley's Mechanical Engineering Design (Vol. 8). New York: McGraw-Hill.
 [3] V. B. Bhandari, 1999. Design of Machine Elements, 8th edition, Wiley.
 [4] Pruthviraj Vitthal Wable, Sahil Sanjog Shah (2017), Design Analysis & Optimization of Hub Used in FSAE Cars, ISSN: 2319-8753, Vol. 6, Issue 8, 16799-16808.

Analysis of Redesign for Conventional Tool Box Using Design for Manufacturing and Assembly Approach

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Abstract

The present work aims to redesign the conventional screwdriver portable tool box using various Design for Manufacturing and Assembly (DFMA) guidelines, based on Boothroyd DFMA techniques. The main consideration for the redesign is based on the KANO model customer satisfaction index, cost competitiveness and sustainability issues of the product. Initially, customer survey has been carried out to understand the customer requirements, followed by analyzing the customer requirements using KANO model. Tool box design has been modeled using SOLIDWORKS. Finally, the proposed modifications have been analyzed using DFMA software and the redesign has been compared with present design.

1. Introduction

Over the years, technological advancement and industrial development requires superior product in terms of cost competitiveness, functionality and sustainability [1]. The one of the biggest challenge to develop a required product is customer demands are very dynamics and changes with respect various categories such as age, gender, country and many more [2]. Estorilio and Marcelo [3] observed that the decisions taken in product design stage not only have a significant effect on product manufacturing ability, but also in the production costs.

DFMA is a methodology which gives the designer a thought process and guidance so that the product may be developed in a way which favors the easy manufacturing and assembly process [4]. DFMA has been translated in numerous operative tools in order to simplify product design and to support designers in making design decisions. In this context, this paper study the effect of Kano model and DFMA analysis on product development. The case study will cover cost estimation, reduction in number of components, assembly time estimation and sustainability analysis.

2. General Specifications

DFA, DFM and sustainability analysis have been done on the design of conventional toolbox. DFA works on the principle of minimizing the number of parts without trading off with the product's functionality. Initially, the product has been modeled in SOLIDWORK software based on customer requirements and KANO model analysis. Figure 1a shows the conventional tool box. After analyzing the conventional toolbox, the DFA software suggested elimination of hinge part. Accordingly, hinge part was eliminated and redesigned the toolbox by introducing a hinge joint between base part and upper cover. After suggested modification, substantial reduction in labor time and cost is observed and DFA index increased by 56.8%.

Furthermore, DFM analysis has been done for each part of the conventional toolbox. Based on the DFM guidelines, the toolbox has been further modified based on the manufacturing process guidelines Implementation of DFA and DFM guidelines shows significant improvement in total cost reduction. The total cost is reduced by 18% for a batch size of 125 with 1000 product life volume. Additionally, the product has been studied based on the sustainability analysis using SOLIDWORK software. The major aim is to reduce carbon footprint, energy consumption and other kind of pollutions. The product has been suitably modified based on the customer requirements, DFA, DFMA and sustainability issues.

3. Equations

The following equation is used to calculate DFA index:

$$DFA = \frac{100N_m t_m}{t_a} \quad (1)$$

where N_m = theoretical minimum number of parts, t_m = minimum assembly time per part (s), t_a = estimated total assembly time(s).

Figure 1. (a) Conventional Toolbox; (b) Redesigned toolbox.

4. Result

The percentage changes can be summed up in the following table:

Table 1. Cost analysis.

	Total Cost (\$)	Piece Part Cost (\$)	Initial Tooling Investment (\$)
Center part	11%	2%	15%
Bottom part	13%	23%	8%
Top part	25%	11%	30%

5. Summary

The conventional tool box is modeled based on the customer requirements (KANO model) and available products in the market. The conventional tool box is modified based on DFAM guidelines. Firstly, the product is evaluated based on the various DFA criteria namely, theoretical minimum number of parts, DFA index and assembly cost. Also, DFM guidelines are implemented to understand the easiness and suitability of the manufacturing process for conventional tool box. The suggested modification shows improvement in the DFA index by 56.8% and reduction in total manufacturing cost by 18%. An attempt has been made to analyze the modified product based on the sustainability analysis.

6. References

- [1] Annamalai K, Naiju CD, Karthik S, Mohan PM, 2013, Early Cost Estimate of Product During Design Stage Using Design for Manufacturing and Assembly Principles, *Advanced Materials Research*, 622, 540-544.
- [2] Gérson T, 2007, Integrating the Kano Model and QFD for Designing New Products, *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 18(6), 599-612.
- [3] Estorilio C, Marcelo CS, 2006, Cost reduction of a diesel engine using the DFMA, *Product: Management and Development*, 4 (2), 95-103.
- [4] Martin O, (2002), Design for Manufacture, *Journal of Material Processing Technology*, 122 (2-3), 318-321.

Formula Generation for Suspension Analysis Using Lotus Shark

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Abstract

Lotus shark is a suspension analysis software with a problem i.e. process of analysis is time consuming as it uses hit and trial method to adjust hard points and there is no specific range of such points through which suspension is considered as a perfect suspension. To solve this problem, new formula is generated to specify a fix range of hard points, which are shown by graphs. It gives quick result in double wishbone suspension analysis.

1. Introduction

Lotus suspension analysis (LSA) software is a suspension analysis software which shows hard point, these points control static and kinematics of suspension. With the help of these hard points, suspension is adjusted by moving them. A roll point is fixed to check the status of suspension while performing analysis. The movement of roll point should be minimum [1]. In this work, formulae are generated to eliminate hit and trail method and find a fix range between which hard points are adjusted to achieve analysis result quickly.

2. Procedure

Process of formula generation through experimentation and calculation is described in flow chart given below.

```

New → file → front suspension → double wishbone → rear suspension → double wishbone → Done
└─ Open list formatted SDF → record hard point values (old value) → analysis performed for both front and rear suspension → start analysis by moving hard points → analyze movement of hard points
└─ roll point movement is minimum → analysis completed → open list formatted SDF again → write down new hard point values (new values) → subtract coordinate of old value from new value of hard points → range obtained from hard points movement → this movement of points shown in graphs → formula generated by interpolation method [2].
    
```

3. Equations

With the help of old and new coordinates, new formula is generated for front and rear suspension.

$$Y_{final} = 1.163y - 133.78 \pm 0.8y \text{ (Front)} \quad (1) \quad Z_{final} = -0.861z + 40.898 \pm 0.2z \text{ (Front)} \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{final} = -0.1723y + 262.74 \pm 0.6y \text{ (Rear)} \quad (3) \quad Z_{final} = -0.7951z + 57.501 \pm 0.15z \text{ (Rear)} \quad (4)$$

where, y and z are old hard point values.

Figure 1. Hard points of double wishbone suspension.

4. Figures

Labeled diagram of hard points of double wishbone suspension in Lotus shark is shown in Figure 1. Variation of old and new point coordinates in rear suspension analysis is shown by graph in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Rear analysis in y-axis.

Similar analysis is being carried in front analysis and generate graph from analyzed data.

5. Tables

Hard points range is defined for rear suspension analysis by subtracting standard coordinate (old) values from analyzed coordinate (new) values as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Old and new coordinates and its ranges for rear suspension.

Point no.	Y(old)	Y(new)	Variation (%)	Z (old)	Z (new)	Variation (%)	Range (%)
1	313	122	-61.02	225	249	10.67	-60 to +10
2	280	199	-28.93	185	204	10.27	-3 to 10
12	308	312	1.3	227	226	-0.44	-1 to 3

Similar method is use to draw table for front analysis and get range for it.

6. Summary

Hit and trial method has been eliminated by generating formula to get quick results and ease in analysis.

7. References

- [1] L. C. Ltd., 2012. Getting started with Lotus Suspension Analysis.
<https://www.scribd.com/document/331039490/Getting-Started-With-Lotus-Suspension-Analysis>
 [2] Rajkumar Kewat, Anil Kumar Kundu, Kuldeep Kumar, Rohit Lather and Mohit Tomar, 2014. Dynamic Analysis of Double Wishbone and Double Wishbone with S Link + Toe Link, Int. J. Eng. Res. Appl., Special Issue, 247-251.

Numerical Simulation of Clot Movement Inside Patient Specific Brain Blood Vessels

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Abstract

In the present work we use the open source flow solver OpenFOAM to simulate the movement of a blood clot in patient specific blood vessels inside human brain. The behavior of the blood clot is captured with a two-phase flow approach where the clot and blood are taken as two different, immiscible phases with different viscoelastic properties. The Hershel-Bulkley non-Newtonian fluid model is used to approximate the shear thinning behavior of blood. The clot behavior is approximated using the same model with different physical parameters. Results related to the clot interaction with the branching in the blood vessels are presented.

1. Introduction

Blood acts as a carrier of oxygen to body parts including the brain and removes carbon dioxide from it. When an artery is blocked because of a clot, the brain cells (neurons) and tissue starve for oxygen and will not be able to generate the required energy without oxygen. Therefore, brain cells are damaged or die within few minutes of blockage leading to a stroke. A simulation based study of the behavior of a blood clot inside brain blood vessels particularly at bifurcations in the vessels can shed more light on the blocking process. In the present study we investigate the movement of a clot inside a patient specific brain blood vessel using the open source flow solver called OpenFOAM [1]. The patient specific blood vessel geometry is extracted using MRI based techniques and is shown in Figure 1. The behavior of the blood clot is captured with a two-phase flow approach where the clot and blood are taken as two different, immiscible phases with different viscoelastic properties.

Figure 1. Patient specific blood vessel geometry inside human brain.

2. Governing Equations

The equations governing the incompressible flow of a viscoelastic fluid are the continuity equation and the Navier-Stokes equations along with the constitutive equation for the fluid. These equations are given respectively by

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{U} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \vec{U}}{\partial t} + \vec{U} \cdot \nabla \vec{U} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \tau' + \rho \vec{g} \quad (2)$$

Here $\tau' = \tau_s + \tau_p$ gives the extra stress tensor, $\tau_s = 2\eta_s(\dot{\gamma})D$ is the solvent contribution to the extra stress tensor, η_s is the solvent viscosity which is the function of shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$, $D = (\nabla\bar{U} + \nabla\bar{U}')/2$ is the rate of deformation tensor. The polymeric contribution to the extra stress tensor τ_p is given by the differential equation shown below where $\overset{\nabla}{\tau}_p$ is the upper convected time derivative:

$$f(\tau_p)\tau_p + \lambda\left(\overset{\nabla}{\dot{\gamma}}\right)\tau_p + h(\tau_p) = 2\eta_p\left(\overset{\nabla}{\dot{\gamma}}\right)D \quad (3)$$

Further details on these equations and the solution procedure for viscoelastic flows is given in Pimenta and Alves [2]. The above mentioned equations are already implemented in OpenFOAM and are used to study the blood flow and clot behavior inside the brain blood vessels.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the clot division process due to shearing at a bifurcation in the blood vessel and the distribution of streamlines which are colored by velocity values. A fixed blood flow velocity of 0.1 m/s is specified at the inlet to the domain. Higher values of flow velocity can be observed in the smaller branches of the blood vessel. We also notice that the initially spherical blood clot deforms and touches the vessel walls as it moves.

Figure 2. Clot (shown in dark red color) shearing at a bifurcation and streamlines distribution during the simulation process.

4. Conclusion

The movement of an initially spherical clot is simulated inside a patient specific blood vessel geometry using the open source flow solver called OpenFOAM. The Hershel Bulkley model is used to approximate the constitutive behavior of the blood and the clot. We observe that the clot sticks to the wall of the blood vessel and is deformed by the fluid flow during movement inside the blood vessel. The clot is then sheared into two portions at the bifurcation in the blood vessel. As expected, higher flow velocities are observed inside the smaller branches of the blood vessel.

5. References

- [1] Henry G Weller, G Tabor, Hrvoje Jasak, and C Fureby. A tensorial approach to computational continuum mechanics using object-oriented techniques. *Computers in physics*, 12(6):620–631, 1998.
- [2] F Pimenta and MA Alves. Stabilization of an open-source finite-volume solver for viscoelastic fluid flows. *Journal of Non-Newtonian Fluid Mechanics*, 239:85–104, 2017.

Self-Rolling of Bio-Polymer Films into Tubular Geometries

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Abstract

Smart biopolymers are known to respond to the stimulus offered by the surrounding environment in various forms such as: temperature, humidity (water), pH, light and electricity. In this work, self-rolling of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) thin films under aqueous environment into tubular structures has been demonstrated through experiments and finite element (FE) simulations. The mechanism of rolling is based on the well-known bi-metallic strip principle in mechanics. However, in the present case, the differential swelling through the thickness of the film provides the driving force for bending in contrast to the differential thermal expansion in the case of bi-metallic strip. The FE simulations help us gain better insight into the folding mechanism and thus pave ways to the development of design rules for predictive design of the rolled-up structures. The dependence of the curvature of the rolled-up film on various parameters such as thickness, eigenstrain and width of the film has been studied through FE simulations and the results are compared with the experiments.

1. Introduction

Smart biopolymers show autonomous response to stimuli of various forms such as temperature, humidity (water), pH and light etc [1, 2]. Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) polymer has superior features such as excellent physico-mechanical and chemical properties, nontoxicity and biocompatibility and high swelling rate, which make them suitable candidates for biomaterial and biomedical applications [3]. PVA films are a family of hydrogel materials, which can accommodate large volume fractions of water amongst the free volume available in the chain network. Hence, when PVA films are exposed to an aqueous environment, water readily diffuses in to the film resulting in swelling. However, due to the time required for diffusion to happen, during the process of water diffusion, there exists a differential swelling through the thickness of the film. The differential swelling through the thickness of the film results in net bending moment causing the film to bend. The above mechanism is similar to the well-known bimetallic strip experiment in mechanics and recently explored area of rolled-up nanotubes through controlled release of eigenstrains due to lattice mis-match [4]. Similarly, the controlled coupling between geometry and strain lead to several interesting features such as wrinkles, folds, delaminated buckles at micro and nano scale [5]. The geometrical features obtained in all the above techniques depend on the loading and the boundary conditions in addition to the initial geometrical configuration of the film-substrate systems. In this work, we primarily focus on the development of a rolled-up PVA tube due to differential swelling through the thickness.

2. Experimental Process

A PVA film is prepared by solvent casting method and cut samples of 5 mm x 2mm x 0.08 mm size. Then, the film is kept on a water layer (fixing the left edge and leaving the right edge free) allowing the water to diffuse into the film. Due to the differential swelling through the thickness, the film starts bending at the free right edge as shown in Figure 1a.

3. Modeling the Rolling Process of the PVA Film

In this work, the thin film is modeled as a composite shell with left end constrained in all directions while the right edge is free in concurrence with the experimental conditions. In the case of experiments, the film bends as the chemical eigenstrain generated due to differential swelling offers the necessary driving force. However, in the model, we idealize the chemical strain as thermal strain and solve the thermo-mechanical problem. To simulate the gradient of chemical strain through the thickness, a linearly varying coefficient of thermal expansion is prescribed through the thickness of the film. Hence, when the film temperature is increased from the initial state, the effect simulates the differential strain through the thickness. We use commercial FEA software Abaqus to perform the simulation of bending of the film. For the present work, the film is assumed to be homogeneous, isotropic and linear elastic with an elastic modulus of $E = 900$ MPa and Poisson's ratio 0.3.

Figure 1. (a) Experimental.

Figure 1. (b) Simulation.

4. FEA Simulations and Results

The film is discretized with composite shell elements (S4R) with through thickness linear variation of coefficient of thermal expansion. In order to account for the differential residence contact time of the film with water surface along the length, a nonlinear temperature variation is prescribed along the length. The objective is to provide higher net eigenstrain at fixed end (highest contact time with water) and minimum eigenstrain at free end (less contact time with water). The simulation has been carried out with four different film thickness values: 80 μm , 120 μm , 160 μm and 200 μm . The representative rolled-up configuration is shown in Figure 1b. All the simulations have been carried out for different thermal strains equivalent to experimental chemical strain. The normalized curvature (k^2/t) at the mid-point (along the length) of the film shows a unique relation with a normalized eigenstrain (ϵ^2/t^2) for films of different lengths and thickness values.

5. Summary

An experimental procedure has been developed to generate rolled-up structures of PVA films. A FEA model to demonstrate the mechanism of folding in the polymeric films has been developed. The normalized curvature of the rolled-up tube at the center of film shows a unique relationship with the normalized eigenstrain for films of different thickness and lengths.

6. References

- [1] Rath Amrita, Mathesan Santhosh, Ghosh Pijush 2016, Folding behaviour and molecular mechanism of cross-linked biopolymer film in response to water, *Soft Matter*, 12: 9210.
- [2] David H Gracias, 2013, Stimuli responsive self-folding using thin polymer films. *Current Opinion in Chemical Engineering*, 2: 112–119.
- [3] Christina L. Randall, Evin Gultepe and David H. Gracias, 2012, Self-folding devices and materials for biomedical applications, *Trends in Biotechnology*, 30(3): 138–146.
- [4] Schmidt O.G., Eberl K., 2001, Nanotechnology: Thin solid films roll up into nanotubes, *Nature*, 410: 168–168.
- [5] Cao Y, and Hutchinson J. W., 2012, Wrinkling Phenomena in Neo-Hookean Film/Substrate Bilayers. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 79(May): 031019.

Effect of Surface Tension on the Self-Folding Behavior of Smart Biopolymers

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Abstract

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is one material which shows hygromorphic behavior. The PVA film folds due to the strain gradient caused by the diffusion of water. This folding is characterized by the rate of folding, the time taken for the initiation of folding and the curvature at the fully folded state. These characteristics have been monitored in water with addition of different concentrations of surfactants. The surfactant used in these experiments is Cetrimonium bromide (CTAB). By this, the effect of surface tension on the folding is studied. It is observed that, with increase in surface tension, these characteristics change significantly. These results help in developing a continuum scale model to depict the folding phenomenon in which a cohesive layer can be used to mimic the surface tension effect.

1. Introduction

Stimuli responsive materials are rapidly growing to an interdisciplinary technology with an idea of incorporating smart behavior materials surrounding our everyday life process. Stimuli responsive materials are smart polymers, which responds to a small change in the humidity, pH, temperature, electric/magnetic field and solvent by undergoing a drastic change in their structure and property. Self-folding is one of the means to respond to these external stimuli. Self-folding is a means of achieving desired patterns and shapes necessary for certain functionality. In this work, the solvent triggered self-folding behavior is studied. Poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) is one such polymer which exhibits reversible self-folding behavior in response to water/water-based solvents [1]. Its biocompatible and biodegradable properties bring a special interest in various biomedical applications [2]. In this work, an attempt has been made to characterize the effect of surface tension of the trigger solvent on the folding characteristics. This study has been performed in order to develop a continuum scale model to mimic the folding phenomenon.

2. Mechanism

The hygromorphic self-folding of PVA is attributed to the differential swelling across the thickness of the sample (Figure 1), which results in differential strain leading to folding of the polymer. This again starts to unfold as and when the strain gradient across the thickness starts to decrease and returns back to its initial state. The diffusion of water/water-based solvents is favored by the alcohol groups present in PVA which forms hydrogen bonds with water [3]. The various parameters of this behavior, namely, the rate of folding, diffusion coefficient of water inside the polymer film, the curvature attained at fully folded state can be changed by changing the thickness of the film, the polymer matrix or the trigger solvent. Since CTAB reduces the surface tension of water, it can be hypothesized that the total time taken to fold reduces and there would be some change in the final curvature. These expected changes are due to the change in surface tension which results in a decrease in the downward force in restricting the film to bend.

Figure 1. Folding Mechanism of polymer film triggered by diffusion of water.

3. Experiments

The PVA films of thickness 80 μm are prepared by using solvent casting method. The film is cut into samples of size 7mmX2mm. The effect of surface tension between the trigger solvent and the polymer film on the folding characteristics like rate of folding, curvature attained at fully folded state are studied in order to know its significance. In this attempt, two different concentrations of CTAB 0.0005M and 0.001M are prepared to attain surface tensions of 55 mN/m and 40 mN/m respectively [4]. The time taken for complete folding and the curvature attained at the fully folded state are observed for the different concentrations.

4. Results

The curvature at the fully folded state and the time take to fold was captured. The final shapes attained after folding for CTAB concentrations of 0M and 0.001M are shown in Figure 2. A decrease in the time taken to fold was observed as expected as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of CTAB concentrations on the time taken to fold.

CTAB concentration (M)	Time taken to fold (sec)
0	90 ± 10
0.0005	65 ± 5
0.001	50 ± 5

Figure 2. Shape of fully folded state in CTAB concentrations (a) 0M; (b) 0.001M.

5. Summary

The time taken to fold completely clearly shows a decline with decrease in surface tension. This shows that there is significant effect of surface tension on the film folding behavior. These results indicate that in the continuum scale modelling of the film folding phenomenon, the surface tension also has to be accounted for by introducing a cohesive layer or the like.

6. References

- [1] A. Rath, S. Mathesan, and P. Ghosh, Nanomechanical characterization and molecular mechanism study of nanoparticle reinforced and cross-linked chitosan biopolymer, *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.*, vol. 55, pp. 42–52, Mar. 2016.
- [2] N. E. Vrana, A. O'Grady, E. Kay, P. A. Cahill, and G. B. McGuinness, Cell encapsulation within PVA-based hydrogels via freeze-thawing: a one-step scaffold formation and cell storage technique, *J. Tissue Eng. Regen. Med.*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 567–572, Oct. 2009.
- [3] A. Rath, S. Mathesan, and P. Ghosh, Folding behavior and molecular mechanism of cross-linked biopolymer film in response to water, *Soft Matter*, vol. 12, no. 45, pp. 9210–9222, 2016.
- [4] U. R. Dharmawardana, S. D. Christian, E. E. Tucker, R. W. Taylor, and J. F. Scamehorn, A surface tension method for determining binding constants for cyclodextrin inclusion complexes of ionic surfactants, *Langmuir*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 2258–2263, 1993.

Study of Comprehensive Aspects of Recent Designs of Laparoscopic Surgery Forceps

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Abstract

Maryland Forceps are Bipolar Electrosurgical Laparoscopic Forceps and these are one of the major instruments that are used in minimally invasive surgical (MIS) procedures. With the growth of Laparoscopic surgical procedures, the instruments used in such procedures require additional features; hence, designers face new challenges. Substantial research has been done for the development of Laparoscopic devices and a few of these collections are being presented in this paper. Many patents and papers related to Laparoscopic forceps are reviewed in this paper in order to understand the chronology of the development of surgical instruments. This paper might assist in developing the future designs for the same. Towards the end, comparative assessment of various products available in the market is also done.

1. Introduction

Laparoscopic surgery, also known as minimally invasive surgery (MIS), is a technology assisted surgical procedure. Small (0.5-1.5cm) incisions are made on the external organs (mostly stomach) near the affected internal organs and required laparoscopic surgical instruments; forceps, laparoscope, needles, electrodes etc., are being inserted to perform the surgery far from the location. This procedure has a number of added advantages over the conventional open surgery. This surgical procedure has been developed over many decades and it is difficult to pinpoint a single inventor behind this. Since then, technicians and engineers have refined the procedure and tried to improve the efficiency and handling of the surgery by improving the designs and mechanisms of the surgical instruments.

The basic idea was to reach the organs similar to access with surgeon's hand but by doing minimal incisions on patient's body. Initially, instruments were developed that can copy the functioning of human hand but on a much smaller scale. These instruments were simple forceps with a handle at one end and cutting jaws at other end of a long tube. With time, new features were added up to the forceps to improve its functioning and other surgical related instruments such as an electrode for searing, a needle holder for suturing and polar claws for ligation were developed. Now a surgeon can see the organs and perform the surgery just by doing small incisions. The use of Laparoscopic instruments for surgery benefitted the patients immensely. Long recovery period of months is not required after surgery. Surgeries involving smaller incisions are least painful.

2. General Specifications

First, the design of a simple laparoscopic forceps is being discussed by Williams et al. [1]. Then, development and functioning of forceps that can perform multiple tasks is being analyzed. Terayama et al. [2] explains such forceps allow to perform the surgery with less number of incisions. Then, improvements in the design and mechanism of forceps are being examined. Jaws, longitudinal tube and handle were the major sites of interest. Allgood et al. [3] studied apparatus that assists to perform the surgery efficiently, comfortably and swiftly. Delaying the surgical procedure may cause infections and blood loss.

Material selection plays a vital role in designing any surgical devices. Properties like strength, stiffness, biocompatibility, corrosivity etc. are taken into consideration for achieving high performance of these devices. Manufacturing cost and material cost are equally important factors to be considered. Special focus is given on biomaterials by reviewing few papers. It is crucial to study different types of biomaterials that are used to manufacture different parts of forceps. Table 1 shows various biomaterials and their applications in surgical instruments. Introduction of automation and robotics in surgical procedures is quite new. Robotic surgery or robot-assisted surgery was developed to overcome the limitations of conventional surgical techniques. The design experts developed various surgery related instruments using the existing patents and paper and brought up to the

market. Erbe, Wisap and B Braun are few leading suppliers of Maryland forceps. An Erbe product is demonstrated in Figure 1. Towards the end, comparative assessment of various products available in the market is done.

Figure 1. Maryland Forceps- Erbe Product.

Table 1. Applications of Biomaterials.

Material Type	Used in manufacturing of	Advantages (+)/ Disadvantages (-)
Metals		
Pure metals	Main body (bulk)	(+) good mechanical properties (-) highly corrosive
Inert metals	Surface coatings	(+) inert (-) costly
Alloy	Main body (Bulk) Surface coating	(+) required properties can be obtained by changing constituent elements and composition.
Polymers	Main body (Bulk)	(-) mostly poor conductor of electricity (+) can be used to fabricate complicated shapes
Ceramics	Surface coatings	(+) inert

3. Summary

It is apparent from the above patents that substantial research has been done in the domain of laparoscopy, particularly in laparoscopic forceps. A detailed study of materials and manufacturing processes involved in production laparoscopic forceps may assist immensely in reduction of its manufacturing costs. Multifunctional forceps and Robotic forceps are other two areas to focus upon as they can provide a huge helping hand in performing the surgeries more conveniently and efficiently.

4. References

- [1] R W Williams, 1977, Forceps, U.S. Patent 4043343.
- [2] Toshiki Terayama, 1981, Ring applicator with an endoscope, U.S. Patent 4257420.
- [3] Allgood, 1887, Automatic irrigator and evacuator for laparoscopic procedures, European Patent 0246492.

Analysis of EEG NeuroFeedback using Brain Machine Interface

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Abstract

Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) systems are the most leading technology in world related to Neurosciences. Human intelligence and imagination have no bounds and this has led to vast advancement in BCI systems related to Neurological and allied sciences. The objective of this BCI system is to design a model, to check the attention level for any movement or action. The movements are based on the EEG signal captured from NeuroSky Mindwave EEG headset with combination of Arduino Uno Board. This allows gaining control over few basic aspects of patient's daily life. The dataset of 152 sample EEG signals is recorded for classification and analysis purpose. The EEG signals are classified using Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Means Clustering and prediction with ZeroR method. It is shown that SVM are the most efficient classifier with highest accuracy of 89%.

Keywords: Brain-Computer Interface, CNS, Electroencephalography, SVM.

1. Introduction

NeuroFeedback is playing an important role in communication based on neural activity generated by brain. It records the brain waves using electrodes and sends them to the computer system to complete the intended tasks. The neuro signals can be used to express an idea or to control the object. The use of such neurological human brain signals, to control the devices is big challenge in biomedical engineering [1]. NMI is an upcoming technology, leading with an intension to provide a communication channel between brain and external devices. This technology is very helpful to the people who are unable to express their thoughts or unable to communicate due to certain medical condition. Therefore, the focus is on people who are in "locked in" meaning the people who can't move or speak due to paralysis or any other medical condition [2].

2. Theory

In BCI techniques, special devices are used to capture brain neuron signals. There are three different methods to signal acquisition is: Invasive BCI Signal Acquisition, Non-Invasive BCI Signal Acquisition and Partially Invasive BCI Signal Acquisition [2, 3].

Figure 1. Dataset Collection using NeuroSky Mindset at Monitor.

The existing systems are very basic one and costly approaches which also requires assistance of another person or remotely operated person. The patient has to depend on others for any movement. Therefore, the proposed system is consisting of the Mind controlled communication model. The willingness to do certain activity is based on EEG signals acquired by NeuroSky Mindwave and operated through Arduino Uno board. The mind wave NeuroSky headset is used to pick up EEG signals from the brain [4] and transfer to the computer system. These signals are processed by a microcontroller which in turn takes a decision regarding the communication and motion of the patient or person [5, 6].

Hundia [5] explains and encompasses with a systematic understanding of the brain. The project alpha brain signal has been used that have a frequency between 8-12 Hz these alpha brain waves are mainly generated by the closure of the eyes and one can vary the amplitude of these waves by eye movements. The investigation of brain processes was done on humans with high and low level of individual alpha-frequency determined in a quiet state during the perception of sensory signals [3].

3. Methodology

Figure 2. Model Designing.

The proposed System will be effective for people suffering from paralysis or physically challenged people to live more normal lives. In the proposed model preprocessing technique is applied for noise removal, spatial and temporal filtering. The dataset is collected for about 152 samples to test the data. For Feature Extraction we have used Support Vector Machine Algorithms, k-Means Clustering and prediction with Decision Tree and ZeroR method to check the patient is in normal class or abnormal class.

4. Result

The K-means clustering forms the clusters with mean 40.27 and standard deviation is 24.44 for EEG signal. The No. of Iterations in the clustering is 6 with the cluster sum of squared errors is 36752.31. The initial starting points was random and forms the cluster for Normal and Abnormal classes as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of clustered for classifier.

Cluster 0:	41	67	20214	0	20:59.8	Abnormal
Cluster 1:	41	60	101727	0	47:10.2	Normal

The clustered Instances for Abnormal and Normal is 67% and 33% respectively as mentioned in the Table 1. The classification Result with the Decision Tree algorithm and prediction with ZeroR Method is gives 100% and 94.7% correctly classified instances. The Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm is very fast and effective way for classification. In this project EEG signals were classified by SVM machine to detect whether a patient's planning to perform a task with different activities is normal or abnormal criteria of classifier. The results show that the accuracy of the task is 62.93% to perform different activities like attention, meditation, activeness.

5. Summary

In this paper, the communication between EEG signal and its accuracy is evaluated for various tasks like attention, meditation and activeness. By applying the decision tree algorithm, the entropy is calculated to get the best decision tree for classifier. The results shown that the accuracy for the task is about 89% approximately. The sensitivity and specificity of the designed mode for EEG signal classification is 94 % and 59% respectively.

6. References

- [1] B. H. Abiyev, Nurullan Akkaya, Ersin Aytac, Irfan Gunsul and Ahmet Cagman, Brain Controlled of Wheelchair, International Conference of Artificial Intelligence, Turkey, 542-547.
- [2] Mohamed Mostafa Fouad, The Brain Computer Interface: A Review, ISBN: 978-3-319-10977-0, 1-28.
- [3] V. Baby Deepa and P. Thangaraj, Classification of EEG data using FHT and SVM based on Bayesian Network, International Journal of Computer Science Issues 8(5): 239-243.
- [4] Tom Carlson, Member IEEE, and Jos'e del R. Mill'an, Senior Member IEEE, Brain controlled wheelchairs: A robotic architecture, IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine 20(1): 65-73.
- [5] Rohan Hundia, Brain computer interface controlling devices utilizing the alpha brain waves, International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research 4(1): 281-285.
- [6] Imran Ali Mirza and Amiya Tripathy, Mind-Controlled Wheelchair using an EEG Headset and Arduino Microcontroller, 2015 International Conference on Technologies for Sustainable Development (ICTSD-2015), ISBN: 978-1-4799-8186-1, IEEE Explorer.

A 1-Dimensional Model for Blood Flow in Compliant Blood Vessels

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Abstract

In this paper, 1D incompressible Navier-Stokes equations along with continuity equation are used to model blood flow. The arterial wall is modeled as a linear viscoelastic compliant vessel. The solution of the resulting equations is obtained numerically using Galerkin finite element in spatial discretization and Crank Nicolson method in time domain. The propagation of pressure pulse in a model of the artery with a more accurate and consistent numerical scheme is studied as an example.

1. Introduction

Heart beat creates blood pressure and flow pulsations that move through the arterial network as waves, carry information about the characteristics of the flow. Modeling of arterial wave propagation improves our knowledge & understanding of the cardiovascular system. Computational advancement and a better understanding of cardiovascular physiology have evolved blood flow model from 0D lumped transition line network to multi-scale models. In this paper, the focus is on the 1D model because of its relative ease of application to a large part of the arterial network and its ability to supply more accurate boundary condition to the more complex higher dimension models.

2. Governing Equations

The 1D reduced form of the Navier-Stokes Equations describing flow in an artery; assuming laminar, incompressible, axis-symmetric, Newtonian and fully-developed flow with negligible body forces; is given by the following continuity and momentum balance relations [1].

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0 \quad t \geq 0, x \in [0, L] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\delta_1 \frac{Q^2}{A} \right) + \frac{A}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = Af_x + \frac{2\pi a}{\rho} \tau_w + \frac{\eta}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial x^2} \quad t \geq 0, x \in [0, L] \quad (2)$$

The fluid is considered flowing only in the axial direction having constant pressure across a cross section. Friction and non-linear terms present in the momentum equation are evaluated by an axial velocity profile function proposed by Bessems et al. [2]. Above system is closed, with a linear viscoelastic constitutive model of the arterial wall, based on three parameter kelvin model as:

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} + \tau \varepsilon \dot{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} = \frac{E_e}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{\theta\theta} + \tau \sigma \dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta\theta}) \quad (3)$$

Using thin cylindrical shell theory, circumferential stress and circumferential strain can be written as $\sigma_{\theta\theta} = ap/h$ and $\varepsilon_{\theta\theta} = \sqrt{A/A_0} - 1$ respectively. Eqs. (1) - (3) constitute a nonlinear hyperbolic system in terms of flow rate Q , pressure p and cross-sectional area A .

3. Solution Methodology

A straight cylindrical vessel representing an artery is considered as undeformed arterial shape, with the dimensions shown in Figure 1. The set of partial differential equations discussed in section 2 converted to a system of nonlinear algebraic equations using *Galerkin finite element* for spatial discretization and *Crank Nicolson method* for temporal discretization. The one-dimensional quadratic finite element is used to interpolate dependent variables Q , p and A . At the inlet of the domain ($x = 0$), a triangular flow rate of amplitude 125cm³/s is imposed as inlet boundary condition for the time period of 50ms whereas outlet ($x = L$) is kept closed. At every time step, non-linear system of equations is solved iteratively using *Newton-Raphson method*. A code for the implementation of numerical solvers is written in Fortran 90. Based on the convergence study, 1D simulation is carried out using ten finite elements and

a time step of 0.005s. The initials condition used are: $Q = 0$, $p = 3kPa$ and $A(x) = A_0(x)$. Fluid and arterial wall properties used in the simulation are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Fluid and arterial wall parameters used in Simulation [2].

Density of blood (ρ)	998 kg/m ³
Storage modulus (E_e)	1.7 x 10 ⁷ Pa
Loss modulus (E_v)	7.6 x 10 ⁶ Pa
Dashpot coefficient of viscosity (η_w)	5.0 x 10 ⁴ Pa s
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.5
Blood viscosity (η)	1.04 x 10 ⁻⁴ Pa s
Womersley parameter (α)	12

Figure 1. Undeformed arterial shape.

4. Results and Discussion

The flow rate and pressure at three different locations of the artery as shown in Figure 2, are in qualitatively good agreement with the published results of Bessems et al. [1].

Figure 2. Flow rate and pressure at different locations of the linear viscoelastic straight vessel.

This model is planned to be used with a computationally efficient 2D model under development.

5. References

- [2] Bessems, D., Rutten, M. and Van De Vosse, F., 2007. A wave propagation model of blood flow in large vessels using an approximate velocity profile function. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 580, 145-168.
 [1] Bessems, D., Giannopapa, C.G., Rutten, M.C. and van de Vosse, F.N., 2008. Experimental validation of a time-domain-based wave propagation model of blood flow in viscoelastic vessels. *Journal of Biomechanics*, 41(2), 284-291.

Risk Assessment of Patient-Specific Femur Under Critical Loads

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Abstract

The femur is a major bone in the human body which undergoes complex loading conditions during daily activities of a patient. The material properties of femur also vary longitudinal and transverse directions with major scatter. The present FE study assess the effect of material models on human femur under the critical load. An advanced convergence study is performed to identify the number of material cards required to depict the scatter in material properties. Based on the response of the femur, under these critical loads, the risk assessment is carried out, using a probabilistic approach to arrive at a realistic material model.

1. Introduction

The femur is the longest and strongest bone which carries the entire upper body weight. The probabilistic stress analysis is being carried out using stochastic FE analysis [1]. A 3D FE model considering scatter material properties is developed from CT data using the empirical relations obtained from the literature. The material model is characterized based on trabecular or cortical nature as both are highly inhomogeneous in nature [2]. In fact, these inhomogeneous nature of bone is lesser explored and the influences of the scatter in material properties and loading conditions are not represented in assessing the risk of femur under critical loading conditions. The present study focuses on risk assessment of patient specific femur under critical loads considering inherent scatter in material properties.

2. Methodology

The patient-specific femur model is developed from CT scans, obtained from AIIMS, New Delhi, using the ScanIP software. From the CT data, in Hounsfield unit (HU), the bone mineral density and Young's modulus were obtained by using empirical relations from Rho et al. [3] as shown in Eqs. (1) and (2)

$$\rho_n = \alpha + \beta \overline{HU}_n \quad (1)$$

where ρ_n is average density of nth element, α and β are the calibrated parameters, \overline{HU}_n is the CT value in Hounsfield unit.

$$E_n = a + b\rho_n^c \quad (2)$$

where a , b and c is the parameters obtained by the statistical method. Likewise, two sets of material data cards, one for trabecular and one for cortical bone, as well as 70 sets of material data cards were developed to represent isotropic homogenous and isotropic inhomogeneous nature of bone. The 75 number of material data cards were obtained from a detailed convergence study as shown in Figure 1. Influence of these material models on the stress distribution is studied under the single leg stance case.

The probabilistic analysis is performed to identify the variation in response due to the randomness in material properties and joint loading conditions. The study considered Tsai-Wu failure criteria as limit state function as shown in Eq. (3). Same failure criteria is used against isotropic homogenous and isotropic inhomogeneous material models for a better assessment of risk.

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

where F_i and F_{ij} are strength parameters. All strength parameters, Young's modulus and joint contact force in longitude direction were considered as random variables which influence the response. The cumulative probability distribution of the response was obtained using Monte Carlo method. Also, sensitivity analysis of individual random variables for both material models was performed (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Material data card convergence study.

Figure 2. Sensitivity analysis of femur for Isotropic inhomogeneous material model.

3. Results

The FE analyses of the femur with two material models show that the von Mises stress has increased by 17% for isotropic inhomogeneous material model compared isotropic homogenous model. Subsequent probabilistic analyses also show that the material model also affected the probability of failure. The probability of failure calculated for the isotropic homogenous material model is 20% lesser compared to the isotropic inhomogeneous material model. The sensitivity analyses show that importance of the random variables is similar irrespective of the material model but the levels have significant differences for individual random variables.

4. Summary

The present study focused on how the material model of the patient-specific human femur is effected on the probability of failure for Tsai-Wu failure criteria. The study also identified the converged material cards required to represent the material characteristics of the patient-specific human femur. Also, the importance of material model in assessing the risk of human femur under critical loads is identified. Sensitivity levels of the random variables show that importance of random variables and these results should be incorporated while designing implants. Further, clinical treatment is facilitated and improved by patient-specific risk assessment under critical loads.

5. References

- [1] Viceconti M, Schileo E, Falcinelli C, Taddei F, 2012, Probabilistic Multiscale Model for the Prediction of Femoral Neck Fractures, *Journal of Biomechanics* 45, S476.
- [2] Yakkala. V., Ahmad, S., Pankaj, P., Mahajan, P., 2014, Static Analysis and Strength Reliability of Human Femur, 12th Biennial Conference on Engineering Systems Design and Analysis (ESDA2014) June 25-27, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- [3] Rho JY, Hobatho MC, Ashman RB, 1995, Relations of mechanical properties to density and CT numbers in human bone. *Medical Engineering & Physics* 17(5), 347-355.

DVC and Fabric Analysis of Trabecular Bone

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Abstract

Structural anisotropy of the bovine trabecular bone can be measured in the form of fabric. Bone is subjected to compressive load and fabric values were calculated. This study investigates the change in the morphology of the bone when it is loaded. In the present study the bone was loaded in the direction where the bone orientation is less that is along the weak strength direction. Apart from morphological investigation the stiffness of the bone was also computed for each load case. Investigation was further extended to measure the strain using Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) technique.

1. Introduction

Trabecular bone is a porous structured material with an interconnected network of trabeculae [1]. Anisotropic behavior can be observed in the bone due to structural anisotropy in the microstructure and therefore it is important to have information regarding the morphology of the bone. Using micro computed tomographic technique bone was scanned at different load and images was obtained which are to be used for analysis. Fabric [2] is also the mathematical quantity which measures the structural anisotropy. Image based analysis has been done in order to find the microstructural variables of bone (fabric and volume fraction of bone). Less bone orientated direction shows early degradation when loaded in that direction. Using Image based FE analysis (Simpleware, ScanIP-Synopsys) orthotropic stiffness matrix was found for each load case. Since displacement load was applied along z direction (less bone oriented direction) the normal z component of stiffness matrix shows degradation after each load case which implies damage in the bone.

2. Sample and Experimental Details

Trabecular bone sample was extracted from bovine femur and was cut into cube form having the dimension of 6x6x10mm as shown in Figure 1. The sample was then kept in the material testing stage in order to obtain micro computed tomographic images. In a μ CT machine (μ CT50 Scanco Medical, Switzerland) Voxel size and resolution of 10 μ m was set for scanning the sample. Sample was loaded from bottom along z direction (vertical in this case) and was initially scanned under no load condition. Further scanning of the sample was done after giving a displacement load (Compressive) of 500 μ m and 1000 μ m respectively.

Figure 1. (a) Bone sample dimension; (b) loaded sample in material testing stage.

For each load case a raw volume file was generated using imageJ imaging software tool in order to find the strain field in the bone using the DVC technique [3].

3. Microstructural Variable Analysis and Stiffness Measurement

For every load the stack of images was converted into binary images in Ctan software and then fabric and porosity analysis has been done in Quant3D software. Mean Intercept Length method was used to compute the fabric tensor and principal values was taken from this tensor as a measurement of structural anisotropy [2]. Volume fraction and fabric Eigen values for each load has been shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Fabric Eigen values (m_i) and Bone volume fraction at each load stage.

Morphological				
Stage	m_1	m_2	m_3	Vol. Fraction
Unload	0.40	0.34	0.26	0.28
1 st	0.41	0.33	0.26	0.29
2 nd	0.41	0.34	0.25	0.30

Using image based FE analysis in ScanIP software tool orthotropic stiffness tensor for each load case was computed. Isotropic Young’s Modulus was also evaluated by doing Isotropic approximation. These values are plotted against volume fraction of bone and are shown in Figure 2. It can be observed in the plot that stiffness of the bone gets degraded along the lowest bone oriented direction whereas there no sign of degradation of bone stiffness in other direction.

Figure 2. Young’s Modulus versus Bone volume fraction.

4. DVC Analysis

DVC analysis has been done in LaVision commercial software (DaVis84) over unload and final load raw volume data in order to obtain strain field (E_{zz}) as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Strain field in one of the bone image.

5. References

- [1] Cowin, Stephen C. The relationship between the elasticity tensor and the fabric tensor. *Mechanics of Materials* 4.2 (1985): 137-147.
- [2] Odgaard, Anders. Three-dimensional methods for quantification of cancellous bone architecture. *Bone* 20.4 (1997): 315-328.
- [3] Liu, Li, and Elise F. Morgan. Accuracy and precision of digital volume correlation in quantifying displacements and strains in trabecular bone. *Journal of biomechanics* 40.15 (2007): 3516-3520.

Influence of Filler Dispersion on the Mechanical Behavior of ZrO₂ Dispersed Epoxy Nano-composites

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Abstract

This communication reports the flexural properties of ZrO₂/epoxy polymer nanocomposites. Dispersion of ZrO₂ nanoparticles in the epoxy polymer is achieved by ultrasonication. ZrO₂/epoxy nanocomposites contain varying amount of nano size zirconia (ZrO₂) up to 10 wt.%. The three-point bending DMA and fracture test are performed to obtain the glass transition temperature and the fracture properties of nanocomposites respectively. The investigated properties of ZrO₂/epoxy nano-composites increase with the increase of nano-particles dispersion up to 6 wt.% of ZrO₂ nano-particles and deterioration in the mechanical properties is realized above 6 wt.%. This may be due to the significant increase in agglomeration and settlement of the ZrO₂ nano-particles during the long curing time. The fracture toughness is found increased from 1.01 MPam^{1/2} for the unmodified epoxy resin to 4.29 MPam^{1/2} for the epoxy resin with 6 wt.% of zirconia nanoparticles.

1. Introduction

Epoxy resins are widely used in aerospace and automobile industries in the areas of structural composites and adhesives and in the electronic industries for encapsulating electrical circuit components and electronics packing [1]. These are known for their excellent engineering properties, such as high modulus, low creep, high strength, good thermal and dimensional stabilities. However, epoxy polymers have low toughness, stiffness and impact resistance due to their highly cross-linked structure. This cross-linked structure leads to brittle behavior resulting in crack initiation and growth [2]. Hence a new development has emerged for increasing the mechanical properties of such thermosetting polymers by addition of nanoparticles in the epoxy resin.

2. Experimentation

2.1. Materials

A two component epoxy adhesive (Araldite AW-106) consists of epoxy resin diglycidylether of bisphenol-A and polyaminoamide hardener (Araldite HV 953 U) procured from Huntsman company has been used as a base material. Commercially available Zirconium dioxide nanoparticles (45nm, purity 99.5 %) having density of 5.68 g/cm³ purchased from Sisco Research Laboratories Maharashtra India, has been employed as the filler material for preparation of the epoxy/Zirconia nanocomposites.

2.2. Preparation of Epoxy/Zirconia Nanocomposite

Initially, ZrO₂ nanoparticles were mixed in the epoxy resin in various weight fractions of 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 wt.% via glass rod stirring for 10 minutes. Then, ZrO₂/epoxy mixture was diluted with Methyl Ether Ketone (MEK) purchased from Merck Company by the addition of 1 parts of MEK to 1 part of mixture by weight to reduce the viscosity. This was followed by ultrasonic mixing (UM) for 2 hours. The MEK was removed from the mixture by heating at 70 °C till all the MEK had been removed. The removal of MEK was ensured by measuring the weight of mixture before and after removal of MEK. After the removal of MEK, the hardener was added into the mixture in the stoichiometric ratio of epoxy resin and hardener 100:80 by weight. The mixture was then thoroughly mixed by a glass rod for 10 minutes. The mixture of epoxy and hardener was degassed in a vacuum oven at 40 °C for about 10 minutes at a vacuum of 760 mm of Hg in order to remove air bubbles trapped during the mixing operation. The degassed mixture was poured in the dies to obtain the specimens for testing of mech properties. The mixture was finally cured in a hot air oven at 40 °C for 16 hours.

3. Specimen Testing

Fracture toughness and fracture energy are calculated according to the ASTM D 4054 standard. Single edge notched beam specimen (SENB) with span length 48 mm, width 12 mm, thickness 6 mm and crack length 6 mm was prepared. A sharp notch was introduced by tapping a hammer on a fresh razor blade directly on the pre-cut

square notch. The SENB test was conducted using a computer-controlled universal testing machine (Make: Tinius Olsen) at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min at room temperature. The results reported are the average of at least three measurements.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Fracture Toughness and Fracture Energy

To assess the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and fracture energy (G_{IC}), curve of ZrO_2 /epoxy nanocomposites are shown in Figure 1 obtained from three-point bending test. The values of fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and fracture energy (G_{IC}) of ZrO_2 /epoxy nanocomposites are increasing with increasing the dispersion of ZrO_2 nanoparticles up to 6 wt. %. as compared to the pristine epoxy. The mean value of fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and fracture energy (G_{IC}) of the pristine epoxy are measured as $1.01 MPam^{1/2}$ and $3.76 KJ/m^2$ respectively. However, maximum fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and maximum fracture energy are found $4.29 MPam^{1/2}$ and $19.17 KJ/m^2$ respectively at 6 wt.% of ZrO_2 nanoparticles. At higher nanoparticles dispersion the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and fracture energy (G_{IC}) decrease which may be attributed to the significant increase in agglomeration and settlement of the nanoparticles during curing but these values are still higher than that of pristine epoxy. The maximum enhancements in the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and fracture energy (G_{IC}) are about 329% and 407% respectively for the 6 wt.% ZrO_2 /epoxy polymer nanocomposites compared to the pristine epoxy. This increase in fracture toughness (K_{IC}) is attributed by various toughening mechanisms such as crack path deflection, crack pinning and plastic void growth. The dislocation energy is proportional to its length; therefore, extra energy is required. Reducing the spacing between the particles and their size will increase the strengthening (toughening) effect [4]. However, for higher dispersion of nanoparticles (above 6 wt.%), the tendency reverses that the agglomeration of ZrO_2 particles might have occurred. These bigger lumps of agglomerated ZrO_2 particles decrease the effective volume fraction and homogeneity of the ZrO_2 nanoparticles; therefore, debonding of particle with polymeric chain reduces which creates cavity and hence due to cavitation, the fracture toughness and fracture energy of composites is reduced. In case of the pristine epoxy the value of glass transition temperature is $61^\circ C$ and increase to $70^\circ C$ up to 6 wt.% of Zirconia nanoparticles. Increased loading fraction of nanoparticles offers hindrance in the cross-linking mechanism leading to decrease in the cross-linking density and causes reduction in glass transition temperature.

Figure 1. Fracture toughness (K_{IC}) ZrO_2 /epoxy nano-composites.

Figure 2. Glass transition temperature of ZrO_2 /epoxy nano-composites.

5. References

- [1] Wetzel P, Rosso F Hauptert and Friedrich K, 2006, Epoxy nanocomposites – fracture and toughening mechanisms. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 73, 2375–2398
- [2] Singh S. K, Singh S, Kumar A. Jain A, 2017, Thermo-mechanical behavior of TiO_2 dispersed epoxy composites, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 184, 241–248.

Impact of Deformation Route Over Mechanical and Magnetic Behavior of Austenitic Stainless Steel

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Abstract

The present work deals with deforming of 316 austenitic stainless steel via room temperature rolling. Austenitic Stainless Steel, find wide applications in chemical, petro chemical, food processing, dairy, nuclear power plant and transportation industries. As-received austenitic stainless steel have been rolled to varied percent of plastic deformation (30, 50, 70 & 90%). Tensile testing and hardness test were also conducted to study mechanical behavior of deformed steel. XRD and Magnetic measurements were also conducted to confirm the formation of martensitic phase due to deformation of the steel. The tensile strength, hardness was found to increase. The ultimate strength has increased from 763MPa (before deformation) to 1750 MPa (after 90% deformation), and hardness too has increased from 180 Vickers (before deformation) to 460 Vickers (after 90% reduction). However, loss of ductility and transformation of austenitic phase is encountered.

1. Introduction

Austenitic stainless steels are the most commonly used stainless steel because of its excellent properties namely good corrosion resistance, excellent weldability, good thermal stability, and superior impact toughness, hence it finds its applications in various industrial sector namely automobile, chemical, petro-chemical, structural industries and many more. However, they possess low yield strength due to presence of soft austenite (γ) phase which results in making them less suitable for structural applications. To strengthen austenitic stainless steels, there are various strengthening mechanism such as grain refinement, transformation strengthening and work hardening. Cold working is a suitable strengthening method as austenitic stainless steels have high strain hardening coefficient [1-3]. For being a good structural material, it should possess high strength to weight ratio. There are various methods for producing high strength material via grain refinement routes such as equal channel angular pressing (ECAP), high pressure torsion (HTP), multiple compression, hydrostatic extrusion etc. [4], however, product produced by these processes are of high strength but size limitation i.e. large size products cannot be produced. Since room temperature rolling being a cold working process can be employed over the austenitic stainless steel to improve get its mechanical properties significantly. More than 70% of metal product are produced by rolling process in one or the other, so rolling being easy method for producing long length sheets can be helpful in producing high strength low weight austenitic stainless steel. The present work is focused on the room temperature rolling of 316 austenitic stainless steel and it's investigated for phase transformation, magnetic behavior and mechanical behavior.

2. Experiment

Commercially available 316 austenitic stainless steel was used as a material for the study. The steel with dimension 300 mm length x 50 mm width x 3 mm thick was procured from cold-rolled plate stock and prior to rolling, the specimen of rectangular size 50 mm length x 25 mm width x 3mm thickness were cut from the cold-rolled plate stock in the direction of rolling to achieve desired 90% reduction in thickness. Reduction of 0.05 mm per pass was given by using rolling mill having 110 mm roller diameter and 8 rpm. The plastic strain rates were assumed to be constant throughout the process. Tensile testing was carried out using ASTM-E8 substandard specimen with gauge length of 16 mm and a crosshead speed of 1 mm/minute. Micro-hardness tester was used with 100 gf load and 12 second dwell time at room temperature with indentation speed of 35 μ m/s. Room temperature rolled stainless steel samples was characterized by using advanced X-ray diffractometer using Cu K α radiation with scan rate of 1° per minute. Magnetic hysteresis loops were obtained by using vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) of VersaLab.

Figure 1. Stress-Strain plot of rolled steel.

Figure 2. Micro hardness of steel with varied % reduction.

Figure 3. XRD pattern of 316 austenitic stainless steel.

Figure 4. Magnetization plot of steel with different % reduction in thickness.

3. Results and Conclusion

The results from the present study can be outlined below:

- Increase in % reduction of 316 austenitic stainless steel enhanced the magnitude of UTS, VHN and amount of deformation induced martensite (α' -martensite).
- The ductility and the toughness gradually drop with the progress of rolling which reflects the development of brittle behavior in the material under study apart from increase in strength.
- The phase transformation of austenite to deformation induced martensite (α' -martensite) reflects the change of behavior of austenitic stainless steel from non-magnetic to magnetic.

4. References

- Sun GS, Du LX, Hu J, Xie H, Wu HY, Misra RDK, 2015. Ultrahigh strength nano/ultrafine-grained 304 stainless steel through three-stage cold rolling and annealing treatment, *Materials Characterization* 110 ,228–235.
- Milada M, Zreiba N, Elhalouan F, Baradai C, 2008. The effect of cold work on structure and properties of AISI 304 stainless steel, *journal of materials processing technology* 203,80–85.
- Hedayati A, Najafzadeh A, Kermanpur A, Forouzan F, 2010. The effect of cold rolling regime on microstructure and mechanical properties of AISI 304L stainless steel, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* 210, 1017–1022.
- Roy B, Kumar R, Das J, 2015. Effect of cryorolling on the microstructure and tensile properties of bulk nano-austenitic stainless steel, *Materials Science & Engineering A* 631, 241–247.

Experimental Study on Concrete Using Plastic and Steel as A Fiber at Various Percentages (0%, 2% & 5%) And Flyash 10% As Partial Replacement of Cement for M35 Grade Concrete

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Abstract

Plastic waste is a silent threat to the environment and their disposal has become a serious issue for waste managers. Now a day's society does not have any alternative to plastic products like plastic bags, plastic bottles, and plastic sheets. All efforts are made to limit its use but unfortunately its utility is increasing day by day. In proper condition plastic waste can be imparted tent in Concrete. This paper will draw our focus toward the impingement on the various properties of concrete when partially replacing with waste plastic and steel fibers in Concrete with 0%, 2% and 5% of fiber. Various tests on cement like specific gravity, fineness, setting time, etc. and tests on coarse and fine aggregates like sieve analysis, fineness modulus, specific gravity are performed. Mix was designed using IS Code 10262 for M25 & M35 grade. On concrete with and without plastics, tests like slump, vee –bee, compaction factor for workability for fresh state and compression and split tensile, and flexure strength were performed to understand their behavior and usefulness as replacement. Result data obtained has been analyzed and compared with a control specimen. A relationship between strength vs. days represented graphically.

Keywords: plastic fibers, steel fibers, workability, strength.

1. Introduction

Plastic being cheap and easily available now it looks like that we have to live up with it. Recycle process and reuse of plastic waste products amount for vast manpower and huge processing cost resultantly very small amount of plastic waste is recycled and used and rest going into landfills, incinerators and dumps. Typical concrete ingredients are cement, sand and coarse aggregate which are used universally for producing concrete. Due to the great utility of concrete, with the passing of each day these materials are getting deficient thus demanding for the alternatives. It is off course a matter of serious concern for the civil engineers who are on the search of suitable materials which can fully or partially replace the typical concrete materials. The attempt is being made to introduce a plastic in construction materials, to monitor the possibility extent of replacement [1, 2]. The objective of the paper is to (i) determine properties of concrete by adding fiber and observe the fresh and hardened state properties; (ii) utilize waste products such as plastic and find out the economical and performance Evaluation of concrete mix; and (iii) create healthy environment world-wide by using plastic as a fiber, to provide feasible and economical constructing material.

2. Methodology

The strength of concrete was investigated by adding plastic fibers of thickness 2mm and length of 40mm (aspect ratio is 20) at 2% and 5% of cementitious material with and without mixed fibers by weight of cement to the concrete and conventional concrete by normal curing. Design mix was obtained based on the materials test results for the below mention grades in Table 1 and were checked for its workability consistency. Other properties were checked by undergoing through trial mixes for desired strength the optimum water cement ratio, superplasticizer used in mix is 0.5. The materials used in preparing concrete mix were tested according to IS codes and standard procedures results given in Table 1 are found to be within the acceptable limits.

3. Results

The various tests were performed on the samples of hardened concrete for 24 cubes of 150mm, 24 cylinder of 150 x300mm and prisms of 150x700mm which were casted and tested for 7 days and 28 days with varying the

percentages of fibers with 0%, 2% and 5% of plastic made of PET and steel fibers obtained are below. It shows that plastic fibers doesnot yelids and mixed fibers were little better when compared to plastic fiber on concrete.

Table 1. Material test results.

Material Tests	Results	Material Tests	Results
Normal consistency of cement PPC 53grade	27%	Specific gravity of cement	3.17
Initial setting time of cement	28min	Fineness of cement	5%
Final setting time of cement	9hr 48min	Specific gravity of coarse aggregate	2.64
Soundness of cement	8mm<10mm	Water absorption of coarse aggregate	0.81%
Compressive strength of cement 28D	34.62 N/mm ²	Aggregate impact test	19%
Fineness modulus of F.A	3.03	Shape test(Flakiness Index)	41.76%

The plastic fibers of 2% which were added in concrete for M25 grade could not show much variation in compressive strength. Although the mix for M35 grade obtained was moderately workable. We found that the mix could not achieve target strength. Observations were made that water to cement ratio and superplastizer dosage should be varied focusing on the strength. It is not remarkable by using mixed fiber that is steel and plastic in concrete. The results were below par average in compression but tensile and flexural strength were improved.

Figure 1. Comparison of 7 days compressive strength.

4. Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from the above work are as follows:

- The compressive strength of concrete for 7 days has increased. For 28 days, it has decreased by adding 2.5% plastic and 2.5% steel as a fiber.
- The mix obtained for M35 grade was moderately workable. We found that the mix could not achieve target strength. We observed that water to cement ratio and superplastizer dosage should be varied. As the strength was not remarkable, mixed fiber were added (steel and plastic). The results were below par average in compression but tensile and flexural strength were improved.

5. References

[1] Huda S, Ahmad A, Ahmad SA and Khan ZA, 2017, An Experimental Study of Fly Ash Concrete with Steel Fiber Hooked Ends of M30 Grade. International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology, 8(3), 282–291.
 [2] Athira O, May 2014, Investigation on analyzing the effects of use of fibers and mineral admixtures in the mechanical properties of high strength concrete, International Journal of Innovative Research in Advanced Engineering (IJIRAE), Volume 1 Issue 4, ISSN: 2349-2163.

Optimum Material Selection for Total Hip Replacement Implant and a Review On Different Types of Material Available Currently

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Abstract

This paper states the materials currently used in the total hip replacements. It discusses the different properties required for the material satisfy all the design considerations and to act as a substitute of cortical bone. It compares different materials, its advantages and disadvantages over conventionally used materials. This paper also sheds light on the current research topics involving new materials and production techniques of different parts of a total hip replacement implant. This paper also discusses the material selections constraints for selecting materials for hip replacement implant. This paper also analyses statically the hip replacement implant in worst conditions the patient experiences and analyses the factor of safety with the chosen material.

1. Introduction

Artificial total hip replacement is a technique that replaces the femur bone upper part. The replacement of hip joint is needed due to damage in the femur bone that can occur due to an accident, old age or any disease.

The implant is made of four different components namely- acetabular cup, shell inner lining, the mechanical ball and the stem. The conventional materials used in India are cobalt-chrome alloy, titanium alloy and high density polyethylene [1-6].

2. Design Considerations

The design considerations important for the better functioning and maximum life is enlisted below.

- a) Young's Modulus and Wolff 's law
- b) Density
- c) Temperature and Pressure.
- d) Wear Properties
- e) Surgical Procedure and Accessibility
- f) Cost
- g) Bio-compatibility

3. Material Selection for Different Components

For different parts of a Hip replacement implant different combinations of materials can be used the optimum combinations are discussed.

- a) *Acetabular Cup and femoral stem*

For selection of the material for acetabular cup, we need to keep in mind the bone remodeling feature and select a material with appropriate elasticity of modulus and density. Therefore, we need to refer the Ashby Plot.

- b) *Shell Lining and Acetabular ball*

Material for these components are chosen in pairs. The common pairs that are currently used are Metal on Metal (MoM), Ceramic on Ceramic (CoC), Metal on Plastic (MoP), Ceramic on Plastic (CoP) etc.

4. Design and Static Structural Analysis Considering Optimum Materials

- a) *Acetabular Cup and femoral stem Initialization and raw data*

To start with the design analysis of optimum materials a 3D model was created using the Solidworks 2017 using the knowledge gained. The Solidworks model was imported to ANSYS Workbench 15 where the engineering data for each component was added.

b) *Results*

The maximum Von misses stress was observed in the stem connecting the acetabular ball 198.6MPa. The factor of safety for the system was found of to be 1.25, which is good considering the event would be rare. This shows that for the design and the choice of materials the implant wouldn't break even if the person experiences a fall from 2m height and falling on straight legs.

5. New Material Technology for Producing Hip Replacement Implant

Some countries like China has already approved production techniques like 3D Printing to produce the hip replacement implant. The advantage includes customizability and increased porosity.

6. Summary

The design study done is just to show the load concentration in the designed implant and also to determine factor of safety of the design assuming the worst conditions the person can experience on his femur bone.

7. References

- [1] Shahar, R., Zaslansky, P., Barak, M., Friesem, A.A., Currey, J.D. and Weiner, S., 2007. Anisotropic Poisson's ratio and compression modulus of cortical bone determined by speckle interferometry. *Journal of biomechanics*, 40(2), 252-264.
- [2] Li, Y., Yang, C., Zhao, H., Qu, S., Li, X. and Li, Y., 2014. New developments of Ti-based alloys for biomedical applications. *Materials*, 7(3), 1709-1800.
- [3] Katti, K.S., 2004. Biomaterials in total joint replacement. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces*, 39(3), 133-142.
- [4] Ogawa, M., Tohma, Y., Ohgushi, H., Takakura, Y. and Tanaka, Y., 2012. Early fixation of cobalt-chromium based alloy surgical implants to bone using a tissue-engineering approach. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 13(5), 5528-5541.
- [5] Li, X., Wang, C.T., Zhang, W.G. and Li, Y.C., 2009. Properties of a porous Ti—6Al—4V implant with a low stiffness for biomedical application. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part H: Journal of Engineering in Medicine*, 223(2), 173-178.
- [6] Colic, K., Sedmak, A., Grbovic, A., Tatic, U., Sedmak, S. and Djordjevic, B., 2016. Finite element modeling of hip implant static loading. *Procedia Engineering*, 149, 257-262.

Effect of Various Nano-Sized TiO₂ Particles on the Mechanical Properties of Aluminium Composites

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Abstract

The Aluminium metal matrix nano composites can be used in various applications because of their Admirable Mechanical, Tribological Properties and Light Weight. The paper presents the outcomes of experimental study on mechanical properties of two nano sized Particles of 25 and 60 nanometer Titanium-di-oxide (TiO₂-p) particles reinforced with LM0 aluminium metal matrix. The reinforced ratios of 0, 4, 8 and 12 wt. % of TiO₂-p on mechanical properties was studied. The composites were produced by Stir Casting method by using bottom pouring muffle furnace and Magnesium was added to the melt in order to improve the wettability of the composites. The results show that mechanical properties of composites depends on Particle size of the reinforcement added and weight % of the particulates.

Keywords: nano TiO₂, LM0 alloy, nano composites, Stir Casting, Hardness and Tensile Properties.

1. Introduction

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) reinforced with nano-particles, also called Metal Matrix Nano-Composites (MMNCs), and are being investigated worldwide in recent years, owing to their potential properties suitable for a large number of functional and structural applications. The reduced size of the reinforcement phase down to the nano-scale is such that interaction of particles with dislocations becomes the significant importance and, when added to other strengthening effects typically found in conventional MMCs, results in a remarkable improvement of mechanical properties [1-4].

Figure 1. Scanning Electron Micrographs of (a) LM0-4 % 25 nmTiO₂; (b) LM0-8 % 25nmTiO₂; (c) LM0-12% 25nmTiO₂; (d) LM0-4 % 60 nmTiO₂; (e) LM0-8 % 60nmTiO₂; (f) LM0-12 % 60nmTiO₂ composites.

2. Experimental Studies

Al (LM0) alloy was chosen as matrix because it is having good castability and good resistance to corrosion. In the present work Anatase grade nano-TiO₂ is used as reinforcement. In stir casting method the reinforcements, stirrer, and permanent mould are preheated to 350°C to eradicate moisture and gases from the surface of the reinforcements, then the necessary amount of LM0 is weighed and placed in the graphite crucible and heated to

730-750°C using bottom pouring muffle furnace when the aluminium LM0 matrix reaches 730°C then the magnesium is added to minimize the coating film defects by expelling the volatile components present in the melt during casting. Then the matrix LM0 is reinforced with nano particle size of TiO₂ particulates with different weight percentages and constant rigorous stirring was done for 3- 4 minutes at a speed of 500-550 rpm until a clear vortex is formed with the help of stirrer.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Microstructure

Figures 1a-1c show the SEM micrographs of LM0 reinforced with 25 nm TiO₂ particles with 4, 8 and 12 wt.%, and Figures 1d-1f show the SEM micrographs of LM0 reinforced with 60 nm TiO₂ particles with 4, 8 and 12 wt.%. From the SEM Micrographs it can be seen that as the particle size decreases the agglomeration and clustering of the particles will be more in composites.

3.2. Hardness and Tensile Properties

From the test it is observed that with increase in weight % of TiO₂ particle and decrease in particles size, the hardness as well as Tensile properties of composites increases which is evident from the below graphs.

Figure 2. Comparison of LM0-60 and 25 nano-TiO₂ composites (a) Hardness Values; (b) Ultimate Tensile Strength; c) Yield Strength.

4. Conclusion

Nano composites were successfully fabricated by Bottom Pouring Stir Casting Method and effect of various nano particle sizes of TiO₂ was evaluated. The micrographs show the uniform distribution of Al₃Ti and Al₂O₃ reinforcements with low amalgamation but at higher weight % of TiO₂ addition in composites, clustering is more in nano size composites of 25nm particles when compared with 60nm particles. The Brinell hardness and tensile properties of the nano-composites increases with the increase in nano TiO₂ particles content, and these increase with the decrease in particles size of nano TiO₂ Particles.

5. References

- [1] Zhang, Z. and Chen, D.L., 2008. Contribution of Orowan strengthening effect in particulate-reinforced metal matrix nanocomposites. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 483, pp.148-152.
- [2] Sanaty-Zadeh, A., 2012. Comparison between current models for the strength of particulate-reinforced metal matrix nanocomposites with emphasis on consideration of Hall–Petch effect. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 531, pp.112-118.
- [3] Luo, P.E.N.G., McDonald, D.T., Xu, W., Palanisamy, S., Dargusch, M.S. and Xia, K.E.N.O.N.G., 2012. A modified Hall–Petch relationship in ultrafine-grained titanium recycled from chips by equal channel angular pressing. *Scripta Materialia*, 66(10), pp.785-788.
- [4] Cammarata, R., 2006. *Introduction to Nano Scale Science and Technology*. Springer Publishers, USA.

Studies on Effective Utilization of Calcined and Uncalcined Zeolite in High Performance Ternary Blended Concretes

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Abstract

Zeolite is a naturally occurring aluminosilicate material, which is highly beneficial when used as a partial replacement material in cement concrete. The present research is focused to study the mechanical and durability characteristics of self-compacting concretes containing 5%, 10% and 15% Calcined & Uncalcined zeolite as a partial replacement of cement in fly ash based binary concrete. The results of compressive strength, resistivity, absorption studies and Rapid Chloride Penetration Tests of zeolite based high performance concrete is being presented with reference to control concrete without any replacements.

1. Introduction

The rapid pace in infrastructure development has laid emphasis on the development and utilization of green materials in construction. Furthermore, cement manufacturing process accompanied with excessive carbon-dioxide emissions has been a major source of global warming. Over many decades, researchers have been working on alternate pozzolanic materials like fly ash, silica fume, metakaolin, rice husk ash and zeolite etc. Zeolite imparts high durability to the structural concrete by reducing the permeability characteristics [1]. The utilization of fly ash reduces the strength of concrete at early age, which could be compensated through the addition of Zeolite. Hence, the following work focuses to determine the effects of replacing calcined & uncalcined zeolite in fly ash based binary concretes. The use of calcined zeolite as a partial replacement of cement would perform better in binary concretes due to enhanced reactivity, hence, an attempt is made to increase the performance characteristics of fly ash based binary concretes by adding calcined and uncalcined Zeolite, compensating the loss of strength due to addition of fly ash which is less reactive.

Table 1. Mix Proportions used for study.

Sl. No.	MIX Designation	Cement	Water	Fly Ash	Zeolite	Fine. Agg.	Coarse Agg.	Slump flow	SP
		Kg/m ³	(mm)	%					
1	M60	560	157	0	0	713	872	610	1.03
2	Z5	420	177	112	28	750	917	645	1.54
3	Z10	392	181	112	56	745	910	450	1.61
4	Z15	364	179	112	84	740	904	490	1.61
5	400Z5	420	153	112	28	750	917	500	1.39
6	400Z10	392	156	112	56	745	910	540	1.32
7	400Z15	364	158	112	84	740	904	550	1.32
8	800Z5	420	153	112	28	750	917	600	1.32
9	800Z10	392	156	112	56	745	910	520	1.47
10	800Z15	364	158	112	84	740	904	440	1.54

2. Experimental Evaluation

A control concrete of M60 grade was designed using BS Method and the remaining mixes consisted of 20% fly ash (by the weight of total cementitious materials) with 5, 10 and 15% of zeolite as shown in Table 1. The zeolite used in the study was calcined at two different temperatures of 400°C and 800°C for a period of 3 hours and 10 minutes respectively. River sand and 20mm crushed aggregates were used as filler. A poly-carboxylic ether based super plasticizer was used to improve the workability characteristics. The mechanical and durability characteristics

of concrete specimens were determined through the evaluation of Compressive strength, Absorption characteristics, Resistivity and Rapid Chloride Penetration test (RCPT) values in accordance with procedures mentioned in IS 516-1959, CEB 1990 & ASTM C1202 respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

Most of the concretes exhibited high slump flow values confirming to class SF1 self-compacting concretes as per EFNARC Guidelines. The values of slump flow are presented in Table 1. The results corresponding to Strength characteristics at the end of 7 and 28 days of curing in fresh water has been presented in Figure 1. A strength reduction was observed in the mixes containing fly ash and zeolite, whereas a Maximum strength was attained by the concrete containing 5% zeolite, calcined at 400 °C. And the results corresponding to the Rapid Chloride permeability characteristics are presented in Figure 1. They are well in synchronization with the strength characteristics. The mechanical and durability characteristics were observed to increase significantly due to calcination of zeolite which is used as cementitious replacement material.

Figure 1. Compressive Strength and RCPT of Fly ash – Zeolite based ternary concrete.

4. Conclusions

The use of zeolite has a substantial improvement in reducing the permeability in ternary concretes and a successful attempt was made to study the effects of using calcined zeolite in ternary blended cement concretes. Maximum strength was attained at 400°C calcination at a 5% replacement in comparison to other percentages. Similarly, the results would be classified based on percentage replacements and presented comprehensively in the full length paper with appropriate correlations between the mechanical and durability characteristics.

5. References

- [1] Eva Vejmelková, Dana Koňáková, Tereza Kulovaná, Martin Keppert, Jaromír Žumár, Pavla Rovnaníková, Zbyněk Keršner, Martin Sedlmajer, Robert Černý, 2015, Engineering properties of concrete containing natural zeolite as supplementary cementitious material: Strength, toughness, durability, and hygrothermal performance. *Cement & Concrete Composites* 55, 259–267.
- [2] Meysam Najimi, Jafar Sobhani, Babak Ahmadi, Mohammad Shekarchi, 2012, An experimental study on durability properties of concrete containing zeolite as a highly reactive natural pozzolan. *Construction and Building Materials* 35, 1023–1033.
- [3] S. Özen, M.C. Göncüoğlu, B. Liguori, B. de Gennaro, P. Cappelletti, G.D. Gatta, F. Iucolano, C. Colella, 2016, A comprehensive evaluation of sedimentary zeolites from Turkey as pozzolanic addition of cement- and lime-based binders. *Construction and Building Materials* 105, 46–61.
- [4] CEB, Diagnosis and assessment of concrete structures-state of the art report, CEB bulletin 192, (1989).
- [5] ASTM C1202-12, Standard Test Method for Electrical Indication of Concrete's Ability to Resist Chloride Ion Penetration, ASTM International, 2012.

Studies on Effective Utilization of Copper Slag Fine Aggregate in High Strength Concretes

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Abstract

In recent days, copper slag is being used as an alternative filler material. It is obtained as by-product from copper industries. The current research is focused towards studying the mechanical and durability characteristics of high strength concretes containing 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% copper slag aggregate as a partial replacement of fine aggregate. The copper slag used in the study was obtained freely from industries in Nalgonda area of Telangana State. The results of compressive strength, resistivity, absorption characteristics and Rapid Chloride Penetration Test would be presented in the paper in comparison to that of concrete without any copper slag additions.

1. Introduction

The excessive sand and gravel mining along the river beds has resulted in deepening of river beds and it also impacts the structures present in the near vicinity. Scarcity of natural sand has forced the researchers to look for alternate filler materials, without any compromise in strength and durability characteristics. In present study high strength Silica fume concrete is used to study the effects of copper slag fine aggregate in concrete composite. Copper slag is less absorbent of water, so the use water will also be optimum. Hence, the present study is based on replacement of Copper slag at different percentages with constant replacement of Silica fume.

Table 1. Mix Proportions used for the study.

MIX Designation	Cement Kg/m ³	Water Kg/m ³	Silica Fume Kg/m ³	Fine aggregate Kg/m ³	Coarse aggregate Kg/m ³	Copper Slag (kg/m ³)	SLUMP (mm)	% SP by weight of cement
CS0	504	203	56	722	845	0	195	1.0
CS10	504	199	56	650	890	72.2	200	1.2
CS20	504	206	56	578	890	144.4	200	1.2
CS30	504	192	56	506	890	216.6	220	1.3
CS40	504	198	56	434	890	288.8	240	1.3
CS50	504	188	56	361	890	361	200	1.2

2. Experimental Investigation

A high strength concrete mix was designed with 10% replacement of cement with Silica fume. Further, other mixes consisted of copper slag aggregate as a partial replacement of fine aggregate at replacement levels of 10, 20, 30, 40 & 50% respectively. The summary of mixes used for the experimental studies is presented in Table 1. Copper slag, river sand and 20mm crushed aggregates were used as filler. A poly-carboxylic ether based super plasticizer was used to increase the workability. The mechanical properties were determined through compressive strength test and durability characteristics determined through Rapid Chloride Penetration Test (RCPT), Absorption & Desorption & Resistivity values in accordance with procedures mentioned in IS 516-1959, CEB 1990 & ASTM C1202 respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

The concretes with and without copper slag aggregate have been tested to determine the compressive strength, electrical resistivity, Absorption characteristics and RCPT values. The concrete containing 10% Copper slag filler

exhibited the highest strength in comparison to other concretes. The reduction in the compressive strength at higher percentages could be attributed to the reduction in bond strength characteristics between cement matrix and copper slag aggregate. The resistivity values indicate that all the concretes containing copper slag aggregate exhibited values indicating a negligible rate of corrosion in accordance with CEB standards. The resistivity value for CS30 after 28 days was recorded to be the highest among all the other mixes. In spite of the higher resistivity at 30% replacement of copper slag aggregate, the RCPT values were found to be optimum for a replacement percentage of 10 & 20% respectively indicating a significant reduction in permeability. The results of absorption studies too indicated a similar trend as that of RCPT. The results with substantial correlations would be presented in the full length paper. The strengthening mechanism of the concretes can be attributed to the strength of copper slag aggregate and bonding between cement matrix and copper slag aggregate.

Figure 1. Compressive Strength and Resistivity of Copper slag-Silica fume based concrete.

4. Conclusion

The performance of cementitious composites containing various percentages of copper slag fine aggregate was evaluated through experiments in the laboratory. The overall results indicate the fact that a replacement percentage of 10 and 20% is optimum in comparison to the higher replacement percentages. But, higher replacement percentages can be utilized in concretes with nominal strength and still be exhaustively used in the construction of structures in regular and marine exposure conditions. The results would be more comprehensively presented in the full length paper with necessary correlations.

5. References

- [1] M.A.G. dos Anjos, A.T.C. Sales, N. Andrade 2017, Blasted copper slag as fine aggregate in Portland cement concrete. *Journal of Environmental Management* 196, 607-613.
- [2] Zine Kiran Sambhaji, Prof. Pankaj B. Autade, 2016, Effect of Copper Slag as a Fine Aggregate on Properties of Concrete. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Advance Engineering* 3, 85-91.
- [3] Romy S. Edwin, Mieke De Schepper, Elke Gruyaert, Nele De Belie 2016, Effect of secondary copper slag as cementitious material in ultra-high-performance mortar. *Construction and Building Materials* 119, 31-44.
- [4] CEB, Diagnosis and assessment of concrete structures-state of the art report, CEB bulletin 192, (1989).
- [5] ASTM C1202-12, Standard Test Method for Electrical Indication of Concrete's Ability to Resist Chloride Ion Penetration, ASTM International, 2012.
- [6] IS: 516 – 1959, Indian Standard methods of Test for strength of concrete, Bureau of Indian Standards New Delhi, Reaffirmed 2004.

Review on CNT Nanofluid Preparation and Thermal Conductivity Enhancement in Carbon Nanotube Nanofluids

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Abstract

This review deals with preparation methods of water based CNT nanofluids and the changes in thermo-physical properties observed on addition of CNT nanoparticles in water. It is observed that thermal conductivity of water is enhanced on addition of millimeter or micrometer-sized solid particles or nanoparticles with higher conductivity such as metallic nanoparticles and CNTs in base liquids such as water. This has applications where heat transfer rate is important such as heat exchangers, coolants, lubricants, etc. Methods of preparation followed by various published papers are reviewed. Results of thermal conductivity enhancement observed are also reviewed.

1. Introduction

It has been known for many years that the addition of particles with higher conductivity than the base liquid increases the thermal conductivity of the resulting liquid. For this purposes fine metallic powders have been used in the past but they suffer from the problem of abrasion especially when used in applications such as lubrication. Nanoparticles have increasingly found use in this application since they are significantly smaller than the surface features and hence don't cause any abrasion. Carbon nanotube (CNT) nanofluids have shown particular promise due to the extremely high thermal conductivity of carbon nanotubes (~4000 W/m K). CNTs offer higher thermal conductivity enhancement than any other nanoparticle and have unique thermal properties due to their high aspect ratio and hence have attracted more attention from researchers.

2. Preparation Methods and Stabilization of Nanofluids

The study of nanofluids preparation is crucial in the study of properties of nanofluids since the final properties of nanofluids are dependent on the stability of the dispersion. The major challenge involved in preparation of nanofluids is the agglomeration of nanoparticles. Due to the low zeta potential the CNT particles attract and form aggregates. CNT Nanoparticles are not stable in solution without special preparation methods. In order to disperse the nanoparticles a technique such as ultrasonication is used. Ultrasonication is the act of applying ultrasonic frequencies to agitate particles in a sample, for various purposes.

Xing et al. [1] used SWCNTs (Single walled carbon nanotubes) and MWCNTs (multi walled carbon nanotubes) synthesized with catalytic decomposition of methane with cobalt catalyst. They used de-ionized water to obtain nanofluids with mass fraction 0.1-1%. To stabilize the nanofluid they used CTAB (hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide) surfactant with mass fraction equal to 25% of the CNT mass fraction. Ultrasonication time was 60 min.

Taherian et al. [2, 3] used MWCNTs with de-ionised water ultrasonicated at 5 min intervals and mixed with a magnetic stirrer to prepare their nanofluids. The nanofluids were observed to be stable.

Chen et al. [4] used commercial MWCNTs, produced using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method with deionised water. They chemically treated the nanoparticles by using Potassium Hydroxide to modify the surfaces of CNTs to introduce hydrophilic functional groups on the surface of the nanotubes. They reported that the non-treated CNTs precipitated to the bottom when dispersed in the fluid without surfactant, even after intensive sonication. On the other hand, the chemically treated CNTs were stable in solution for many weeks.

Ding et al. [5] used distilled water with 0.25 wt.% Gum Arabic dispersant. They put the fluid in a high shear homogenizer for 30 min. They reported that the CNT nanofluids prepared with this method were stable for months. No sedimentation was observed.

Phuoc et al. [6] used MWCNTs with base fluid created by adding a preset amount of chitosan with deionized water with 0.5 vol% acetic acid. The resulting fluid was put for 24h in a magnetic stirrer and ultrasonicated for 10 min followed by 20 min stirring using magnetic stirrer. The process was repeated for 1 h. They reported that the nanofluid prepared without chitosan showed poor stability with the nanoparticles precipitating quickly and settling down after 30 min. The nanofluid prepared by 0.2 wt.% chitosan showed good stability.

3. Thermal Properties of CNT Nanofluids

Taherian et al. [2, 3] found that the values reported in literature on thermal conductivity enhancement showed a large variation and disagreed with theoretical predictions. Data on reduction of dynamic viscosity showed much better agreement between researchers and there is much less discrepancy. The authors carried out thermal conductivity and viscosity measurement of MWCNT nanofluids. The results of the thermal conductivity measurement showed that the thermal conductivity enhancement increases with temperature. Highest thermal conductivity enhancement was found to be 8% at 32°C and ultrasonication time of 10 min. Also a decrease in thermal conductivity enhancement was observed for ultrasonication time beyond 10 min. The dynamic viscosity measurement showed that viscosity decreases with increased shear rate, and with increased ultrasonication time. This was explained by suggesting that high ultrasonication time breaks the long MWCNTs reducing viscosity since shorter nanotubes are expected to show reduced viscosity.

Thermal conductivity studies were carried out on water based nanofluids using three different types of nanoparticles [1]. The results show that the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid is higher than that of the base fluid and increases both with increasing concentration of CNTs and increasing temperature. All three different types of nanoparticles showed a similar trend but L-SWNTs showed maximum thermal conductivity enhancement followed by S-SWNTs and MWNTs. For example, at 60°C, the ratios of thermal conductivity enhancement of the CNTs-nanofluids at 0.48 vol% are 8.1%, 16.2% and 5.0% for S-SWNTs, L-SWNTs and MWNTs nanofluids, respectively. Since L-SWNTs have the highest aspect ratio, it is concluded that thermal conductivity enhancement is positively correlated with aspect ratio, temperature and concentration. The authors review various models in literature used to predict the thermal conductivity of liquids with suspended particles. They show that none of the models agree with the experimental results of the study. In order to overcome this, the authors introduce a new model based on the Deng model. The Deng model is chosen since it shows similar trend in thermal conductivity as the experimental results (L-SWNTs > S-SWNTs > MWNTs). But since the Deng model underestimates the thermal conductivity at the lower concentration and higher temperature, a correction factor is introduced to the Deng model. This proposed modified model shows good agreement with the experimental values.

Lamas et al. [7] carried out a statistical analysis of the various predictive models available in literature dealing with the thermal conductivity enhancement in CNT based nanofluids. A divergence is observed as some models predict a decrease in thermal conductivity enhancement with increase in CNT diameter while some predicted an increase. In effect of length it was observed that all models showed linear increase in thermal conductivity enhancement with increase in CNT length. When both factors were combined into aspect ratio the models showed significant differences in predicted thermal conductivity enhancement. The authors identify this as a drawback in their application in industrial environment, since reliable prediction of thermal conductivity enhancement is crucial for usage in industry. The models showed a linear increase in thermal conductivity enhancement with increasing volume fraction, which is in contradiction to nonlinear increase reported in experimental findings.

4. References

- [1] Xing, M., Yu, J. and Wang, R. (2018). Experimental investigation and modelling on the thermal conductivity of CNTs based nanofluids. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 104, 404-411.
- [2] Taherian, H., Alvarado, J. and Languri, E. (2017). Enhanced thermophysical properties of multiwalled carbon nanotubes based nanofluids. Part 2: Experimental verification. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*.
- [3] Taherian, H., Alvarado, J. and Languri, E. (2018). Enhanced thermophysical properties of multiwalled carbon nanotubes based nanofluids. Part 1: Critical review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*.
- [4] Chen, L., Xie, H., Li, Y. and Yu, W. (2008). Nanofluids containing carbon nanotubes treated by mechanochemical reaction. *Thermochemica Acta*, 477(1-2), 21-24.
- [5] Ding, Y., Alias, H., Wen, D. and Williams, R. (2006). Heat transfer of aqueous suspensions of carbon nanotubes (CNT nanofluids). *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 49(1-2), 240-250.
- [6] Phuoc, T., Massoudi, M. and Chen, R. (2011). Viscosity and thermal conductivity of nanofluids containing multi-walled carbon nanotubes stabilized by chitosan. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 50(1), 12-18.
- [7] Lamas, B., Abreu, B., Fonseca, A., Martins, N. and Oliveira, M. (2018). Critical analysis of the thermal conductivity models for CNT based nanofluids. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*. 78, 65-76.

Feasible Study on Geocell, Geogrid and Geotextile as Geo Reinforcement in Subgrade

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Abstract

In highway construction, if soil is of Black cotton which is having conventional CBR value of 0.9% is not suitable for pavement sub grade as per IRC: 37-2012. In this research we emphasis on geocell, geogrid and geotextile as Soil reinforcement. Coir Geotextile and Geogrid of uniaxial, biaxial, triaxial are installed at 1/3H, 1/2H and 2/3H from top of CBR mould. From this we suggest Triaxial Geogrid and Coir Geotextile with 1/3H are most effective in increasing the CBR value. Vehicle Tyre tube are cut into hollow cylinder are used as Geocell with different aspect ratio (0.75, 1 and 1.5) at different heights with chevron pattern are investigated and suggested that geocell with aspect ratio 1.5 and 1/3H is effective in increasing the CBR value. CBR test is performed by data acquisition method which directly gives the load at deformation 2.5mm and 5mm.

1. Introduction

Pavements are composed of different layers such as sub grade, sub base, base and surface layers. The common layer that has flexible and rigid pavement is sub grade which should be well compacted to achieve 98% dry density in field. It should be well compacted to limit the scope of rutting in pavement due to additional densification during the service life of pavement (IRC: 37-2012). During soil exploration, if soil found to be black cotton which is having worst property of swelling and shrinkage (SP: 89, 2010). In order to overcome such problems soil stabilization is preferred one decade ago. Stabilization can be done by mechanical and chemical. Mechanical stabilization can be accomplished by blending of soil of two or more gradations which should be compacted by mechanical means to achieve required specifications (SP: 89, 2010). Chemical stabilization can be done by adding additives along with soils such as lime, flyash (SP:89, 2010). Treating coir geocell with sodium hydroxide improves the CBR values. Geocells are the honeycomb structure which are interconnected at joints which provide all-round confinement of soil, distributes the load to wider area.

2. Material Properties

Table 1. Material Properties.

Property	Value	Property	Value
Liquid Limit (%)	53	Maximum Dry Density(gm/cc)	19.2
Plastic Limit (%)	44.3%	Specific Gravity	1.68
Plasticity Index	8.7%	Silt content (%)	57.32
Optimum moisture content (%)	12%	Clay content (%)	14.33
Gravel content (%)	0	Sand content (%)	28.3
IS classification of soil	MH or OH		

Conventional CBR value of Black Cotton Soil: 0.9%.

3. Methodology

Physical tests on the black cotton soil → selected soil should be pass through sieve sizes of 4.75mm and free of gravel and pebble → preparing the conventional CBR mould and subjecting to soaking condition for 4days → preparing the CBR mould by installing the Geogrids, Geocells and Geotextiles at 1/3H,1/2H,2/3H and subjecting to soaking → conducting the CBR test for all moulds by using the Data Acquisition method → comparing the conventional CBR mould with remaining CBR moulds of Geocells, Geogrids, Geotextiles → suggesting the optimum CBR mould of Geocell, Geogrid, Geotextiles.

4. Experiment

CBR test are conducted for all specimen which includes Geocells, Geogrid and Geotextiles. CBR is calculated by using data acquisition equipment with LVDT (linear variation differential transformer) which deformation 2.5mm and 5mm so that loads at that deformation can obtained directly. Below shown graph are the highest CBR value of Geocell (aspect ratio 1.5at 1/3H), Triaxial Geogrid at 1/3H, Geotextile at 1/3H.

Figure 1. Loads v/s Penetration Graph.

5. Results

CBR values of different Geosynthetics at different heights are tabulated below:

Table 2. CBR value of Geocell.

Geocell height	1/3H	1/2H	2/3H
Aspect ratio			
0.75	2.5%	1.99%	1.67%
1	3.4%	3.1%	1.8%
1.5	3.941%	2.846%	2.33%

Table 3. CBR value of Geogrid.

Height	1/3H	1/2H	2/3H
Type of Geogrid			
Uniaxial	1.94%	1.751%	1.313%
Biaxial	2.77%	2.481%	2.1%
Triaxial	3.649%	3.357%	2.62%

6. Summary

CBR values of different Geosynthetics have highest value at 1/3H due to pressure bulb exist at that height. Geocell with aspect ratio of 1.5 gives highest CBR value which increases 22.83% compared to conventional CBR. CBR with Triaxial Geogrid gives better performance in spreading the load to wider area. Geotextile increases the CBR value to 2.99%

7. References

- [1] Khalak, A.A., Juremalani, J. and Parmar, N.B., 1990. Critical Appraisal on Utilization of Geocell for Improving the Unpaved or Earthen Shoulder. International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology 2(1), 267-271.
- [2] Sasi, A.J., A. S. 2017. Improvement of subgrade soil using coir geotextiles and geocells. International Conference on Geotechniques for Infrastructure Projects .
- [3] IRC: 37-2012. GUIDELINES FOR THE DESIGN OF FLEXIBLE PAVEMENTS (Third Revision). INDIAN ROADS CONGRESS.

Microstructure Evolution as a Function of Annealing Temperature in a Cold Rolled Magnesium Alloy Mg - 6 wt.% Al - 3 wt.% Sn (AT63) Alloy

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Abstract

Annealing of unidirectional cold rolled magnesium alloy Mg-6Al-3Sn (AT63) is done from 150°C to 400°C. It was observed that the microstructure is completely inhomogeneous after cold rolling and shows typical basal texture. Annealing of deformed samples at 200°C for 60 seconds, nucleation of new grains just starts to form mainly at high energy nucleation sites whereas at 150°C for a long annealing time of 100 h, nucleation of any grains is hardly to be observed through optical micrographs. The microstructure still consists of new set of strain free grains as well as deformed region for annealing time of 7 days at 200°C temperature. Grain refinement was attained approximately 80% by annealing at a temperature of 250°C in 1 h. Beyond 250°C temperature, the coarsening was found predominantly restoration mechanism i.e. at temperatures above 250°C the recrystallization process is very rapid.

Keywords: Magnesium alloy, Cold rolling, Hardness, Recrystallization, Grain growth, Annealing.

1. Introduction

A lot of attempts have been made to reduce vehicle weight in automotive industries and in aerospace application. Magnesium alloys are such one of the promising candidate that received more attraction over the last decade due to its low density and appreciable strength [1]. But Mg-alloys show exhibit low formability at ambient temperature because of hexagonal close packed (HCP) crystal structure. Improvement in properties may be attributed to resulting microstructure continuously dynamic recrystallization (DRX). Additionally, set of new free strain grains can be also done after annealing of deformed material, a mechanism called static recrystallization (SRX). In this paper, study of recrystallization behaviors is done after cold deformation of Mg-alloys. In this study, new developed magnesium alloy Mg-6Al-3sn (AT63) alloy was first homogenized followed by cold deformation and subsequently annealed to a range of temperature to investigate the microstructure evolution and recrystallization kinetics.

2. Experimental Methodology

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of experimental procedure.

Metallographic preparation was done on the surface of the samples to analyze the microstructures using picric based etchant. An indirect method using indentation hardness values was done to estimate the recrystallized volume fraction. Fraction can be expressed with the formula: $X = \frac{H_0 - H_t}{H_0 - H_{min}}$, Where H_0 is maximum hardness corresponding to the deformed material ($t = 0$), H_t is the micro-hardness of annealed sample at time t and H_{min} is the hardness of fully recrystallized sample [2-4].

3. Results and Discussion

The deformed samples are completely inhomogeneous (Figure 2a). The microstructure is characterized by fine twins (shown by blue arrow) and accumulation of fine twins (shown by white arrow) within grains. These are the high energy sites for nucleation of grains after annealing of deformed samples.

The microstructure shown in Figure 2b for annealed sample at 200°C is inhomogeneous in nature. Nucleation of grains is clearly visible at high energy sites like boundaries of twin and at intersections of twins in general so-called twin-related SRX [4].

Figure 2. the microstructure of (a) cold-rolled; (b) 200°C @ 60 seconds; (c) 350°C @ 42 h.

4. Conclusion

Deformed microstructure is completely heterogeneous in nature. It mainly contains shear bands, fine twins. Recrystallization was not complete even after annealing for 150 h at 200°C. Kinetics of recrystallization is very fast above the temperature of 250°C. The coarsening of grains was readily observed at 400°C.

5. References

- [1] Aghion, E. and Bronfin, B., 2000. Magnesium alloys development towards the 21st century. In Materials Science Forum (Vol. 350, pp. 19-30). Trans Tech Publications.
- [2] Su, C.W., Lu, L. and Lai, M.O., 2008. Recrystallization and grain growth of deformed magnesium alloy. Philosophical Magazine, 88(2), pp.181-200.
- [3] Ma, X., Huang, Z., Li, M. and Allison, J.E., 2015. Recrystallization Behavior of the Magnesium Alloy ZE20. In Magnesium Technology 2015 (pp. 177-182). Springer, Cham.
- [4] Huang, X., Suzuki, K., Chino, Y. and Mabuchi, M., 2012. Influence of rolling temperature on static recrystallization behavior of AZ31 magnesium alloy. Journal of Materials Science, 47(11), pp.4561-4567.

Performance Studies of Diesel Engine Fuelled by Biodiesel Extracted from Sunflower Vegetable Oil

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Abstract

The world faces the crises of energy demand, rising petroleum prices and depletion of fossil fuel resources. Biodiesel obtained from vegetable is considered as a promising alternate fuel. The present work aims to understand the performance of the diesel engine fueled by biodiesel extracted from sunflower vegetable oil. Initially, the extraction of biofuel is carried out from sunflower vegetable oil. The various influencing reaction parameters namely; methanol: oil ratio, concentration of catalyst, reaction temperature and reaction time have been varied using Taguchi analysis and maximize yield of biofuels is obtained. Subsequently, diesel engine performance has been analyzed based on the brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC), brake power, and brake thermal efficiency (BTE) in relation to various input variables such as engine speed and biodiesel blend ratios.

1. Introduction

Biodiesel is a promising renewable substitute source of fuel produced from tree born oils, vegetable based oils, fats of animals and even waste cooking oil has been identified as one of the key solutions for the alarming global twin problems of fossil fuel depletion and environmental degradation. Biodiesel has a number of advantages over conventional fuel such as renewable and biodegradable, higher cetane number, lower emission of carbon monoxide, particulate matters and unburnt hydrocarbon lower sulfur and aromatic content [1]. However, still it is not fully replacing fossil diesel, because of disadvantages such as higher NO_x emission, higher viscosity, lower oxidative and storage stability [2].

A major problem with biofuel here is that most of the sources used are from edible sources and thus the cost of the fuel production and manufacture is high. This study aims to find a solution to the problem [2].

2. General Specifications

For the transesterification process (to extract the fuel from sunflower oil), The vegetable oil is first tested for its free fatty acid (FFA) contents. It is found to be sufficiently low as the oil being used is pure. After a few initial tests on acidity (all of which yield satisfactory results), the production of biodiesel from the oil is started. The parameters such as the reaction temperature, methanol to oil molar ratio, reaction time and catalyst concentration are varied according to the experiment design according to the Taguchi DoE [3]. The best yield combination has been used for the production of biodiesel. The biodiesel obtained from the above transesterification process is mixed with pure diesel in varying ratios to form different blends of biodiesel which is then tested in a single cylinder diesel engine. Exhaust emission data is recorded at different engine loads and the data is used to train an artificial neural network later and then the neural network is used to predict the results for other test cases accurately.

3. Equations

The engine efficiency is evaluated on parameters like Brake Power (BP), Fuel Consumption (W_f), Specific consumption of fuel (W_{sf}).

$$BP = \frac{W \times N \times 0.746}{2000} \text{ kW} \quad (1)$$

$$W_f = \frac{x \times \rho_f}{t \times 10^6} \text{ kg/sec} \quad (2)$$

$$W_{sf} = \frac{W_f}{BP} \text{ kg/kW - sec} \quad (3)$$

Table 1. Design of Experiment with Taguchi.

EXPERIMENT NO.	PARAMETERS AND THEIR LEVELS			
	Methanol/oil (molar ratio)	Conc. Of catalyst (wt%)	Time (min)	Temperature (°C)
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2	2
3	1	3	3	3
4	2	1	2	3
5	2	2	3	1
6	2	3	1	2
7	3	1	3	2
8	3	2	1	3
9	3	3	2	1

Table 2. Parameters and their levels.

Parameters	Levels		
	1	2	3
A Methanol to oil (molar ratio)	4:1	6:1	8:1
B Conc. Of catalyst (wt%)	0.5	1	1.5
C Time of reaction (min)	60	90	120
D Temperature of reaction (°C)	50	60	70

4. Summary

The optimal results for the manufacture of biofuel were as follows:

- a) Methanol to oil (molar ratio): 6:1
- b) Concentration of catalyst (wt%): 1%
- c) Time of reaction (mins): 90
- d) Temperature of reaction (°C): 60

The four factors considered in the first part of the experiment thus appear to be in direct relation to the efficiency of the transesterification process. The degree of influence of each factor on the efficiency was evaluated after the relevant data was collected and analysed. In the second part of the experiment, using B20(20% biofuel and 80% mineral diesel) appears to lower the total engine emissions and improve engine performance in terms of BSFC and BTE.

5. References

- [1] Demirbas A., 2009 Progress and recent trends in biodiesel fuels. *Energ Convers Manage*; 50:14–34.
- [2] Ellis Naoko, Guan Feng, Chen Tim, Poon Conrad, 2008. Monitoring biodiesel production (transesterification) using in situ viscometer. *Chem Eng J*; 138(1–3):200–206.
- [3] Shahid Ejaz M, Jamal Younis, 2008. A review of biodiesel as vehicular fuel. *Renew Sust Energy Rev*; 12(9):2484–2494.

Experimental Analysis of Process Parameters for Surface Roughness Using Response Surface Methodology

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Abstract

The experimental study has been conducted on CNC turning on EN-31 tool steel with coated carbide insert. The machining parameters such as cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut have been studied for the response surface roughness. Five levels and three factors full factorial design of experiments have been considered to develop the experimental plan. Analysis of variance has been used to study the effects of process parameters and their interactions on surface roughness. It has been observed that the surface roughness increases with increase of feed rate and depth of cut while decreases with increase in cutting speed.

Keywords: Turning, Process parameters, DOE, RSM, ANOVA, Surface Roughness.

1. Introduction

Turning is an important machining process in which a single point cutting tool is used to remove unwanted material from the rotating cylindrical work-piece surface. Although roughness is usually undesirable, it is difficult and expensive to control in manufacturing. Decreasing the roughness of a surface will usually increase exponentially its manufacturing costs. Surface roughness plays a very important role in the utility and life of a machined component due to its dependence on several process parameters and numerous uncontrollable factors. An attempt has been made for optimization of cutting parameters in EN -8 material for surface roughness in turning [1]. An optimal combination of low feed rate and low depth of cut is found beneficial for good surface finish. The Genetic algorithm has been used to optimize the process parameters for the response material removal rate [2]. The statistical analysis has been done to study the process parameters and empirical model has been developed for the prediction of surface roughness [3]. The machining parameters have been optimized for the response material removal rate and surface roughness on different materials with the use of Tin coated cutting tools [4].

2. Experimental Work

The experiments have been conducted on EN-31 tool steel using CNC Lathe machine (LL-20TL3) under dry condition. The samples of 20 mm diameters and 100 mm length of EN-31 tool steel have been prepared. The chemical composition and physical properties of EN -31 tool steel is given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1. Chemical composition of EN-31 tool steel.

Chemical composition	Min%	Max%
Carbon	0.90	1.02
Silicon	0.10	0.35
Manganese	0.30	0.75
Chromium	1.00	1.60
Phosphorous	0	0.04
Sulphur	0	0.04

Table 2. Mechanical properties of EN-31 tool steel.

Elements	Objective
Tensile strength	750 N/mm ²
Yield Stress	450 N/mm ²
Elongation	30%
Density	7.8 kg/m ³
Hardness	63HRC

3. Statistical Analysis

Most favorable selection of process parameters combinations is needed for obtaining minimum surface roughness. Design of experiment with full factorial design using response surface methodology has been done and experimental plan has been developed with 20 set of experiments. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been done to test the adequacy of model and is used to investigate the machining parameters which significantly influence the roughness. The empirical model has been developed to predict the surface roughness.

4. Result Analysis

The behavior of surface roughness has been studied with the help of empirical model developed by statistical analysis as shown below. Analysis of variance has been used to study the effect of these machining parameters and their interaction on surface roughness as shown in Table 3. It has been found that the surface roughness increases with increase in feed rate and depth of cut while it decreases with increase in cutting speed within the given range.

Table 3. Analysis of variance for Ra.

Sl. No.	Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F Value	P-Value Prob>F	
1	Model	2.02	9	0.22	128.71	<0.0001	Significant
2	A-Speed	0.47	1	0.47	267.55	<0.0001	Significant
3	B-Feed	1.03	1	1.03	590.78	<0.0001	Significant
4	C-DOC	0.35	1	0.35	201.17	<0.0001	Significant
5	AB	0.012	1	0.012	6.62	0.0277	Significant
6	AC	0.010	1	0.010	5.78	0.0370	Significant
7	BC	0.028	1	0.028	16.24	0.0024	Significant
8	A ²	0.066	1	0.066	37.81	0.0001	Significant
9	B ²	0.0097	1	0.0097	5.61	0.0394	Significant
10	C ²	0.035	1	0.035	19.86	0.0012	Significant
11	Residual	0.017	10	0.0017			
12	Lack of fit	0.0099	5	0.00199	1.33	0.3808	Not Significant

(Ra = 1.29 - 0.18 * cutting speed + 0.27 * feed + 0.16 * depth of cut + 0.038 * cutting speed * feed + 0.036 * cutting speed * depth of cut + 0.060 * feed * depth of cut - 0.068 * cutting speed² + 0.026 * feed² + 0.049 * depth of cut²).

5. Conclusion

The following conclusions have been drawn on study of process parameters in turning operation.

- The surface roughness increases with increase in feed rate and depth of cut while it decreases with increase in cutting speed within the given range.
- Minimum value of surface roughness has been found as 0.706 micron at 2700 rpm cutting speed, 0.05 mm/rev feed rate and 0.25 mm depth of cut.

6. References

- [1] Yadav A, Bangar A, Sharma R and Pal D, 2012, Optimization of turning process parameters for their effect on EN-8 material by using parametric optimization method, International Journal of Mechanical and industrial Engineering, 1(3), 36-40.
- [2] Shivvakoti I, Diyaley S, Kibria G and Pradhan B B, 2012, Analysis of material removal rate using Genetic algorithm approach, International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, 3(5), 747-752.
- [3] Feng C X and Wang X, 2002, Development of empirical models for surface roughness prediction in finish turning, International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 20 (5), 348-356.
- [4] Dave H K, Patel L S and Rawal H K, 2012, Effect of machining conditions on MRR and Surface Roughness during CNC turning of different materials using TiN Coated cutting tools- A Taguchi approach, International Journal of Industrial Engineering Computations, 3(5), 925-930.

A Comparison of Damping Coefficient of Multi-Grade Oils

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Abstract

In the present work, damping coefficient of SAE20W40 and SAE10W30 multi-grade oils is determined experimentally using Torsional vibration setup. The concept of logarithmic decrement is used to calculate the damping factor and damping coefficient for under-damped vibration system. Each experiment is repeated three times to observe the variability in the readings. The damping factor values for both the oils are less one, thus follows the under-damped system. The results show that the damping coefficient of SAE20W40 and SAE10W30 oils are 4.13 and 2.28 respectively. The higher value of damping coefficient of SAE20W40 is due to its higher viscosity at lower and higher temperatures.

Keywords: Multi grade oil, torsional vibration setup, logarithmic decrement, viscosity, damping factor, damping coefficient.

1. Introduction

The dissipation of vibrational energy of a mechanical system operate in a fluid medium depends upon the viscosity of the fluid, vibration frequency and velocity. Viscous medium such as air, gas, water and lubricating oil offers variable resistance to shear deformation due to their varying viscosity. As far as the lubricating oil is concern, it serves two purposes (1) reduce wear in the moving parts by separating them with an oil layer; (2) reduce vibration by absorbing the vibrational energy of the moving parts. In vehicle and engines, the viscous dampers are widely used to reduce the amplitude of vibration by absorbing/ dissipating energy. The effectiveness of a viscous damper in reducing vibration and shock energies depends upon the damping capability of the viscous medium used in these dampers. In the present work, the damping capability of two multi grade oils is experimentally measured and compared in terms of their damping coefficient.

Figure 1. Torsional vibration setup.

2. Experimental Setup

The torsional vibration setup as shown in Figure 1 is used to determine the damping coefficient of multi-grade oils. It consists of a long elastic shaft gripped by a chuck at the upper end of a bracket. The bracket is clamped to the upper beam of the main frame. A heavy steel flywheel clamped at the lower end of the shaft suspends from the bracket. Damping drum is fixed to the lower face of the flywheel. This drum is immersed in the fluid/liquid which provides damping resistance. Recording drum is mounted to the upper face of the flywheel. Oscillations are

recorded on the on-graph paper with the help of specially designed piston arrangement which carries the attachment for fixing the sketch pen/pencil.

3. Methodology

The displacement-time plots as shown in Figure 2 are used to determine the damping coefficient of the oils. The amplitudes of two successive peaks (X_1 and X_2) are measured and the logarithmic decrement (δ) is calculated as

$$\delta = \ln\left(\frac{X_1}{X_2}\right) = \frac{2\pi\xi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \quad (1)$$

where ξ is the damping factor.

Figure 2. Displacement time plots of SAE 10W30 oil.

4. Conclusions

This study is useful for selecting oil for shock absorber, hydraulic actuator, and any tribo-pair like gearbox/fluid film bearing etc. for reducing vibration/noise. The following conclusions are drawn:

- The displacement-time plots show the variability in the amplitudes of successive peaks (X_1 and X_2).
- The damping factor for both the oils are less one, thus follows the under-damped system.
- The damping coefficient of SAE20W40 and SAE10W30 oils are 4.13 and 2.28 respectively.
- The higher value of damping coefficient of SAE20W40 is due to its higher viscosity at lower and higher temperatures.

5. References

- [1] Ananya S, Chandratre KV, Varade BV, 2016, Determination of damping coefficient of engine oil by adding viscosity index improver, International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology, 6(3), 802-805.
- [2] Rao SS, Fook FY, 2011, Mechanical Vibrations, Upper Saddle River, Prentice Hall.
- [3] Abdullaha MA, Salemana SA, Tamaldina N, Suhaimia MS, 2013, Reducing wear and friction by means of lubricants mixtures, Procedia Engineering, 68, 338-344.

Sub Grade Stabilization of Soil Using Enzyme

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Abstract

In India, since last two decades, tremendous increase in infrastructure development has been taking place. As part of it, the development of pavements is taking place at a rapid pace. In the process, many a times, the pavements need to be laid on soft and un-favorable grounds, As California Bearing Ratio (CBR) value of such type of subgrade soils is very low due to which the thickness of pavement layers increases. This in turn requires large quantities of natural materials leading to depletion of valuable natural resources. Hence, of thickness of pavement layers by enhancing the CBR value of subgrade amounts to sustainable development, which is much desirable in a country like ours. At times, construction on such grounds may lead to distresses arisen from low shear strength, substantial total and differential settlement, excessive seepage and liquefaction. Conversion of locally available difficult soil into suitable construction material would be an economical solution. Many researchers have focused on study of the properties of the cement stabilized soil. The main purpose of this research is to improve the CBR characters of the soft clayey soil.

1. Introduction

For many decades, Engineers and Researchers have attempted to solve problems posed by various types of soft grounds. Due to various reasons and there may be need to improve their strength and durability. When poor quality soil is encountered at construction site, the structure can be designed accordingly or the unsatisfactory soil can be replaced with a suitable soil borrowed from nearby area. Another option is to modify the properties of the existing soil so that it meets the design requirements. This last alternative has led to the development of soil stabilization techniques.

Soil stabilization is a process of improving the engineering properties of the soil. Stabilization can be derived from thermal, electrical, mechanical or chemical means. The first two options are rarely used. Chemical stabilization involves mixing or injecting the soil with chemically active compounds such as Portland cement, lime, fly ash, calcium or sodium chloride or with viscoelastic materials such as bitumen. Chemical stabilizers can be broadly divided into two groups viz., the traditional stabilizers such as hydrated lime, Portland cement and Fly ash and the non-traditional stabilizers comprised of sulfonated oils, ammonium chloride, enzymes, polymers, and potassium compounds.

Roy [1] studied the high plasticity soft soil stabilized with different percentages of Rice Husk Ash and a small amount of Cement. Observations are made for the changes in the properties of the soil such as MDD, OMC, CBR and UCS. The results obtained show that the increase in RHA content increases the OMC but decreases the MDD. Also, the CBR value and UCS of soil are considerably improved with the RHA content. From the observation of maximum improvement in strength, 10% RHA content with 6% cement is recommended as optimum amount for practical purposes by observing the tremendous improvement of CBR Value of soil.

Khalid et al. [2] studied the effectiveness of using mixtures of lime with palm oil fly ash (Lime-POFA) in soft soil stabilization was investigated by mean of laboratory testing to evaluate the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) value. The Palm Oil Fly Ash (POFA) additives used is a finely waste product material from the process of burning palm oil fibre. The POFA used is classified as Class-F fly ash accordingly to ASTM C618 and described as siliceous and aluminous materials with possess little or no cementitious value. The optimum of 6% hydrated lime used their study as an active additive to the various % mixtures of POFA for the pozzolanic reaction. The result shown that the mixing of 6% Lime with 3% POFA was giving the higher CBR value for soaked and unsoaked condition. It shows the POFA can be used as additives to stabilized soft soil subgrade.

The use of cement as a stabilizer is more widespread than lime. This is due to many reasons, but the main factors are likely to be the cost and the higher strengths that are attainable using cement.

2. Methodology

In order to meet the objectives, the procedure adopted in performing the three modules of experiments, is described in this section. The test specimen is prepared as per IS: 2720 (Part16)-1987, with some modifications as per the requirement of each specimen. The moulding dry density is calculated for each specimen.

2.1. CBR Test Procedure

The mould containing the sample, with the base plate in position but the top face exposed shall be placed on the lower plate of the testing machine; surcharge weight is placed on the sample. If the sample is soaked previously, the surcharge is placed equal to that used during the soaking period. The plunger is seated under a load of 4kg so that full contact is established between the surface of the specimen and the plunger. The load and deformation gauges are then set to zero. Load is applied to the plunger into the clay at the rate of 1.25mm per minute. Reading of the load is taken at penetrations of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.5 mm. The plunger is then raised and the mould is detached from the loading equipment.

Figure 1. CBR Moulds.

Figure 2. Soil sample for CBR Test.

3. Results

Table 1. Test results of CBR.

Test condition	CBR Test Results	
	Unsoaked	Soaked 4days
Un-stabilized Clayey soil	2.9	2.16

- The CBR value has decreased from 2.9 % to 2.16 %, when it was soaked for four days amounting to 25.51% decrease.
- This significant decrease may be attributed to the plasticity characteristics of the clayey soil. The large value of PI of 40.56 emphasizes the high plasticity of clay and hence the steep drop in CBR value.

4. Summary

Based the results and observations presented in the previous chapter, the following conclusions are drawn.

- For the clay used in this study there was an increase of 133% in the CBR value for unsoaked condition when it is stabilized with Bioenzyme.
- All other parameters remaining same, higher the soaking period (up to 28 days observed in this study), higher was the improvement in CBR value.

5. References

- Roy, A., 2014. Soil stabilization using rice husk ash and cement. *International Journal of Civil Engineering Research*, 5(1), pp.49-54.
- Khalid, N., Arshad, M.F., Mukri, M., Kamarudin, F. and Ghani, A.H.A., 2014. The California bearing ratio (CBR) value for banting soft soil subgrade stabilized using lime-pofa mixtures. *Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 19(A), pp.155-163.

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Products

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Figure 2. High efficient Perovskite Solar Cells at R&D stage- CSIR.